

Description of *Candidatus Acidilobus isalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Acidilobus isalella (N.L. fem. n. *isalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Acidilobus sp003431325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003431325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.78 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Acidilobus ofarosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Acidilobus ofarosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Acidilobus sp000495735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000495695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.39 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Cistern Spring (CIS_19); temperature 78C; pH 4.4".

Description of *Candidatus Acidilobus ovaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Acidilobus ovaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ovaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Acidilobus sp002496425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.19 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Aciduliprofundum agavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Aciduliprofundum agavana (N.L. fem. n. *agavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Aciduliprofundum sp000327505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000327505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.13 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "not provided; submitted under MIGS 2.1".

Description of *Candidatus Aciduliprofundum esalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Aciduliprofundum esalana (N.L. fem. n. *esalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Aciduliprofundum sp015520565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.09 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Aciduliprofundum uvafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Aciduliprofundum uvafosa (N.L. fem. n. *uvafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Aciduliprofundum sp015523135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.47 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Aeropyrum acamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Aeropyrum acamosa (N.L. fem. n. *acamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Aeropyrum sp015523465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.03 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Aeropyrum ecafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Aeropyrum ecafella (N.L. fem. n. *ecafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Aeropyrum sp015521685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.13 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Afabarcha upexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Afabarcha upexosa (N.L. fem. n. *upexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA186 sp002494765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.18 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Afabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Afabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Afabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the

phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA186. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Afabarcha upexosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Afabarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Afabarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Afabarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Afabarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA186. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Afabarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Afabarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Afabarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Afabarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Afabarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA186. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Afabarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Afabarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Afracarcha ipafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Afracarcha ipafella (N.L. fem. n. *ipafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTJL01 sp011333845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011333845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.97 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Afracarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Afracarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Afracarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is DTJL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Afracarcha ipafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Afracarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Afracarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Afracarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Afracarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTJL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Afracarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Conexivisphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Altiarchaeum edagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Altiarchaeum edagia (N.L. fem. n. *edagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Altiarchaeum sp018260755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018260675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.95 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Altiarchaeum emabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Altiarchaeum emabella (N.L. fem. n. *emabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Altiarchaeum sp002083985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002083985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.83 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Altiarchaeum odacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Altiarchaeum odacella (N.L. fem. n. *odacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Altiarchaeum sp002841105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018260615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.05 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Amisarcha egavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Amisarcha egavosa (N.L. fem. n. *egavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA148 sp013415795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013415795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.7 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Amisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Amisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Amisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA148. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Amisarcha egavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Amisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Amisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Amisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Amisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA148. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Amisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Amisarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Amisarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Amisarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Amisarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA148. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Amisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Amisarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Amisarcha ivafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Amisarcha ivafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA148 sp002495885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.6 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Anstonella phaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Anstonella phaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *phaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Anstonella sp018304295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.34 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Apegarcha ilabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Apegarcha ilabia (N.L. fem. n. *ilabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B88-G9 sp003660555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003660555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.25 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Apegarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Apegarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Apegarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B88-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Apegarcha ilabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Apegarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Apegarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Apegarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Apegarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B88-G9. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Apegarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Apegarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Apegarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Apegarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Apegarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B88-G9. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Apegarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Apegarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus ebegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus ebegella (N.L. fem. n. *ebegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Archaeoglobus sp017656475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017656475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.96 % and the genome length is 2.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus utedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus utedosa (N.L. fem. n. *utedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Archaeoglobus sp016757965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_016757965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.05 % and the genome length is 2.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus vupia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus vupia (N.L. fem. n. *vupia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Archaeoglobus sp002507545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002507315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.3 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus ibaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus ibaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ibaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Archaeoglobus_A* sp002011215. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002011215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.49 % and the genome length is 2.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus imavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus imavia (N.L. fem. n. *imavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Archaeoglobus_A* sp002010195. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002010155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.32 % and the genome length is 2.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus ufaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus ufaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Archaeoglobus_A* sp003662985. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.64 % and the genome length is 2.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus unafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus unafia (N.L. fem. n. *unafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Archaeoglobus_A* sp017656505. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017656505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.76 % and the genome length is 2.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus upafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus upafana (N.L. fem. n. *upafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Archaeoglobus_A sp002494625. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004367345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.11 % and the genome length is 2.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus upedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus upedella (N.L. fem. n. *upedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Archaeoglobus_A sp002011235. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002011235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.46 % and the genome length is 2.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus quefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus quefosa (N.L. fem. n. *quefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Archaeoglobus_B sp003663025. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.2 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus ifevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus ifevosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Archaeoglobus_C sp003978865. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003978865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.16 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus muvaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus muvaria (N.L. fem. n. *muvaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Archaeoglobus_C* sp015520485. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.98 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Archaeoglobus upetana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Archaeoglobus upetana (N.L. fem. n. *upetana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Archaeoglobus_C* sp003663055. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.88 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Asafarcha ebamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Asafarcha ebamana (N.L. fem. n. *ebamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LC30 sp019058495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.3 % and the genome length is 2.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Asafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Asafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Asafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is LC30. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Asafarcha ebamana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Asafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Asafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Asafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Asafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is LC30. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Asafarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Asafarchales.

Description of *Candidatus Asafarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Asafarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Asafarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is LC30. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Asafarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Asafarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Astofarcha iregia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Astofarcha iregia (N.L. fem. n. *iregia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALL01 sp015522845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.06 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Astofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Astofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Astofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Astofarcha iregia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Astofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Astofarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Astofarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Astofarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WALL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Astofarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Astofarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Astofarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Astofarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Astofarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WALL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Astofarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Oferarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Atilarcha obagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Atilarcha obagana (N.L. fem. n. *obagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-6 sp002254385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.84 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Atilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Atilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Atilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-6. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Atilarcha obagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Atilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Atilarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Atilarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Atilarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-6. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Atilarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Atilarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Atilarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Atilarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Atilarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-6. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Atilarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Atilarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Atrorarcha evecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Atrorarcha evecella (N.L. fem. n. *evecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAF CGN01 sp017609105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.63 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Atrorarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Atrorarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Atrorarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAF CGN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Atrorarcha evecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Atrorarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Atrorarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Atrorarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Atrorarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAF CGN01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Atrorarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Falicarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Atrorarcha obaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Atrorarcha obaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *obaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAF CGN01 sp017608045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.71 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Axalarcha erapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Axalarcha erapana (N.L. fem. n. *erapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-52 sp002254415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.95 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Axalarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Axalarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Axalarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-52. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Axalarcha erapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Axalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Axalarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Axalarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Axalarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-52. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Axalarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Axalarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Axalarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Axalarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Axalarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-52. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Axalarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Axalarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Axalarchota* phyl. nov.

Candidatus Axalarchota (N.L. fem. n. *Axalarchota* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-52. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Axalarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this phylum belongs to the domain *Archaea*.

Description of *Candidatus Axalarcha upedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Axalarcha upedana (N.L. fem. n. *upedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-52 sp003660905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003660905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.36 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Badimarcha inafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Badimarcha inafia (N.L. fem. n. *inafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZT01 sp003663325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011039365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.72 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Badimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Badimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Badimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMZT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Badimarcha inafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Badimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Badimarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Badimarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Badimarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMZT01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Badimarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Bimafarchales.

Description of *Candidatus Bafomarcha agepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bafomarcha agepella (N.L. fem. n. *agepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHENH01 sp018609935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018609935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.51 % and the genome length is 2.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bafomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bafomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bafomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHENH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bafomarcha agepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bafomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bafomarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Bafomarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Bafomarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHENH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Bafomarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Bafomarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Bafomarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Bafomarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Bafomarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHENH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Bafomarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Halobacteria*.

Description of *Candidatus Bafomarcha igecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bafrudrarcha igecosa (N.L. fem. n. *igecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAMZ01 sp015522055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.96 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Bafrudrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Bafrudrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bafrudrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAMZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bafrudrarcha igecosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Bafrudrarcha odegia sp. nov.

Candidatus Bafrudrarcha odegia (N.L. fem. n. *odegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAMZ01 sp015523725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.95 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Bafustarcha apagella sp. nov.

Candidatus Bafustarcha apagella (N.L. fem. n. *apagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKB01 sp014729345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.86 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Bafustarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Bafustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bafustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJKB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bafustarcha apagella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bafustarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bafustarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Bafustarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Bafustarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJKB01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Bafustarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Basifrarcha ovafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Basifrarcha ovafia (N.L. fem. n. *ovafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BE-D sp003019595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003019595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.81 % and the genome length is 2.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Basifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Basifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Basifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BE-D. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Basifrarcha ovafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Marsarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bastafrarcha unaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bastafrarcha unaposa (N.L. fem. n. *unaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRHU01 sp016211995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016211995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.5 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bastafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bastafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bastafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRHU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bastafarcha unaposa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Micubrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Batofrarcha atedia sp. nov.

Candidatus Batofrarcha atedia (N.L. fem. n. *atedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAMD01 sp015522495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.26 % and the genome length is 0.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Batofrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Batofrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Batofrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAMD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Batofrarcha atedia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Batofrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Batofrarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Batofrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Batofrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WAMD01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Batofrarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Astofarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Bebrastarcha efaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Bebrastarcha efaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *efaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2686855 sp002686855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002686855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.09 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bebrastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bebrastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bebrastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2686855. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bebrastarcha efaxosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Becabrarcha ivecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Becabrarcha ivecana (N.L. fem. n. *ivecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA543 sp002502135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.54 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Becabrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Becabrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Becabrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA543. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Becabrarcha ivecana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Becabrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Becabrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Becabrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Becabrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA543. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Becabrarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Undinarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Beclustarcha inemana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Beclustarcha inemana (N.L. fem. n. *inemana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS750m-G24 sp016783545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016783545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.94 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Beclustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Beclustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Beclustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BS750m-G24. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Beclustarcha inemana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Befrimarcha ipafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Befrimarcha ipafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 18H4-34 sp019057815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.75 % and the genome length is 3.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Befrimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Befrimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Befrimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 18H4-34. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Befrimarcha ipafosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sobomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Berafarcha ebafeffa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Berafarcha ebafeffa (N.L. fem. n. *ebafeffa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWC01 sp018304465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.87 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Berafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Berafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Berafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVWC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Berafarcha ebafera*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Berafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Berafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Berafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Berafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVWC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Berafarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Bestemarcha oragaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bestemarcha oragaria (N.L. fem. n. *oragaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-965745 sp000965745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000965745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.42 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Acid sulfate soils".

Description of *Candidatus Bestemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bestemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bestemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-965745. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bestemarcha oragaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Thermoplasmataceae.

Description of *Candidatus Bestutrarcha ecemia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bestutrarcha ecemia (N.L. fem. n. *ecemia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J07HR59 sp000496235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000496235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.1 % and the genome length is 2.88 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "hypersaline water sample from Lake Tyrrell".

Description of *Candidatus Bestutrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bestutrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bestutrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J07HR59. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bestutrarcha ecemia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloferacaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Betrefarcha otexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Betrefarcha otexana (N.L. fem. n. *otexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-45 sp002011395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002011395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.59 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Betrefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Betrefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Betrefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-45. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Betrefarcha otexana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Betrefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Betrefarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Betrefarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Betrefarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JdFR-45. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Betrefarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Aciduliprofundales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Bexafrarcha ategosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Bexafrarcha ategosa (N.L. fem. n. *ategosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSZJ01 sp011367145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011367145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.81 % and the genome length is 0.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Bexafrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Bexafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bexafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSZJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bexafrarcha ategosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bexafrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Bexafrarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Bexafrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Bexafrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DSZJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Bexafrarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hadarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Bexafrarcha ibavana sp. nov.

Candidatus Bexafrarcha ibavana (N.L. fem. n. *ibavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSZJ01 sp011361855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011361855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.31 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Beximarcha epavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Beximarcha epavana (N.L. fem. n. *epavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADEF01 sp015520895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.5 % and the genome length is 0.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Beximarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Beximarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Beximarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADEF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Beximarcha epavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Beximarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Beximarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Beximarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Beximarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAADEF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Beximarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Axalarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Beximarcha orabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Beximarcha orabaria (N.L. fem. n. *orabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADEF01 sp013153555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013153555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.15 % and the genome length is 0.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bidasarcha umenana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bidasarcha umenana (N.L. fem. n. *umenana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA119 sp002505945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.6 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bidasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bidasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bidasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA119. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bidasarcha umenana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bidasarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bidasarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Bidasarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Bidasarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA119. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Bidasarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Bifucarcha ubafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bifucarcha ubafana (N.L. fem. n. *ubafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJC01 sp018304445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.2 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bifucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bifucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bifucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPJC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bifucarcha ubafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bifucarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bifucarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Bifucarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Bifucarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPJC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Bifucarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Bifucarcha ufasosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bifucarcha ufasosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufasosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJC01 sp016187745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.49 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum agaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum agaxella (N.L. fem. n. *agaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp016926175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.22 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum asagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum asagaria (N.L. fem. n. *asagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp018813505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018818705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.71 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum edabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum edabaria (N.L. fem. n. *edabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp903835325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903835325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.25 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum epaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum epaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *epaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp016212505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016212505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.11 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum eregana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum eregana (N.L. fem. n. *eregana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp018812715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018812715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.78 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum ipedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum ipedia (N.L. fem. n. *ipedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp016212525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016212525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.57 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum ipegaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum ipegaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp014730115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014730115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.05 % and the genome

length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum ufavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum ufavia (N.L. fem. n. *ufavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp018812625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018812625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.18 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bilamarchaeum unexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bilamarchaeum unexia (N.L. fem. n. *unexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bilamarchaeum sp013425375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013425375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.23 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bimafarcha esaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bimafarcha esaxia (N.L. fem. n. *esaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZP01 sp003663225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.92 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bimafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bimafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bimafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMZP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bimafarcha esaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bimafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Bimafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Bimafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMZP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Bimafarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Bimafarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Bimafarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Bimafarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Bimafarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMZP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Bimafarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Aenigmatarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Bimigrarcha ucarosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bimigrarcha ucarosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPCD01 sp016179955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016179955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.33 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bimigrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bimigrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bimigrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPCD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bimigrarcha ucarosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Binidarcha imafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Binidarcha imafella (N.L. fem. n. *imafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQIF01 sp016198635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.7 % and the genome length is 0.54

Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Binidarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Binidarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Binidarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQIF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Binidarcha imafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Binidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Binidarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Binidarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Binidarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQIF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Binidarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Butolarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Binidarcha obafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Binidarcha obafaria (N.L. fem. n. *obafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQIF01 sp016432325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016432325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.91 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bistubrarcha ocesaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bistubrarcha ocesaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocesaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-58 sp002254665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.43 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bistubrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bistubrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bistubrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-58. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bistubrarcha ocesaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Desulfurococcaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Blacusarcha ecabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Blacusarcha ecabella (N.L. fem. n. *ecabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAF CFZ01 sp017608385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.81 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blacusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Blacusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Blacusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAF CFZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Blacusarcha ecabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Falicarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha afixia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha afixia (N.L. fem. n. *afixia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp011363945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011363945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.12 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bladenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTEX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bladenarcha afixia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Omagarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha afevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha afevaria (N.L. fem. n. *afevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp018396655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.49 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha apafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha apafella (N.L. fem. n. *apafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp011380195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011380195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.35 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha ibaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha ibaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ibaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp011363705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011363705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.47 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha icebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha icebella (N.L. fem. n. *icebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp018396975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.96 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha inaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha inaxella (N.L. fem. n. *inaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp018396435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.77 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha ocesella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha ocesella (N.L. fem. n. *ocesella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp018396555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.87 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha odapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha odapana (N.L. fem. n. *odapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp018396795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.23 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha omevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha omevaria (N.L. fem. n. *omevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp018396405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.65 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha ufabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha ufabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp018396995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.62 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha ulabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha ulabella (N.L. fem. n. *ulabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp018396635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.45 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha unavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha unavana (N.L. fem. n. *unavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp011364715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.64 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bladenarcha unexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bladenarcha unexaria (N.L. fem. n. *unexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTEX01 sp011366945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011366945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.99 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blaglufarcha ilemia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Blaglufarcha ilemia (N.L. fem. n. *ilemia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VBQI01 sp008297865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008297865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.84 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blaglufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Blaglufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Blaglufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VBQI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Blaglufarcha ilemia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Parutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Blecloxarcha igecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Blecloxarcha igecia (N.L. fem. n. *igecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAYNL01 sp012520845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012520845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.72 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blecloxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Blecloxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Blecloxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAYNL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Blecloxarcha igecia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bleclumarcha icanana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bleclumarcha icanana (N.L. fem. n. *icanana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGQX01 sp016935455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.54 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bleclumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bleclumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bleclumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGQX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bleclumarcha icanana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Blefecarcha inaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Blefecarcha inaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *inaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXQ01 sp018303705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.72 % and the genome length is 0.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blefecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Blefecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Blefecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Blefecarcha inaxaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bliximarcha epabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bliximarcha epabella (N.L. fem. n. *epabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA117 sp002494785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.41 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bliximarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bliximarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bliximarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA117. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bliximarcha epabella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanobacteriaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bludufarcha acagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bludufarcha acagosa (N.L. fem. n. *acagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9949 sp013415575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013415575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.63 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blutufarcha gen. nov.*

Candidatus Blutufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Blutufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA9949. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Blutufarcha acagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanoregulaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Blutufarcha afacana sp. nov.*

Candidatus Blutufarcha afacana (N.L. fem. n. *afacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9949 sp013415565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013415565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.03 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blutufarcha elaxosa sp. nov.*

Candidatus Blutufarcha elaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *elaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9949 sp002499905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.74 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blutufarcha icagana sp. nov.*

Candidatus Blutufarcha icagana (N.L. fem. n. *icagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9949 sp002068435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019136535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.05 % and the genome length is 3.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blutufarcha ipemella sp. nov.*

Candidatus Blutufarcha ipemella (N.L. fem. n. *ipemella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is UBA9949 sp10516u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.85 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bludufarcha irafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bludufarcha irafaria (N.L. fem. n. *irafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9949 sp016699325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016699325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.6 % and the genome length is 1.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bludufarcha ofaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bludufarcha ofaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ofaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9949 sp012516785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012516785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.82 % and the genome length is 1.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blumaxarcha icagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Blumaxarcha icagella (N.L. fem. n. *icagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARK-14 sp011333245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009904115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.6 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blumaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Blumaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Blumaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARK-14. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Blumaxarcha icagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fervidicoccaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Blumaxarcha ilasia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Blumaxarcha ilasia (N.L. fem. n. *ilasia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARK-14 sp002899805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002899805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.83 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blusegarcha omafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Blusegarcha omafosa (N.L. fem. n. *omafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYEN01 sp009903825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011380155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.46 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Blusegarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Blusegarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Blusegarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WYEN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Blusegarcha omafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Paxotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Boblimarcha usagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Boblimarcha usagella (N.L. fem. n. *usagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJAQ01 sp018813975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018813975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.47 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Boblimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Boblimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Boblimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJAQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Boblimarcha usagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Berafarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Boblucrarcha ilevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Boblucrarcha ilevia (N.L. fem. n. *ilevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1515 sp015661775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015661775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.48 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Boblucrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Boblucrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Boblucrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZUA-1515. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Boblucrarcha ilevia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Caldarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bofristarcha ebecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bofristarcha ebecella (N.L. fem. n. *ebecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRKF01 sp016219865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016219865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.78 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bofristarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bofristarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bofristarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRKF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bofristarcha ebecella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nerisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bofristarcha edepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bofristarcha edepia (N.L. fem. n. *edepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRKF01 sp018303075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.77 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bogrufrarcha odegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bogrufrarcha odegella (N.L. fem. n. *odegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPTE01 sp016192945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016192945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.84 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bogrufrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bogrufrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bogrufrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPTE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bogrufrarcha odegella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bolabrarcha ovabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bolabrarcha ovabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ovabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQMX01 sp016203375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.65 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bolabrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bolabrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bolabrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQMX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bolabrarcha ovabosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Hamosarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Bonostarcha icavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bonostarcha icavia (N.L. fem. n. *icavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BOG-1369 sp003164815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003164815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.46 % and the genome length is 2.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bonostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bonostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bonostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BOG-1369. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bonostarcha icavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Naraxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bonostarcha ivaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bonostarcha ivaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ivaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BOG-1369 sp003135575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003135575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.43 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Borrarchaeum ipemia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Borrarchaeum ipemia (N.L. fem. n. *ipemia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Borrarchaeum sp016840315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.61 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Borrarchaeum phapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Borrarchaeum phapia (N.L. fem. n. *phapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Borrarchaeum sp016840645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.33 % and the genome length is 4.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bosatarcha ivagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bosatarcha ivagella (N.L. fem. n. *ivagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-13-38-9 sp001775955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001775955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.68 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 13ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Bosatarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bosatarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bosatarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is RBG-13-38-9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bosatarcha ivagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bosatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bosatarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Bosatarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Bosatarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is RBG-13-38-9. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Bosatarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omubarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Bosatarcha obavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bosatarcha obavana (N.L. fem. n. *obavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-13-38-9 sp007050885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007050885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.82 % and the genome

length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha afacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha afacosa (N.L. fem. n. *afacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp8574u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.64 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bostedarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIa-L2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bostedarcha afacosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha ebaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha ebaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ebaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002502215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.43 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha ifalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha ifalaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp009887135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905182505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.83 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha ipataria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha ipataria (N.L. fem. n. *ipataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp018623995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018623995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.06 % and the genome length is 1.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha ivebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha ivebana (N.L. fem. n. *ivebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp018645535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018645535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.78 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha oladella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha oladella (N.L. fem. n. *oladella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002692685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002692685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.75 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha omexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha omexia (N.L. fem. n. *omexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002496635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.61 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha opavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha opavella (N.L. fem. n. *opavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp003602665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.86 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha osacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha osacana (N.L. fem. n. *osacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002722615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002703075.2. The GC content of the type genome is 47.12 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha quaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha quaxana (N.L. fem. n. *quaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp016777125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016777245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.93 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha ruxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha ruxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ruxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002698145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.62 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha ucagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha ucagella (N.L. fem. n. *ucagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002706065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002706065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.06 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha ucamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha ucamia (N.L. fem. n. *ucamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002726845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902625045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.67 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha udexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha udexaria (N.L. fem. n. *udexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp012270265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012270265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.29 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha unaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha unaparia (N.L. fem. n. *unaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002171315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002171315.2. The GC content of the type genome is 44.47 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha upabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha upabella (N.L. fem. n. *upabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp018666575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018666575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.15 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha upelella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha upelella (N.L. fem. n. *upelella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002719815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002719815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.3 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha upexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha upexella (N.L. fem. n. *upexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp013911465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013911465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.37 % and the genome length is

1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostedarcha vupella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostedarcha vupella (N.L. fem. n. *vupella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L2 sp002499195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.75 % and the genome length is 1.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostoxarcha ifacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bostoxarcha ifacana (N.L. fem. n. *ifacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CADBMS01 sp902795935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902795935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.3 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bostoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bostoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bostoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CADBMS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bostoxarcha ifacana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanobacteriaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Botrenarcha oraxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Botrenarcha oraxella (N.L. fem. n. *oraxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPNE01 sp016185615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.33 % and the genome length is 0.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Botrenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Botrenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Botrenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPNE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Botrenarcha oraxella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Boxugrarcha oraxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Boxugrarcha oraxosa (N.L. fem. n. *oraxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMWW01 sp003661825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.61 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Boxugrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Boxugrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Boxugrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMWW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Boxugrarcha oraxosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Desulfurococcaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Bradresarcha onemia sp. nov.

Candidatus Bradresarcha onemia (N.L. fem. n. *onemia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZV01 sp018302265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.1 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Bradresarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Bradresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bradresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bradresarcha onemia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Cuxufarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Brexisarcha quavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brexisarcha quavana (N.L. fem. n. *quavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP5-2226 sp016841005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016841005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.01 % and the genome length is 4.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brexisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Brexisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Brexisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MP5-2226. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Brexisarcha quavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Brexisarcha uravana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brexisarcha uravana (N.L. fem. n. *uravana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP5-2226 sp016840825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.31 % and the genome length is 4.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bricadarcha ufaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bricadarcha ufaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ufaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SpSt-9 sp011333035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011333035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.61 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bricadarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bricadarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bricadarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SpSt-9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bricadarcha ufaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Disocarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bridayarcha esabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bridayarcha esabana (N.L. fem. n. *esabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VYCS01 sp009843815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009846455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.75 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bridayarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bridayarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bridayarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VYCS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bridayarcha esabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bridayarcha evabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bridayarcha evabella (N.L. fem. n. *evabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VYCS01 sp016126025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016126025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.25 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bridayarcha gixaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bridayarcha gixaria (N.L. fem. n. *gixaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VYCS01 sp009840065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009836545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.45 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brofoxarcha arexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brofoxarcha arexosa (N.L. fem. n. *arexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TH5896 sp014523625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.93 % and the genome length is 2.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brofoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Brofoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Brofoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TH5896. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Brofoxarcha arexosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrososphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Brofoxarcha avafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brofoxarcha avafella (N.L. fem. n. *avafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TH5896 sp009377575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009377575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.71 % and the genome length is 3.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brofoxarcha efararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brofoxarcha efararia (N.L. fem. n. *efararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TH5896 sp014523695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.99 % and the genome length is 3.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brofoxarcha iraxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brofoxarcha iraxia (N.L. fem. n. *iraxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is TH5896 sp014523665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.85 % and the genome length is 4.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brosaxarcha ivagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brosaxarcha ivagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAXVZ01 sp013335235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013335235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.37 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brosaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Brosaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Brosaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAXVZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Brosaxarcha ivagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hudomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Brostufarcha umexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brostufarcha umexia (N.L. fem. n. *umexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWU01 sp018304145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.57 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brostufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Brostufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Brostufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVWU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Brostufarcha umexia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Brufrunarcha afebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brufrunarcha afebaria (N.L. fem. n. *afebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-2 sp002254565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.61 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Brufrunarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Brufrunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Brufrunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Brufrunarcha afebaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lanaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Brufrunarcha eregosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Brufrunarcha eregosa (N.L. fem. n. *eregosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-2 sp002254405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.32 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Brumefarcha efalana sp. nov.

Candidatus Brumefarcha efalana (N.L. fem. n. *efalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEE01 sp017609285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.68 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Brumefarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Brumefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Brumefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCEE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Brumefarcha efalana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Brumusarcha ifavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brumusarcha ifavana (N.L. fem. n. *ifavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHWS01 sp018815925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018817265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.3 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brumusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Brumusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Brumusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHWS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Brumusarcha ifavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Brustecarcha ifepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Brustecarcha ifepia (N.L. fem. n. *ifepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRY01 sp011375665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011375665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.46 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Brustecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Brustecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Brustecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Brustecarcha ifepia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Habrutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bublesarcha ugaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bublesarcha ugaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ugaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B12-G17 sp003661905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.93 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Bublesarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Bublesarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bublesarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B12-G17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bublesarcha ugaxia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ignisphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Bufodrarcha epamaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Bufodrarcha epamaria (N.L. fem. n. *epamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S141-84 sp015521705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.34 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Bufodrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Bufodrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bufodrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S141-84. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Bufodrarcha epamaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Acidilobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Bufrucrarcha edepella sp. nov.

Candidatus Bufrucrarcha edepella (N.L. fem. n. *edepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JACRKG01 sp016215315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016215315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.4 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bufrucrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bufrucrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bufrucrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRKG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bufrucrarcha edepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Bufrucrarcha itefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bufrucrarcha itefana (N.L. fem. n. *itefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRKG01 sp016213425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016213425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.01 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bugromarcha ilaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Bugromarcha ilaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ilaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXV01 sp018303625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.44 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Bugromarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Bugromarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Bugromarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Bugromarcha ilaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Buligrarcha ecasaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Buligrarcha ecasaria (N.L. fem. n. *ecasaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPDF01 sp016180235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.69 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Buligrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Buligrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Buligrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPDF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Buligrarcha ecasaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Buligrarcha phepana sp. nov.

Candidatus Buligrarcha phepana (N.L. fem. n. *phepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPDF01 sp016184145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016184145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.44 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Buridrarcha ubavia sp. nov.

Candidatus Buridrarcha ubavia (N.L. fem. n. *ubavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJJT01 sp014729555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.81 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Buridrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Buridrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Buridrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJJT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Buridrarcha ubavia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Busilarcha umaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Busilarcha umaxosa* (N.L. fem. n. *umaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQSR01 sp016211215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016211215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.18 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Busilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus *Busilarcha* (N.L. fem. n. *Busilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQSR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Busilarcha umaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Busilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Busilarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus *Busilarchaceae* (N.L. fem. n. *Busilarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQSR01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* *Busilarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Busufarcha uvapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Busufarcha uvapella* (N.L. fem. n. *uvapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10191 sp10036u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.85 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Busufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Busufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Busufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10191. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Busufarcha uvapella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Busufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Busufarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Busufarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Busufarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10191. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Busufarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Butolarcha ebatia sp. nov.

Candidatus Butolarcha ebatia (N.L. fem. n. *ebatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWEA01 sp003550625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003550625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.83 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Butolarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Butolarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Butolarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PWEA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Butolarcha ebatia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Butolarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Butolarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Butolarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Butolarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PWEA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Butolarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Butolarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Butolarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Butolarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Butolarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PWEA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Butolarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Aenigmatarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Butolarcha efabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Butolarcha efabosa (N.L. fem. n. *efabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWEA01 sp003554235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003554235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.82 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Butolarcha evabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Butolarcha evabana (N.L. fem. n. *evabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWEA01 sp003555465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003555465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.01 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Butolarcha onagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Butolarcha onagia (N.L. fem. n. *onagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWEA01 sp003554845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003554845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.4 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Butolarcha oraxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Butolarcha oraxana (N.L. fem. n. *oraxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWEA01 sp003553905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003553905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.54 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Buxobrarcha osafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Buxobrarcha osafia (N.L. fem. n. *osafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJUI01 sp018829185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018828805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.77 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Buxobrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Buxobrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Buxobrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJUI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Buxobrarcha osafia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nipetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Caclustarcha aselella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caclustarcha aselella (N.L. fem. n. *aselella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOZP01 sp016181265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.63 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Caclustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Caclustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Caclustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JACOZP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Caclustarcha aselella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Caclustarcha ilavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caclustarcha ilavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ilavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOZP01 sp016203205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.46 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Caclustarcha ugepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caclustarcha ugepia (N.L. fem. n. *ugepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOZP01 sp016203215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.27 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Caclustarcha utedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caclustarcha utedana (N.L. fem. n. *utedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOZP01 sp018302605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.24 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cacrosarcha efabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cacrosarcha efabaria (N.L. fem. n. *efabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIPG01 sp018894775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018894775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.43 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cacrosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cacrosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cacrosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIPG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cacrosarcha efabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cexitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cadolarcha ivacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cadolarcha ivacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 0-14-0-20-30-16 sp002779075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002779075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.71 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cadolarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cadolarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cadolarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 0-14-0-20-30-16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cadolarcha ivacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cadolarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cadolarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cadolarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cadolarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is 0-14-0-20-30-16. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cadolarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Forterreales*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Cadolarcha ubenaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cadolarcha ubenaria (N.L. fem. n. *ubenaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is 0-14-0-20-30-16 sp903916665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903916665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.68 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cadrafarcha uracia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cadrafarcha uracia (N.L. fem. n. *uracia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQC01 sp015520425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.35 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cadrafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cadrafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cadrafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cadrafarcha uracia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Caldarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Caldisphaera epagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caldisphaera epagaria (N.L. fem. n. *epagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Caldisphaera sp015523575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.94 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Caldisphaera omeposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caldisphaera omeposa (N.L. fem. n. *omeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Caldisphaera sp015522625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.9 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Caldisphaera otevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caldisphaera otevana (N.L. fem. n. *otevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Caldisphaera* sp002506595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.62 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Caldisphaera ulacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Caldisphaera ulacana* (N.L. fem. n. *ulacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Caldisphaera* sp002877855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002877855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.99 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Caldivirga onexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Caldivirga onexaria* (N.L. fem. n. *onexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Caldivirga* sp002506515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.3 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Caldivirga opabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Caldivirga opabella* (N.L. fem. n. *opabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Caldivirga* sp001663375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011054495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.44 % and the genome length is 2.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Camoparcha ogaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Camoparcha ogaxana* (N.L. fem. n. *ogaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA11716 sp9638u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.36 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Camoparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Camoparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Camoparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA11716. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Camoparcha ogaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Camoparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Camoparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Camoparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Camoparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA11716. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Camoparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Caprafrarcha odecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caprafrarcha odecella (N.L. fem. n. *odecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYN01 sp018303265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.03 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Caprafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Caprafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Caprafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Caprafrarcha odecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Casatrarcha ocapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Casatrarcha ocapana (N.L. fem. n. *ocapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JADGNF01 sp017883615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017883615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.57 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Casatrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Casatrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Casatrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JADGNF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Casatrarcha ocapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Casibarcha ifaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Casibarcha ifaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA12030 sp10106u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.53 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Casibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Casibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Casibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA12030. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Casibarcha ifaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Casibarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Casibarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Casibarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Casibarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA12030. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Casibarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Pacearchaeales.

Description of *Candidatus Castonarcha icebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Castonarcha icebosa (N.L. fem. n. *icebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADER01 sp013154355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013154355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.73 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Castonarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Castonarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Castonarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADER01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Castonarcha icebosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermocladaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Castonarcha igafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Castonarcha igafaria (N.L. fem. n. *igafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADER01 sp013153275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013153275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.75 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Castonarcha omacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Castonarcha omacana (N.L. fem. n. *omacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADER01 sp013153895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013153895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.18 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Catrabrarcha usabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Catrabrarcha usabella (N.L. fem. n. *usabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B1-G15 sp003662715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.57 % and the genome length is 2.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Catrabrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Catrabrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Catrabrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B1-G15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Catrabrarcha usabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Saxararchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Caxorarcha udaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Caxorarcha udaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *udaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA97 sp001871595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001871595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.75 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "groundwater filtered through a 3.0 um filter and then through a 0.2 um filter".

Description of *Candidatus Caxorarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Caxorarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Caxorarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA97. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Caxorarcha udaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Caxorarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Caxorarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Caxorarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Caxorarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA97. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Caxorarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ceblosarcha afavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ceblosarcha afavaria (N.L. fem. n. *afavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WUQU01 sp009889605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009889605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.25 % and the genome length is 2.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ceblosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ceblosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ceblosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WUQU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ceblosarcha afavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ceclecrarcha omexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ceclecrarcha omexosa (N.L. fem. n. *omexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QS-1-68-17 sp003021105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.32 % and the genome length is 2.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ceclecrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ceclecrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ceclecrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QS-1-68-17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ceclecrarcha omexosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloarculaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ceclemarcha afadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ceclेमarcha afadaria (N.L. fem. n. *afadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2687275 sp002687275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002687275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.67 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Ceclेमarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Ceclेमarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ceclेमarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2687275. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ceclेमarcha afadaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Cefrosarcha eravosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Cefrosarcha eravosa (N.L. fem. n. *eravosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is G60ANME1 sp003194435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003194435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.84 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Cefrosarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Cefrosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cefrosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is G60ANME1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Cefrosarcha eravosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Cenarchaeum ebecosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Cenarchaeum ebecosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Cenarchaeum* sp007570915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007570915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.14 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cenarchaeum itavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cenarchaeum itavella (N.L. fem. n. *itavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Cenarchaeum* sp003724275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003724175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.51 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cenurarcha epadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cenurarcha epadia (N.L. fem. n. *epadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOZS01 sp016181215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.44 % and the genome length is 0.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cenurarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cenurarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cenurarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOZS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cenurarcha epadia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cenurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cenurarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cenurarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cenurarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACOZS01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cenurarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cericrarcha ogexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cericrarcha ogexaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8941 sp016867505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016867505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.67 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cericrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cericrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cericrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA8941. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cericrarcha ogexaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ibidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cericrarcha phabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cericrarcha phabia (N.L. fem. n. *phabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8941 sp8941u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.89 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cericrarcha ubemosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cericrarcha ubemosa (N.L. fem. n. *ubemosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8941 sp016930055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016930055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.92 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cericrarcha udacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cericrarcha udacia (N.L. fem. n. *udacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8941 sp001774245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001774245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.8 % and the genome length is 2.08

Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 13ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Cericrarcha ugafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cericrarcha ugafana (N.L. fem. n. *ugafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8941 sp017883585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017883585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.91 % and the genome length is 1.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cesedarcha igaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cesedarcha igaparia (N.L. fem. n. *igaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is NZ13-MG1 sp003056285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003056285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.29 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cesedarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cesedarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cesedarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is NZ13-MG1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cesedarcha igaparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cesedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cesedarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cesedarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cesedarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is NZ13-MGT. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cesedarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Caldarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cesedarcha quaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cesedarcha quaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *quaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is NZ13-MG1 sp011364235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.14 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cesedarcha utagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cesedarcha utagia (N.L. fem. n. *utagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is NZ13-MG1 sp011363045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011331845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.7 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cesifrarcha ubafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cesifrarcha ubafella (N.L. fem. n. *ubafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S143-140 sp015521205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.95 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cesifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cesifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cesifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S143-140. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cesifrarcha ubafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Acidilobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cesticrarcha epegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cesticrarcha epegella (N.L. fem. n. *epegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J101 sp003695435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003695435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.23 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cesticrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cesticrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cesticrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J101. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cesticrarcha epegella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hicuparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cestotarcha edexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cestotarcha edexaria (N.L. fem. n. *edexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10210 sp018304285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.49 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cestotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cestotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cestotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10210. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cestotarcha edexaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cestotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cestotarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cestotarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cestotarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10210. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cestotarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cestotarcha ifesella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cestotarcha ifesella (N.L. fem. n. *ifesella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10210 sp10210u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.58 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cetrararcha utaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cetrararcha utaposa (N.L. fem. n. *utaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSZD01 sp011364805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.67 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cetrararcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cetrararcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cetrararcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSZD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cetrararcha utaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cexitarcha otegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cexitarcha otegella (N.L. fem. n. *otegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGLX01 sp016866645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016866645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.3 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cexitarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cexitarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cexitarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGLX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cexitarcha otegella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cexitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cexitarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cexitarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cexitarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is VGLX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cexitarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cibetarcha etafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cibetarcha etafella (N.L. fem. n. *etafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MCBC01 sp001723855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001723855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.83 % and the genome length is 2.09 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-methane transition zone estuary sediments 16-26 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Cibetarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cibetarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cibetarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MCBC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cibetarcha etafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cibetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cibetarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cibetarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cibetarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is MCBC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cibetarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Usinarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ciclobarcha egaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ciclobarcha egaxia (N.L. fem. n. *egaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHYY01 sp018653605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018653605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.28 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ciclobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ciclobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ciclobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHYY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ciclobarcha egaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cifranarcha etabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cifranarcha etabaria (N.L. fem. n. *etabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPIK01 sp016188115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.62 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cifranarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cifranarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cifranarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPIK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cifranarcha etabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cimetrarcha esabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cimetrarcha esabaria (N.L. fem. n. *esabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PIYA01 sp003601785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_003662325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.6 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cimetrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cimetrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cimetrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PIYA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cimetrarcha esabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Citucrarcha ivacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Citucrarcha ivacia (N.L. fem. n. *ivacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHYIG01 sp018815265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018815265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.02 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Citucrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Citucrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Citucrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHYIG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Citucrarcha ivacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiragarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cixedrarcha acagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cixedrarcha acagaria (N.L. fem. n. *acagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MVRE01 sp002067895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.47 % and the genome length is 2.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cixedrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cixedrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cixedrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MVRE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cixedrarcha acagara*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanoregulaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cixedrarcha umapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cixedrarcha umapella (N.L. fem. n. *umapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MVRE01 sp903900025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903900025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.85 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cixedrarcha uvaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cixedrarcha uvaxella (N.L. fem. n. *uvaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MVRE01 sp015660965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015660965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.36 % and the genome length is 2.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clafrudarcha elafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clafrudarcha elafella (N.L. fem. n. *elafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAANXH01 sp018263355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018263355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.42 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clafrudarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clafrudarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clafrudarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAANXH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clafrudarcha elafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Tafrurarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Clamasarcha emagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clamasarcha emagella (N.L. fem. n. *emagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPAH01 sp016180925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.68 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clamasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clamasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clamasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPAH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clamasarcha emagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Clamasarcha iteposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clamasarcha iteposa (N.L. fem. n. *iteposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPAH01 sp016187365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.07 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clatrunarcha alebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clatrunarcha alebosa (N.L. fem. n. *alebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGWAD01 sp018302105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.73 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clatrunarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clatrunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clatrunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGWAD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clatrunarcha alebosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Deraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Clexisarcha apabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clexisarcha apabella (N.L. fem. n. *apabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCCL01 sp017610205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.69 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clexisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clexisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clexisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCCL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clexisarcha apabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nogelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Clexisarcha ecavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clexisarcha ecavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCCL01 sp017610485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.98 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clexisarcha icafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clexisarcha icafana (N.L. fem. n. *icafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCCL01 sp017610265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.14 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clexisarcha idapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clexisarcha idapella (N.L. fem. n. *idapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCCL01 sp017610335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.4 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Climedarcha ivadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Climedarcha ivadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABJPM01 sp018663865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018696535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.87 % and the genome length is 0.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Climedarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Climedarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Climedarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABJPM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Climedarcha ivadaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nipetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Climedarcha otexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Climedarcha otexosa (N.L. fem. n. *otexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABJPM01 sp018693795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018693795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.81 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Climufarcha agafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Climufarcha agafella (N.L. fem. n. *agafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JABJOX01 sp018664115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018664115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.36 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Climufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Climufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Climufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABJOX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Climufarcha agafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Climufarcha ibadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Climufarcha ibadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ibadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABJOX01 sp018696595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018656325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.28 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Climufarcha ilemaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Climufarcha ilemaria (N.L. fem. n. *ilemaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABJOX01 sp018670095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018670095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.43 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clipidarcha ebagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clipidarcha ebagia (N.L. fem. n. *ebagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJAV01 sp018813685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018816725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.87 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clipidarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clipidarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clipidarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJAV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Clipidarcha ebagia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hocularhaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Cliposarcha ebafaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Cliposarcha ebafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA147 sp002496385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.98 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Cliposarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Cliposarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cliposarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA147. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Cliposarcha ebafaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ocuparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Cliposarcha ecagia sp. nov.

Candidatus Cliposarcha ecagia (N.L. fem. n. *ecagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA147 sp002499085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.26 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Cliposarcha ifaxella sp. nov.

Candidatus Cliposarcha ifaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA147 sp013791785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_018899285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.46 % and the genome length is 2.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clistumarcha omavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clistumarcha omavana (N.L. fem. n. *omavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQW01 sp015520045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.51 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clistumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clistumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clistumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clistumarcha omavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermoplasmataceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Clitrebarcha acevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clitrebarcha acevosa (N.L. fem. n. *acevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA582 sp002502705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.26 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clitrebarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clitrebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clitrebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA582. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clitrebarcha acevosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermoplasmataceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Clitrebarcha uceposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clitrebarcha uceposa (N.L. fem. n. *uceposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA582 sp011370275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011370275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.24 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clofiparcha opafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clofiparcha opafana (N.L. fem. n. *opafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPID01 sp016188265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.27 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clofiparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clofiparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clofiparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPID01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clofiparcha opafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Clomoxarcha ovaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clomoxarcha ovaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ovaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOVN01 sp016177315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016177315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.97 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clomoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clomoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clomoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOVN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clomoxarcha ovaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Hamosarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Clufrisarcha ogexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Clufrisarcha ogexia (N.L. fem. n. *ogexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B5-G16 sp003662995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.41 % and the genome length is 2.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Clufrisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Clufrisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Clufrisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B5-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Clufrisarcha ogexia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Archaeoglobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cluxonarcha orafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cluxonarcha orafia (N.L. fem. n. *orafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBP01 sp011366735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011366735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.15 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cluxonarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cluxonarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cluxonarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTBP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cluxonarcha orafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Desulfurococcaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cobisarcha ifamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cobisarcha ifamia (N.L. fem. n. *ifamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2685855 sp002685855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002685855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.3 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cobisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cobisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cobisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2685855. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Cobisarcha ifamia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cobisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cobisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cobisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cobisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-2685855. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Cobisarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Coblanarcha itabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Coblanarcha itabaria (N.L. fem. n. *itabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LC-3 sp001940645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001940645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.72 % and the genome length is 5.68 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "LokiAmp MDA-amplified sample from Loki s castle hydrothermal vent sediment".

Description of *Candidatus Coblanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Coblanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Coblanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is LC-3. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Coblanarcha itabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coblanarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Coblanarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Coblanarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Coblanarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is LC-3. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Coblanarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hodarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cobritarcha ugavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cobritarcha ugavella (N.L. fem. n. *ugavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSAL01 sp011380095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011380095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.88 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cobritarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cobritarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cobritarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSAL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cobritarcha ugavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiragarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cobustarcha emafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cobustarcha emafosa (N.L. fem. n. *emafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B44-G15 sp003649845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.5 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cobustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cobustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cobustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B44-G15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cobustarcha emafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cocloxarcha evabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cocloxarcha evabia (N.L. fem. n. *evabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIXOA01 sp013425455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013425455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.13 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cocloxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cocloxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cocloxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIXOA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cocloxarcha evabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cocloxarcha opaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cocloxarcha opaxia (N.L. fem. n. *opaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIXOA01 sp903920925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903920925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.51 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cocrafarcha afaivia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cocrafarcha afaivia (N.L. fem. n. *afaivia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-20 sp005877305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005877115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.45 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cocrafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cocrafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cocrafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TA-20. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cocrafarcha afavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cocrafarcha ucenaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cocrafarcha ucenaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucenaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-20 sp016201435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016201435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.5 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cocrafarcha unavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cocrafarcha unavella (N.L. fem. n. *unavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-20 sp013287585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013287585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.4 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cocrafarcha uvabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cocrafarcha uvabia (N.L. fem. n. *uvabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-20 sp007280335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007280335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.51 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cofanarcha ifepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cofanarcha ifepana (N.L. fem. n. *ifepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAZKV01 sp012799645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012799645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.06 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cofanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cofanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cofanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAZKV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cofanarcha ifepana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cofanarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cofanarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cofanarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cofanarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAAZKV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cofanarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cofanarcha onacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cofanarcha onacosa (N.L. fem. n. *onacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAZKV01 sp902385225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.59 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cofanarcha onemosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cofanarcha onemosa (N.L. fem. n. *onemosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JAAZKV01 sp002068885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002068885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.23 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cofodrarcha idafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cofodrarcha idafella (N.L. fem. n. *idafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA206 sp002503105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.0 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cofodrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cofodrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cofodrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA206. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cofodrarcha idafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanoculleaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cofrixarcha acafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cofrixarcha acafosa (N.L. fem. n. *acafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B1-Br10-U2g19 sp001563905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.95 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample B1-Br-g2; brine of Lake Bitter-1".

Description of *Candidatus Cofrixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cofrixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cofrixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B1-Br10-U2g19. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cofrixarcha acafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nanosalineeae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cofrixarcha udaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cofrixarcha udaxia (N.L. fem. n. *udaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B1-Br10-U2g19 sp001563875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001564195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.36 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample PL-Br10; brine of Picturesque Lake".

Description of *Candidatus Conexivisphaera asaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Conexivisphaera asaxana (N.L. fem. n. *asaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Conexivisphaera* sp011054345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011054345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.85 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Costatrarcha enexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Costatrarcha enexia (N.L. fem. n. *enexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRBY01 sp011042755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011042755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.12 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Costatrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Costatrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Costatrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRBY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Costatrarcha enexia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Korarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Costoparcha efacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Costoparcha efacia (N.L. fem. n. *efacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPNI01 sp016185555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.04 % and the genome length is 0.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Costoparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Costoparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Costoparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPNI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Costoparcha efacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cotricrarcha omexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cotricrarcha omexana (N.L. fem. n. *omexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJRB01 sp018831025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018831025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.72 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cotricrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cotricrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cotricrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJRB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cotricrarcha omexana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lagoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Coxenarcha umexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Coxenarcha umexaria (N.L. fem. n. *umexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-13 sp002011075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002011075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.62 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Coxenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Coxenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Coxenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-13. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Coxenarcha umexaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Coxenarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Coxenarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Coxenarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JdFR-13. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Coxenarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Geothermarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Coxistarcha amevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Coxistarcha amevella (N.L. fem. n. *amevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJJB01 sp014729935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.9 % and the genome length is 4.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Coxistarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Coxistarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Coxistarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJJB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Coxistarcha amevella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxistarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Coxistarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Coxistarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Coxistarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJJB01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Coxosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Promethoarchaeales*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Coxosarcha itadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Coxosarcha itadana (N.L. fem. n. *itadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR5 sp018304605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.18 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Coxosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Coxosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Coxosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR5. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Coxosarcha itadana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Coxosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Coxosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Coxosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR5. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Coxosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Coxosarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Coxosarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Coxosarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Coxosarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR5. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Coxosarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Aenigmatarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Coxosarcha obapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Coxosarcha obapia (N.L. fem. n. *obapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR5 sp10154u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.6 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Coxosarcha umabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Coxosarcha umabaria (N.L. fem. n. *umabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR5 sp000806115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000806115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.01 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle groundwater metagenome at time 1".

Description of *Candidatus Cradaxarcha ifarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cradaxarcha ifarella (N.L. fem. n. *ifarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS1285 sp002688335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.97 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cradaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cradaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cradaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS1285. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cradaxarcha ifarella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cradaxarcha ipafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cradaxarcha ipafana (N.L. fem. n. *ipafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS1285 sp002688875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.48 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Cradaxarcha uvagana sp. nov.

Candidatus Cradaxarcha uvagana (N.L. fem. n. *uvagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS1285 sp002688165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014240435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.09 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Cretofarcha vucia sp. nov.

Candidatus Cretofarcha vucia (N.L. fem. n. *vucia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHWZ01 sp018657525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018693615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.13 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Cretofarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Cretofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cretofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHWZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Cretofarcha vucia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Cribefarcha epecella sp. nov.

Candidatus Cribefarcha epecella (N.L. fem. n. *epecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WRKA01 sp009780795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009780795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.51 % and the genome length is 1.2

Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cribefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cribefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cribefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WRKA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cribefarcha epecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cribefarcha icafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cribefarcha icafia (N.L. fem. n. *icafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WRKA01 sp009780575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009780575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.65 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cribefarcha ipatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cribefarcha ipatosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WRKA01 sp009776695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009776695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.57 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cribefarcha ucalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cribefarcha ucalaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WRKA01 sp009778265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009778265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.89 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cribefarcha umaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cribefarcha umaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *umaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WRKA01 sp009784745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009784745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.48 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crifinarcha osaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crifinarcha osaxia (N.L. fem. n. *osaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJV01 sp016187395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.84 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crifinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Crifinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Crifinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPJV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Crifinarcha osaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tefagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Crimeparcha apabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crimeparcha apabaria (N.L. fem. n. *apabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FEN-33 sp016919565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016919565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.22 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crimeparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Crimeparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Crimeparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is FEN-33. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Crimeparcha apabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sogexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Crimeparcha ipalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crimeparcha ipalia (N.L. fem. n. *ipalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FEN-33 sp003153895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003153895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.03 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crimeparcha ufecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crimeparcha ufecia (N.L. fem. n. *ufecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FEN-33 sp003135935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003135935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.65 % and the genome length is 2.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cristexarcha abevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cristexarcha abevella (N.L. fem. n. *abevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAON01 sp015521265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.54 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cristexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cristexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cristexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAON01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cristexarcha abevella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Desulfurococcaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Crixafarcha opagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crixafarcha opagaria (N.L. fem. n. *opagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JACAFH01 sp013538715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013538715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.89 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crixafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Crixafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Crixafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACAFH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Crixafarcha opagara*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosocaldaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Crixibarcha avefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crixibarcha avefia (N.L. fem. n. *avefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-8 sp008080735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008080735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.6 % and the genome length is 4.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crixibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Crixibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Crixibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TEKIR-8. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Crixibarcha avefia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Crixibarcha ilacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crixibarcha ilacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ilacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-8 sp008080765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008080765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.19 % and the genome length is 3.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crixibarcha odagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crixibarcha odagella (N.L. fem. n. *odagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-8 sp014730165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014730125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.87 % and the genome length is 5.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Crixibarcha opamana sp. nov.

Candidatus Crixibarcha opamana (N.L. fem. n. *opamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-8 sp004524365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.01 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Crixibarcha otamaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Crixibarcha otamaria (N.L. fem. n. *otamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-8 sp016839555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.57 % and the genome length is 3.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Crixibarcha upetia sp. nov.

Candidatus Crixibarcha upetia (N.L. fem. n. *upetia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-8 sp014730295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014730295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.41 % and the genome length is 6.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Crodruxarcha ebexaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Crodruxarcha ebexaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is A-MIC-10 sp014874295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014874295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.02 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crodruxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Crodruxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Crodruxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is A-MIC-10. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Crodruxarcha ebexaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Micrarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Crostutarcha epaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crostutarcha epaxia (N.L. fem. n. *epaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHLM001 sp018920305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018920305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 25.5 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crostutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Crostutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Crostutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHLM001. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Crostutarcha epaxia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Disocarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Crubrexarcha ogemaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Crubrexarcha ogemaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogemaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS750m-G28 sp016783455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016783455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.52 % and the genome length is 2.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Crubrexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Crubrexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Crubrexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BS750m-G28. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Crubrexarcha ogemaria*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ibidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cubocrarcha acaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cubocrarcha acaxana (N.L. fem. n. *acaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8886 sp002509165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.9 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cubocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cubocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cubocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA8886. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cubocrarcha acaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Naporarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cubocrarcha efaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cubocrarcha efaposa (N.L. fem. n. *efaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8886 sp003193815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003193815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.42 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cubocrarcha evegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cubocrarcha evegella (N.L. fem. n. *evegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8886 sp002731905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002731905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.91 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cubocrarcha omafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cubocrarcha omafaria (N.L. fem. n. *omafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8886 sp002687355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002687355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.4 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cubocrarcha upafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cubocrarcha upafosa (N.L. fem. n. *upafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8886 sp002731655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004195655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.55 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cumaxarcha ipalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cumaxarcha ipalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RDOG01 sp011365055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011365055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.06 % and the genome length is 4.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cumaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cumaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cumaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is RDOG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Cumaxarcha ipalosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cumaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cumaxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cumaxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cumaxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

taxon is RDOG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cumaxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Helarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cunadarcha ocepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cunadarcha ocepella (N.L. fem. n. *ocepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRMX01 sp016219485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016219485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.49 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cunadarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cunadarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cunadarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRMX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cunadarcha ocepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cunadarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cunadarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cunadarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cunadarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACRMX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cunadarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Coxosarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Curatrarcha acegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Curatrarcha acegana (N.L. fem. n. *acegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RumEn-M2 sp002506255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.09 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Curatrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Curatrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Curatrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is RumEn-M2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Curatrarcha acegana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Curatrarcha etafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Curatrarcha etafia (N.L. fem. n. *etafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RumEn-M2 sp012522645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012522645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.5 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Curatrarcha pefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Curatrarcha pefella (N.L. fem. n. *pefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RumEn-M2 sp001421175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.15 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Curatrarcha ufavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Curatrarcha ufavana (N.L. fem. n. *ufavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RumEn-M2 sp002502965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.26 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cutiparcha ifacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cutiparcha ifacia (N.L. fem. n. *ifacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is DTMW01 sp011355145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011355145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.59 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cutiparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cutiparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cutiparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTMW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Cutiparcha ifacia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cutiparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cutiparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cutiparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cutiparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTMW01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Cutiparcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hiturarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cutrubarcha inemosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cutrubarcha inemosa (N.L. fem. n. *inemosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is YT1-039 sp016840025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.9 % and the genome length is 6.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cutrubarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cutrubarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cutrubarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is YT1-039. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Cutrubarcha inemosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cutrubarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Cutrubarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Cutrubarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cutrubarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is YT1-039. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Cutrubarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hodarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Cutuprarcha opavosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Cutuprarcha opavosa (N.L. fem. n. *opavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHWJ01 sp018657845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018657845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.29 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Cutuprarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Cutuprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cutuprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHWJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Cutuprarcha opavosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Cuxoprarcha ofegella sp. nov.

Candidatus Cuxoprarcha ofegella (N.L. fem. n. *ofegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS1178 sp002688325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.75 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Cuxoprarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Cuxoprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cuxoprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS1178. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cuxoprarcha ofegella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cuxoprarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cuxoprarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cuxoprarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cuxoprarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is ARS1178. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cuxoprarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Cuxufarcha efarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Cuxufarcha efarana (N.L. fem. n. *efarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDX01 sp017609465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.59 % and the genome length is 0.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Cuxufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Cuxufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Cuxufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Cuxufarcha efarana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cuxufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Cuxufarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Cuxufarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Cuxufarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFCDX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Cuxufarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Ogusarchales.

Description of *Candidatus Dablicrarcha ebevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dablicrarcha ebevia (N.L. fem. n. *ebevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJSW01 sp018830245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.78 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dablicrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dablicrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dablicrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJSW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dablicrarcha ebevia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dadribarcha amapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dadribarcha amapia (N.L. fem. n. *amapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688265 sp018697095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018697095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.61 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dadribarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dadribarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dadribarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2688265. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dadribarcha amapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dadribarcha idafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dadribarcha idafaria (N.L. fem. n. *idafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688265 sp002688265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.2 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dadribarcha udaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dadribarcha udaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *udaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688265 sp018670085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018656565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.18 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dadrufarcha avaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dadrufarcha avaxia (N.L. fem. n. *avaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SW-9-67-25 sp018609945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018609945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.25 % and the genome length is 2.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dadrufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dadrufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dadrufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SW-9-67-25. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dadrufarcha avaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloarculaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dadrufarcha egabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dadrufarcha egabella (N.L. fem. n. *egabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SW-9-67-25 sp003022745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.1 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dadrufarcha ufebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dadrufarcha ufebana (N.L. fem. n. *ufebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SW-9-67-25 sp003023485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.02 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dafruxarcha efavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dafruxarcha efavia (N.L. fem. n. *efavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JGI-OTU-1 sp011364265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.83 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dafruxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dafruxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dafruxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JGI-OTU-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dafruxarcha efavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiserarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dafruxarcha egaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dafruxarcha egaria (N.L. fem. n. *egaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JGI-OTU-1 sp000494145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000405905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.08 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Daliprarcha esafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Daliprarcha esafana (N.L. fem. n. *esafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is PXYB01 sp003352285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003352285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.55 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Daliprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Daliprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Daliprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PXYB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Daliprarcha esafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Daliprarcha inacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Daliprarcha inacia (N.L. fem. n. *inacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PXYB01 sp014078545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_014078545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.78 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dalofarcha idatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dalofarcha idatella (N.L. fem. n. *idatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTDM01 sp011362245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011366965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.95 % and the genome length is 2.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dalofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dalofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dalofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTDM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dalofarcha idatella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dalofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dalofarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dalofarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dalofarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTDM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Dalofarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Dalofarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dalofarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Dalofarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Dalofarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTDM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Dalofarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Methanomethylica*.

Description of *Candidatus* Danibarcha edavana sp. nov.

Candidatus Danibarcha edavana (N.L. fem. n. *edavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZN01 sp011605775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011605775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.17 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Danibarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Danibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Danibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOZN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Danibarcha edavana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Danibarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Danibarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Danibarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Danibarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAAOZN01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Danibarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Danibarcha upaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Danibarcha upaxella (N.L. fem. n. *upaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZN01 sp011355215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011355215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.29 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dapodrarcha erepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dapodrarcha erepella (N.L. fem. n. *erepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-13-33-26 sp012798335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012798335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 26.18 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dapodrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dapodrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dapodrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is RBG-13-33-26. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dapodrarcha erepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dapodrarcha phavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dapodrarcha phavia (N.L. fem. n. *phavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-13-33-26 sp001786415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001786415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.44 % and the genome length is 0.6 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 19ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Dapodrarcha utedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dapodrarcha utedaria (N.L. fem. n. *utedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-13-33-26 sp902386025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902386025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.35 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dastagrarcha elafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dastagrarcha elafosa (N.L. fem. n. *elafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKI01 sp016929895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016929895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.05 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dastagrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dastagrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dastagrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJKI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dastagrarcha elafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dastagrarcha erebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dastagrarcha erebaria (N.L. fem. n. *erebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKI01 sp014729195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.45 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dastunarcha asabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dastunarcha asabia (N.L. fem. n. *asabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is MGIIb-P sp002722595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002722595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.71 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dastunarcha gen. nov.*

Candidatus Dastunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dastunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIb-P. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dastunarcha asabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thalassarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dastunarcha puxana sp. nov.*

Candidatus Dastunarcha puxana (N.L. fem. n. *puxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-P sp002498455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.97 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dastunarcha quaxaria sp. nov.*

Candidatus Dastunarcha quaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *quaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-P sp002505685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002719355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.28 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dastunarcha unafaria sp. nov.*

Candidatus Dastunarcha unafaria (N.L. fem. n. *unafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-P sp002701965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002701965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.45 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dastunarcha utafaria sp. nov.*

Candidatus Dastunarcha utafaria (N.L. fem. n. *utafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-P sp002724815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002724815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.5 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dastunarcha uvecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dastunarcha uvecella (N.L. fem. n. *uvecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-P sp002457195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002457195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.15 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Debefarcha avabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Debefarcha avabana (N.L. fem. n. *avabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQJH01 sp016205145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016205145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.31 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Debefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Debefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Debefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQJH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Debefarcha avabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Debefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Debefarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Debefarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Debefarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQJH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Debefarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Iainarchaeales.

Description of *Candidatus Debifrarcha itepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Debifrarcha itepella (N.L. fem. n. *itepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGTRB01 sp018396515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.3 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Debifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Debifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Debifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGTRB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Debifrarcha itepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ibidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Debifrarcha ivagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Debifrarcha ivagana (N.L. fem. n. *ivagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGTRB01 sp018396865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.84 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deblustarcha anacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deblustarcha anacia (N.L. fem. n. *anacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B46-G15 sp003662205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.89 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deblustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Deblustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Deblustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B46-G15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Deblustarcha anacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ibidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Degufrarcha osebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Degufrarcha osebella (N.L. fem. n. *osebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SDNM01 sp004524385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.48 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Degufrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Degufrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Degufrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SDNM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Degufrarcha osebella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Degufrarcha udexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Degufrarcha udexosa (N.L. fem. n. *udexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SDNM01 sp019058295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.77 % and the genome length is 3.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Degufrarcha unarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Degufrarcha unarella (N.L. fem. n. *unarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SDNM01 sp004524535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.4 % and the genome length is 3.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Degifarcha ecararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Degifarcha ecararia (N.L. fem. n. *ecararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABICX01 sp018652045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018650885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.89 % and the genome length is 0.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Degifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Degifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Degifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABICX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Degifarcha ecararia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Degifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Degifarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Degifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Degifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JABICX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Degifarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Laxucarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Degifarcha ufebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Degifarcha ufebia (N.L. fem. n. *ufebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABICX01 sp018692915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018692915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.22 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha ebapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha ebapella (N.L. fem. n. *ebapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002685415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002685415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.68 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Deglofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIb-O1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Deglofarcha ebapella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thalassarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha efataria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha efataria (N.L. fem. n. *efataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002457555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002501975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.86 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha egabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha egabana (N.L. fem. n. *egabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002457595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002457595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.65 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha ifagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha ifagia (N.L. fem. n. *ifagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp8684u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.05 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha isabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha isabia (N.L. fem. n. *isabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002502365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.51 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Deglofarcha ivalaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha ivalaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp902560445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902560445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.12 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Deglofarcha ivecella sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha ivecella (N.L. fem. n. *ivecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp016845365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016845365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.15 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Deglofarcha mivosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha mivosa (N.L. fem. n. *mivosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002502175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.58 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Deglofarcha opabosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha opabosa (N.L. fem. n. *opabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002498725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.43 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha ovacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha ovacia (N.L. fem. n. *ovacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002497025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.99 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha puxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha puxella (N.L. fem. n. *puxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002498525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004195625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.27 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha ucaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha ucaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002708385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002708385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.51 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha unabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha unabosa (N.L. fem. n. *unabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp12570u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.54 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha upagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha upagana (N.L. fem. n. *upagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002497895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.11 % and the genome length is

1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Deglofarcha utapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deglofarcha utapella (N.L. fem. n. *utapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O1 sp002496905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.64 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Degrexarcha ivabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Degrexarcha ivabana (N.L. fem. n. *ivabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHILJ01 sp018897135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018818075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.67 % and the genome length is 0.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Degrexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Degrexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Degrexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHILJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Degrexarcha ivabana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Deraparcha enagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Deraparcha enagana (N.L. fem. n. *enagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR18 sp000806155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000806155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.72 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle groundwater metagenome at time 1".

Description of *Candidatus Deraparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Deraparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Deraparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR18. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Deraparcha enagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Deraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Deraparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Deraparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Deraparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR18. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Deraparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Oqusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Diblafarcha edafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Diblafarcha edafia (N.L. fem. n. *edafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAF CGC01 sp017608305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.97 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Diblafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Diblafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Diblafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAF CGC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Diblafarcha edafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Diclocrarcha edefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Diclocrarcha edefana (N.L. fem. n. *edefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAF CFT01 sp017608505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.29 % and the genome length is

0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Diclocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Diclocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Diclocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFcFT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Diclocrarcha edefana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hubexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Didresarcha ilaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Didresarcha ilaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ilaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SpSt-971 sp011334385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011334385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.11 % and the genome length is 0.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Didresarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Didresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Didresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SpSt-971. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Didresarcha ilaxana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Didrograrcha esefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Didrograrcha esefia (N.L. fem. n. *esefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B82-G9 sp003649715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.7 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Didrograrcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Didrograrcha (N.L. fem. n. *Didrograrcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B82-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Didrograrcha esefia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Difregarcha edaparia sp. nov.

Candidatus Difregarcha edaparia (N.L. fem. n. *edaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZY01 sp003663415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.7 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Difregarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Difregarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Difregarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMZY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Difregarcha edaparia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dinafrarcha iraxana sp. nov.

Candidatus Dinafrarcha iraxana (N.L. fem. n. *iraxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PFDC01 sp002763035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002763035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.72 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dinafrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dinafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dinafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PFDC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dinafrarcha iraxana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Midifarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Dinufarcha udabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dinufarcha udabosa (N.L. fem. n. *udabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAPJ01 sp015520785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.34 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dinufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dinufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dinufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAPJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dinufarcha udabosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dinufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dinufarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dinufarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dinufarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WAPJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Dinufarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Diprifrarcha upelia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Diprifrarcha upelia (N.L. fem. n. *upelia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXO01 sp018303755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.51 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Diprifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Diprifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Diprifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Diprifrarcha upelia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Disocarcha imabia sp. nov.

Candidatus Disocarcha imabia (N.L. fem. n. *imabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-224 sp002254545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.75 % and the genome length is 0.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Disocarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Disocarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Disocarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-224. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Disocarcha imabia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Disocarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Disocarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Disocarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Disocarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-224. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Disocarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Isoxarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Distiprarcha iledia sp. nov.

Candidatus Distiprarcha iledia (N.L. fem. n. *iledia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JABLXE01 sp013178225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013178225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.74 % and the genome length is 2.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Distiprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Distiprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Distiprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABLXE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Distiprarcha iledia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanotrichaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Distofarcha edaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Distofarcha edaposa (N.L. fem. n. *edaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDW01 sp017609475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.76 % and the genome length is 0.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Distofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Distofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Distofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Distofarcha edaposa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Distuxarcha onapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Distuxarcha onapana (N.L. fem. n. *onapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGTQX01 sp018396675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.86 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Distuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Distuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Distuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGTQX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Distuxarcha onapana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dixemarcha eraposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Dixemarcha eraposa (N.L. fem. n. *eraposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGJJ01 sp016867455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016867455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.46 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dixemarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dixemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dixemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGJJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dixemarcha eraposa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dixemarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dixemarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Dixemarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dixemarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is VGJJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Dixemarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dixemarcha ifataria sp. nov.

Candidatus Dixemarcha ifataria (N.L. fem. n. *ifataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGJJ01 sp016699555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016699555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.96 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dobararcha agacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dobararcha agacana (N.L. fem. n. *agacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM23-78 sp016935175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.77 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dobararcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dobararcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dobararcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SM23-78. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dobararcha agacana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dobararchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dobararchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dobararchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dobararchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SM23-78. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Dobararcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Dobararcha opabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dobararcha opabia (N.L. fem. n. *opabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM23-78 sp018819305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018820305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.26 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dobararcha oraxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dobararcha oraxia (N.L. fem. n. *oraxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM23-78 sp011372335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011372335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.29 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dobararcha ovaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dobararcha ovaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ovaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM23-78 sp001595785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001595785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.74 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-methane transition zone estuary sediments 16-26 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Dobararcha ucafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dobararcha ucafana (N.L. fem. n. *ucafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM23-78 sp016932315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.54 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dodererarcha egapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dodererarcha egapana (N.L. fem. n. *egapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS750m-G81 sp016782405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016782405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.9 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dodererarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dodererarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dodererarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BS750m-G81. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dodererarcha egapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dofaxarcha ifavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dofaxarcha ifavella (N.L. fem. n. *ifavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTCF01 sp011364865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.29 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dofaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dofaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dofaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTCF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dofaxarcha ifavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dofaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dofaxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dofaxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dofaxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTCF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Dofaxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nezhaarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Dofesarcha adafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dofesarcha adafia (N.L. fem. n. *adafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMDW01 sp902385045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.5 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dofesarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dofesarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dofesarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CABMDW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dofesarcha adafia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dofesarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dofesarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Dofesarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dofesarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CABMDW01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Dofesarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Doglibarcha udaxella sp. nov.

Candidatus Doglibarcha udaxella (N.L. fem. n. *udaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIDZ01 sp018901755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018901755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.94 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Doglibarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Doglibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Doglibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIDZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Doglibarcha udaxella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aenigmataarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dolonarcha omexaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Dolonarcha omexaria (N.L. fem. n. *omexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FEN-987 sp001768965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001768965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.76 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 16ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Dolonarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dolonarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dolonarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is FEN-987. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dolonarcha omexaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dolonarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dolonarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dolonarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dolonarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is FEN-987. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Dolonarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omubarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Dolonarcha ufabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dolonarcha ufabia (N.L. fem. n. *ufabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FEN-987 sp003152955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003152955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.96 % and the genome length is 2.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dosicrarcha abevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dosicrarcha abevana (N.L. fem. n. *abevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIKOA01 sp014727925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014727925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.9 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dositrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dositrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dositrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIKOA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dositrarcha abevana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dositrarcha afadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dositrarcha afadia (N.L. fem. n. *afadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIKOA01 sp016932815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.71 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dositrarcha ibadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dositrarcha ibadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ibadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIKOA01 sp903828955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903922105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.6 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dositrarcha ifavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dositrarcha ifavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIKOA01 sp014727975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014727935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.99 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dostacarcha ilaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dostacarcha ilaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ilaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JABABT01 sp014238095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014238095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 24.3 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dostacarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dostacarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dostacarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABABT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dostacarcha ilaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dostacarcha iperana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dostacarcha iperana (N.L. fem. n. *iperana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABABT01 sp016213525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016213525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.31 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dosudrarcha ocapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dosudrarcha ocapella (N.L. fem. n. *ocapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPAS01 sp016180665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.38 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dosudrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dosudrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dosudrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPAS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dosudrarcha ocapella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drabilarcha unadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drabilarcha unadella (N.L. fem. n. *unadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4572-44 sp905171695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905171685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.51 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Drabilarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Drabilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drabilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4572-44. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drabilarcha unadella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ethanoperedentaceae*[@].

Description of *Candidatus* Drabilarcha utagara sp. nov.

Candidatus Drabilarcha utagara (N.L. fem. n. *utagara* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4572-44 sp002254825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254825.2. The GC content of the type genome is 46.29 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Drafasarcha epagella sp. nov.

Candidatus Drafasarcha epagella (N.L. fem. n. *epagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWKY01 sp003560595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003560595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.15 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Drafasarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Drafasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drafasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PWKY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drafasarcha epagella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natronoplasmataceae*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Drafasarcha irebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drafasarcha irebella (N.L. fem. n. *irebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWKY01 sp007133925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007133925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.04 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drafasarcha unavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drafasarcha unavaria (N.L. fem. n. *unavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWKY01 sp003553085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003553355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.99 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drafuxarcha omevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drafuxarcha omevana (N.L. fem. n. *omevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WUQV01 sp009889585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009889585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.44 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drafuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drafuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drafuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WUQV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Drafuxarcha omevana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Drafuxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drafuxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Drafuxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Drafuxarchaceae* a name created from the name of

the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WUQV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Drafuxarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omagarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dralabarcha ivapella sp. nov.

Candidatus Dralabarcha ivapella (N.L. fem. n. *ivapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA492 sp016185705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.47 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dralabarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dralabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dralabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA492. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dralabarcha ivapella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dralabarcha osavella sp. nov.

Candidatus Dralabarcha osavella (N.L. fem. n. *osavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA492 sp002688315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.79 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dralabarcha umavella sp. nov.

Candidatus Dralabarcha umavella (N.L. fem. n. *umavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA492 sp018303115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_018303115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.62 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Draxomarcha egaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Draxomarcha egaposa (N.L. fem. n. *egaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA6 sp002067635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.8 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Draxomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Draxomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Draxomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA6. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Draxomarcha egaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomassiliicoccaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Draxomarcha elagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Draxomarcha elagella (N.L. fem. n. *elagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA6 sp002508545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002508545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.74 % and the genome length is 2.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Draxomarcha esebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Draxomarcha esebia (N.L. fem. n. *esebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA6 sp012719175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012719175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.14 % and the genome length is 2.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Draxomarcha olacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Draxomarcha olacaria (N.L. fem. n. *olacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA6 sp016109435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016109435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.13 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Draxomarcha omepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Draxomarcha omepia (N.L. fem. n. *omepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA6 sp018262895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018262895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.42 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drebofarcha etaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drebofarcha etaxia (N.L. fem. n. *etaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIVQ01 sp018816585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018816585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.73 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drebofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drebofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drebofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIVQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drebofarcha etaxia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cuxufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dreceparcha agaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dreceparcha agaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *agaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPCE01 sp018302765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.23 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dreceparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dreceparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dreceparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPCE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dreceparcha agaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Deraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dreceparcha ovapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dreceparcha ovapia (N.L. fem. n. *ovapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPCE01 sp016179945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016179945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.3 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drepuxarcha omavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drepuxarcha omavaria (N.L. fem. n. *omavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1514 sp015661745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015661745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.44 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drepuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drepuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drepuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZUA-1514. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Drepuxarcha omavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drepuxarcha ubamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drepuxarcha ubamana (N.L. fem. n. *ubamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1514 sp015523605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.51 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drepuxarcha unadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drepuxarcha unadaria (N.L. fem. n. *unadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1514 sp015523545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.27 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drerasarcha ipabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drerasarcha ipabia (N.L. fem. n. *ipabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJMJ01 sp014729675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.24 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drerasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drerasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drerasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJMJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Drerasarcha ipabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Horetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drestoparcha ecaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drestoparcha ecaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ecaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGSP01 sp016934775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016934775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.07 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drestoparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drestoparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drestoparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGSP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drestoparcha ecaxia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hudomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Drestufarcha ubenana sp. nov.

Candidatus Drestufarcha ubenana (N.L. fem. n. *ubenana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACWAH01 sp014874365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014874365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.38 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Drestufarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Drestufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drestufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACWAH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drestufarcha ubenana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermoplasmataceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dricraparcha upetella sp. nov.

Candidatus Dricraparcha upetella (N.L. fem. n. *upetella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRIF01 sp011052825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011052825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.81 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dricraparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dricraparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dricraparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is DRIF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dricraparcha upetella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Parutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drigaxarcha emaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drigaxarcha emaposa (N.L. fem. n. *emaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS1301 sp017609205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.34 % and the genome length is 0.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drigaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drigaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drigaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS1301. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Drigaxarcha emaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drigaxarcha ogeposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drigaxarcha ogeposa (N.L. fem. n. *ogeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS1301 sp002686355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002686355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.92 % and the genome length is 0.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dripenarcha asedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dripenarcha asedosa (N.L. fem. n. *asedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10161 sp903892905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903892905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.68 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dripenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dripenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dripenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10161. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dripenarcha asedosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Anstonellaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dripenarcha otaxaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Dripenarcha otaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *otaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10161 sp10161u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013332015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.89 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Direxarcha ereposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Direxarcha ereposa (N.L. fem. n. *ereposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABMQF01 sp018830225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.04 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Direxarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Direxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Direxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABMQF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Direxarcha ereposa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hicuparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Direxarcha ovabia sp. nov.

Candidatus Direxarcha ovabia (N.L. fem. n. *ovabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JABMQF01 sp016929255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016929255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.13 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drirexarcha uvafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drirexarcha uvafaria (N.L. fem. n. *uvafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABMQF01 sp013203345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013203345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.85 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dristigarcha ufecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dristigarcha ufecana (N.L. fem. n. *ufecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYP01 sp018303205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.27 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dristigarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dristigarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dristigarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dristigarcha ufecana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Luglotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drofrexarcha ilacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drofrexarcha ilacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ilacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDM01 sp017609695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.88 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drofrexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drofrexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drofrexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Drofrefarcha ilacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drofrefarcha unegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drofrefarcha unegana (N.L. fem. n. *unegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDM01 sp017609795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.34 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drogifarcha ogaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drogifarcha ogaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ogaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PSPM01 sp004195435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012960605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.23 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drogifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drogifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drogifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PSPM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Drogifarcha ogaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drolefarcha egamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drolefarcha egamia (N.L. fem. n. *egamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PL-Br10-E2g29 sp001563965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank

assembly GCA_001563965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.21 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample PL-Br10; brine of Picturesque Lake".

Description of *Candidatus Drolefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drolefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drolefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PL-Br10-E2g29. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Drolefarcha egamia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloferacaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dronusarcha epabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dronusarcha epabia (N.L. fem. n. *epabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSZV01 sp011367065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011367065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.7 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dronusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dronusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dronusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSZV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dronusarcha epabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Acidilobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drosirarcha evafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drosirarcha evafella (N.L. fem. n. *evafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VBQP01 sp008297795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008297795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.83 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drosirarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drosirarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drosirarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VBQP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drosirarcha evafella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Puresarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Drostaxarcha itabella sp. nov.

Candidatus Drostaxarcha itabella (N.L. fem. n. *itabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOZM01 sp016181345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.41 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Drostaxarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Drostaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drostaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOZM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drostaxarcha itabella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Droxecarcha gaxella sp. nov.

Candidatus Droxecarcha gaxella (N.L. fem. n. *gaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA509 sp002498845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000447225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.23 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "isolated from slime streamers and attached to pyrite surfaces at a sulfide ore body".

Description of *Candidatus* Droxecarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Droxecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Droxecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA509. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Droxecarcha* *gaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermoplasmataceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Drubasarcha* *anacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Drubasarcha* *anacosa* (N.L. fem. n. *anacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VadinCA11 sp011620825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011620825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.19 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Drubasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus *Drubasarcha* (N.L. fem. n. *Drubasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VadinCA11. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Drubasarcha* *anacosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Drubasarcha* *cebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Drubasarcha* *cebella* (N.L. fem. n. *cebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VadinCA11 sp002498365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.69 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Drubasarcha* *epamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Drubasarcha* *epamia* (N.L. fem. n. *epamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VadinCA11 sp002498605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.02 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drubasarcha ipefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drubasarcha ipefosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VadinCA11 sp002509405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.94 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drubasarcha mubana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drubasarcha mubana (N.L. fem. n. *mubana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VadinCA11 sp002505345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.87 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drubraxarcha osebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drubraxarcha osebana (N.L. fem. n. *osebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAJW01 sp015523685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.24 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drubraxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drubraxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drubraxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAJW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drubraxarcha osebana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rosutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Drustularcha abemia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Drustularcha abemia (N.L. fem. n. *abemia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is WALT01 sp015522695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.54 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Drustularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Drustularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Drustularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Drustularcha abemia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Conexivisphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dublinarcha ugaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dublinarcha ugaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ugaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZJ01 sp003663115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.55 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dublinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dublinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dublinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMZJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dublinarcha ugaposa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lanaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dudraxarcha epabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dudraxarcha epabosa (N.L. fem. n. *epabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ANME1a sp003194425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003194425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.19 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dudraxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dudraxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dudraxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ANME1a. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dudraxarcha epabosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dudribrarcha afedosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Dudribrarcha afedosa (N.L. fem. n. *afedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPTB01 sp016192995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016192995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.07 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dudribrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dudribrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dudribrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPTB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dudribrarcha afedosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nerisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dudricarcha evebana sp. nov.

Candidatus Dudricarcha evebana (N.L. fem. n. *evebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is HRBIN02 sp002898395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002898395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.45 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dudricarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dudricarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dudricarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is HRBIN02. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dudricarcha evebana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiserarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dudricarcha igeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dudricarcha igeparia (N.L. fem. n. *igeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is HRBIN02 sp009889515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009889515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.3 % and the genome length is 2.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dudricarcha ocevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dudricarcha ocevia (N.L. fem. n. *ocevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is HRBIN02 sp011373505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011373505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.66 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dudricarcha ugaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dudricarcha ugaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ugaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is HRBIN02 sp011373385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011373385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.05 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dufanarcha obagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dufanarcha obagella (N.L. fem. n. *obagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B10-G16 sp003649185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.17 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dufanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dufanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dufanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B10-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dufanarcha obagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dufanarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dufanarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dufanarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dufanarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B10-G16. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Dufanarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hibecarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Dufoparcha apafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dufoparcha apafosa (N.L. fem. n. *apafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BMS3B sp002897955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002897955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.07 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dufoparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dufoparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dufoparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BMS3B. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dufoparcha apafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dufoparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dufoparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dufoparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dufoparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

taxon is BMS3B. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Dufoparcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hydrothermarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dufoparcha ufavaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Dufoparcha ufavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BMS3B sp003229935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003229935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.99 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dufreocrarcha otafia sp. nov.

Candidatus Dufreocrarcha otafia (N.L. fem. n. *otafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTJS01 sp011333755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011333755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.52 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dufreocrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dufreocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dufreocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTJS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dufreocrarcha otafia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixabarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dufrestarcha asebia sp. nov.

Candidatus Dufrestarcha asebia (N.L. fem. n. *asebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCX01 sp017609995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.46 % and the genome length is 0.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dufrestarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dufrestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dufrestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dufrestarcha asebia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Degifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dumacarcha otabaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Dumacarcha otabaria (N.L. fem. n. *otabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9212 sp9212u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.91 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Dumacarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Dumacarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dumacarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA9212. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dumacarcha otabaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dumacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dumacarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Dumacarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dumacarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA9212. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Dumacarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Dumacarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Dumacarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Dumacarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Dumacarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA9212. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* *Dunularcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Enedarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Dunularcha* *ecepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Dunularcha* *ecepia* (N.L. fem. n. *ecepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-135 sp002255025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002255025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.77 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Dunularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus *Dunularcha* (N.L. fem. n. *Dunularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-135. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Dunularcha* *ecepia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dunularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Dunularchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus *Dunularchaceae* (N.L. fem. n. *Dunularchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-135. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* *Dunularcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Dunularchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Dunularchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus *Dunularchales* (N.L. fem. n. *Dunularchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-135. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* *Dunularcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class

Bathyarchaeia.

Description of *Candidatus Dunularcha phapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dunularcha phapana (N.L. fem. n. *phapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-135 sp011040545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011040545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.89 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dupecarcha amaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dupecarcha amaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *amaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGQM01 sp016935655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.68 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dupecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dupecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dupecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGQM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Dupecarcha amaxaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dupecarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dupecarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dupecarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dupecarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGQM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Dupecarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Dupecarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Dupecarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Dupecarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Dupecarchales* a name created from the name of the

type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGQM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Dupisarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Altiarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Dupisarcha ebefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dupisarcha ebefia (N.L. fem. n. *ebefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADDC01 sp013154145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013154145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.9 % and the genome length is 0.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Dupisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Dupisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Dupisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADDC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Dupisarcha ebefia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dupisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Dupisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Dupisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Dupisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAADDC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Dupisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Dupisarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Dupisarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Dupisarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Dupisarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

taxon is JAADDC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Dupisarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Iainarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Dupisarcha ubaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Dupisarcha ubaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ubaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADDC01 sp015520865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.66 % and the genome length is 0.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Efretarcha igexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Efretarcha igexia (N.L. fem. n. *igexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA287 sp002495235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.15 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Efretarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Efretarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Efretarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA287. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Efretarcha igexia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Efretarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Efretarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Efretarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Efretarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA287. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Efretarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Efretarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Efretarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Efretarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Efretarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA287. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Efretarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Afabarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Efretarcha unaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Efretarcha unaxella (N.L. fem. n. *unaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA287 sp011620765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011620765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.25 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Emilarcha eseparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Emilarcha eseparia (N.L. fem. n. *eseparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B47-G6 sp003663585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.74 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Emilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Emilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Emilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B47-G6. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Emilarcha eseparia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Emilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Emilarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Emilarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Emilarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is 47-G6. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Emilarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Emilarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Emilarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Emilarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Emilarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B47-G6B. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Emilarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Emilarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Emilarcha onataria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Emilarcha onataria (N.L. fem. n. *onataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B47-G6 sp003663565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.73 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Enedarcha upedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Enedarcha upedia (N.L. fem. n. *upedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA202 sp002502685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.05 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Enedarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Enedarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Enedarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA202. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Enedarcha upedia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Enedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Enedarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Enedarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Enedarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA202. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Enedarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Enedarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Enedarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Enedarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Enedarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA202. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Enedarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Enedarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus* Esacarcha ibavia sp. nov.

Candidatus Esacarcha ibavia (N.L. fem. n. *ibavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B24-G9 sp003651045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003651045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.77 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Esacarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Esacarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Esacarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B24-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Esacarcha ibavia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Esacarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Esacarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Esacarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DHVEG-1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Esacarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Esacarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Esacarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Esacarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Esacarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DHVEG-1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Esacarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Enedarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus* Ethanoperedens enafaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Ethanoperedens enafaria (N.L. fem. n. *enafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Ethanoperedens sp004212095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004212095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.95 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fabidrarcha ucania sp. nov.

Candidatus Fabidrarcha ucania (N.L. fem. n. *ucania* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIQQL01 sp903873955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903873955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.4 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fabidrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fabidrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fabidrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIQQL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fabidrarcha ucania.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Midifarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Facrestarcha elagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Facrestarcha elagia (N.L. fem. n. *elagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIYYO01 sp903930485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903930485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.54 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Facrestarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Facrestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Facrestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIYYO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Facrestarcha elagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lanaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fadasarcha etecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fadasarcha etecella (N.L. fem. n. *etecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DXJG01 sp019056805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019056805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.48 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fadasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fadasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fadasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DXJG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fadasarcha etecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fadasarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fadasarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fadasarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fadasarchaceae* a name created from the name of the

type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DXJG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fadasarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Baldrarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fadasarcha odafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fadasarcha odafia (N.L. fem. n. *odafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DXJG01 sp016840485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.67 % and the genome length is 3.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fadrenarcha esefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fadrenarcha esefella (N.L. fem. n. *esefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCGM01 sp017608025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.54 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fadrenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fadrenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fadrenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCGM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fadrenarcha esefella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fadrenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fadrenarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fadrenarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fadrenarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFCGM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fadrenarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Laxucarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fafruparcha onatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fafruparcha onatia (N.L. fem. n. *onatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGFG01 sp016931255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016931255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.85 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fafruparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fafruparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fafruparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGFG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fafruparcha onatia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Risibarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Falabarcha elapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Falabarcha elapana (N.L. fem. n. *elapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQSS01 sp016211195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016211195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.66 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Falabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Falabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Falabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQSS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Falabarcha elapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Falabarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Falabarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Falabarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Falabarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQSS01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Falabarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Falicarcha ufepia sp. nov.

Candidatus Falicarcha ufepia (N.L. fem. n. *ufepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B33-G15 sp003660925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003660925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.89 % and the genome length is 0.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Falicarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Falicarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Falicarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B33-G15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Falicarcha ufepia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Falicarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Falicarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Falicarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Falicarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B33-G15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Falicarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Falicarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Falicarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Falicarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Falicarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B33-G15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Falicarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Nanoarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus* Famebrarcha avabia sp. nov.

Candidatus Famebrarcha avabia (N.L. fem. n. *avabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPIL01 sp016188105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.12 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Famebrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Famebrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Famebrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPIL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Famebrarcha avabia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fapladrarcha enexella sp. nov.

Candidatus Fapladrarcha enexella (N.L. fem. n. *enexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is HRBIN01 sp002898355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002898355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.58 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fapladrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fapladrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fapladrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is HRBIN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fapladrarcha enexella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Caldarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fapocarcha onaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fapocarcha onaposa (N.L. fem. n. *onaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRGF01 sp016212395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016212395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.35 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fapocarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fapocarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fapocarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRGF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fapocarcha onaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fapocarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fapocarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fapocarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fapocarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACRGF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fapocarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Fapocarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fapocarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Fapocarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Fapocarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACRGF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fapocarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Micrarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Fapresarcha ufexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fapresarcha ufexosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQNH01 sp016203175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.11 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fapresarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fapresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fapresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQNH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fapresarcha ufexosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fapresarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fapresarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fapresarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fapresarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQNH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fapresarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Faribrarcha omabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Faribrarcha omabella (N.L. fem. n. *omabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQIB01 sp016198755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.3 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Faribrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Faribrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Faribrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQIB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Faribrarcha omabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Faribrarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Faribrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Faribrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Faribrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQIB01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Faribrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Aenigmataarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fastedrarcha afevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fastedrarcha afevosa (N.L. fem. n. *afevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCCK01 sp017610245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.76 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fastedrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fastedrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fastedrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCCK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fastedrarcha afevosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nogelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fastutarcha igabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fastutarcha igabella (N.L. fem. n. *igabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA349 sp002509745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.63 % and the genome length is 2.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fastutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fastutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fastutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA349. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fastutarcha igabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanobacteriaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fastutarcha upelaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fastutarcha upelaria (N.L. fem. n. *upelaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA349 sp002839705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002839705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.96 % and the genome length is 2.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatostarcha ebarosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatostarcha ebarosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABJCP01 sp018668595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018671815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.82 % and the genome length is 2.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fatostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fatostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABJCP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fatostarcha ebarosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hicuparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fatostarcha elapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatostarcha elapella (N.L. fem. n. *elapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABJCP01 sp018675335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_018675335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.26 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha epanella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha epanella (N.L. fem. n. *epanella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ASMP01 sp018830685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.2 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fatracarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ASMP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fatracarcha epanella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha ibacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha ibacia (N.L. fem. n. *ibacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ASMP01 sp018821425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018821425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.11 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha idabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha idabana (N.L. fem. n. *idabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ASMP01 sp018829425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018829425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.37 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha irefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha irefella (N.L. fem. n. *irefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ASMP01 sp000405225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000405225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.27 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha itadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha itadaria (N.L. fem. n. *itadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ASMP01 sp016866915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016866915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.19 % and the genome length is 0.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha ivamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha ivamia (N.L. fem. n. *ivamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ASMP01 sp017610405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.34 % and the genome length is 0.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha omavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha omavella (N.L. fem. n. *omavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ASMP01 sp018303885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.6 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fatracarcha ucalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fatracarcha ucalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ASMP01 sp018830905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.31 % and the genome length is 0.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Faxisarcha oragosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Faxisarcha oragosa (N.L. fem. n. *oragosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYL01 sp018303285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.14 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Faxisarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Faxisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Faxisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Faxisarcha oragosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Faxisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Faxisarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Faxisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Faxisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVYL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Faxisarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Faxumarcha asaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Faxumarcha asaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *asaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKSH01 sp007118145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007125235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.67 % and the genome length is 2.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Faxumarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Faxumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Faxumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is SKSH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Faxumarcha asaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Faxumarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Faxumarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Faxumarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Faxumarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SKSH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Faxumarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Halobacteriales*.

Description of *Candidatus Faxumarcha edexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Faxumarcha edexana (N.L. fem. n. *edexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKSH01 sp007118075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007118075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.78 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Febimarcha ipetosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Febimarcha ipetosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipetosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B29-G15 sp003650585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.81 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Febimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Febimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Febimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B29-G15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Febimarcha ipetosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Febimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Febimarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Febimarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Febimarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B29-G15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Febimarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fecibrarcha ocafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fecibrarcha ocafia (N.L. fem. n. *ocafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SURF-58 sp003599145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003599145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.92 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fecibrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fecibrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fecibrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SURF-58. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fecibrarcha ocafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tusixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Feclosarcha afevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Feclosarcha afevana (N.L. fem. n. *afevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PXRE01 sp003021085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.02 % and the genome length is 3.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Feclosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Feclosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Feclosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PXRE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Feclosarcha afevana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Feclosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Feclosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Feclosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Feclosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PXRE01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Feclosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Halobacteriales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fedobarcha efaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fedobarcha efaria (N.L. fem. n. *efaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAILAH01 sp011389055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011389055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.08 % and the genome length is 0.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fedobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fedobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fedobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAILAH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fedobarcha efaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fedobarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fedobarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fedobarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fedobarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CAILAH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fedobarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Fedobarchales.

Description of *Candidatus Fedobarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Fedobarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Fedobarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CAILAH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fedobarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Micrarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Fedobarcha uenia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fedobarcha uenia (N.L. fem. n. *uenia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAILAH01 sp903832205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903832205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.56 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fedrarcha ilavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fedrarcha ilavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ilavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZZ01 sp018302205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.22 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fedrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fedrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fedrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fedrarcha ilavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fedrarcha oevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fedrarcha oevosa (N.L. fem. n. *oevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZZ01 sp018302165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.35 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fedrifrarcha ilevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fedrifrarcha ilevana (N.L. fem. n. *ilevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQIA01 sp016198705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.46 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fedrifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fedrifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fedrifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQIA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fedrifrarcha ilevana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fedufrarcha imafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fedufrarcha imafana (N.L. fem. n. *imafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPND01 sp016185625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.31 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fedufrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fedufrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fedufrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPND01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fedufrarcha imafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Fipalarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Fefrabrarcha edevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fefrabrarcha edevaria (N.L. fem. n. *edevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA114 sp002506335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.02 % and the genome length is 2.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fefrabrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fefrabrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fefrabrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA114. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fefrabrarcha edevaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanotrichaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fegrafrarcha irebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fegrafrarcha irebaria (N.L. fem. n. *irebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYC01 sp018303485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.95 % and the genome length is 0.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fegrafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fegrafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fegrafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fegrafrarcha irebaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Femaparcha onaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Femaparcha onaxella (N.L. fem. n. *onaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGOX01 sp016926295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.09 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Femaparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Femaparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Femaparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGOX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Femaparcha onaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Femaparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Femaparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Femaparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Femaparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGOX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Femaparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Femaparchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Femaparchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Femaparchales (N.L. fem. n. *Femaparchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGOX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Femaparcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Iainarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Fepagrarcha efapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepagrarcha efapana (N.L. fem. n. *efapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JAAEEW01 sp013415595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013415595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.54 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepagrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fepagrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fepagrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAEEW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fepagrarcha efapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanotrichaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha asagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha asagosa (N.L. fem. n. *asagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002506825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002704585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.07 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fepladarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIb-O5. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fepladarcha asagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thalassarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha cixaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha cixaria (N.L. fem. n. *cixaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002498925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.09 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha cuxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha *cuxella* (N.L. fem. n. *cuxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002501605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.66 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fepladarcha *duvia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha *duvia* (N.L. fem. n. *duvia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002502095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003673035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.66 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fepladarcha *ecalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha *ecalaria* (N.L. fem. n. *ecalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002499865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.5 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fepladarcha *idacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha *idacia* (N.L. fem. n. *idacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002501805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.83 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fepladarcha *imadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha *imadella* (N.L. fem. n. *imadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002497985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.68 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha isalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha isalana (N.L. fem. n. *isalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002726275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002726275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.17 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha itacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha itacana (N.L. fem. n. *itacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002499325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.54 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha ivabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha ivabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002504435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002504435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.36 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha onavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha onavana (N.L. fem. n. *onavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002718995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002711985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.37 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha osacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha osacia (N.L. fem. n. *osacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002499345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.76 % and the genome length is

1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha osafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha osafana (N.L. fem. n. *osafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002730095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002702715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.78 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha usalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha usalaria (N.L. fem. n. *usalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002496725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.8 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepladarcha vuparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepladarcha vuparia (N.L. fem. n. *vuparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O5 sp002505775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.71 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepregrarcha umefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fepregrarcha umefia (N.L. fem. n. *umefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABZYC01 sp902529885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902529885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.56 % and the genome length is 0.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fepregrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fepregrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fepregrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is CABZYC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fepregrarcha umefia*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fermentimicrarchaeum etacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fermentimicrarchaeum etacaria (N.L. fem. n. *etacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Fermentimicrarchaeum* sp013425405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013425405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.06 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fermentimicrarchaeum omaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fermentimicrarchaeum omaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *omaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Fermentimicrarchaeum* sp013425335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013425335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.74 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ferroglobus uvabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ferroglobus uvabaria (N.L. fem. n. *uvabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Ferroglobus* sp015520115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.96 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ferroplasma ofadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ferroplasma ofadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Ferroplasma* sp002505185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.08 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ferumarcha inacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ferumarcha inacella (N.L. fem. n. *inacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADFI01 sp013152905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013152905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.78 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ferumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ferumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ferumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADFI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ferumarcha inacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ferumarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ferumarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ferumarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ferumarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAADFI01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ferumarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Aenigmataarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Festebrarcha afevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Festebrarcha afevella (N.L. fem. n. *afevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRKJ01 sp016219825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016219825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.61 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Festebrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Festebrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Festebrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRKJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Festebrarcha afevella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Deraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fetrurarcha ufalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fetrurarcha ufalaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADDH01 sp013154035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013154035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.31 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fetrurarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fetrurarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fetrurarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADDH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fetrurarcha ufalaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dupisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fetuxarcha ifepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fetuxarcha ifepella (N.L. fem. n. *ifepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8480 sp013425325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013425325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.66 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fetuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fetuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fetuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA8480. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fetuxarcha ifepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fetuxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fetuxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fetuxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fetuxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA8480. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fetuxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fetuxarcha omapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fetuxarcha omapella (N.L. fem. n. *omapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8480 sp001871495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.89 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fexostarcha ocesana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fexostarcha ocesana (N.L. fem. n. *ocesana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DG-33 sp001515185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001515185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.48 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Methane-rich estuary sediments 52-54 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Fexostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fexostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fexostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DG-33. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fexostarcha ocesana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hadarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fexostarcha phavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fexostarcha phavaria (N.L. fem. n. *phavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DG-33 sp004375695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004375695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.78 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fiblemarcha ugafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fiblemarcha ugafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ugafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPAO01 sp016180755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.46 % and the genome length is 2.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fiblemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fiblemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fiblemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPAO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fiblemarcha ugafosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fiblemarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fiblemarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fiblemarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fiblemarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPAO01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Fiblemarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Dumacarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fiblubrarcha imecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fiblubrarcha imecana (N.L. fem. n. *imecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGKQ01 sp016866995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016866995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.57 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fiblubrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fiblubrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fiblubrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGKQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fiblubrarcha imecana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ficlitrarcha oceposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ficlitrarcha oceposa (N.L. fem. n. *oceposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQSU01 sp016211165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016211165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.28 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ficlitrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ficlitrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ficlitrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQSU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ficlitrarcha oceposa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Luglotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fifreocrarcha ucadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fifreocrarcha ucadana (N.L. fem. n. *ucadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRGG01 sp016217775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016217775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.61 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fifreocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fifreocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fifreocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRGG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fifreocrarcha ucadana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Caxorarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fifrilarcha uvaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fifrilarcha uvaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *uvaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJQN01 sp018819225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018819225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.55 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fifrilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fifrilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fifrilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJQN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fifrilarcha uvaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ticixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fifruetrarcha agecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fifruetrarcha agecana (N.L. fem. n. *agecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S139-21 sp015522385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.73 % and the genome length is 4.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fifruetrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fifruetrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fifruetrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S139-21. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fifruetrarcha agecana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Kariarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha asebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha asebella (N.L. fem. n. *asebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.61 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Figanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is RBG-16-68-12. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Figanarcha asebella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Figanarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Figanarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Figanarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is RBG-16-68-12. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Figanarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Figanarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Figanarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Figanarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is RBG-16-68-12. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Figanarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha epamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha epamosa (N.L. fem. n. *epamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp011362635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011362635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.85 % and the genome length is 2.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha ilasana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha ilasana (N.L. fem. n. *ilasana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.86 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha imavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha imavella (N.L. fem. n. *imavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.56 % and the genome length is 2.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha ipalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha ipalaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp001800825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001800825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.31 % and the genome length is 2.21 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 19ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha itagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha itagana (N.L. fem. n. *itagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.14 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha itaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha itaposa (N.L. fem. n. *itaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.65 % and the genome length is 1.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Figanarcha ocebaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha ocebaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.93 % and the genome length is 2.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Figanarcha ogabella sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha ogabella (N.L. fem. n. *ogabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp001800745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001800745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.99 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 16ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus* Figanarcha onalella sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha onalella (N.L. fem. n. *onalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005879045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005879045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.1 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Figanarcha oraposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha oraposa (N.L. fem. n. *oraposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.05 % and the genome

length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha osagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha osagana (N.L. fem. n. *osagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.24 % and the genome length is 2.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha osavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha osavia (N.L. fem. n. *osavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005879065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005879065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.77 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha phafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha phafella (N.L. fem. n. *phafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.45 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha ubapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha ubapella (N.L. fem. n. *ubapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.15 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha umefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha umefella (N.L. fem. n. *umefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is RBG-16-68-12 sp011331255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011331255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.03 % and the genome length is 2.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha upacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha upacana (N.L. fem. n. *upacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005878485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.69 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha upaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha upaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *upaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp005879015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005879015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.78 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figanarcha utavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figanarcha utavia (N.L. fem. n. *utavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-68-12 sp8695u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.7 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figlinarcha imadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Figlinarcha imadosa (N.L. fem. n. *imadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDY01 sp017609445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.02 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Figlinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Figlinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Figlinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Figlinarcha imadosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aenigmatarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Filatarcha ifetaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Filatarcha ifetaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifetaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMEP01 sp902385155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.23 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Filatarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Filatarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Filatarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CABMEP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Filatarcha ifetaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Filatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Filatarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Filatarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Filatarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CABMEP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Filatarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Filatarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Filatarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Filatarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Filatarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CABMEP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Filatarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Micrarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Fimusarcha adafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fimusarcha adafaria (N.L. fem. n. *adafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALA01 sp015523085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.86 % and the genome length is 0.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fimusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fimusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fimusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fimusarcha adafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fimusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fimusarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fimusarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fimusarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WALA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fimusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Coxosarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fimusarcha obapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fimusarcha obapella (N.L. fem. n. *obapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALA01 sp015522745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.16 % and the genome length is 0.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fipalarcha onavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fipalarcha onavaria (N.L. fem. n. *onavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR9 sp10194u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000805935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.18 % and the genome length is 0.49 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle groundwater metagenome at time 1".

Description of *Candidatus* Fipalarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fipalarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fipalarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fipalarcha onavaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fipalarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Fipalarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fipalarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR9. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Fipalarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fipruxarcha emadana sp. nov.

Candidatus Fipruxarcha emadana (N.L. fem. n. *emadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZW01 sp018302235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.95 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fipruxarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fipruxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fipruxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fipruxarcha emadana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Deraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Firefrarcha ilaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Firefrarcha ilaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ilaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Kmv04 sp014859725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014859725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.75 % and the genome length is 2.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Firefrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Firefrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Firefrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Kmv04. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Firefrarcha ilaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanocomedenaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fisamarcha ifaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fisamarcha ifaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 0-14-0-20-34-12 sp002779065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002779065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.3 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fisamarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fisamarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fisamarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 0-14-0-20-34-12. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fisamarcha ifaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fisamarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fisamarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Fisamarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fisamarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is 0-14-0-20-34-12. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Fisamarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fisaprarcha ipegosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Fisaprarcha ipegosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWH01 sp018304345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.06 % and the genome length is 0.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fisaprarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fisaprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fisaprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVWH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fisaprarcha ipegosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Laxucarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fisaprarcha ogadella sp. nov.

Candidatus Fisaprarcha ogadella (N.L. fem. n. *ogadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWH01 sp018304365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.29 % and the genome length is 0.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fistoxarcha acegaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Fistoxarcha acegaria (N.L. fem. n. *acegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA288 sp012728895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012728895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.82 % and the genome length is 2.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fistoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fistoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fistoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA288. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fistoxarcha acegaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanosphaerulaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fistoxarcha ebecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fistoxarcha ebecana (N.L. fem. n. *ebecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA288 sp11384u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.66 % and the genome length is 2.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fistoxarcha ecemana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fistoxarcha ecemana (N.L. fem. n. *ecemana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA288 sp002495225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.61 % and the genome length is 1.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fistoxarcha efadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fistoxarcha efadosa (N.L. fem. n. *efadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA288 sp004332335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004332335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.4 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fistoxarcha itedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Fistoxarcha itedella* (N.L. fem. n. *itedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA288 sp017883495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017883495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.03 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Fistularcha ageparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Fistularcha ageparia* (N.L. fem. n. *ageparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LKUD01 sp001412355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001412355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.59 % and the genome length is 2.09 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "methanogenic consortium capable of long-chain paraffin degradation (SDB culture) enriched from contaminated sediments of San Diego Bay; California; degrades n-alkanes from C25 to C50".

Description of *Candidatus* *Fistularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus *Fistularcha* (N.L. fem. n. *Fistularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is LKUD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Fistularcha ageparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomicrobiaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Fistularcha inacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Fistularcha inacaria* (N.L. fem. n. *inacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LKUD01 sp013415665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013415665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.62 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Fistularcha utedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Fistularcha utedella* (N.L. fem. n. *utedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LKUD01 sp016926855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.84 % and the genome length is 1.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fitomarcha ilafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fitomarcha ilafia (N.L. fem. n. *ilafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADFO01 sp013152815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013152815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.34 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fitomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fitomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fitomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADFO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fitomarcha ilafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fitomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fitomarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fitomarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fitomarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAADFO01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fitomarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fitriparcha usavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fitriparcha usavia (N.L. fem. n. *usavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQJG01 sp016198125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.13 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fitriparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fitriparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fitriparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQJG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fitriparcha usavia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dixemarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fixabarcha ocepia sp. nov.

Candidatus Fixabarcha ocepia (N.L. fem. n. *ocepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CSSed11-243R1 sp003563585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003563585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.52 % and the genome length is 0.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fixabarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fixabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fixabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CSSed11-243R1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fixabarcha ocepia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixabarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fixabarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Fixabarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fixabarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CSSed11-243R1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Fixabarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Fixabarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fixabarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Fixabarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Fixabarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CSSed11-243R1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Fixabarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Nanoarchaea*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fixabarcha ufolia sp. nov.

Candidatus Fixabarcha ufolia (N.L. fem. n. *ufolia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CSSed11-243R1 sp007133845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007133845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.94 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fixiprarcha aselosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Fixiprarcha aselosa (N.L. fem. n. *aselosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJIZ01 sp014729995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.67 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fixiprarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fixiprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fixiprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJIZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fixiprarcha aselosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixiprarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fixiprarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Fixiprarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fixiprarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJIZ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Fixiprarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Woesearchaeales.

Description of *Candidatus Fixurarcha ogaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fixurarcha ogaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR20 sp000830315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.65 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fixurarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fixurarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fixurarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR20. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fixurarcha ogaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fixurarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fixurarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fixurarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR20. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fixurarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Flacosarcha afebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flacosarcha afebella (N.L. fem. n. *afebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRVP01 sp018396875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.02 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flacosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flacosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flacosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRVP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Flacosarcha afebella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flacosarcha amaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flacosarcha amaxella (N.L. fem. n. *amaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRVP01 sp018396705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.23 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flacosarcha ivafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flacosarcha ivafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRVP01 sp011364585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011366615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.25 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flacosarcha utafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flacosarcha utafana (N.L. fem. n. *utafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRVP01 sp011373965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011374045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.23 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fladaxarcha icafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fladaxarcha icafosa (N.L. fem. n. *icafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSBS01 sp011045925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011045925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.87 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fladaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fladaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fladaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSBS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fladaxarcha icafosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bidasarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flaglixarcha icebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flaglixarcha icebia (N.L. fem. n. *icebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWR01 sp018304205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.14 % and the genome length is 0.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flaglixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flaglixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flaglixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVWR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flaglixarcha icebia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flamitarcha epaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flamitarcha epaxella (N.L. fem. n. *epaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1535 sp015521535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.03 % and the genome length is 0.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flamitarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flamitarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flamitarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZUA-1535. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Flamitarcha epaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Flamitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flamitarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Flamitarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Flamitarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SZUA-1535. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Flamitarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Aenigmatarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Flamitarcha ifatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flamitarcha ifatia (N.L. fem. n. *ifatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1535 sp015661515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015661515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.94 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flasabarcha odagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flasabarcha odagia (N.L. fem. n. *odagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCFX01 sp017608405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.96 % and the genome length is 0.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flasabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flasabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flasabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCFX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Flasabarcha odagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flastagarcha phepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flastagarcha phepia (N.L. fem. n. *phepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQN01 sp015520195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.59 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flastagarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flastagarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flastagarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Flastagarcha phepia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Acidilobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fleblicarcha apegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fleblicarcha apegosa (N.L. fem. n. *apegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWGL01 sp003554465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003554465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.02 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fleblicarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fleblicarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fleblicarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PWGL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fleblicarcha apegosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flebogarcha cuxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flebogarcha cuxaria (N.L. fem. n. *cuxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10452 sp002501855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002501935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.86 % and the genome length is 3.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flebogarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flebogarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flebogarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10452. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flebogarcha *cuxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrososphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flebogarcha omevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flebogarcha *omevia* (N.L. fem. n. *omevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10452 sp003176995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003176995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.89 % and the genome length is 3.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flebogarcha ubaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flebogarcha *ubaposa* (N.L. fem. n. *ubaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10452 sp009898475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009898475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.92 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flebogarcha ufatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flebogarcha *ufatosa* (N.L. fem. n. *ufatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10452 sp009665115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009665115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.3 % and the genome length is 2.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fleclomarcha ibaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fleclemarcha ibaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ibaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is YT1-065 sp016839905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.62 % and the genome length is 4.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fleclemarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fleclemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fleclemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is YT1-065. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fleclemarcha ibaxana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flefrigarcha upexana sp. nov.

Candidatus Flefrigarcha upexana (N.L. fem. n. *upexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTIP01 sp011333955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011333955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.6 % and the genome length is 0.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flefrigarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Flefrigarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flefrigarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTIP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flefrigarcha upexana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Laxucarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flefrunarcha etamaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Flefrunarcha etamaria (N.L. fem. n. *etamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JACQST01 sp016211185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016211185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.98 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flefrunarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flefrunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flefrunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQST01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flefrunarcha etamaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fliclaparcha amecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fliclaparcha amecaria (N.L. fem. n. *amecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VHBM01 sp016176745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016176745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.14 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fliclaparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fliclaparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fliclaparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VHBM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fliclaparcha amecaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fliclaparcha onevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fliclaparcha onevia (N.L. fem. n. *onevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VHBM01 sp016871975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016871975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.03 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flidosarcha oreccella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flidosarcha orecella (N.L. fem. n. *orecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B47-G15 sp003660975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003660975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.48 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flidosarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Flidosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flidosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B47-G15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flidosarcha orecella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Flidosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flidosarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Flidosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Flidosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B47-G15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Flidosarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Oferarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Fligamarcha inabia sp. nov.

Candidatus Fligamarcha inabia (N.L. fem. n. *inabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L4 sp002718195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.78 % and the genome length is 2.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fligamarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fligamarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fligamarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is MGIIa-L4. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fligamarcha inabia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flistaparcha onemaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Flistaparcha onemaria (N.L. fem. n. *onemaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9640 sp9640u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.62 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flistaparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Flistaparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flistaparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA9640. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flistaparcha onemaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flistaparcha oredella sp. nov.

Candidatus Flistaparcha oredella (N.L. fem. n. *oredella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9640 sp018830945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.12 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flodragarcha esaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Flodragarcha esaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *esaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZE01 sp018302815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.16 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flodragarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Flodragarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flodragarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flodragarcha esaxosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha acevana sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha acevana (N.L. fem. n. *acevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017475875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017475875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.38 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flonuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA71. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha acevana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylphilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha cufosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha cufosa (N.L. fem. n. *cufosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp015063285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015063285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.47 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha cuxana sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha cuxana (N.L. fem. n. *cuxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is UBA71 sp002506425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.57 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha ecanana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha ecanana (N.L. fem. n. *ecanana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp015063125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015063125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.47 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha ecanella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha ecanella (N.L. fem. n. *ecanella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp015063135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017412185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.51 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha edefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha edefia (N.L. fem. n. *edefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017507885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017507885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.61 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha egefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha egefella (N.L. fem. n. *egefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp002504405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002504405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.37 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha epegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha epegosa (N.L. fem. n. *epegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp001563305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.53 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Ovine rumen".

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha erebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha erebella (N.L. fem. n. *erebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp002506175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.15 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha icaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha icaxana (N.L. fem. n. *icaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp015063245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015063245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.11 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha ilafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha ilafana (N.L. fem. n. *ilafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017461225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017461225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.64 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha iledana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha iledana (N.L. fem. n. *iledana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp015063235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015063235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.44 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha iragaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha iragara (N.L. fem. n. *iragara* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp006954465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900768585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.72 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha ivagara sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha ivagara (N.L. fem. n. *ivagara* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp905187815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905187815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.83 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha odaposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha odaposa (N.L. fem. n. *odaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp016282555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016282555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.7 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha ofararia sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha ofararia (N.L. fem. n. *ofararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp015063165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017508945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.44 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flonuxarcha omaxia sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha omaxia (N.L. fem. n. *omaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp016281925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016281925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.81 % and the genome length is 1.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha opagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha opagia (N.L. fem. n. *opagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017519045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017542975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.76 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha opavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha opavia (N.L. fem. n. *opavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017468935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017468935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.22 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha phaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha phaposa (N.L. fem. n. *phaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp002504495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002504495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.97 % and the genome length is 1.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha ucepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha ucepella (N.L. fem. n. *ucepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp016284295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016284295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.14 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha udafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha udafaria (N.L. fem. n. *udafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp016296195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016296195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.2 % and the genome length is 1.54

Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha ugaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha ugaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ugaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017540825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017540825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.01 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha urafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha urafaria (N.L. fem. n. *urafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017935945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017472625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.28 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha uraxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha uraxia (N.L. fem. n. *uraxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp006954425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009911715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.55 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha utebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha utebaria (N.L. fem. n. *utebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017616575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017616575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.44 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha uvacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha uvacana (N.L. fem. n. *uvacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is UBA71 sp900767505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900767505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.05 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flonuxarcha uvagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flonuxarcha uvagaria (N.L. fem. n. *uvagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA71 sp017524805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017524805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.35 % and the genome length is 1.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Floplaxarcha ucedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Floplaxarcha ucedosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA587 sp002504725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002504725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.1 % and the genome length is 2.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Floplaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Floplaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Floplaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA587. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Floplaxarcha ucedosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanobacteriaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flotabarcha agevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flotabarcha agevaria (N.L. fem. n. *agevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRZQ01 sp011055445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011055445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.29 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flotabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flotabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flotabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRZQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flotabarcha agevaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermofilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flotabarcha epaxaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Flotabarcha epaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *epaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRZQ01 sp011369665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011369665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.93 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flotabarcha ocebana sp. nov.

Candidatus Flotabarcha ocebana (N.L. fem. n. *ocebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRZQ01 sp011372935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011372935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.63 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flotabarcha otabia sp. nov.

Candidatus Flotabarcha otabia (N.L. fem. n. *otabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRZQ01 sp011053655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011375505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.92 % and the genome length is 0.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flubinarcha ifaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Flubinarcha ifaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA60 sp002503395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012965105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.77 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flubinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flubinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flubinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA60. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Flubinarcha ifaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha amaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha amaposa (N.L. fem. n. *amaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp902514485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902513375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.63 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fludanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIb-O2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fludanarcha amaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thalassarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha ebapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha ebapia (N.L. fem. n. *ebapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp002495525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.73 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha epafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha epafella (N.L. fem. n. *epafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp902511005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902511005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.58 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha gaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha gaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *gaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp002494975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.53 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha gixia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha gixia (N.L. fem. n. *gixia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp002686525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902635905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.94 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha iledella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha iledella (N.L. fem. n. *iledella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp002685315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002685315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.18 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha iragia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha iragia (N.L. fem. n. *iragia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp004195525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012960975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.97 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha mubella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha mubella (N.L. fem. n. *mubella* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp002504905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.51 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha ocarosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha ocarosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp902593945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902593945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.18 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha ogaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha ogaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp002497245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002714605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.82 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha olagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha olagosa (N.L. fem. n. *olagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp002498985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.08 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha pefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha pefosa (N.L. fem. n. *pefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp002499785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.84 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fludanarcha ucaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fludanarcha ucaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ucaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O2 sp016777225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016777225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.64 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flugiparcha igaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flugiparcha igaxia (N.L. fem. n. *igaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOYJ01 sp016181885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.67 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flugiparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flugiparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flugiparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOYJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Flugiparcha igaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Flupexarcha ecagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Flupexarcha ecagella (N.L. fem. n. *ecagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B17-G15 sp003649495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.88 % and the genome length is 2.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Flupexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Flupexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flupexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is B17-G15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flupexarcha ecagella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermofilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flutogarcha ogadaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Flutogarcha ogadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJJV01 sp018812465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018812465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.77 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Flutogarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Flutogarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Flutogarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJJV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Flutogarcha ogadaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hamosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Flutogarcha osebica sp. nov.

Candidatus Flutogarcha osebica (N.L. fem. n. *osebica* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJJV01 sp014729495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.75 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fobixarcha umaxana sp. nov.

Candidatus Fobixarcha umaxana (N.L. fem. n. *umaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPIF01 sp016188215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.2 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Fobixarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Fobixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fobixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPIF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fobixarcha umaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fobixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fobixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fobixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fobixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPIF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fobixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fobrifrarcha abevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fobrifrarcha abevia (N.L. fem. n. *abevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1435 sp015662595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015662595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.41 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fobrifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fobrifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fobrifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZUA-1435. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fobrifrarcha abevia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ignisphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Foclaxarcha efanana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Foclaxarcha efanana (N.L. fem. n. *efanana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PSPT01 sp018649825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018649825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.15 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Foclaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Foclaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Foclaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PSPT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Foclaxarcha efanana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Foclaxarcha unadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Foclaxarcha unadia (N.L. fem. n. *unadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PSPT01 sp004195635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004195635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.38 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Focrabarcha ecapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Focrabarcha ecapana (N.L. fem. n. *ecapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGPP01 sp016936135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016936135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.14 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Focrabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Focrabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Focrabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGPP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Focrabarcha ecapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fodebrarcha apabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fodebrarcha apabosa (N.L. fem. n. *apabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGOM01 sp016926505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.48 % and the genome length is 2.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fodebrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fodebrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fodebrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGOM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fodebrarcha apabosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanospirillaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fodrarcha ipefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fodrarcha ipefaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCGI01 sp017608235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.78 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fodrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fodrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fodrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCGI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fodrarcha ipefaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fodrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fodrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fodrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fodrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAF CGI01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fodraxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Laxucarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fofrestarcha edeposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fofrestarcha edeposa (N.L. fem. n. *edeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIXRF01 sp903921825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903921825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.51 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fofrestarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fofrestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fofrestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIXRF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fofrestarcha edeposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Uglutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fogaxarcha avaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fogaxarcha avaposa (N.L. fem. n. *avaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACTUA01 sp015660865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015660865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.51 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fogaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fogaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fogaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACTUA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fogaxarcha avaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fogaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fogaxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fogaxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fogaxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACTUA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fogaxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanomicrobiales*.

Description of *Candidatus Foguparcha avabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Foguparcha avabella (N.L. fem. n. *avabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2687795 sp002687795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002687795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.27 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Foguparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Foguparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Foguparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2687795. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Foguparcha avabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Foguparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Foguparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Foguparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Foguparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-2687795. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Foguparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Folistarcha upedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Folistarcha upedosa (N.L. fem. n. *upedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PXDW01 sp003564925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003564925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.99 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Folistarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Folistarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Folistarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PXDW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Folistarcha upedosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Folistarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Folistarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Folistarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Folistarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PXDW01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Folistarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Forusarcha icaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Forusarcha icaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *icaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPRH01 sp016190055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016190055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.68 % and the genome length is 2.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Forusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Forusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Forusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPRH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Forusarcha icaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Forusarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Forusarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Forusarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Forusarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPRH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Forusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fosilarcha ivecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fosilarcha ivecia (N.L. fem. n. *ivecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQR01 sp015520145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.27 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fosilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fosilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fosilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fosilarcha ivecia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fosilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fosilarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fosilarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fosilarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WAQR01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fosilarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hydrothermarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fostinarcha quebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fostinarcha quebosa (N.L. fem. n. *quebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGDB01 sp017608725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.84 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fostinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fostinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fostinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGDB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fostinarcha quebosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nogelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fostinarcha umafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fostinarcha umafaria (N.L. fem. n. *umafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGDB01 sp016932355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.17 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fostobarcha itecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fostobarcha itecella (N.L. fem. n. *itecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADGB01 sp015521085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.17 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fostobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fostobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fostobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADGB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fostobarcha itecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Acidilobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fostobarcha ogafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fostobarcha ogafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADGB01 sp013152575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013152575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.83 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fostobarcha osacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fostobarcha osacaria (N.L. fem. n. *osacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADGB01 sp015523485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.64 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fostobarcha udagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fostobarcha udagana (N.L. fem. n. *udagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADGB01 sp015521175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.66 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fotigrarcha ufatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fotigrarcha ufatella (N.L. fem. n. *ufatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WANN01 sp015521775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.47 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fotigrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fotigrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fotigrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WANN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fotigrarcha ufatella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermoproteaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fotresarcha ofagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fotresarcha ofagana (N.L. fem. n. *ofagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJJD01 sp014729915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.5 % and the genome length is 2.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fotresarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fotresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fotresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJJD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fotresarcha ofagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hudomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frasaxarcha ocabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frasaxarcha ocabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GLR112 sp013139905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013139905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.76 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frasaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frasaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frasaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GLR112. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frasaxarcha ocabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Gunesarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Frastodarcha umegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frastodarcha umegosa (N.L. fem. n. *umegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOYC01 sp018221125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.77 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frastodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frastodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frastodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOYC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frastodarcha umegosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Horetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frecoxarcha edavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frecoxarcha edavia (N.L. fem. n. *edavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-57-9 sp014729945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.34 % and the genome length is 2.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frecoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frecoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frecoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is RBG-16-57-9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frecoxarcha edavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ibidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frecoxarcha itapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frecoxarcha itapella (N.L. fem. n. *itapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-57-9 sp001775965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001775965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.18 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 13ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Frecoxarcha mupella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frecoxarcha mupella (N.L. fem. n. *mupella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-57-9 sp018652685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018702655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.84 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frecoxarcha onevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frecoxarcha onevella (N.L. fem. n. *onevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-57-9 sp014730055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014730055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.91 % and the genome length is 2.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frecoxarcha opafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frecoxarcha opafaria (N.L. fem. n. *opafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-57-9 sp013619005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013619005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.78 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frecoxarcha otafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frecoxarcha otafaria (N.L. fem. n. *otafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-57-9 sp016934355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016934355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.52 % and the genome length is 2.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frecredarcha agecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frecredarcha agecia (N.L. fem. n. *agecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SpSt-734 sp011363135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011363135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.8 % and the genome length is 0.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frecredarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frecredarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frecredarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SpSt-734. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Frecredarcha agecia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fredresarcha ivebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fredresarcha ivebosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGGT01 sp016930445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016930445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.87 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fredresarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fredresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fredresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGGT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fredresarcha ivebosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ligedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frefriparcha ipefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frefriparcha ipefia (N.L. fem. n. *ipefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABICB01 sp018652475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018652475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.81 % and the genome length is 0.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frefriparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frefriparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frefriparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABICB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frefriparcha ipefia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nipetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frepudarcha iralana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frepudarcha iralana (N.L. fem. n. *iralana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIMK01 sp018896675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.85 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frepudarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frepudarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frepudarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIMK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frepudarcha iralana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frestunarcha agevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frestunarcha agevella (N.L. fem. n. *agevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-19 sp003661015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.84 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frestunarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frestunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frestunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-19. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frestunarcha agevella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methermicocaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frestunarcha ebexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frestunarcha ebexosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-19 sp002010075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002010075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.2 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fretrebarcha epagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fretrebarcha epagosa (N.L. fem. n. *epagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGIZ01 sp016867675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016867675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.64 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fretrebarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fretrebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fretrebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGIZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fretrebarcha epagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fribridarcha ipedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fribridarcha ipedella (N.L. fem. n. *ipedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCES01 sp017609045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.2 % and the genome length is 0.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fribridarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fribridarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fribridarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCES01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fribridarcha ipedella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frisatarcha itefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frisatarcha itefella (N.L. fem. n. *itefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTFW01 sp011363025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011363025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.86 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frisatarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frisatarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frisatarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTFW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Frisatarcha itefella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Frisatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frisatarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Frisatarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Frisatarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTFW01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Frisatarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Sobucarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fritrumarcha inemia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fritrumarcha inemia (N.L. fem. n. *inemia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPCC01 sp016179995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016179995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.59 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fritrumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fritrumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fritrumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPCC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fritrumarcha inemia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frixumarcha egabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frixumarcha egabosa (N.L. fem. n. *egabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACXTP01 sp016919625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016919625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.28 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frixumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frixumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frixumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACXTP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frixumarcha egabosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sogexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frobasarcha idanosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frobasarcha idanosa (N.L. fem. n. *idanosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGOA01 sp016926735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 26.23 % and the genome length is 3.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frobasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frobasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frobasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGOA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frobasarcha idanosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frofrusarcha ifedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frofrusarcha ifedana (N.L. fem. n. *ifedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIYYQ01 sp903930505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903930505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.01 % and the genome length is 2.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frofrusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frofrusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frofrusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIYYQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frofrusarcha ifedana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Froxicarcha onalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Froxicarcha onalaria (N.L. fem. n. *onalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPNN01 sp016185435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.12 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Froxicarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Froxicarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Froxicarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPNN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Froxicarcha onalaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frubranarcha odapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frubranarcha odapia (N.L. fem. n. *odapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTDI01 sp011362255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011362255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.61 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frubranarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frubranarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frubranarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTDI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frubranarcha odapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiserarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frubranarcha umaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frubranarcha umaparia (N.L. fem. n. *umaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTDI01 sp011334935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011334935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.0 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frugrisarcha orecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frugrisarcha orecaria (N.L. fem. n. *orecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADCV01 sp013154235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013154235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.86 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frugrisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frugrisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frugrisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADCV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frugrisarcha orecaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ignisphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frunebarcha alebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frunebarcha alebana (N.L. fem. n. *alebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKNY01 sp007123105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007123105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.08 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frunebarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frunebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frunebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SKNY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frunebarcha alebana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Frunebarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frunebarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Frunebarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Frunebarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SKNY01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Frunebarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Halobacteriales*.

Description of *Candidatus Frunebarcha igecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frunebarcha igecaria (N.L. fem. n. *igecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKNY01 sp007118975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007118975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.0 % and the genome length is 3.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frusagarcha ibaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frusagarcha ibaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ibaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B63 sp001593845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001593845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.87 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "marine sediment sample collected by push cores at a deep sea vent site during cruise AT15-25 on Alvin dive 4358; sediment was oily and the sediment surface was covered with a white microbial mat".

Description of *Candidatus Frusagarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frusagarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frusagarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B63. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frusagarcha ibaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frusagarcha irefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frusagarcha irefana (N.L. fem. n. *irefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B63 sp003601695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003601695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.73 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frusagarcha onalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frusagarcha onalia (N.L. fem. n. *onalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B63 sp003601725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003601725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.83 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frusagarcha umegaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frusagarcha umegaria (N.L. fem. n. *umegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B63 sp003661975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.65 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frusonarcha quefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Frusonarcha quefana (N.L. fem. n. *quefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B15-G16 sp003649205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.25 % and the genome length is 2.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Frusonarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Frusonarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Frusonarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B15-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Frusonarcha quefana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Frusonarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Frusonarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Frusonarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Frusonarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B15-G16. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Frusonarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Thermoproteales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fruxibarcha otavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fruxibarcha otavosa (N.L. fem. n. *otavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1443 sp015662475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015662475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.39 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fruxibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fruxibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fruxibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZUA-1443. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fruxibarcha otavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pyrodictiaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fubastarcha acegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fubastarcha acegella (N.L. fem. n. *acegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SIG5 sp017508065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017508065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.79 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fubastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fubastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fubastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SIG5. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fubastarcha acegella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fubastarcha ecagaría* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fubastarcha ecagaría (N.L. fem. n. *ecagaría* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SIG5 sp015063195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017407825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.49 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fubastarcha egabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fubastarcha egabaria (N.L. fem. n. *egabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SIG5 sp017395275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017395275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.4 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fubastarcha ogaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fubastarcha ogaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ogaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SIG5 sp016297775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016297015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.81 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fubastarcha ufepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fubastarcha ufepella (N.L. fem. n. *ufepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SIG5 sp015063185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015063185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.83 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fucetrarcha ecatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fucetrarcha ecatana (N.L. fem. n. *ecatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-83 sp011365025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011365025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.2 % and the genome length is 3.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fucetrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fucetrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fucetrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SMTZ1-83. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fucetrarcha ecatana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fucetrarcha efapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fucetrarcha efapia (N.L. fem. n. *efapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-83 sp011364985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.51 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fucetrarcha onadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fucetrarcha onadella (N.L. fem. n. *onadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-83 sp001563325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.28 % and the genome length is 3.26 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-methane transition zone estuary sediments 16-26 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Fucetrarcha ufaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fucetrarcha ufaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ufaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-83 sp016839605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.42 % and the genome length is 3.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fucladarcha ugapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fucladarcha ugapella (N.L. fem. n. *ugapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIRCU01 sp903877165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903907105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.78 % and the genome length is

1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fucladarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fucladarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fucladarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIRCU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fucladarcha ugapella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fugleprarcha imecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fugleprarcha imecella (N.L. fem. n. *imecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-002792115 sp002792115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002792115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.22 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fugleprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fugleprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fugleprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-002792115. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Fugleprarcha imecella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fugosarcha epavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fugosarcha epavosa (N.L. fem. n. *epavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688965 sp002688965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.71 % and the genome length is 1.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fugosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fugosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fugosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2688965. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fugosarcha epavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fugosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fugosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fugosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fugosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-2688965. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fugosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Coxosarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Fugustarcha enafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fugustarcha enafosa (N.L. fem. n. *enafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQID01 sp016198645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.38 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fugustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fugustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fugustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQID01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fugustarcha enafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fugustarcha etabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fugustarcha etabella (N.L. fem. n. *etabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQID01 sp018304585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.58 % and the genome length is

0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fugustarcha unegaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fugustarcha unegaria (N.L. fem. n. *unegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQID01 sp016198685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.2 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fumotarcha ovacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fumotarcha ovacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ovacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQK01 sp015520265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.96 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fumotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fumotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fumotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fumotarcha ovacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fumotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fumotarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fumotarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fumotarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WAQK01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fumotarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Sulfolobales*.

Description of *Candidatus Funistarcha ivadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Funistarcha ivadia (N.L. fem. n. *ivadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA95 sp002499405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002785565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.55 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Funistarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Funistarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Funistarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA95. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Funistarcha ivadia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Norongarragalinae*.

Description of *Candidatus Funixarcha udeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Funixarcha udeparia (N.L. fem. n. *udeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA12382 sp009889625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009889625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.24 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Funixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Funixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Funixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA12382. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Funixarcha udeparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Funixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Funixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Funixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Funixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA12382. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Funixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Halobacteriales.

Description of *Candidatus Funixarcha uvaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Funixarcha uvaxana (N.L. fem. n. *uvaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA12382 sp009889685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009889685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.72 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Funixarcha vuxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Funixarcha vuxella (N.L. fem. n. *vuxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA12382 sp002503845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.55 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Funocrarcha elaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Funocrarcha elaxia (N.L. fem. n. *elaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Acd1 sp000389735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000389735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.68 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "hot spring water and gravel".

Description of *Candidatus Funocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Funocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Funocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Acd1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Funocrarcha elaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sulfolobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fupristarcha ucedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fupristarcha ucedia (N.L. fem. n. *ucedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQPM01 sp016207475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016207475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.46 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fupristarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fupristarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fupristarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQPM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fupristarcha ucedia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fosilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Furograrcha utacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Furograrcha utacella (N.L. fem. n. *utacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA11998 sp002686315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002686315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.19 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Furograrcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Furograrcha (N.L. fem. n. *Furograrcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA11998. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Furograrcha utacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fustecarcha itagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fustecarcha itagia (N.L. fem. n. *itagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AD8-1 sp016649625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_016649625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.9 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fustecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fustecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fustecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is AD8-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fustecarcha itagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fustecarcha opavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fustecarcha opavaria (N.L. fem. n. *opavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AD8-1 sp001273385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001273385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.43 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-rich zone estuary sediments 8-12 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Fusticrarcha ubemia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fusticrarcha ubemia (N.L. fem. n. *ubemia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQMV01 sp016203395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.94 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fusticrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fusticrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fusticrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQMV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fusticrarcha ubemia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Futrostarcha amacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Futrostarcha amacella (N.L. fem. n. *amacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIDC01 sp018651925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018651925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.99 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Futrostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Futrostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Futrostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABIDC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Futrostarcha amacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fuxofrarcha ogepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Fuxofrarcha ogepia (N.L. fem. n. *ogepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGTQN01 sp018396395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.38 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Fuxofrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Fuxofrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Fuxofrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGTQN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Fuxofrarcha ogepia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fuxofrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Fuxofrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Fuxofrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Fuxofrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

taxon is JAGTQN01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Fuxofrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omexarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gafrabarcha edafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gafrabarcha edafaria (N.L. fem. n. *edafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA226 sp002719475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002719475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.05 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gafrabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gafrabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gafrabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA226. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gafrabarcha edafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gafrabarcha idabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gafrabarcha idabosa (N.L. fem. n. *idabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA226 sp012959275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012959275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.67 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gafrabarcha ilacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gafrabarcha ilacia (N.L. fem. n. *ilacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA226 sp014240385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014240385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.66 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gafrabarcha iperella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gafrabarcha iperella (N.L. fem. n. *iperella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA226 sp002505935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.87 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Gagliprarcha ipedaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Gagliprarcha ipedaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCB01 sp017610445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.47 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Gagliprarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Gagliprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gagliprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Gagliprarcha ipedaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Gaglitarcha enexana sp. nov.

Candidatus Gaglitarcha enexana (N.L. fem. n. *enexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B-DKE sp011334705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011334705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.75 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Gaglitarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Gaglitarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gaglitarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B-DKE. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Gaglitarcha enexana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermoplasmataceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gaglitarcha uvagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gaglitarcha uvagia (N.L. fem. n. *uvagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B-DKE sp002204705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016806715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.42 % and the genome length is 1.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gamifrarcha esacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gamifrarcha esacia (N.L. fem. n. *esacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSLH01 sp011053435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011053435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.96 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gamifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gamifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gamifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSLH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gamifrarcha esacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gasuxarcha itefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gasuxarcha itefia (N.L. fem. n. *itefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B20-G17 sp003650785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.15 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gasuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gasuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gasuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B20-G17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gasuxarcha itefia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gasuxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gasuxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gasuxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gasuxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B20-G17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gasuxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Thermofilales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gefrugrarcha ifetana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gefrugrarcha ifetana (N.L. fem. n. *ifetana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQNX01 sp016202875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.96 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gefrugrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gefrugrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gefrugrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQNX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gefrugrarcha ifetana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gefuprarcha ucarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gefuprarcha ucarella (N.L. fem. n. *ucarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JAGTQI01 sp018396955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.94 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gefuprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gefuprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gefuprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGTQI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gefuprarcha ucarella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Geoglobus amevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Geoglobus amevaria (N.L. fem. n. *amevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Geoglobus sp015523645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.37 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Geoglobus itavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Geoglobus itavaria (N.L. fem. n. *itavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Geoglobus sp002494725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004366975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.48 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Geoglobus itepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Geoglobus itepana (N.L. fem. n. *itepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Geoglobus sp015522195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.62 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Geprottrarcha inegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Geprottrarcha inegosa (N.L. fem. n. *inegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOXS01 sp018220985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018220985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.03 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Geprotrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Geprotrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Geprotrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOXS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Geprotrarcha inegosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Getofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gesefarcha isatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gesefarcha isatana (N.L. fem. n. *isatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCGA01 sp017608345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.71 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gesefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gesefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gesefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCGA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gesefarcha isatana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gesefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gesefarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gesefarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gesefarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFCGA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gesefarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Laxucarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gestalarcha alebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gestalarcha alebia (N.L. fem. n. *alebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPAE01 sp016187385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.69 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gestalarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gestalarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gestalarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPAE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gestalarcha alebia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gestalarcha ipatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gestalarcha ipatella (N.L. fem. n. *ipatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPAE01 sp016181005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.93 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gestifrarcha isalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gestifrarcha isalia (N.L. fem. n. *isalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WRER01 sp009779205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009779205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.49 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gestifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gestifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gestifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WRER01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gestifrarcha isalia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanospirillaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Getastarcha cufella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Getastarcha cufella (N.L. fem. n. *cufella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K2 sp002719395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002695145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.07 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Getastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Getastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Getastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIa-K2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Getastarcha cufella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Getastarcha ebavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Getastarcha ebavia (N.L. fem. n. *ebavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K2 sp002699425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002699425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.54 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Getastarcha igacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Getastarcha igacella (N.L. fem. n. *igacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K2 sp905181715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_905181715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.96 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Getisarcha efalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Getisarcha efalaria (N.L. fem. n. *efalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKR01 sp014729015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.75 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Getisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Getisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Getisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJKR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Getisarcha efalaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Getisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Getisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Getisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Getisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJKR01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Getisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Getisarcha onevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Getisarcha onevosa (N.L. fem. n. *onevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKR01 sp016927245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016927245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.09 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Getofarcha icabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Getofarcha icabosa (N.L. fem. n. *icabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PEZQ01 sp002763265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002763265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.86 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Getofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Getofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Getofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PEZQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Getofarcha icabosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Getofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Getofarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Getofarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Getofarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PEZQ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Getofarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Getofarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Getofarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Getofarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Getofarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PEZQ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Getofarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Nanoarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Getrafrarcha ucenosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Getrafrarcha ucenosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucenosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is B1SED10-34 sp003551065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003551065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.04 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Getrafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Getrafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Getrafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B1SED10-34. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Getrafrarcha ucenosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natronoplasmataceae*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Giboxarcha ufapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Giboxarcha ufapia (N.L. fem. n. *ufapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA489 sp002505585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.03 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Giboxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Giboxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Giboxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA489. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Giboxarcha ufapia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Giboxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Giboxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Giboxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Giboxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA489. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Giboxarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gifedarcha apabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gifedarcha apabana (N.L. fem. n. *apabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCFF01 sp017608775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.0 % and the genome length is 0.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gifedarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gifedarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gifedarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCFF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gifedarcha apabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gifedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gifedarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gifedarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gifedarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFCCFF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gifedarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Forterreales*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Gifisarcha umavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gifisarcha umavaria (N.L. fem. n. *umavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B18-G2 sp003651105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003651105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.22 % and the genome length is 0.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gifisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gifisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gifisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B18-G2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gifisarcha umavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gifisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gifisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gifisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gifisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B18-G2. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gifisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Esacarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gilonarcha ibetia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gilonarcha ibetia (N.L. fem. n. *ibetia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS21 sp002725495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002725495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.28 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gilonarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gilonarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gilonarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS21. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gilonarcha ibetia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gilonarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gilonarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gilonarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gilonarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is ARS21. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gilonarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Laxucarchales.

Description of *Candidatus Gilonarcha ovelaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gilonarcha ovelaria (N.L. fem. n. *ovelaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS21 sp002686215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002686215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.34 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gilonarcha udavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gilonarcha udavosa (N.L. fem. n. *udavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS21 sp014239585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014239585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.13 % and the genome length is 0.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gimagrarcha ebamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gimagrarcha ebamia (N.L. fem. n. *ebamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MTP4 sp000970045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016841785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.82 % and the genome length is 4.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gimagrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gimagrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gimagrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MTP4. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Gimagrarcha ebamia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanosarcinaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gimagrarcha egacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gimagrarcha egacosa (N.L. fem. n. *egacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MTP4 sp9310u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.79 % and the genome length is 3.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gimagrarcha enafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gimagrarcha enafella (N.L. fem. n. *enafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MTP4 sp016841625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016841625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.26 % and the genome length is 3.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gimagrarcha ifeposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gimagrarcha ifeposa (N.L. fem. n. *ifeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MTP4 sp016841265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016841265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.0 % and the genome length is 3.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gimifarcha itecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gimifarcha itecaria (N.L. fem. n. *itecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO6 sp011367165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011367165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.88 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gimifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gimifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gimifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WYZ-LMO6. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gimifarcha itecaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gimifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gimifarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gimifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gimifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WYZ-LMO6. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gimifarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hadarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gimifarcha ovaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gimifarcha ovaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ovaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO6 sp004347925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004347925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.02 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Giprufarcha upabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Giprufarcha upabosa (N.L. fem. n. *upabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDZ01 sp017609405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.77 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Giprufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Giprufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Giprufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Giprufarcha upabosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gistibrarcha ucenella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gistibrarcha ucenella (N.L. fem. n. *ucenella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PUNK01 sp003552585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003552585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.6 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gistibrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gistibrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gistibrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PUNK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gistibrarcha ucenella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natronoplasmataceae*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Gisumarcha igexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gisumarcha igexana (N.L. fem. n. *igexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-236 sp003230355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003230355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.58 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gisumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gisumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gisumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZUA-236. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gisumarcha igexana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gisumarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gisumarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gisumarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gisumarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SZUA-236. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gisumarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hydrothermarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gisumarcha itacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gisumarcha itacaria (N.L. fem. n. *itacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-236 sp002923215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002923215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.74 % and the genome length is 1.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gitrisarcha olabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gitrisarcha olabana (N.L. fem. n. *olabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WTHC01 sp011523285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012271085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.23 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gitrisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gitrisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gitrisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WTHC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Gitrisarcha olabana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Glastefarcha ebegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Glastefarcha ebegosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTHR01 sp011334665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011334665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.91 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Glastefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Glastefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Glastefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is DTHR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Glastefarcha ebegosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Gledebarcha adafella sp. nov.

Candidatus Gledebarcha adafella (N.L. fem. n. *adafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOXY01 sp018221065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.23 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Gledebarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Gledebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gledebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOXY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Gledebarcha adafella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aenigmataarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Gletasarcha agacosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Gletasarcha agacosa (N.L. fem. n. *agacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPNA01 sp016185725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.12 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Gletasarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Gletasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gletasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPNA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Gletasarcha agacosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Glidimarcha esacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Glidimarcha esacaria (N.L. fem. n. *esacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXD01 sp018303945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.13 % and the genome length is 0.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Glidimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Glidimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Glidimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Glidimarcha esacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Glidrefarcha alebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Glidrefarcha alebaria (N.L. fem. n. *alebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYS01 sp018303125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.39 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Glidrefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Glidrefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Glidrefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Glidrefarcha alebaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixiprarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Glisiparcha unagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Glisiparcha unagosa (N.L. fem. n. *unagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MWBV01 sp002069705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017991485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.38 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Glisiparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Glisiparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Glisiparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MWBV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Glisiparcha unagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Globuxarcha ucaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Globuxarcha ucaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAMX01 sp015522095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.11 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Globuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Globuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Globuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAMX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Globuxarcha ucaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iduparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Glosifarcha udefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Glosifarcha udefella (N.L. fem. n. *udefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRGE01 sp016212465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016212465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.15 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Glosifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Glosifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Glosifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRGE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Glosifarcha udefella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Glosifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Glosifarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Glosifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Glosifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACRGE01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Glosifarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Glublamarcha ogefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Glublamarcha ogefaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXL01 sp018303805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.1 % and the genome length is 0.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Glublamarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Glublamarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Glublamarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Glublamarcha ogefaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Micubrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gobedrarcha ibapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gobedrarcha ibapia (N.L. fem. n. *ibapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QENH01 sp003336485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003336485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.89 % and the genome length is 3.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gobedrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gobedrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gobedrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QENH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gobedrarcha* *ibapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gobedrarcha igexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gobedrarcha igexella (N.L. fem. n. *igexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QENH01 sp013180565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013180565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.03 % and the genome length is 2.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gobedrarcha ocevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gobedrarcha ocevaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QENH01 sp013139985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013139985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.88 % and the genome length is 2.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gobedrarcha orafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gobedrarcha orafaria (N.L. fem. n. *orafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QENH01 sp009903405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009903405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.76 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gobrostarcha ogefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gobrostarcha ogefella (N.L. fem. n. *ogefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOYM01 sp016181905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.5 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gobrostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gobrostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gobrostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOYM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gobrostarcha ogefella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Godrimarcha udexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Godrimarcha udexia (N.L. fem. n. *udexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGLG01 sp016928155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016928155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.39 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Godrimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Godrimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Godrimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGLG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Godrimarcha udexia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Godrimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Godrimarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Godrimarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Godrimarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGLG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Godrimarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Gofestarcha abemella sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha abemella (N.L. fem. n. *abemella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002727515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002727515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.44 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Gofestarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gofestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIa-K1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Gofestarcha abemella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Gofestarcha agafana sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha agafana (N.L. fem. n. *agafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002689345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002689345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.77 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Gofestarcha asabaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha asabaria (N.L. fem. n. *asabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002701145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002701145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.62 % and the genome length is 1.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ecabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ecabia (N.L. fem. n. *ecabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp011522915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011522915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.06 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ecepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ecepella (N.L. fem. n. *ecepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002506705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.28 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha epafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha epafaria (N.L. fem. n. *epafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002715725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002715725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.56 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ibacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ibacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ibacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002498185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.92 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ibetaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ibetaria (N.L. fem. n. *ibetaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp902605365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902605365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.39 % and the genome length is

1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ifabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ifabia (N.L. fem. n. *ifabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002720115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002720115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.03 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ifatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ifatana (N.L. fem. n. *ifatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002727695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002727695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.63 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha imavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha imavosa (N.L. fem. n. *imavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002706615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.69 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha inafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha inafella (N.L. fem. n. *inafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp003602415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.93 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ocanella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ocanella (N.L. fem. n. *ocanella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is MGIIa-K1 sp002694245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002694245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.81 % and the genome length is 1.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha olagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha olagaria (N.L. fem. n. *olagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp902563095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.86 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha oredia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha oredia (N.L. fem. n. *oredia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002709705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002709705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.03 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha osavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha osavosa (N.L. fem. n. *osavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp018650165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018650165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.92 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha osebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha osebosa (N.L. fem. n. *osebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp003602535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.04 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha phepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha phepella (N.L. fem. n. *phepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002707335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002707335.2. The GC content of the type genome is 40.51 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ubenella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ubenella (N.L. fem. n. *ubenella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002689565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002689565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.32 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha udaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha udaxana (N.L. fem. n. *udaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002507425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002504995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.94 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha ufadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha ufadella (N.L. fem. n. *ufadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp011525095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011525095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.88 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha unafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha unafosa (N.L. fem. n. *unafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002710205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002710205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.94 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha urafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha urafosa (N.L. fem. n. *urafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp009936765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009936765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.71 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha utafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha utafia (N.L. fem. n. *utafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp002710015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.21 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gofestarcha uvaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gofestarcha uvaposa (N.L. fem. n. *uvaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-K1 sp004195515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015659875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.09 % and the genome length is 2.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Goglidrarcha ofalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Goglidrarcha ofalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGWAC01 sp018302125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.0 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Goglidrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Goglidrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Goglidrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGWAC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Goglidrarcha ofalosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hicrosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gogrofrarcha uvecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gogrofrarcha uvecosa (N.L. fem. n. *uvecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOYK01 sp018221305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.29 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gogrofrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gogrofrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gogrofrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOYK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gogrofrarcha uvecosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gopruxarcha ipavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gopruxarcha ipavia (N.L. fem. n. *ipavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMGE01 sp018304045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.15 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gopruxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gopruxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gopruxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CABMGE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gopruxarcha ipavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gopruxarcha ugabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gopruxarcha ugabana (N.L. fem. n. *ugabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMGE01 sp902385625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.71 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gopurarcha udagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gopurarcha udagosa (N.L. fem. n. *udagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CR-4 sp001940655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001940655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.06 % and the genome length is 4.33 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 13ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Gopurarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gopurarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gopurarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CR-4. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gopurarcha udagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gopurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gopurarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gopurarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gopurarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CR-4. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gopurarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Prometheoarchaeales*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Gorufrarcha efarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gorufrarcha efarella (N.L. fem. n. *efarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYX01 sp018303045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.32 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gorufrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gorufrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gorufrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gorufrarcha efarella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gosularcha esepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gosularcha esepella (N.L. fem. n. *esepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZF01 sp018302785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.29 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gosularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gosularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gosularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gosularcha esepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gosularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gosularchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gosularchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gosularchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVZF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gosularcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gosularcha ifacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gosularcha ifacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZF01 sp018302805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.06 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Goxafrarcha utacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Goxafrarcha utacia (N.L. fem. n. *utacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA11855 sp11852u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.22 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Goxafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Goxafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Goxafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA11855. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Goxafrarcha utacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Goxograrcha unaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Goxograrcha unaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *unaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGBZ01 sp016932875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.72 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Goxograrcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Goxograrcha (N.L. fem. n. *Goxograrcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGBZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Goxograrcha unaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Goxograrchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Goxograrchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Goxograrchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Goxograrchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGBZ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Goxograrcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Grabinarcha ebacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grabinarcha ebacia (N.L. fem. n. *ebacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B67-G16 sp003650675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.12 % and the genome length is 2.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grabinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Grabinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grabinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B67-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Grabinarcha ebacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gasuxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Graprusarcha omabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Graprusarcha omabosa (N.L. fem. n. *omabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QH-10-67-22 sp003021305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.13 % and the genome length is 2.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Graprusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Graprusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Graprusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QH-10-67-22. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Graprusarcha omabosa. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloarculaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Grepridarcha itadia sp. nov.

Candidatus Grepridarcha itadia (N.L. fem. n. *itadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOYC01 sp016182015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016182015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.82 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Grepridarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Grepridarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grepridarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOYC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Grepridarcha itadia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Laxucarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Grepridarcha uvacia sp. nov.

Candidatus Grepridarcha uvacia (N.L. fem. n. *uvacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOYC01 sp016204275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016204275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.89 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Gretrosarcha efexosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Gretrosarcha efexosa (N.L. fem. n. *efexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SW-4-43-9 sp003009815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003009815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.5 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gretrosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gretrosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gretrosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SW-4-43-9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Gretrosarcha efexosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nanosalinaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gretrosarcha phebica* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gretrosarcha phebica (N.L. fem. n. *phebica* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SW-4-43-9 sp003009795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003009795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.61 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grifixarcha upamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grifixarcha upamana (N.L. fem. n. *upamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJDQ01 sp018812355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018812355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.55 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grifixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Grifixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grifixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJDQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Grifixarcha upamana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Grifrimarcha erabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grifrimarcha erabana (N.L. fem. n. *erabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA204 sp002501765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002501765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.54 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grifrimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Grifrimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grifrimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA204. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Grifrimarcha erabana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanotrichaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Grisomarcha ibacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grisomarcha ibacana (N.L. fem. n. *ibacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJDB01 sp018812765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018822605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.51 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grisomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Grisomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grisomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJDB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Grisomarcha ibacana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Grofetarcha onatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grofetarcha onatosa (N.L. fem. n. *onatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is YT-029 sp016840245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.62 % and the genome length is 4.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grofetarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Grofetarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grofetarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is YT-029. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Grofetarcha onatosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Grofrebarcha ebexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grofrebarcha ebexella (N.L. fem. n. *ebexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYY01 sp018303005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.73 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grofrebarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Grofrebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grofrebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Grofrebarcha ebexella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Grufraxarcha egefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grufraxarcha egefia (N.L. fem. n. *egefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SICU01 sp018303995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.11 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grufraxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Grufraxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grufraxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SICU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Grufraxarcha egefia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Grufraxarcha ogexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grufraxarcha ogexella (N.L. fem. n. *ogexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SICU01 sp009694755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009694755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.56 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grufraxarcha ugabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grufraxarcha ugabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ugabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SICU01 sp016866935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016866935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.99 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grusetarcha epanana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Grusetarcha epanana (N.L. fem. n. *epanana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWJ01 sp018304385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.5 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Grusetarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Grusetarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Grusetarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVWJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Grusetarcha epanana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gublubrarcha ifevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gublubrarcha ifevia (N.L. fem. n. *ifevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMCB01 sp902384455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902384455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.5 % and the genome length is 2.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gublubrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gublubrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gublubrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CABMCB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gublubrarcha ifevia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiragarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gudamarcha ereparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gudamarcha ereparia (N.L. fem. n. *ereparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTGL01 sp011334955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011334955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.32 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gudamarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gudamarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gudamarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTGL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gudamarcha ereparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gudamarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gudamarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gudamarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gudamarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTGL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gudamarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gufagrarcha avafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gufagrarcha avafia (N.L. fem. n. *avafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EA-19 sp005878915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.9 % and the genome length is 2.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gufagrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gufagrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gufagrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EA-19. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gufagrarcha avafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Figanarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gufagrarcha ifesana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gufagrarcha ifesana (N.L. fem. n. *ifesana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EA-19 sp005878955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.8 % and the genome length is 2.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gufrotarcha ivacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gufrotarcha ivacella (N.L. fem. n. *ivacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOXW01 sp018221005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.28 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gufrotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gufrotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gufrotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOXW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gufrotarcha ivacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iduparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gulusarcha unegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gulusarcha unegella (N.L. fem. n. *unegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQQB01 sp016207225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016207225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.45 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gulusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gulusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gulusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQQB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gulusarcha unegella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gulusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gulusarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gulusarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gulusarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQQB01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gulusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Gulusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gulusarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Gulusarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Gulusarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQQB01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gulusarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Micrarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Gumostarcha usaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gumostarcha usaxella (N.L. fem. n. *usaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIKMX01 sp903828655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903828655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.75 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gumostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gumostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gumostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIKMX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gumostarcha usaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gunesarcha arexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gunesarcha arexana (N.L. fem. n. *arexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B79-G9 sp003660865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003660865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.17 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gunesarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gunesarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gunesarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B79-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gunesarcha arexana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Gunesarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Gunesarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gunesarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gunesarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B79-G9. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gunesarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Axalarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Gunesarcha ulavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gunesarcha ulavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ulavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B79-G9 sp017610525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.94 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gutrixarcha agevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gutrixarcha agevosa (N.L. fem. n. *agevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-13 sp005877185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005877185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.54 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gutrixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gutrixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gutrixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TA-13. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gutrixarcha agevosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Naraxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gutrixarcha efavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gutrixarcha efavella (N.L. fem. n. *efavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-13 sp005877365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005877365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.97 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gutrixarcha iragana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gutrixarcha iragana (N.L. fem. n. *iragana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-13 sp005877225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005877455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.5 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gutufrarcha umenaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Gutufrarcha umenaria (N.L. fem. n. *umenaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B3-WOES sp005222965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005222965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.17 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Gutufrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Gutufrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Gutufrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B3-WOES. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Gutufrarcha umenaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gutufrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Gutufrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Gutufrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Gutufrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B3-WOES. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Gutufrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Woesearchaeales.

Description of *Candidatus Habrasarcha anabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Habrasarcha anabosa (N.L. fem. n. *anabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4572-64 sp002254895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.24 % and the genome length is 0.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Habrasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Habrasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Habrasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4572-64. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Habrasarcha anabosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermocladiaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Habrutarcha ecavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Habrutarcha ecavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ecavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B40-G2 sp003649615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.12 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Habrutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Habrutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Habrutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B40-G2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Habrutarcha ecavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Habrutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Habrutarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Habrutarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Habrutarchaceae* a name created from the name of

the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B40-G2. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Habrutarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nezhaarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hacexarcha osaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hacexarcha osaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *osaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRUP01 sp011371845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011371845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.11 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hacexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hacexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hacexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRUP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hacexarcha osaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hacexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hacexarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hacexarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hacexarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DRUP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hacexarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ifutarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Haclunarcha efabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haclunarcha efabana (N.L. fem. n. *efabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is CAIXYX01 sp903923795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903923795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.36 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haclunarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Haclunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Haclunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIXYX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Haclunarcha efabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Anstonellaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Haclunarcha odafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haclunarcha odafaria (N.L. fem. n. *odafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIXYX01 sp902384555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902384555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.71 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hacrixarcha etacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hacrixarcha etacana (N.L. fem. n. *etacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGQV01 sp016935475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.4 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hacrixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hacrixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hacrixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGQV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hacrixarcha etacana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanosarcinaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hacrixarcha umacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hacrixarcha umacaria (N.L. fem. n. *umacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGQV01 sp016926455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.43 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hadarchaeum ebataria sp. nov.

Candidatus Hadarchaeum ebataria (N.L. fem. n. *ebataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hadarchaeum sp014361095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.89 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hadrebarcha ifabella sp. nov.

Candidatus Hadrebarcha ifabella (N.L. fem. n. *ifabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 0-14-0-80-44-23 sp002779235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002779235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.26 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hadrebarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hadrebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hadrebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 0-14-0-80-44-23. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hadrebarcha ifabella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hadrebarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hadrebarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hadrebarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hadrebarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is 0-14-0-80-44-23. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hadrebarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hafolarcha ocagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafolarcha ocagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACIWG01 sp014361085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.65 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafolarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hafolarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hafolarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACIWG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hafolarcha ocagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hafolarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hafolarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hafolarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hafolarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACIWG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hafolarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hafolarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hafolarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Hafolarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Hafolarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACIWG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hafolarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Nitrososphaeria*.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrodarcha ivecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrodarcha ivecaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ECH-B-1 sp902812505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902812505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.14 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hafrodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hafrodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ECH-B-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hafrodarcha ivecaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Marsarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrodarcha muvosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrodarcha muvosa (N.L. fem. n. *muvosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ECH-B-1 sp003019535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003019535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.76 % and the genome length is 2.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha afebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha afebana (N.L. fem. n. *afebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp003589585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003589585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.9 % and the genome length is 2.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hafrusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is PALSA-986. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hafrusarcha afebana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hafrusarcha agepia sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha agepia (N.L. fem. n. *agepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp003164295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003164295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.33 % and the genome length is 3.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hafrusarcha apagia sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha apagia (N.L. fem. n. *apagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp009778385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009778385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.31 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hafrusarcha asafana sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha asafana (N.L. fem. n. *asafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp011367965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011367965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.67 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hafrusarcha ecaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha ecaria (N.L. fem. n. *ecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp009787585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009787585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.81 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hafrusarcha emabaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha emabaria (N.L. fem. n. *emabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp009787175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009787255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.5 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha epadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha epadella (N.L. fem. n. *epadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp012513715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012513715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.68 % and the genome length is 2.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha epafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha epafana (N.L. fem. n. *epafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp003141855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003141295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.34 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha ibaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha ibaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ibaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp003165195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003165195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.93 % and the genome length is 3.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha icagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha icagaria (N.L. fem. n. *icagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp009779045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009784175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.17 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha idacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha idacana (N.L. fem. n. *idacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp903901015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903884205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.43 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha igaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha igaxella (N.L. fem. n. *igaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp009781395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009781395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.03 % and the genome length is 2.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha ilavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha ilavella (N.L. fem. n. *ilavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp003133625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003133625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.81 % and the genome length is 2.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha ocaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha ocaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ocaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp012511995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012511995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.89 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha onabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha onabosa (N.L. fem. n. *onabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp012515445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012515445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.01 % and the genome length is

2.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha otamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha otamella (N.L. fem. n. *otamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp011332615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011332615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.23 % and the genome length is 2.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha otegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha otegia (N.L. fem. n. *otegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp009776805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009776805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.58 % and the genome length is 2.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha quefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha quefia (N.L. fem. n. *quefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp003151735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003151735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.32 % and the genome length is 3.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha ugapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha ugapana (N.L. fem. n. *ugapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PALSA-986 sp009781675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009785285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.38 % and the genome length is 2.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hafrusarcha upamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hafrusarcha upamia (N.L. fem. n. *upamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is PALSA-986 sp009783705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009783705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.28 % and the genome length is 2.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hagefarcha urelosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hagefarcha urelosa (N.L. fem. n. *urelosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LCB-4 sp001940665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001940665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.05 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "lower Culex Basin hot spring".

Description of *Candidatus Hagefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hagefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hagefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is LCB-4. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hagefarcha urelosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hagefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hagefarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hagefarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hagefarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is LCB-4. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hagefarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Odinarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hagefarcha utavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hagefarcha utavella (N.L. fem. n. *utavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LCB-4 sp016839265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.28 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haladaptatus etabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haladaptatus etabosa (N.L. fem. n. *etabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haladaptatus sp003298465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003298465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.96 % and the genome length is 5.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haladaptatus onagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haladaptatus onagella (N.L. fem. n. *onagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haladaptatus sp001625445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001625445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.18 % and the genome length is 4.9 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "saltern".

Description of *Candidatus Halalkalirubrum orafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halalkalirubrum orafella (N.L. fem. n. *orafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halalkalirubrum sp003551725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003551725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.03 % and the genome length is 3.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halalkalirubrum ucanaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halalkalirubrum ucanaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucanaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halalkalirubrum sp005239175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005239175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.02 % and the genome length is 3.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halapricum asebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halapricum asebosa (N.L. fem. n. *asebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halapricum sp017094465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_017094465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.09 % and the genome length is 2.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halapricum edalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halapricum edalaria (N.L. fem. n. *edalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halapricum sp017094505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017094505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.68 % and the genome length is 2.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halapricum inabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halapricum inabaria (N.L. fem. n. *inabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halapricum sp017094525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017094445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.85 % and the genome length is 3.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halapricum isatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halapricum isatella (N.L. fem. n. *isatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halapricum sp009741825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009741825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.19 % and the genome length is 2.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halegenticoccus ocamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halegenticoccus ocamosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halegenticoccus sp004116405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004116405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.72 % and the genome length is 4.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haloarcula acevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloarcula acevaria (N.L. fem. n. *acevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloarcula sp001485575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001485575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.95 % and the genome length is 4.36 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "solar salt".

Description of *Candidatus Haloarcula eracana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloarcula eracana (N.L. fem. n. *eracana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloarcula sp005406125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_005406125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.08 % and the genome length is 4.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haloarcula ilasaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloarcula ilasaria (N.L. fem. n. *ilasaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloarcula sp008729015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_008729015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.58 % and the genome length is 4.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobacterium ebevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobacterium ebevella (N.L. fem. n. *ebevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobacterium sp000230955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000230955.2. The GC content of the type genome is 66.43 % and the genome length is 3.16 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "not provided; submitted under MGS 2.1".

Description of *Candidatus Halobacterium epebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobacterium epebella (N.L. fem. n. *epebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobacterium sp011734195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_011734195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.94 % and the genome length is 2.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobacterium ilepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobacterium ilepella (N.L. fem. n. *ilepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobacterium sp009831555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009831555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.78 % and the genome length is 3.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobacterium ipedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobacterium ipedosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobacterium sp001485535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001485535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.95 % and the genome length is 3.01 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "solar salt".

Description of *Candidatus Halobacterium ugabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobacterium ugabella (N.L. fem. n. *ugabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobacterium sp009741975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009741975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.15 % and the genome length is 2.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobaculum avefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobaculum avefaria (N.L. fem. n. *avefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobaculum sp003020945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003020945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 70.91 % and the genome length is 2.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobaculum omexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobaculum omexella (N.L. fem. n. *omexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobaculum sp009831625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009831625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.62 % and the genome length is

3.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobaculum oragella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobaculum oragella (N.L. fem. n. *oragella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobaculum sp013401515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_013401515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.2 % and the genome length is 4.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobaculum otegaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobaculum otegaria (N.L. fem. n. *otegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobaculum sp013402875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_013402875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.65 % and the genome length is 4.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobaculum umafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobaculum umafana (N.L. fem. n. *umafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobaculum sp018609965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018609965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.78 % and the genome length is 2.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobellus enafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobellus enafia (N.L. fem. n. *enafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halobellus sp003665925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003665925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.56 % and the genome length is 3.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halobellus iregaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halobellus iregaria (N.L. fem. n. *iregaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Halobellus sp003665935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003665935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.32 % and the genome length is 3.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halococcus abemaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halococcus abemaria (N.L. fem. n. *abemaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halococcus sp003021725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.87 % and the genome length is 3.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halococcus ecabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halococcus ecabana (N.L. fem. n. *ecabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halococcus sp003022925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.19 % and the genome length is 3.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halococcus enabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halococcus enabana (N.L. fem. n. *enabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halococcus sp003021235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.65 % and the genome length is 3.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halococcus ilabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halococcus ilabana (N.L. fem. n. *ilabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halococcus sp003021045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.36 % and the genome length is 2.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halococcus ofaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halococcus ofaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ofaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halococcus sp003022685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.96 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halococcus umafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halococcus umafia (N.L. fem. n. *umafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halococcus sp003021705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.08 % and the genome length is 2.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halodesulfurarchaeum olacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halodesulfurarchaeum olacana (N.L. fem. n. *olacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halodesulfurarchaeum sp018334775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018334775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.45 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haloferax efatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloferax efatana (N.L. fem. n. *efatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloferax sp009674605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_008806815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.69 % and the genome length is 3.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haloferax ifavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloferax ifavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloferax sp009674585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009674585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.79 % and the genome length is 3.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haloferax uracella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloferax uracella (N.L. fem. n. *uracella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloferax sp009674625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_008806905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.06 % and the genome length is 3.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Haloferax urapia sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloferax urapia (N.L. fem. n. *urapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloferax sp001482285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001482285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.06 % and the genome length is 3.98 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "salt mine".

Description of *Candidatus* Haloglomus udapana sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloglomus udapana (N.L. fem. n. *udapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloglomus sp003020985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003020985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.69 % and the genome length is 2.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Halohasta ogemosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Halohasta ogemosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogemosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halohasta sp003554115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003554115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.82 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Halohasta phavosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Halohasta phavosa (N.L. fem. n. *phavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halohasta sp001563795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.8 % and the genome length is 2.37

Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample B1-Br-g2; brine of Lake Bitter-1".

Description of *Candidatus Halolamina onapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halolamina onapia (N.L. fem. n. *onapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halolamina sp000224475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000224475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.38 % and the genome length is 3.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halolamina otegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halolamina otegana (N.L. fem. n. *otegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halolamina sp002025255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_002025255.2. The GC content of the type genome is 66.75 % and the genome length is 3.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halomarina ecapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halomarina ecapella (N.L. fem. n. *ecapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halomarina sp003021975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 70.52 % and the genome length is 2.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halomicroarcula ufebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halomicroarcula ufebosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halomicroarcula sp003021755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.83 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halomicroarcula uravaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halomicroarcula uravaria (N.L. fem. n. *uravaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halomicroarcula sp003020925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003020925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.66 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halomicrobium esebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halomicrobium esebosa (N.L. fem. n. *esebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halomicrobium sp003021685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.94 % and the genome length is 2.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halomicrobium iragosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halomicrobium iragosa (N.L. fem. n. *iragosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halomicrobium sp009617995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012726095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.65 % and the genome length is 3.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halonotius avabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halonotius avabosa (N.L. fem. n. *avabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halonotius sp003605575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003605575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.22 % and the genome length is 2.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halonotius inabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halonotius inabosa (N.L. fem. n. *inabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halonotius sp000496215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000496215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.14 % and the genome length is 2.39 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "hypersaline water sample from Lake Tyrrell".

Description of *Candidatus Haloquadratum apavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloquadratum apavia (N.L. fem. n. *apavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloquadratum sp000416005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000416005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.68 % and the genome length is 3.02 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "filtered surface water from Lake Tyrrell".

Description of *Candidatus Halorhabdus isecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorhabdus isecia (N.L. fem. n. *isecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorhabdus sp013839425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_013839425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.51 % and the genome length is 2.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorhabdus ocadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorhabdus ocadella (N.L. fem. n. *ocadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorhabdus sp009690625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009797925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.42 % and the genome length is 2.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorhabdus ubefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorhabdus ubefana (N.L. fem. n. *ubefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorhabdus sp004944975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004944975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.1 % and the genome length is 3.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorientalis efexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorientalis efexella (N.L. fem. n. *efexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorientalis sp004118325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004118325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.7 % and the genome length is

4.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorientalis idafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorientalis idafia (N.L. fem. n. *idafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorientalis sp001989615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001989615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.58 % and the genome length is 3.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorientalis utedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorientalis utedia (N.L. fem. n. *utedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorientalis sp005049285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005049285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.24 % and the genome length is 3.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubellus ategaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubellus ategaria (N.L. fem. n. *ategaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubellus sp011440375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_011440375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.12 % and the genome length is 3.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum apavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum apavella (N.L. fem. n. *apavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp003781945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003781945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.47 % and the genome length is 3.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum ecafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum ecafana (N.L. fem. n. *ecafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Halorubrum sp003554605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003551525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.73 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum edapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum edapana (N.L. fem. n. *edapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp001564205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001564005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.48 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample PL-Br10; brine of Picturesque Lake".

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum edavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum edavosa (N.L. fem. n. *edavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp001261915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001261915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.56 % and the genome length is 3.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum emapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum emapia (N.L. fem. n. *emapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp003990725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003990725.2. The GC content of the type genome is 66.64 % and the genome length is 3.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum emefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum emefaria (N.L. fem. n. *emefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp000496175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000496175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.15 % and the genome length is 2.89 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "hypersaline water sample from Lake Tyrrell".

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum ibadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum ibadia (N.L. fem. n. *ibadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp002252755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_002252925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.65 % and the genome length is 3.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum idabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum idabaria (N.L. fem. n. *idabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp003023405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.71 % and the genome length is 2.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum iperaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum iperaria (N.L. fem. n. *iperaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp003721435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003721435.2. The GC content of the type genome is 67.66 % and the genome length is 3.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum obamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum obamaria (N.L. fem. n. *obamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp003697845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003697845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.1 % and the genome length is 3.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum obaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum obaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *obaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp002286985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_002286985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.4 % and the genome length is 3.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum ofabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum ofabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp005435165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_005435165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.39 % and the genome length is 3.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum ofaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum ofaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ofaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp000296615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000296615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.48 % and the genome length is 3.17 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "solar saltern from Mohei salt mine".

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum ogadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum ogadana (N.L. fem. n. *ogadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp004114375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004114375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.89 % and the genome length is 3.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum ovamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum ovamosa (N.L. fem. n. *ovamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp003666015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003666015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.47 % and the genome length is 4.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum ucafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum ucafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp018623055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

RS_GCF_018623055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.74 % and the genome length is 3.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum udabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum udabana (N.L. fem. n. *udabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp003287355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003287355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.11 % and the genome length is 3.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum udagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum udagia (N.L. fem. n. *udagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp009806985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009806985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.36 % and the genome length is 3.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum ufecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum ufecaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp009742825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009742825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.8 % and the genome length is 3.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorubrum utefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorubrum utefana (N.L. fem. n. *utefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorubrum sp000746205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000746205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.01 % and the genome length is 2.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorussus afadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorussus afadana (N.L. fem. n. *afadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorussus sp004765805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004765805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.27 % and the genome length is 3.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorussus agaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorussus agaxana (N.L. fem. n. *agaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorussus sp005239435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005239435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.29 % and the genome length is 5.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorussus esebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorussus esebella (N.L. fem. n. *esebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorussus sp008831545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_008831545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.52 % and the genome length is 4.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorussus etaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorussus etaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *etaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorussus sp004765795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004521895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.11 % and the genome length is 3.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorussus ogafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorussus ogafella (N.L. fem. n. *ogafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorussus sp010747475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_010747475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.95 % and the genome length is 4.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorussus omecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorussus omecosa (N.L. fem. n. *omecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorussus sp004087835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004087835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.77 % and the genome length is 3.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halorussus umavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halorussus umavosa (N.L. fem. n. *umavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halorussus sp003023465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.22 % and the genome length is 2.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halosimplex otaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halosimplex otaxia (N.L. fem. n. *otaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halosimplex sp003023165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.27 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halostagnicola upelosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halostagnicola upelosa (N.L. fem. n. *upelosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halostagnicola sp000691505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000691505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.78 % and the genome length is 3.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halostella ilasella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halostella ilasella (N.L. fem. n. *ilasella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halostella sp003675875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003675875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.18 % and the genome length is 4.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halostella imecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halostella imecaria (N.L. fem. n. *imecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halostella sp003023565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.11 % and the genome length is 2.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haloterrigena asavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloterrigena asavosa (N.L. fem. n. *asavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloterrigena sp013342135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_013342135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.59 % and the genome length is 4.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haloterrigena iteiparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haloterrigena iteiparia (N.L. fem. n. *iteiparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Haloterrigena sp017352155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_017352155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.54 % and the genome length is 3.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus asavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus asavella (N.L. fem. n. *asavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp003021015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.9 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus egefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus egefosa (N.L. fem. n. *egefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp009831575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009831575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.97 % and the genome length is

3.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus emapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus emapana (N.L. fem. n. *emapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp001564135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001564135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.95 % and the genome length is 2.1 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample Tc-Br; brine of Tanatar trona crystallizer".

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus epavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus epavaria (N.L. fem. n. *epavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp003022725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.37 % and the genome length is 2.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus idaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus idaxia (N.L. fem. n. *idaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp004015825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004015825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.96 % and the genome length is 3.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus irefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus irefosa (N.L. fem. n. *irefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp000416085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000416085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.06 % and the genome length is 2.98 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "filtered surface water from Lake Tyrrell".

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus ocebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus ocebosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp003021285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.73 % and the genome length is 1.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus ogepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus ogepana (N.L. fem. n. *ogepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp003022085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.67 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus oladana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus oladana (N.L. fem. n. *oladana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp003551265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003551265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.52 % and the genome length is 2.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus osaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus osaxana (N.L. fem. n. *osaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp003021335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.46 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus ufalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus ufalana (N.L. fem. n. *ufalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp003551945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003551945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.83 % and the genome length is 2.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovenus unagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovenus unagia (N.L. fem. n. *unagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovenus sp003022845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.0 % and the genome length is 2.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovivax irebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovivax irebana (N.L. fem. n. *irebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovivax sp007119345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007119345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.64 % and the genome length is 3.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Halovivax ogapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Halovivax ogapana (N.L. fem. n. *ogapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Halovivax sp007135505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007135505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.45 % and the genome length is 2.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hamosarcha utaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hamosarcha utaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *utaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA12501 sp10192u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.98 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hamosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hamosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hamosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA12501. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hamosarcha utaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hamosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hamosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hamosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hamosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA12501. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hamosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Haprigarcha idafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haprigarcha idafosa (N.L. fem. n. *idafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WIAN01 sp015519985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015519985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 24.28 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haprigarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Haprigarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Haprigarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WIAN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Haprigarcha idafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dinufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Haselarcha ivaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haselarcha ivaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ivaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTKF01 sp011370445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011370445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.75 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haselarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Haselarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Haselarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTKF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Haselarcha ivaparia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haselarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Haselarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Haselarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Haselarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTKF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Haselarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hadarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Haselarcha olabia sp. nov.

Candidatus Haselarcha olabia (N.L. fem. n. *olabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTKF01 sp011367225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011367225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.78 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hastexarcha ucarana sp. nov.

Candidatus Hastexarcha ucarana (N.L. fem. n. *ucarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPVU01 sp016191585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016191585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.32 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hastexarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hastexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hastexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPVU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hastexarcha ucarana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hatraxarcha ebefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hatraxarcha ebefana (N.L. fem. n. *ebefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTNV01 sp011358415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011358415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.4 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hatraxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hatraxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hatraxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTNV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hatraxarcha ebefana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hatraxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hatraxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hatraxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hatraxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTNV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hatraxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Haxemarcha etecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haxemarcha etecaria (N.L. fem. n. *etecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AMARA-1 sp016933055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016933055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.32 % and the genome length is 3.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haxemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Haxemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Haxemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is AMARA-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Haxemarcha etecaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haxemarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Haxemarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Haxemarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Haxemarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is AMARA-1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Haxemarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Prometheoarchaeales*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Haxemarcha evecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haxemarcha evecosa (N.L. fem. n. *evecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AMARA-1 sp004524545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.73 % and the genome length is 2.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haxemarcha evegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haxemarcha evegia (N.L. fem. n. *evegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AMARA-1 sp016839865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.31 % and the genome length is 3.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Haxemarcha uvatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Haxemarcha uvatia (N.L. fem. n. *uvatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AMARA-1 sp016839385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.19 % and the genome length is 3.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hecribarcha ocebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hecribarcha ocebia (N.L. fem. n. *ocebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWA01 sp018304505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.08 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hecribarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hecribarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hecribarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVWA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hecribarcha ocebia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hecribarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hecribarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hecribarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hecribarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVWA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hecribarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Oferarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hedrecarcha avafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hedrecarcha avafana (N.L. fem. n. *avafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMGO01 sp902385655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.74 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hedrecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hedrecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hedrecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CABMGO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hedrecarcha avafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hemolarcha olabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hemolarcha olabaria (N.L. fem. n. *olabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B14-G2 sp003661385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.83 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hemolarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hemolarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hemolarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B14-G2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hemolarcha olabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hemolarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hemolarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hemolarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hemolarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B14-G2. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hemolarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Korarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hermodarchaeum amapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hermodarchaeum amapana (N.L. fem. n. *amapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hermodarchaeum sp016550425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016550495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.71 % and the genome

length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hermodarchaeum edefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hermodarchaeum edefaria (N.L. fem. n. *edefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hermodarchaeum sp016840185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.29 % and the genome length is 2.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hermodarchaeum elapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hermodarchaeum elapia (N.L. fem. n. *elapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hermodarchaeum sp016839805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.84 % and the genome length is 2.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hermodarchaeum eracosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hermodarchaeum eracosa (N.L. fem. n. *eracosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hermodarchaeum sp016840595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.54 % and the genome length is 2.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hermodarchaeum eregella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hermodarchaeum eregella (N.L. fem. n. *eregella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hermodarchaeum sp016550405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016550405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.52 % and the genome length is 2.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hermodarchaeum igapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hermodarchaeum igapia (N.L. fem. n. *igapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Hermodarchaeum sp016839365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.88 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hermodarchaeum ucadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hermodarchaeum ucadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hermodarchaeum sp016839995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.21 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hermodarchaeum utacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hermodarchaeum utacosa (N.L. fem. n. *utacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hermodarchaeum sp016550395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016550395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.05 % and the genome length is 2.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hesegarcha ifapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hesegarcha ifapella (N.L. fem. n. *ifapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKY01 sp014728835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014728835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.45 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hesegarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hesegarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hesegarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJKY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hesegarcha ifapella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hesegarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hesegarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Heseqarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Heseqarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJKY01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Heseqarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Laxucarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hestamarcha abafosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha abafosa (N.L. fem. n. *abafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp018667575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018647775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.04 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hestamarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hestamarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIa-L1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hestamarcha abafosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hestamarcha acaxella sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha acaxella (N.L. fem. n. *acaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp9354u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.8 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hestamarcha amaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha amaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *amaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is MGIIa-L1 sp011526375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011526375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.18 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha asevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha asevana (N.L. fem. n. *asevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp012959845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012959845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.84 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha avagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha avagana (N.L. fem. n. *avagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp003602645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.93 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha cufaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha cufaria (N.L. fem. n. *cufaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002729095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.81 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ebadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ebadana (N.L. fem. n. *ebadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp018701175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018676255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.56 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ebatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ebatella (N.L. fem. n. *ebatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp018691345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018691345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.64 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ebaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ebaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ebaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp9596u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.5 % and the genome length is 1.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ecagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ecagana (N.L. fem. n. *ecagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp018659375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018673655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.78 % and the genome length is 1.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ecalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ecalana (N.L. fem. n. *ecalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002172355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002701025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.2 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha efadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha efadia (N.L. fem. n. *efadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002495535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.53 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha efarosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha efarosa (N.L. fem. n. *efarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002506025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.18 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hestamarcha epecosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha epecosa (N.L. fem. n. *epecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp905182715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905182715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.33 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hestamarcha esabella sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha esabella (N.L. fem. n. *esabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002702945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002702945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.56 % and the genome length is 1.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hestamarcha esafella sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha esafella (N.L. fem. n. *esafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp8160u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.48 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hestamarcha etafosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha etafosa (N.L. fem. n. *etafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002495945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.14 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha etavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha etavia (N.L. fem. n. *etavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002688825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.25 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha icanella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha icanella (N.L. fem. n. *icanella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002727485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002727485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.95 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha idatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha idatana (N.L. fem. n. *idatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp018650105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018661885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.52 % and the genome length is 1.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha idavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha idavaria (N.L. fem. n. *idavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp009887195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016777145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.52 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ipabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ipabana (N.L. fem. n. *ipabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp009937025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009937025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.96 % and the genome length is

1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha obafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha obafana (N.L. fem. n. *obafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp009937205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009937205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.53 % and the genome length is 1.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha obaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha obaxana (N.L. fem. n. *obaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp9513u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.07 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ocamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ocamia (N.L. fem. n. *ocamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002726395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002726395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.88 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha odacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha odacosa (N.L. fem. n. *odacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002502605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.48 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ofalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ofalella (N.L. fem. n. *ofalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is MGIIa-L1 sp002505355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.77 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha olagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha olagia (N.L. fem. n. *olagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002687075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.0 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha omavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha omavia (N.L. fem. n. *omavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002499705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.38 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha omecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha omecana (N.L. fem. n. *omecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp003602575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.84 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha opafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha opafosa (N.L. fem. n. *opafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp009887095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009887095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.14 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha otabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha otabosa (N.L. fem. n. *otabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp8725u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.0 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ovamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ovamana (N.L. fem. n. *ovamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp905182635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905182635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.55 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha phebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha phebana (N.L. fem. n. *phebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp902520595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902520595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.0 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha quebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha quebia (N.L. fem. n. *quebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp905182725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905182725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.42 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ruxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ruxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ruxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp000246735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018695505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.68 % and the genome length is 1.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ubegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ubegia (N.L. fem. n. *ubegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp003602605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.3 % and the genome length is 2.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ubegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ubegosa (N.L. fem. n. *ubegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp905182125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905182125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.22 % and the genome length is 1.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ufabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ufabana (N.L. fem. n. *ufabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002170315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002170315.2. The GC content of the type genome is 46.44 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha ufavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha ufavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002499545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002730005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.56 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha unegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha unegia (N.L. fem. n. *unegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp905181785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905181785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.2 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha upavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha upavosa (N.L. fem. n. *upavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002697705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.63 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha usabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha usabosa (N.L. fem. n. *usabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002499015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.6 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha usegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha usegosa (N.L. fem. n. *usegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp905182185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905182185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.44 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha utacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha utacaria (N.L. fem. n. *utacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp8734u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.56 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha uvabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha uvabosa (N.L. fem. n. *uvabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002496955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.56 % and the genome length is

1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha vupana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha vupana (N.L. fem. n. *vupana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp002506275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016777205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.04 % and the genome length is 2.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hestamarcha vuxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hestamarcha vuxia (N.L. fem. n. *vuxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L1 sp018662825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018666535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.78 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hetrofarcha ofadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hetrofarcha ofadella (N.L. fem. n. *ofadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CS3-C152 sp011772645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011772255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.3 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hetrofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hetrofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hetrofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CS3-C152. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hetrofarcha ofadella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Badimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hibecarcha avefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hibecarcha avefana (N.L. fem. n. *avefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B29-G17 sp003650625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.52 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hibecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hibecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hibecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B29-G17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hibecarcha avefana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hibecarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hibecarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hibecarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hibecarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B29-G17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hibecarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hibecarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hibecarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Hibecarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Hibecarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B29-G17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hibecarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Methanomethylica*.

Description of *Candidatus Hibecarcha upabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hibecarcha upabana (N.L. fem. n. *upabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B29-G17 sp003649145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.57 % and the genome length is

0.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hicrosarcha ebeqaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hicrosarcha ebeqaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebeqaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPIM01 sp016188045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.44 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hicrosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hicrosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hicrosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPIM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hicrosarcha ebeqaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hicrosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hicrosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hicrosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hicrosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPIM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hicrosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hicuparcha efacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hicuparcha efacaria (N.L. fem. n. *efacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA11576 sp11576u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.01 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hicuparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hicuparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hicuparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA11576. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hicuparcha efacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hicuparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hicuparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hicuparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hicuparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA11576. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hicuparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hidisarcha amevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hidisarcha amevia (N.L. fem. n. *amevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABMPP01 sp013202955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013202955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.64 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hidisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hidisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hidisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABMPP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hidisarcha amevia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hidisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hidisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hidisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hidisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JABMPP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hidisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hifaxarcha otabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hifaxarcha otabana (N.L. fem. n. *otabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBI01 sp011364305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.54 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hifaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hifaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hifaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTBI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hifaxarcha otabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hifaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hifaxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hifaxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hifaxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTBI01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hifaxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Jordarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hifaxarcha otaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hifaxarcha otaxana (N.L. fem. n. *otaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBI01 sp011362025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011362025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.51 % and the genome length is 2.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hifraparcha esaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hifraparcha esaxella (N.L. fem. n. *esaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B54-G15 sp003648985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003648985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.94 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hifraparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hifraparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hifraparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B54-G15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hifraparcha esaxella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hifraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hifraparchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hifraparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hifraparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B54-G15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hifraparcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hifrorarcha edapia sp. nov.

Candidatus Hifrorarcha edapia (N.L. fem. n. *edapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B65-G9 sp003662765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.77 % and the genome length is 2.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hifrorarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hifrorarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hifrorarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is B65-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hifrorarcha edapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Higimarcha epamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Higimarcha epamana (N.L. fem. n. *epamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQNV01 sp016202865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.11 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Higimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Higimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Higimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQNV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Higimarcha epamana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Higimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Higimarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Higimarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Higimarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQNV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Higimarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Bimafarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hiragarcha efalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hiragarcha efalosa (N.L. fem. n. *efalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SCGC-AAA252-I15 sp000402775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000402775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.76 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hiragarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hiragarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hiragarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SCGC-AAA252-I15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hiragarcha efalosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiragarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hiragarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hiragarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hiragarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SCGC-AAA252-I15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hiragarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Usinarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hiremarcha osafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hiremarcha osafaria (N.L. fem. n. *osafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9989 sp9989u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.79 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hiremarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hiremarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hiremarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA9989. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hiremarcha osafaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiremarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hiremarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hiremarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hiremarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA9989. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hiremarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hisadarcha inabella sp. nov.

Candidatus Hisadarcha inabella (N.L. fem. n. *inabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAEEP01 sp013415695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013415715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.47 % and the genome length is 2.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hisadarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hisadarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hisadarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAEEP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hisadarcha inabella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hisadarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hisadarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hisadarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hisadarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAAEEP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hisadarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanomassiliicoccales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Histilarcha egasosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Histilarcha egasosa (N.L. fem. n. *egasosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQOD01 sp016202725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.15 % and the genome length is

0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Histilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Histilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Histilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQOD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Histilarcha egasosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Histilarcha ucagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Histilarcha ucagaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQOD01 sp016198585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.17 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hitafarcha emadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hitafarcha emadaria (N.L. fem. n. *emadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S146-22 sp015520535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.93 % and the genome length is 4.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hitafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hitafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hitafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S146-22. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hitafarcha emadaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hitafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hitafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hitafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hitafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is S146-22. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hitafarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hodarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hiturarcha ucafia sp. nov.

Candidatus Hiturarcha ucafia (N.L. fem. n. *ucafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10834 sp10834u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.34 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hiturarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hiturarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hiturarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10834. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hiturarcha ucafia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiturarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hiturarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hiturarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hiturarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10834. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hiturarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hiturarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hiturarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Hiturarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Hiturarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10834. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hiturarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus Hixefarcha ebevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hixefarcha ebevana (N.L. fem. n. *ebevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABXJV01 sp013375355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013375355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.73 % and the genome length is 4.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hixefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hixefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hixefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABXJV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hixefarcha ebevana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hixefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hixefarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hixefarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hixefarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JABXJV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hixefarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Helarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hixefarcha imabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hixefarcha imabana (N.L. fem. n. *imabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABXJV01 sp019058315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.49 % and the genome length is 5.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hocularcha apegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hocularcha apegella (N.L. fem. n. *apegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPBV01 sp016180165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.5 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hocularcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hocularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hocularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPBV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hocularcha apegella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hocularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hocularchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hocularchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hocularchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPBV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hocularcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hocularcha emafia sp. nov.

Candidatus Hocularcha emafia (N.L. fem. n. *emafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPBV01 sp016180135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.33 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hodarchaeum afedia sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum afedia (N.L. fem. n. *afedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Hodarchaeum sp016839625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.16 % and the genome length is 4.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum arexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum arexia (N.L. fem. n. *arexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp016840305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.92 % and the genome length is 4.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum emavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum emavosa (N.L. fem. n. *emavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp016840285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.0 % and the genome length is 4.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum ibapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum ibapella (N.L. fem. n. *ibapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp016839815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.05 % and the genome length is 4.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum idaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum idaxana (N.L. fem. n. *idaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp016839665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.48 % and the genome length is 3.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum ilevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum ilevaria (N.L. fem. n. *ilevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp019057635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.17 % and the genome length is 3.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum omaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum omaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *omaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp016839785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.09 % and the genome length is 4.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum onevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum onevana (N.L. fem. n. *onevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp003144275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003144275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.14 % and the genome length is 3.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum opafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum opafella (N.L. fem. n. *opafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp016840035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.07 % and the genome length is 4.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodarchaeum upavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodarchaeum upavia (N.L. fem. n. *upavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Hodarchaeum sp011364965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.73 % and the genome length is 3.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hodixarcha ilabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hodixarcha ilabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ilabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PIYN01 sp003601775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003601775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.43 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hodixarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hodixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hodixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PIYN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hodixarcha ilabosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hodixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hodixarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hodixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hodixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PIYN01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hodixarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ibidarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hofrimarcha apagana sp. nov.

Candidatus Hofrimarcha apagana (N.L. fem. n. *apagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWHV01 sp007116915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007116915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.91 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hofrimarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hofrimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hofrimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is PWHV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hofrimarcha apagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hofrimarcha ecedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hofrimarcha ecedia (N.L. fem. n. *ecedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWHV01 sp007117455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007117455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.58 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hofrimarcha efadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hofrimarcha efadella (N.L. fem. n. *efadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWHV01 sp003555025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003555025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.98 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hofrimarcha ofadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hofrimarcha ofadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWHV01 sp003557905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003557905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.87 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hofrimarcha ofaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hofrimarcha ofaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ofaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWHV01 sp003550345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003550345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.57 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hofrimarcha upavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hofrimarcha upavaria (N.L. fem. n. *upavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWHV01 sp003560875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003560875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.75 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Honifarcha asedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Honifarcha asedella (N.L. fem. n. *asedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B25 sp003662485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.9 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Honifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Honifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Honifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B25. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Honifarcha asedella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Honifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Honifarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Honifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Honifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B25. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Honifarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Honifarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Honifarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Honifarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Honifarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B25. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Honifarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Bathyarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Honifarcha isabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Honifarcha isabosa (N.L. fem. n. *isabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B25 sp003662515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.63 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Honifarcha ogefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Honifarcha ogefia (N.L. fem. n. *ogefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B25 sp003662305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.86 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Honifarcha ubefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Honifarcha ubefaria (N.L. fem. n. *ubefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B25 sp001593855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001593855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.5 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "marine sediment sample collected by push cores at a deep sea vent site during cruise AT15-25 on Alvin dive 4358; sediment was oily and the sediment surface was covered with a white microbial mat".

Description of *Candidatus Honocarcha asagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Honocarcha asagia (N.L. fem. n. *asagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZP01 sp011363915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011363915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.31 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Honocarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Honocarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Honocarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOZP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Honocarcha asagia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Honocarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Honocarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Honocarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Honocarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAAOZP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Honocarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ifutarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Honocarcha ecaparia sp. nov.

Candidatus Honocarcha ecaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ecaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZP01 sp011362045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011362045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.05 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Honocarcha ivaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Honocarcha ivaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZP01 sp011389375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011389375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.01 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Honocarcha omafia sp. nov.

Candidatus Honocarcha omafia (N.L. fem. n. *omafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JAAOZP01 sp017601395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017601305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.84 % and the genome length is 2.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Honocarcha ufabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Honocarcha ufabella (N.L. fem. n. *ufabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZP01 sp011605725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011605725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.43 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Honocarcha ufaella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Honocarcha ufaella (N.L. fem. n. *ufaella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZP01 sp017601225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017601225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.52 % and the genome length is 2.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Honocarcha unexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Honocarcha unexosa (N.L. fem. n. *unexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZP01 sp017601345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017601345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.23 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hopelarcha umacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hopelarcha umacia (N.L. fem. n. *umacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688095 sp002688095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.02 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hopelarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hopelarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hopelarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2688095. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hopelarcha umacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hopelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hopelarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hopelarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hopelarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-2688095. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hopelarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Oqusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Horaxarcha ebaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Horaxarcha ebaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ebaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8471 sp001871535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002778915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.24 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Horaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Horaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Horaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA8471. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Horaxarcha ebaparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Horaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Horaxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Horaxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Horaxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA8471. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Horaxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Anstonellales*.

Description of *Candidatus Horetarcha evebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Horetarcha evebia (N.L. fem. n. *evebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKL01 sp014729145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.29 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Horetarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Horetarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Horetarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJKL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Horetarcha evebia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Horetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Horetarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Horetarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Horetarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJKL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Horetarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hosobarcha ufexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hosobarcha ufexella (N.L. fem. n. *ufexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKIA01 sp007117065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007117065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.78 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hosobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hosobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hosobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SKIA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hosobarcha ufexella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hosobarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hosobarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hosobarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hosobarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SKIA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hosobarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hosobarcha ugaxana sp. nov.

Candidatus Hosobarcha ugaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ugaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKIA01 sp007116645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007116645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.85 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hosobarcha uraxaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Hosobarcha uraxaria (N.L. fem. n. *uraxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKIA01 sp007128245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007128245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.23 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hotrularcha avabaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Hotrularcha avabaria (N.L. fem. n. *avabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JACIWB01 sp014361195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.78 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hotrularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hotrularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hotrularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACIWB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hotrularcha avabaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Parutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hotrularcha esaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hotrularcha esaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *esaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACIWB01 sp014361245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.76 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hubexarcha apevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hubexarcha apevaria (N.L. fem. n. *apevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKC01 sp014729335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.75 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hubexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hubexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hubexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJKC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hubexarcha apevaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hubexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hubexarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hubexarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hubexarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJKC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hubexarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hubexarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hubexarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Hubexarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Hubexarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJKC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hubexarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Nanoarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus* Huclufarcha avafosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Huclufarcha avafosa (N.L. fem. n. *avafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is YT-063 sp016840065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.87 % and the genome length is 2.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Huclufarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Huclufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Huclufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is YT-063. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Huclufarcha avafosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hermodarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Huclufarcha edexosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Huclufarcha edexosa (N.L. fem. n. *edexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is YT-063 sp016840135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.08 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Huclufarcha egavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Huclufarcha egavella (N.L. fem. n. *egavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is YT-063 sp016550485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016550485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.97 % and the genome length is 2.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hudomarcha buvana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hudomarcha buvana (N.L. fem. n. *buvana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR15 sp018657065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018672255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.66 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hudomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hudomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hudomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hudomarcha buvana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hudomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hudomarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hudomarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hudomarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hudomarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hudomarcha unadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hudomarcha unadana (N.L. fem. n. *unadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR15 sp000830295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000830295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.49 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "groundwater".

Description of *Candidatus Hudrusarcha elaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hudrusarcha elaparia (N.L. fem. n. *elaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10536 sp10536u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.21 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hudrusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hudrusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hudrusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10536. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hudrusarcha elaparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanoperedenaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hufasarcha ogadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hufasarcha ogadia (N.L. fem. n. *ogadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIVG01 sp018816705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018816705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.23 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hufasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hufasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hufasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIVG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hufasarcha ogadia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hufasarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hufasarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hufasarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hufasarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHIVG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hufasarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hufonarcha ecania sp. nov.

Candidatus Hufonarcha ecania (N.L. fem. n. *ecania* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10219 sp10219u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.69 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hufonarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hufonarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hufonarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10219. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hufonarcha ecania.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hufonarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Hufonarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Hufonarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hufonarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10219. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hufonarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Iainarchaeales.

Description of *Candidatus Hufracarcha egabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hufracarcha egabia (N.L. fem. n. *egabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRPI01 sp016215305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016215305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.02 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hufracarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hufracarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hufracarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRPI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hufracarcha egabia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nerisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hufracarcha utavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hufracarcha utavana (N.L. fem. n. *utavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRPI01 sp016214075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016214075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.25 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Huprifarcha ocararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Huprifarcha ocararia (N.L. fem. n. *ocararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTQO01 sp017601265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017601265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.29 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Huprifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Huprifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Huprifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTQO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Huprifarcha ocararia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Huprifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Huprifarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Huprifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Huprifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTQO01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Huprifarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ifutarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Huprifarcha udeposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Huprifarcha udeposa (N.L. fem. n. *udeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTQO01 sp011332645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011332645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.63 % and the genome length is 2.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hurebarcha edafana sp. nov.

Candidatus Hurebarcha edafana (N.L. fem. n. *edafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRY501 sp011375775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011375775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.75 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Hurebarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Hurebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hurebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRY501. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hurebarcha edafana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Hurebarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Hurebarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hurebarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hurebarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DRYS01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Hurebarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omexarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hurebarcha esabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hurebarcha esabia (N.L. fem. n. *esabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRYS01 sp011367275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011367275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.93 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hutrenarcha efagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hutrenarcha efagaria (N.L. fem. n. *efagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO11 sp004348015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004212145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.44 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hutrenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hutrenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hutrenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WYZ-LMO11. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Hutrenarcha efagaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylicaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hutubarcha adafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hutubarcha adafosa (N.L. fem. n. *adafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LFW-46 sp902384675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902384675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.69 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Hutubarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Hutubarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Hutubarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is LFW-46. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Hutubarcha adafosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hutubarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Hutubarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Hutubarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Hutubarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is LFW-46. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Hutubarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Axalarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Hutubarcha iralia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Hutubarcha iralia (N.L. fem. n. *iralia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LFW-46 sp018897155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018895095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.91 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ibidarcha udafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ibidarcha udafella (N.L. fem. n. *udafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B23 sp001593875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_001593875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.8 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "marine sediment sample collected by push cores at a deep sea vent site during cruise AT15-25 on Alvin dive 4358; sediment was oily and the sediment surface was covered with a white microbial mat".

Description of *Candidatus Ibidarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ibidarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ibidarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B23. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ibidarcha udafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ibidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ibidarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ibidarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ibidarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is TCS64. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ibidarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ibidarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ibidarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Ibidarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Ibidarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is TCS64. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ibidarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Bathyarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha afavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha afavosa (N.L. fem. n. *afavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp019057735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.57 % and the genome length is

3.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Iblitarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SOKP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Iblitarcha afavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Iblitarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SOKP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Iblitarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Prometheoarchaeales*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha amaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha amaparia (N.L. fem. n. *amaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp005222975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005222975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.51 % and the genome length is 3.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha asafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha asafosa (N.L. fem. n. *asafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp016840545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.59 % and the genome length is 2.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha epanaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha epanaria (N.L. fem. n. *epanaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp011364925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.98 % and the genome length is 3.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha imabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha imabosa (N.L. fem. n. *imabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp019057795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.36 % and the genome length is 4.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha irafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha irafella (N.L. fem. n. *irafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp016839745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.34 % and the genome length is 3.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha ofalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha ofalana (N.L. fem. n. *ofalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp013375495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013375495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.3 % and the genome length is 4.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha ogapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha ogapella (N.L. fem. n. *ogapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp013375475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013375475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.54 % and the genome length is 3.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha otxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha otexia (N.L. fem. n. *otexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp016839765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.69 % and the genome length is 3.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha ovagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha ovagia (N.L. fem. n. *ovagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp004524725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.08 % and the genome length is 2.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha puxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha puxosa (N.L. fem. n. *puxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp018238625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018238345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.25 % and the genome length is 3.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha ugabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha ugabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ugabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp004375715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004375715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.3 % and the genome length is 3.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha umefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha umefaria (N.L. fem. n. *umefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp016840165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.62 % and the genome length is 3.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iblitarcha utaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iblitarcha utaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *utaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOKP01 sp011364975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.62 % and the genome length is 3.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Idrufarcha acamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Idrufarcha acamaria (N.L. fem. n. *acamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZS01 sp003663295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.9 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Idrufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Idrufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Idrufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMZS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Idrufarcha acamaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Idrufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Idrufarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Idrufarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Idrufarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMZS01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Idrufarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Idrufarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Idrufarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Idrufarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Idrufarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMZS01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Idrufarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Aenigmataarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Idrufarcha ifabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Idrufarcha ifabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZS01 sp003663355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.13 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iduparcha epecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Iduparcha epecaria (N.L. fem. n. *epecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SpSt-1190 sp011049195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011049195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.54 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Iduparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Iduparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Iduparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SpSt-1190. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Iduparcha epecaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iduparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Iduparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Iduparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Iduparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SpSt-1190. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Iduparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iduparchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Iduparchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Iduparchales (N.L. fem. n. *Iduparchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SpSt-1190. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Iduparcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Iduparchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Iduparchota* phyl. nov.

Candidatus Iduparchota (N.L. fem. n. *Iduparchota* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SpSt-1190. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Iduparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this phylum belongs to the domain *Archaea*.

Description of *Candidatus Ifrisarcha afavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ifrisarcha afavana (N.L. fem. n. *afavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2686295 sp014384375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014384375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.56 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ifrisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ifrisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ifrisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2686295. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ifrisarcha afavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ifrisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ifrisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ifrisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ifrisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-2686295. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Ifrisarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Ifrisarcha agecaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Ifrisarcha agecaria (N.L. fem. n. *agecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2686295 sp002686295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002686295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.16 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Ifrisarcha efanosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Ifrisarcha efanosa (N.L. fem. n. *efanosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2686295 sp018819065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018828865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.96 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Ifrisarcha imavaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Ifrisarcha imavaria (N.L. fem. n. *imavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2686295 sp014384455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016784125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.69 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Ifrisarcha ipavana sp. nov.

Candidatus Ifrisarcha ipavana (N.L. fem. n. *ipavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2686295 sp018812505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018812505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.77 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ifrisarcha usecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ifrisarcha usecosa (N.L. fem. n. *usecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2686295 sp013202845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013202845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.89 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ifrunarcha ebaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ifrunarcha ebaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ebaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-31-27 sp002763115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001872145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.33 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "groundwater filtered through a 3.0 um filter and then through a 0.2 um filter".

Description of *Candidatus Ifrunarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ifrunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ifrunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG1-02-31-27. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ifrunarcha ebaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ifrunarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ifrunarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ifrunarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ifrunarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG1-02-31-27. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ifrunarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pacearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ifutarcha opagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ifutarcha opagosa (N.L. fem. n. *opagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-205 sp002255045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011042415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.52 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ifutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ifutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ifutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-205. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ifutarcha opagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ifutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ifutarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ifutarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ifutarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-205. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ifutarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ifutarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ifutarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Ifutarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Ifutarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-205. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ifutarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Ifutarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Ignicoccus igecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ignicoccus igecella (N.L. fem. n. *igecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Ignicoccus_A* sp015521275. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.11 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ignicoccus udabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ignicoccus udabaria (N.L. fem. n. *udabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Ignicoccus_A* sp013154085. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013154085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.18 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Infirmifilum ugadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Infirmifilum ugadia (N.L. fem. n. *ugadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Infirmifilum* sp002855745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002855745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.7 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Isoxarcha cixella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Isoxarcha cixella (N.L. fem. n. *cixella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG10238-14 sp002789635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002782805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.28 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Isoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Isoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Isoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG10238-14. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Isoxarcha cixella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Isoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Isoxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Isoxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Isoxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG10238-14. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Isoxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Isoxarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Isoxarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Isoxarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Isoxarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG10238-14. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Isoxarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Aenigmataarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Isoxarcha ifevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Isoxarcha ifevana (N.L. fem. n. *ifevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG10238-14 sp017610225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.74 % and the genome length is 2.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Isoxarcha ogemella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Isoxarcha ogemella (N.L. fem. n. *ogemella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG10238-14 sp014728985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014728985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.91 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Itregarcha ipalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Itregarcha ipalella (N.L. fem. n. *ipalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CADDZS01 sp902812485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902812485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.08 % and the genome length is 2.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Itregarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Itregarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Itregarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CADDZS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Itregarcha ipalella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Itregarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Itregarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Itregarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Itregarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CADDZS01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Itregarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Itregarcha pheparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Itregarcha pheparia (N.L. fem. n. *pheparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CADDZS01 sp013288145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013288145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.73 % and the genome length is 2.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Kariarchaeum eseposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Kariarchaeum eseposa (N.L. fem. n. *eseposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Kariarchaeum sp016839545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.13 % and the genome length is 2.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Korarchaeum itadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Korarchaeum itadella (N.L. fem. n. *itadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Korarchaeum sp011056255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011056255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.85 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Korarchaeum ofeposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Korarchaeum ofeposa (N.L. fem. n. *ofeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Korarchaeum sp003344655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003344655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.65 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lablamarcha ubavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lablamarcha ubavana (N.L. fem. n. *ubavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOYB01 sp018221135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.9 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lablamarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lablamarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lablamarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOYB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lablamarcha ubavana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Regomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ladroxarcha ibafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ladroxarcha ibafia (N.L. fem. n. *ibafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JACQIC01 sp016203345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.9 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ladroxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ladroxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ladroxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQIC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ladroxarcha ibafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ladroxarcha ugadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ladroxarcha ugadana (N.L. fem. n. *ugadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQIC01 sp016198725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.95 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Laglobarcha enabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Laglobarcha enabosa (N.L. fem. n. *enabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWT01 sp018304175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.9 % and the genome length is 0.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Laglobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Laglobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Laglobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVWT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Laglobarcha enabosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Laglobarcha ucararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Laglobarcha ucararia (N.L. fem. n. *ucararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWT01 sp016234065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016234065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.81 % and the genome length is 0.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lagoxarcha egefana sp. nov.

Candidatus Lagoxarcha egefana (N.L. fem. n. *egefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS1403 sp002687825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002687825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.55 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lagoxarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Lagoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lagoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS1403. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lagoxarcha egefana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lagoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lagoxarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Lagoxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lagoxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is ARS1403. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Lagoxarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lagoxarcha epegaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Lagoxarcha epegaria (N.L. fem. n. *epegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is ARS1403 sp002688395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.27 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lagufarcha urafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lagufarcha urafana (N.L. fem. n. *urafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR10 sp000830275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.16 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lagufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lagufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lagufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR10. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lagufarcha urafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lagufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lagufarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Lagufarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lagufarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR10. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Lagufarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Lagustarcha idatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lagustarcha idatosa (N.L. fem. n. *idatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJLK01 sp014728565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014728565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.95 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lagustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lagustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lagustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJLK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lagustarcha idatosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lanaxarcha ipaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Lanaxarcha ipaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZM01 sp003663175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011044085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.04 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lanaxarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Lanaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lanaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMZM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lanaxarcha ipaxosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lanaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lanaxarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Lanaxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lanaxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMZM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Lanaxarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Usinarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lanegarcha efapella sp. nov.

Candidatus Lanegarcha efapella (N.L. fem. n. *efapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQRY01 sp016206275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016206275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.47 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lanegarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lanegarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lanegarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQRY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lanegarcha eapella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lanegarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lanegarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Lanegarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lanegarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQRY01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Lanegarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Lanegarcha usaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lanegarcha usaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *usaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQRY01 sp016184315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016184315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.3 % and the genome length is 2.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Latefrarcha imafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Latefrarcha imafosa (N.L. fem. n. *imafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is NP1466 sp002689985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002689985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 26.36 % and the genome length is 0.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Latefrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Latefrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Latefrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is NP1466. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Latefrarcha imafosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Latefrarcha uvaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Latefrarcha uvaxia (N.L. fem. n. *uvaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is NP1466 sp002731115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002731115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.46 % and the genome length is 0.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Laxofarcha mubosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Laxofarcha mubosa (N.L. fem. n. *mubosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-36 sp002254765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.25 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Laxofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Laxofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Laxofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-36. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Laxofarcha mubosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Laxofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Laxofarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Laxofarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Laxofarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-36. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Laxofarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Atilarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Laxucarcha ogabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Laxucarcha ogabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10117 sp10117u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.09 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Laxucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Laxucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Laxucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10117. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Laxucarcha ogabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Laxucarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Laxucarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Laxucarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Laxucarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10117. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Laxucarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Laxucarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Laxucarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Laxucarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Laxucarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10117. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Laxucarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class

Nanoarchaeia.

Description of *Candidatus Ledabarcha edalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ledabarcha edalia (N.L. fem. n. *edalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B39-G2 sp003661185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.89 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ledabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ledabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ledabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B39-G2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ledabarcha edalia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ledabarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ledabarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ledabarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ledabarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B39-G2. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ledabarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Rixusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ledrestarcha acevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ledrestarcha acevia (N.L. fem. n. *acevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJP01 sp016187495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.36 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ledrestarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ledrestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ledrestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPJP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ledrestarcha acevia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Ledrestarcha urelana sp. nov.

Candidatus Ledrestarcha urelana (N.L. fem. n. *urelana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJP01 sp016185955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.65 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lefrinarcha edabosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Lefrinarcha edabosa (N.L. fem. n. *edabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-121 sp002255105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002255105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.51 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lefrinarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Lefrinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lefrinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-121. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lefrinarcha edabosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cesedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lefrinarcha udavella sp. nov.

Candidatus Lefrinarcha udavella (N.L. fem. n. *udavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-121 sp003660635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_003660635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.43 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lefubarcha enagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lefubarcha enagella (N.L. fem. n. *enagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-47-18 sp002763335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002763335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.74 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lefubarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lefubarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lefubarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG1-02-47-18. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lefubarcha enagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lefubarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lefubarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Lefubarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lefubarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG1-02-47-18. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Lefubarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Leglifarcha icadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Leglifarcha icadia (N.L. fem. n. *icadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOWB01 sp016177025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016177025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.54 % and the genome length is 0.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Leglifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Leglifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Leglifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the

phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOWB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Leglifarcha icadia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Leglifarcha inacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Leglifarcha inacana (N.L. fem. n. *inacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOWB01 sp016187415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.45 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Leglifarcha ofepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Leglifarcha ofepia (N.L. fem. n. *ofepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOWB01 sp018920185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018920185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.17 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Leglistarcha ovagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Leglistarcha ovagana (N.L. fem. n. *ovagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-16432305 sp016432305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016432305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.42 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Leglistarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Leglistarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Leglistarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-16432305. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Leglistarcha ovagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Toxoprarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Lemudrarcha egasaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lemudrarcha egasaria (N.L. fem. n. *egasaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFNKG01 sp017883965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017883965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.92 % and the genome length is 2.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lemudrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lemudrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lemudrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFNKG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lemudrarcha egasaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lepafarcha emadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lepafarcha emadia (N.L. fem. n. *emadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is HEL-GB-B sp005191425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005191425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.04 % and the genome length is 3.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lepafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lepafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lepafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is HEL-GB-B. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lepafarcha emadia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lepafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lepafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Lepafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lepafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the

type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is HEL-GB-B. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Lepafarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Helarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lestofarcha opamia sp. nov.

Candidatus Lestofarcha opamia (N.L. fem. n. *opamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGTQT01 sp018396615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.09 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lestofarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Lestofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lestofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGTQT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lestofarcha opamia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Letromarcha emafaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Letromarcha emafaria (N.L. fem. n. *emafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MVRC01 sp002067865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.99 % and the genome length is 2.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Letromarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Letromarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Letromarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MVRC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Letromarcha emafaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sogexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Letromarcha ibafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Letromarcha ibafella (N.L. fem. n. *ibafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MVRC01 sp013415865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013415865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.34 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lifestarcha omaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lifestarcha omaxana (N.L. fem. n. *omaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGDH01 sp016932215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.08 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lifestarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lifestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lifestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGDH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lifestarcha omaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Badimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lighedarcha edalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lighedarcha edalana (N.L. fem. n. *edalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is NM3 sp011372835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011372835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.8 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lighedarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lighedarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lighedarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the

phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is NM3. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ligedarcha edalana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ligedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ligedarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ligedarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ligedarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is NM3. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ligedarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanofastidiosales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ligedarcha orabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ligedarcha orabosa (N.L. fem. n. *orabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is NM3 sp004212155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004212155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.16 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Limibrarcha ofabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Limibrarcha ofabana (N.L. fem. n. *ofabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGRM01 sp016935125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.72 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Limibrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Limibrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Limibrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGRM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Limibrarcha ofabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nerisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lipluxarcha efabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lipluxarcha efabella (N.L. fem. n. *efabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVVW01 sp018304635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.32 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lipluxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lipluxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lipluxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVVW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lipluxarcha efabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cunadarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Listibarcha umafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Listibarcha umafosa (N.L. fem. n. *umafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Kmv02 sp014859755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014859755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.2 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Listibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Listibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Listibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Kmv02. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Listibarcha umafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Saxararchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lixudrarcha ilemella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lixudrarcha ilemella (N.L. fem. n. *ilemella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-218 sp003661965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.11 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lixudrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Lixudrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lixudrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-218. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lixudrarcha ilemella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Honifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lixudrarcha ucamana sp. nov.

Candidatus Lixudrarcha ucamana (N.L. fem. n. *ucamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-218 sp002254975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.1 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Loclotrarcha ocavana sp. nov.

Candidatus Loclotrarcha ocavana (N.L. fem. n. *ocavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOYE01 sp018221175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.06 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Loclotrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Loclotrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Loclotrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOYE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Loclotrarcha ocavana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Regomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Locusarcha ufagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Locusarcha ufagia (N.L. fem. n. *ufagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B48-G16 sp003660605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003660605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.25 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Locusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Locusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Locusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B48-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Locusarcha ufagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Locusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Locusarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Locusarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Locusarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B48-G16. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Locusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanofastidiosales*.

Description of *Candidatus Lofodarcha odabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lofodarcha odabia (N.L. fem. n. *odabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXP01 sp018303725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.69 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lofodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lofodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lofodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lofodarcha odabia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lofodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lofodarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Lofodarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lofodarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVXP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Lofodarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lopecarcha ifarosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Lopecarcha ifarosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADFM01 sp013152845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013152845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.77 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lopecarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Lopecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lopecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADFM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lopecarcha ifarosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lopecarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lopecarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Lopecarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lopecarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAADFM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Lopecarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hydrothermarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Losatrarcha efagella sp. nov.

Candidatus Losatrarcha efagella (N.L. fem. n. *efagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO2 sp011605865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004347845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.93 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Losatrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Losatrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Losatrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WYZ-LMO2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Losatrarcha efagella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Archaeoglobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Losatrarcha emalaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Losatrarcha emalaria (N.L. fem. n. *emalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO2 sp011361745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011329185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.09 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Losatrarcha etafaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Losatrarcha etafaria (N.L. fem. n. *etafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO2 sp011367245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011367245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.32 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Losatrarcha odafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Losatrarcha odafella (N.L. fem. n. *odafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO2 sp011048195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011048195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.1 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Losatrarcha utaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Losatrarcha utaparia (N.L. fem. n. *utaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO2 sp004347865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011332835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.85 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lostucrarcha edevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lostucrarcha edevella (N.L. fem. n. *edevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEK01 sp017609225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.6 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lostucrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lostucrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lostucrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCEK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lostucrarcha edevella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lotrubarcha aselana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lotrubarcha aselana (N.L. fem. n. *aselana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is SURF-65 sp003599055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003599055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.52 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lotrubarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lotrubarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lotrubarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SURF-65. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lotrubarcha aselana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lotrubarcha avacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lotrubarcha avacia (N.L. fem. n. *avacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SURF-65 sp016203305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.81 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lotruprarcha evepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lotruprarcha evepella (N.L. fem. n. *evepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEM01 sp017609145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.89 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lotruprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lotruprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lotruprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCEM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lotruprarcha evepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Loxeprarcha acavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Loxeprarcha acavaria (N.L. fem. n. *acavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOZO01 sp016181325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.47 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Loxeprarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Loxeprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Loxeprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOZO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Loxeprarcha acavaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lublocrarcha epagana sp. nov.

Candidatus Lublocrarcha epagana (N.L. fem. n. *epagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAJX01 sp015523665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.86 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Lublocrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Lublocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lublocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAJX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Lublocrarcha epagana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Archaeoglobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Lubuxarchaifaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Lubuxarchaifaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JdFR-21 sp002011165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002011165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.21 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lubuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lubuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lubuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-21. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lubuxarchaifaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lubuxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lubuxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Lubuxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Lubuxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JdFR-21. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Lubuxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Lubuxarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Lubuxarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Lubuxarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Lubuxarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JdFR-21. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Lubuxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Archaeoglobi*.

Description of *Candidatus Lubuxarcha upaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lubuxarcha upaxana (N.L. fem. n. *upaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-21 sp014361165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.68 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lufraparcha uracana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lufraparcha uracana (N.L. fem. n. *uracana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIOIN01 sp903858385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903858385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.15 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lufraparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lufraparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lufraparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIOIN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lufraparcha uracana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Micrarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Luglotarcha agaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Luglotarcha agaxia (N.L. fem. n. *agaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGWAF01 sp018302085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.96 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Luglotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Luglotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Luglotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGWAF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Luglotarcha agaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Luglotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Luglotarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Luglotarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Luglotarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGWAF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Luglotarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Luplidrarcha abemana sp. nov.

Candidatus Luplidrarcha abemana (N.L. fem. n. *abemana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADDK01 sp015523125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.85 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Luplidrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Luplidrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Luplidrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADDK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Luplidrarcha abemana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aciduliprofundaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Luplidrarcha adevella sp. nov.

Candidatus Luplidrarcha adevella (N.L. fem. n. *adevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADDK01 sp015520985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.46 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Luplidrarcha ecemella sp. nov.

Candidatus Luplidrarcha ecemella (N.L. fem. n. *ecemella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADDK01 sp015521465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.71 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Luplidrarcha ugabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Luplidrarcha ugabia (N.L. fem. n. *ugabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADDK01 sp013154005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013154005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.96 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Luplistarcha efexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Luplistarcha efexana (N.L. fem. n. *efexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SpSt-742 sp011335085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011335085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.17 % and the genome length is 0.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Luplistarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Luplistarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Luplistarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SpSt-742. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Luplistarcha efexana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lusagrarcha enacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lusagrarcha enacosa (N.L. fem. n. *enacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CS1-C013 sp011773475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011773475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.22 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lusagrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lusagrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lusagrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is CS1-C013. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lusagrarcha enacosa*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aenigmatarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Lusagrarcha osagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lusagrarcha osagella (N.L. fem. n. *osagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CS1-C013 sp017608545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.14 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lustefrarcha udepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Lustefrarcha udepia (N.L. fem. n. *udepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-44-13 sp002762985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002762985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.41 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Lustefrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Lustefrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Lustefrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 1-14-0-10-44-13. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Lustefrarcha udepia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hamosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Luxamarcha ufagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Luxamarcha ufagaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJR01 sp016187565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.45 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Luxamarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Luxamarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Luxamarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPJR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Luxamarcha ufagaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Luxamarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Luxamarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Luxamarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Luxamarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPJR01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Luxamarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Macastarcha phaxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Macastarcha phaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *phaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYD01 sp018303405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.0 % and the genome length is 1.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Macastarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Macastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Macastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Macastarcha phaxosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hidisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Macifarcha ecaposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Macifarcha ecaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ecaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSZF01 sp011367155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011367155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.94 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Macifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Macifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Macifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSZF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Macifarcha ecaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Macifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Macifarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Macifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Macifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DSZF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Macifarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hibecarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Macifarcha emalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Macifarcha emalella (N.L. fem. n. *emalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSZF01 sp011605825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011605825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.75 % and the genome length is 0.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Macifarcha unabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Macifarcha unabella (N.L. fem. n. *unabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSZF01 sp011372955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011372955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.62 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Madeparcha agavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Madeparcha agavia (N.L. fem. n. *agavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-37-12 sp002762795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002762795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.82 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Madeparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Madeparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Madeparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 1-14-0-10-37-12. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Madeparcha agavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Madeparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Madeparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Madeparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is ARS49. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Madeparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Mafuparcha isatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mafuparcha isatosa (N.L. fem. n. *isatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WOR-SM1-SCG sp001723845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001723845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.12 % and the genome length is 2.55 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "single cell amplified by MDA; Methane-rich estuary sediments 72-75 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Mafuparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mafuparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mafuparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WOR-SM1-SCG. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mafuparcha isatosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Mafuparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mafuparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Mafuparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Mafuparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WOR-SM1-SCG. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Mafuparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Usinarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Magrigrarcha ocevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Magrigrarcha ocevana (N.L. fem. n. *ocevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is M55A3 sp018399355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018399355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.09 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Magrigrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Magrigrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Magrigrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is M55A3. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Magrigrarcha ocevana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pufisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Magrixarcha egamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Magrixarcha egamaria (N.L. fem. n. *egamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is B14-G17 sp003649515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.48 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Magrixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Magrixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Magrixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B14-G17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Magrixarcha egamaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gasuxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Maposarcha ifamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Maposarcha ifamana (N.L. fem. n. *ifamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SCSR01 sp004297575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004297575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.82 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Maposarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Maposarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Maposarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SCSR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Maposarcha ifamana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Maposarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Maposarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Maposarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SCSR01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Maposarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Isoxarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Masatarcha eracella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Masatarcha eracella (N.L. fem. n. *eracella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA583 sp002506365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 25.57 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Masatarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Masatarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Masatarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA583. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Masatarcha eracella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Masatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Masatarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Masatarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Masatarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA583. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Masatarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Masatarcha ipabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Masatarcha ipabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA583 sp007117405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007117405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.06 % and the genome length is 0.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Masatarcha opamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Masatarcha opamosa (N.L. fem. n. *opamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA583 sp002505525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.72 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Masatarcha ulabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Masatarcha ulabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ulabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA583 sp013215525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013215525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 25.85 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mastocrarcha ugeposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mastocrarcha ugeposa (N.L. fem. n. *ugeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQMU01 sp016203425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.39 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mastocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mastocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mastocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQMU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mastocrarcha ugeposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mataprarcha acaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mataprarcha acaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *acaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B109-G9 sp003661505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.91 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mataprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mataprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mataprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B109-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Mataprarcha acaxaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Matracrarcha ibavosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Matracrarcha ibavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ibavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABXGU01 sp016550415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016550415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.21 % and the genome length is 4.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Matracrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Matracrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Matracrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABXGU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Matracrarcha ibavosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hermodarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Matrurparcha isalosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Matrurparcha isalosa (N.L. fem. n. *isalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B66-G16 sp003649085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.68 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Matrurparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Matrurparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Matrurparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is B66-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Matruparcha isalosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Matruparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Matruparchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Matruparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Matruparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B66-G16. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Matruparcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanomethylicaes*.

Description of *Candidatus* Meblitarcha orapana sp. nov.

Candidatus Meblitarcha orapana (N.L. fem. n. *orapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTGH01 sp011335015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011335015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.61 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Meblitarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Meblitarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Meblitarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTGH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Meblitarcha orapana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fermentimicrarchaeaceae*[@].

Description of *Candidatus* Medriprarcha irebia sp. nov.

Candidatus Medriprarcha irebia (N.L. fem. n. *irebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPIG01 sp016188205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.44 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Medriprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Medriprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Medriprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPIG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Medriprarcha irebia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mefularcha emaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mefularcha emaparia (N.L. fem. n. *emaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B12-G16 sp003650925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.5 % and the genome length is 2.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mefularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mefularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mefularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B12-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mefularcha emaparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Mefularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mefularchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Mefularchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Mefularchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMSL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Mefularcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Mefularchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Mefularchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Mefularchales (N.L. fem. n. *Mefularchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMSL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Mefularcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoproteia*.

Description of *Candidatus Megreprarcha amaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Megreprarcha amaxana (N.L. fem. n. *amaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TH1177 sp014523515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.08 % and the genome length is 2.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Megreprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Megreprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Megreprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TH1177. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Megreprarcha amaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrososphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Megreprarcha opebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Megreprarcha opebella (N.L. fem. n. *opebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TH1177 sp014523485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.84 % and the genome length is 2.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Melastarcha idafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Melastarcha idafana (N.L. fem. n. *idafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J060 sp003695745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003695745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.93 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Melastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Melastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Melastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J060. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Melastarcha idafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gisumarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mepigrarcha quafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mepigrarcha quafella (N.L. fem. n. *quafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHXC01 sp018657475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018667585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.24 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mepigrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mepigrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mepigrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHXC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mepigrarcha quafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mesabrarcha ocamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mesabrarcha ocamaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA92 sp002497285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001872795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.35 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "groundwater filtered through a 3.0 um filter and then through a 0.2 um filter".

Description of *Candidatus Mesabrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mesabrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mesabrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA92. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mesabrarcha ocamaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mestubarcha avagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mestubarcha avagia (N.L. fem. n. *avagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZC01 sp018302915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.74 % and the genome length is 0.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mestubarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mestubarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mestubarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mestubarcha avagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mestubarcha irefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mestubarcha irefaria (N.L. fem. n. *irefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZC01 sp018302885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.94 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanimicrococcus avefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanimicrococcus avefella (N.L. fem. n. *avefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanimicrococcus* sp009783635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009783635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.95 % and the genome

length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanimicrococcus evafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanimicrococcus evafia (N.L. fem. n. *evafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanimicrococcus sp009776675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009776675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.61 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanimicrococcus itedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanimicrococcus itedaria (N.L. fem. n. *itedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanimicrococcus sp009784005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009784005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.53 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanimicrococcus ofapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanimicrococcus ofapia (N.L. fem. n. *ofapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanimicrococcus sp017613335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017394465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.19 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanimicrococcus ulacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanimicrococcus ulacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ulacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanimicrococcus sp012518265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012518265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.39 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium adepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium adepia (N.L. fem. n. *adepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium sp012838205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012838205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.5 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ebadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ebadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium sp002496805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012842025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.48 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium efacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium efacana (N.L. fem. n. *efacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium sp013403005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013403005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.08 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium efexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium efexia (N.L. fem. n. *efexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium sp002067065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.06 % and the genome length is 2.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium obavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium obavosa (N.L. fem. n. *obavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium sp000499765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000499765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.74 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ocaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ocaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ocaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium sp000309865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000309865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.59 % and the genome length is 2.42 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sub-cultured for isolation from anaerobic microbial enrichment culture derived from a coal seam gas formation water sample".

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium onalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium onalosa (N.L. fem. n. *onalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium sp003491305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003491305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.4 % and the genome length is 2.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ufeposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ufeposa (N.L. fem. n. *ufeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium sp016217785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016217785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.05 % and the genome length is 2.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium afebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium afebia (N.L. fem. n. *afebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp002502855. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.25 % and the genome length is 2.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium efagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium efagosa (N.L. fem. n. *efagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp002067325. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.74 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium etacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium etacosa (N.L. fem. n. *etacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp011620845. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011620845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.16 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium etarosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium etarosa (N.L. fem. n. *etarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp003161815. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003161815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.27 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ibalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ibalella (N.L. fem. n. *ibalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp002067565. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.63 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ifagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ifagella (N.L. fem. n. *ifagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp003166335. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003168635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.43 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ogemana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ogemana (N.L. fem. n. *ogemana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp018263005. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018263005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.25 % and the genome length is 2.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium pefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium pefana (N.L. fem. n. *pefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp002494495. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.65 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ufaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ufaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ufaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp002495625. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002504505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.77 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ugaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ugaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ugaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp017883605. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017883605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.67 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium unararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium unararia (N.L. fem. n. *unararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_A sp015661405. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015661405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.24 % and the genome length is 2.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium acafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium acafaria (N.L. fem. n. *acafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_B sp003164415. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003164415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.42 % and the genome length is 2.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium edagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium edagana (N.L. fem. n. *edagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_B sp003162115. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with

an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003161875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.8 % and the genome length is 2.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium oragia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium oragia (N.L. fem. n. *oragia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_B sp003162655. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003162655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.87 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium quaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium quaxia (N.L. fem. n. *quaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_B sp000744455. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017883565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.96 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ufaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ufaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_B sp003151535. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003151535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.5 % and the genome length is 3.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium ugadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium ugadella (N.L. fem. n. *ugadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_B sp009712615. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009712615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.77 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium vucella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium vucella (N.L. fem. n. *vucella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_B sp003158115. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003158115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.07 % and the genome length is 2.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium naxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium naxana (N.L. fem. n. *naxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_C sp002498385. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.16 % and the genome length is 2.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium agacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium agacella (N.L. fem. n. *agacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_D sp002509665. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.96 % and the genome length is 2.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium egafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium egafella (N.L. fem. n. *egafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in

apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_D sp002505765. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.83 % and the genome length is 2.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium omacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium omacosa (N.L. fem. n. *omacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_D sp002494885. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.09 % and the genome length is 2.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobacterium udefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobacterium udefia (N.L. fem. n. *udefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobacterium_D sp016222945. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016222945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.57 % and the genome length is 2.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter amacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter amacosa (N.L. fem. n. *amacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp017646885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017646885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.51 % and the genome length is 2.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter amecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter amecosa (N.L. fem. n. *amecosa* a species epithet created

arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp017410345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017410345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.23 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter avacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter avacosa (N.L. fem. n. *avacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp016291275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016291275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.62 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter gaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter gaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *gaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp900314635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902777105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.87 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter guxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter guxaria (N.L. fem. n. *guxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp902784195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902765275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.35 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ibafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ibafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ibafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp902774685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902774685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.42 % and the genome length is 2.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter igabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter igabia (N.L. fem. n. *igabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp902769175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902769175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.9 % and the genome length is 3.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter isecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter isecana (N.L. fem. n. *isecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp905235495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905235495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.05 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter obagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter obagosa (N.L. fem. n. *obagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp900321995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900321995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.47 % and the genome length is 1.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter odagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter odagana (N.L. fem. n. *odagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp016838945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.54 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ogabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ogabana (N.L. fem. n. *ogabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp017652345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017652345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.29 % and the genome length is 4.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter orabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter orabia (N.L. fem. n. *orabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp017432245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017432245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.17 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ucanella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ucanella (N.L. fem. n. *ucanella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter sp017404125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017404125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.27 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter adevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter adevana (N.L. fem. n. *adevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp001548675. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001548675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.25 % and the genome length is 2.27 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "pooled rumen fluid".

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter afedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter afedaria (N.L. fem. n. *afedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp015062985. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015062985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.99 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanobrevibacter agaxaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter agaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *agaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902788255. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902788255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.74 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanobrevibacter asagella sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter asagella (N.L. fem. n. *asagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900769095. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900769095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.48 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanobrevibacter atafosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter atafosa (N.L. fem. n. *atafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902801725. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome

for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902801725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.45 % and the genome length is 2.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ebagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ebagaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902770715. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902770715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.42 % and the genome length is 2.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ebevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ebevosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017406825. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017406825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.9 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ecedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ecedella (N.L. fem. n. *ecedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017473945. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017473945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.43 % and the genome length is 2.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter edabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter edabana (N.L. fem. n. *edabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017539065. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017539065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.8 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter edebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter edebana (N.L. fem. n. *edebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017434525. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017434525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.47 % and the genome length is 3.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter edevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter edevia (N.L. fem. n. *edevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902783085. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902783085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.38 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter egamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter egamosa (N.L. fem. n. *egamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900316895. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900316895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.49 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter egarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter egarella (N.L. fem. n. *egarella* a species epithet created

arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902789505. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017433025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.87 % and the genome length is 2.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter egefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter egefaria (N.L. fem. n. *egefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902777885. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902777885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.85 % and the genome length is 1.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter elacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter elacella (N.L. fem. n. *elacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902772665. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902772665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.57 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter elagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter elagosa (N.L. fem. n. *elagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017431965. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017431965.1. The GC content of the type

genome is 33.78 % and the genome length is 2.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter emapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter emapella (N.L. fem. n. *emapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902785855. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015063015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.26 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter epamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter epamella (N.L. fem. n. *epamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902782595. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902782595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.19 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter eravana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter eravana (N.L. fem. n. *eravana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017940815. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017940815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.89 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter eravaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter eravaria (N.L. fem. n. *eravaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Methanobrevibacter_A* sp017468685. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017468685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.07 % and the genome length is 2.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter erebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter erebosa (N.L. fem. n. *erebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanobrevibacter_A* sp002496065. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.8 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter evafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter evafosa (N.L. fem. n. *evafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanobrevibacter_A* sp017407115. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017407115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.78 % and the genome length is 2.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter gaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter gaxana (N.L. fem. n. *gaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanobrevibacter_A* sp900314695. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.88 % and the genome length is 2.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter gixana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter gixana (N.L. fem. n. *gixana* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900320515. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900313195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.32 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ifamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ifamella (N.L. fem. n. *ifamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902794475. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902794475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.86 % and the genome length is 2.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter igacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter igacana (N.L. fem. n. *igacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017634055. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017634055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.32 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter igefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter igefella (N.L. fem. n. *igefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902771435. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902771435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.45 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter igefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter igefosa (N.L. fem. n. *igefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017459665. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017459665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.32 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter imecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter imecia (N.L. fem. n. *imecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017427765. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017427765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.69 % and the genome length is 2.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ipaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ipaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900313645. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017389565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.04 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ipemaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ipemaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipemaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017553445. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed

binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017553445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.06 % and the genome length is 1.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ivafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ivafana (N.L. fem. n. *ivafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900314615. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902758945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.1 % and the genome length is 2.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter omacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter omacella (N.L. fem. n. *omacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902774605. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902774605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.99 % and the genome length is 2.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter omafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter omafella (N.L. fem. n. *omafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900320955. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900320955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.65 % and the genome length is 2.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter omecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter omecaria (N.L. fem. n. *omecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902764015. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902764015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.54 % and the genome length is 1.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter pefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter pefia (N.L. fem. n. *pefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900319535. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900313245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.83 % and the genome length is 1.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter phabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter phabella (N.L. fem. n. *phabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902796575. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902796575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.32 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter quafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter quafia (N.L. fem. n. *quafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp904501935. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_904501935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.32 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter quefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter quefaria (N.L. fem. n. *quefaria* a species epithet created

arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp015062935. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015062935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.17 % and the genome length is 2.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ubefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ubefella (N.L. fem. n. *ubefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017460025. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017460025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.38 % and the genome length is 2.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ufapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ufapella (N.L. fem. n. *ufapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900318035. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902759475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.15 % and the genome length is 2.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ugacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ugacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ugacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017447225. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017447225.1. The GC content of the type

genome is 34.32 % and the genome length is 2.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter unabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter unabaria (N.L. fem. n. *unabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900766745. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905213915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.68 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter upafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter upafia (N.L. fem. n. *upafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900319985. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902758075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.88 % and the genome length is 2.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter upefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter upefaria (N.L. fem. n. *upefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp902764455. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902764455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.57 % and the genome length is 2.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter usecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter usecia (N.L. fem. n. *usecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017409525. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed

binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017409525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.9 % and the genome length is 2.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter utaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter utaxana (N.L. fem. n. *utaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp017434555. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015063065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.46 % and the genome length is 2.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter vubaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter vubaria (N.L. fem. n. *vubaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_A sp900317865. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902799005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.08 % and the genome length is 3.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter enaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter enaxia (N.L. fem. n. *enaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_B sp002208625. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_002208625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 24.41 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ivedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ivedosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_B sp905235195. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905235195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 26.24 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter mivana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter mivana (N.L. fem. n. *mivana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_B sp900314605. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902759335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 25.87 % and the genome length is 2.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter apavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter apavana (N.L. fem. n. *apavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_C sp009784145. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009784145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 25.54 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ugafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ugafella (N.L. fem. n. *ugafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_C sp009777005. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009777005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 25.46 % and the genome length is 2.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ugavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter ugavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ugavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_C sp003315655. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003315655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 25.26 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanobrevibacter umacana sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanobrevibacter umacana (N.L. fem. n. *umacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanobrevibacter_C sp009776495. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009776495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.02 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanocalculus enagia sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocalculus enagia (N.L. fem. n. *enagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocalculus sp9912u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001508455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.9 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "oil reservoir sample SB1".

Description of *Candidatus* Methanocalculus epanosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocalculus epanosa (N.L. fem. n. *epanosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocalculus sp007130455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007130455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.45 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanocalculus itafana sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocalculus itafana (N.L. fem. n. *itafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocalculus sp003838185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003552845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.67 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocalculus ogabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocalculus ogabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocalculus sp002496395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.7 % and the genome length is 2.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocalculus unagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocalculus unagella (N.L. fem. n. *unagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocalculus sp003838065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003550375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.46 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocaldococcus ageposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocaldococcus ageposa (N.L. fem. n. *ageposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocaldococcus sp013153845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013153845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.27 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocaldococcus elagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocaldococcus elagana (N.L. fem. n. *elagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocaldococcus sp000025525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000025525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.04 % and the

genome length is 1.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocaldococcus isabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocaldococcus isabaria (N.L. fem. n. *isabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocaldococcus sp902827205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902827205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.08 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocella ufagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocella ufagella (N.L. fem. n. *ufagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocella_A sp002067315. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.83 % and the genome length is 3.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanococcoides ubenosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanococcoides ubenosa (N.L. fem. n. *ubenosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanococcoides sp900774055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_900774055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.66 % and the genome length is 2.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocomedens egaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocomedens egaxana (N.L. fem. n. *egaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocomedens sp7939u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.5 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocomedens ovafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocomedens ovafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ovafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocomedens sp009649835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009649835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.03 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocomedens urabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocomedens urabaria (N.L. fem. n. *urabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocomedens sp014237145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014237495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.9 % and the genome length is 3.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum atafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum atafia (N.L. fem. n. *atafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp001940805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001940805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.9 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "feces from Phil the wombat".

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum ipaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum ipaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ipaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp002498375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.03 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum omepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum omepana (N.L. fem. n. *omepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp002506085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.08 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum onagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum onagana (N.L. fem. n. *onagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp017555685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017555685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.94 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum ovapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum ovapana (N.L. fem. n. *ovapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp018065685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018065685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.2 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum phapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum phapella (N.L. fem. n. *phapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp017622255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017622255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.72 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum ucedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum ucedaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp003315675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003315675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.11 % and the genome

length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum upabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum upabia (N.L. fem. n. *upabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp017399555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017435435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.45 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum upafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum upafella (N.L. fem. n. *upafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp017387505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017561385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.62 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanocorpusculum utagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanocorpusculum utagana (N.L. fem. n. *utagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanocorpusculum sp017408885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017411925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.4 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus atedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus atedosa (N.L. fem. n. *atedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp000691865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000691865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.44 % and the genome length is 2.54 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sediment associated with methane hydrate from Krishna Godavari Basin".

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus ebadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus ebadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp002497965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018053465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.02 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus efagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus efagia (N.L. fem. n. *efagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp018433835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018432605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.49 % and the genome length is 2.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus erapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus erapia (N.L. fem. n. *erapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp002839645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002839645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.83 % and the genome length is 2.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus icadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus icadana (N.L. fem. n. *icadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp012510335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012510335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.47 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus idataria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus idataria (N.L. fem. n. *idataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp016841955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016841295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.87 % and the genome length is 2.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus ifacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus ifacella (N.L. fem. n. *ifacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp002498065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.35 % and the genome length is 2.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus ifacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus ifacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp019136335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019136335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.79 % and the genome length is 2.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus ilacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus ilacana (N.L. fem. n. *ilacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp002506585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.96 % and the genome length is 2.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus itavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus itavia (N.L. fem. n. *itavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp001896715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017994915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.61 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus ocagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus ocagaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp002501655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002501655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.85 % and the genome

length is 2.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus ofabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus ofabia (N.L. fem. n. *ofabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp012521035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012521035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.47 % and the genome length is 2.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus ofepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus ofepana (N.L. fem. n. *ofepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp002839575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002839575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.51 % and the genome length is 2.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus opebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus opebaria (N.L. fem. n. *opebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp016841385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016841385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.62 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus pefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus pefaria (N.L. fem. n. *pefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoculleus sp002508705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002508705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.28 % and the genome length is 2.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus ucerana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus ucerana (N.L. fem. n. *ucerana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Methanoculleus* sp012510295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012510295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.45 % and the genome length is 1.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus unagara* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus unagara (N.L. fem. n. *unagara* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoculleus* sp012797575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013201385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.04 % and the genome length is 2.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus unaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus unaxana (N.L. fem. n. *unaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoculleus* sp012511245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012511245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.82 % and the genome length is 2.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoculleus usavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoculleus usavella (N.L. fem. n. *usavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoculleus* sp002499455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.33 % and the genome length is 2.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofastidiosum ebagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofastidiosum ebagella (N.L. fem. n. *ebagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanofastidiosum* sp001587575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001587575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.49 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Methanogenic purified terephthalic acid process wastewater treatment bioreactor".

Description of *Candidatus Methanofastidiosum igafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofastidiosum igafia (N.L. fem. n. *igafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofastidiosum sp003558335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003558335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.8 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofastidiosum ilabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofastidiosum ilabella (N.L. fem. n. *ilabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofastidiosum sp9950u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.52 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofastidiosum ileitaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofastidiosum ileitaria (N.L. fem. n. *ileitaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofastidiosum sp001587715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001587715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.38 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Methanogenic purified terephthalic acid process wastewater treatment bioreactor".

Description of *Candidatus Methanofastidiosum onabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofastidiosum onabia (N.L. fem. n. *onabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofastidiosum sp013178285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013178285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.53 % and the genome length is 2.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofastidiosum otaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofastidiosum otaxella (N.L. fem. n. *otaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofastidiosum sp001587675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012797645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.72 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofastidiosum ubafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofastidiosum ubafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ubafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofastidiosum sp012799835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012799835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.81 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofastidiosum urabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofastidiosum urabella (N.L. fem. n. *urabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofastidiosum sp001587595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001587635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.31 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Urbana Champaign Sanitary District anaerobic digester sludge".

Description of *Candidatus Methanofervidicoccus itabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofervidicoccus itabia (N.L. fem. n. *itabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofervidicoccus sp003351865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003351865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.1 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofollis edabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofollis edabia (N.L. fem. n. *edabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofollis sp004297185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004297185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.54 % and the genome length is 2.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofollis itabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofollis itabosa (N.L. fem. n. *itabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofollis sp002498315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.87 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanofollis ofagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanofollis ofagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanofollis sp017875325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_017875325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.1 % and the genome length is 2.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogaster acegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogaster acegia (N.L. fem. n. *acegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogaster sp003601535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003601535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.69 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogaster adevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogaster adevaria (N.L. fem. n. *adevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogaster sp003194445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003194445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.68 % and the genome length is 3.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogaster afadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogaster afadosa (N.L. fem. n. *afadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogaster sp002506015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.34 % and the genome

length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogaster apagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogaster apagosa (N.L. fem. n. *apagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogaster sp013572355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013572355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.6 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogaster ecasia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogaster ecasia (N.L. fem. n. *ecasia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogaster sp003661105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.97 % and the genome length is 2.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogaster ifarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogaster ifarana (N.L. fem. n. *ifarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogaster sp002503595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.2 % and the genome length is 2.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogaster orapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogaster orapella (N.L. fem. n. *orapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogaster sp012961645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012961645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.05 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogaster upaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogaster upaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *upaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Methanogaster sp004211975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004211975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.45 % and the genome length is 2.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogenium ebeigia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogenium ebeigia (N.L. fem. n. *ebeigia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogenium sp012523385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012523385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.79 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogenium ipatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogenium ipatia (N.L. fem. n. *ipatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogenium sp016841485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016841485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.32 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogenium oredosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogenium oredosa (N.L. fem. n. *oredosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogenium sp009914725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009914725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.7 % and the genome length is 2.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogenium ucadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogenium ucadia (N.L. fem. n. *ucadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogenium sp018687785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018687785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.23 % and the genome length is 2.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogenium usegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogenium usegana (N.L. fem. n. *usegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogenium sp011045995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011045995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.06 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogranum edeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogranum edeparia (N.L. fem. n. *edeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogranum sp012719315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012719315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.73 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogranum etaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogranum etaxana (N.L. fem. n. *etaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogranum sp002506905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.67 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanogranum udafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanogranum udafosa (N.L. fem. n. *udafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanogranum sp019262145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019262145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.73 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanohalobium ilabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanohalobium ilabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ilabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanohalobium sp018609725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018609725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.76 % and the genome length is 2.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanohalophilus etabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanohalophilus etabana (N.L. fem. n. *etabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanohalophilus sp003722075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003722075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.56 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolacinia egavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolacinia egavana (N.L. fem. n. *egavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolacinia sp016928355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016928355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.65 % and the genome length is 1.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolinea afaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolinea afaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *afxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolinea_A sp002067155. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018263335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.99 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolinea enagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolinea enagosa (N.L. fem. n. *enagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolinea_A sp018262855. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.01 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolinea itadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolinea itadosa (N.L. fem. n. *itadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolinea_A sp002509495. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.33 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolinea muposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolinea muposa (N.L. fem. n. *muposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolinea_A sp002506105. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.97 % and the genome length is 2.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolinea odacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolinea odacia (N.L. fem. n. *odacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolinea_A sp11423u. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.67 % and the genome length is 2.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolinea odexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolinea odexosa (N.L. fem. n. *odexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolinea_A sp002067095. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.79 % and the genome length is 2.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolinea umexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolinea umexella (N.L. fem. n. *umexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolinea_A sp002501965. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002501965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.18 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoliparum ecanosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoliparum ecanosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecanosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoliparum sp8915u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.59 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolliviera igefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolliviera igefaria (N.L. fem. n. *igefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolliviera sp902158735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902158735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.58 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolliviera utebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolliviera utebia (N.L. fem. n. *utebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolliviera sp902158745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902158745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.73 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolobus atafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolobus atafella (N.L. fem. n. *atafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolobus sp002508635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002508635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.22 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolobus evegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolobus evegana (N.L. fem. n. *evegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanolobus* sp016932675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.07 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolobus ogebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolobus ogebia (N.L. fem. n. *ogebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanolobus* sp004745425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004745425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.58 % and the genome length is 2.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolobus otabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolobus otabella (N.L. fem. n. *otabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanolobus* sp003565715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003565715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.88 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolobus otamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolobus otamia (N.L. fem. n. *otamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanolobus* sp016278365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016278365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.4 % and the genome length is 2.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolobus ovapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolobus ovapella (N.L. fem. n. *ovapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanolobus* sp016278385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016278385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.17 % and the genome

length is 2.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolobus phebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolobus phebosa (N.L. fem. n. *phebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolobus sp002507205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002507205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.29 % and the genome length is 2.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanolobus ufebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanolobus ufebella (N.L. fem. n. *ufebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanolobus sp002501695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002501695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.23 % and the genome length is 2.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomarinus ovafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomarinus ovafella (N.L. fem. n. *ovafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomarinus sp002926195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013374495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.81 % and the genome length is 2.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomassiliicoccus obamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomassiliicoccus obamia (N.L. fem. n. *obamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomassiliicoccus_A sp905203995. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905203995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.78 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomassiliicoccus omaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomassiliicoccus omaxella (N.L. fem. n. *omaxella* a species epithet created

arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomassiliicoccus_A sp905202485. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905202485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.72 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylophilus apevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylophilus apevia (N.L. fem. n. *apevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylophilus sp000350305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000350305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.3 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylophilus cebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylophilus cebosa (N.L. fem. n. *cebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylophilus sp001481295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902777245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.97 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylophilus ecalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylophilus ecalia (N.L. fem. n. *ecalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylophilus sp902787415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902787415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.38 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylophilus ecavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylophilus ecavella (N.L. fem. n. *ecavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylophilus sp002495325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.13 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylophilus icanaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylophilus icanaria (N.L. fem. n. *icanaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylophilus sp015063225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015063225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.23 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylophilus idavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylophilus idavella (N.L. fem. n. *idavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylophilus sp001560915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001560915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.0 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylophilus udavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylophilus udavaria (N.L. fem. n. *udavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylophilus sp002503545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.12 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylophilus umaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylophilus umaxia (N.L. fem. n. *umaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylophilus sp902763685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902763685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.15 % and the genome

length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylovorans abafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylovorans abafella (N.L. fem. n. *abafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylovorans sp001896725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018433205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.43 % and the genome length is 1.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylovorans epadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylovorans epadosa (N.L. fem. n. *epadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylovorans sp002508425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002508425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.12 % and the genome length is 2.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylovorans phafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylovorans phafana (N.L. fem. n. *phafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylovorans sp002067265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.97 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylovorans phafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylovorans phafosa (N.L. fem. n. *phafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylovorans sp014361205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.12 % and the genome length is 2.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanomethylovorans ucalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomethylovorans ucalia (N.L. fem. n. *ucalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomethylovorans sp002067275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.31 % and the genome length is 2.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanomicrobium opebosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomicrobium opebosa (N.L. fem. n. *opebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomicrobium sp017875315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_017875315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.97 % and the genome length is 2.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanomicrobium ulavaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomicrobium ulavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ulavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomicrobium sp017553245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017553245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.74 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanomicrobium unaxia sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomicrobium unaxia (N.L. fem. n. *unaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanomicrobium sp016937345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016937345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.43 % and the genome length is 2.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanomicrobium usagia sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanomicrobium usagia (N.L. fem. n. *usagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Methanomicrobium* sp017412625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017412935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.31 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanonatronarchaeum asaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanonatronarchaeum asaxella (N.L. fem. n. *asaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanonatronarchaeum* sp004212035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003555005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.52 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens amecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens amecana (N.L. fem. n. *amecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoperedens* sp012026795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012026795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.58 % and the genome length is 3.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens amecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens amecia (N.L. fem. n. *amecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoperedens* sp902386135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902386135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.05 % and the genome length is 3.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens edepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens edepana (N.L. fem. n. *edepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoperedens* sp902386205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902386205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.88 % and the genome length is 2.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens ibafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens ibafana (N.L. fem. n. *ibafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp018900975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018900975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.32 % and the genome length is 2.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens ifaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens ifaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ifaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp902386115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902386115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.36 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens ivabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens ivabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp018899795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018899795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.0 % and the genome length is 2.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens ivacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens ivacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp902386255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902386255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.14 % and the genome length is 2.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens ofegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens ofegosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp902384525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902384525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.43 % and the genome length is 2.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens ogafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens ogafia (N.L. fem. n. *ogafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp012026835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012026835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.92 % and the genome length is 3.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens onatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens onatella (N.L. fem. n. *onatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp003104905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003104905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.81 % and the genome length is 2.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens oredana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens oredana (N.L. fem. n. *oredana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp902386085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902386085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.13 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens ovacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens ovacana (N.L. fem. n. *ovacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp002487355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008933945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.25 % and the genome length is 3.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens umaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens umaxella (N.L. fem. n. *umaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens sp905339155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank

assembly GCA_905339155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.81 % and the genome length is 3.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens enabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens enabella (N.L. fem. n. *enabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens_A sp002839545. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002839545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.15 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoperedens oredaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoperedens oredaria (N.L. fem. n. *oredaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoperedens_A sp014859785. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014859785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.0 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoplasma efaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoplasma efaparia (N.L. fem. n. *efaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoplasma sp009778275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009778275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.02 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoplasma ilafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoplasma ilafella (N.L. fem. n. *ilafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoplasma sp009786295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009786295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.3 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoplasma ipabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoplasma ipabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoplasma sp009776625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009776625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.56 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoplasma itefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoplasma itefosa (N.L. fem. n. *itefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoplasma sp009778575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009778575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.09 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoplasma udapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoplasma udapella (N.L. fem. n. *udapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoplasma sp009777615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009777615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.26 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanopyrus ogalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanopyrus ogalella (N.L. fem. n. *ogalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanopyrus sp013154335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013154335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.43 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanopyrus onadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanopyrus onadia (N.L. fem. n. *onadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanopyrus sp002201895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_002201915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.67 % and the

genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula apafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula apafaria (N.L. fem. n. *apafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoregula* sp002495065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.15 % and the genome length is 2.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula apavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula apavaria (N.L. fem. n. *apavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoregula* sp002839605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002839605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.31 % and the genome length is 2.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula ebaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula ebaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoregula* sp903832665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903832665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.16 % and the genome length is 2.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula ecasana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula ecasana (N.L. fem. n. *ecasana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoregula* sp002835825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002835825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.64 % and the genome length is 2.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula egafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula egafana (N.L. fem. n. *egafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Methanoregula* sp015660885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015660885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.79 % and the genome length is 2.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula emagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula emagia (N.L. fem. n. *emagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoregula* sp003136075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003136075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.55 % and the genome length is 2.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula idavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula idavosa (N.L. fem. n. *idavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoregula* sp003157895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003157895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.77 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula ilavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula ilavia (N.L. fem. n. *ilavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoregula* sp002502735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.43 % and the genome length is 2.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula ipavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula ipavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanoregula* sp002508495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002508495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.84 % and the genome length is 1.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula iralaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula iralaria (N.L. fem. n. *iralaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp002495055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.32 % and the genome length is 2.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula ivafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula ivafia (N.L. fem. n. *ivafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp002067035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.47 % and the genome length is 2.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula ogefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula ogefana (N.L. fem. n. *ogefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp11803u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.12 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula onaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula onaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *onaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp002839675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002839675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.45 % and the genome length is 2.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula ovacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula ovacella (N.L. fem. n. *ovacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp003154335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003153835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.91 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula puxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula puxia (N.L. fem. n. *puxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp002502245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.12 % and the genome length is 2.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula ubafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula ubafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ubafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp002497485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.85 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula udaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula udaposa (N.L. fem. n. *udaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp003141335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003141335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.9 % and the genome length is 2.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula udavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula udavia (N.L. fem. n. *udavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp012798365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012798365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.77 % and the genome length is 2.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanoregula uravia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanoregula uravia (N.L. fem. n. *uravia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanoregula sp003170075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003170075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.99 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosalsum obamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosalsum obamella (N.L. fem. n. *obamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosalsum sp007127385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007127385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.49 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina acaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina acaxia (N.L. fem. n. *acaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp002496565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.98 % and the genome length is 3.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcinaifaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcinaifaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp002509325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.24 % and the genome length is 2.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina agacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina agacia (N.L. fem. n. *agacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp017883485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017883485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.49 % and the genome length is 2.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina asavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina asavaria (N.L. fem. n. *asavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp001714685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017883465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.01 % and the genome

length is 3.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina avacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina avacaria (N.L. fem. n. *avacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp8098u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.41 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina ecafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina ecafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ecafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp000969965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000969965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.69 % and the genome length is 4.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina emavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina emavaria (N.L. fem. n. *emavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp002505485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.16 % and the genome length is 3.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina eregia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina eregia (N.L. fem. n. *eregia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp11020u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.11 % and the genome length is 4.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina ibaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina ibaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ibaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp003157235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003157235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.81 % and the genome length is 2.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina mupana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina mupana (N.L. fem. n. *mupana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp000979455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000979385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.93 % and the genome length is 3.91 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sediment".

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina naxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina naxaria (N.L. fem. n. *naxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp002499445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.47 % and the genome length is 2.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina ofebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina ofebaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp10923u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.6 % and the genome length is 3.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina otegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina otegosa (N.L. fem. n. *otegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp003164755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003164755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.74 % and the genome length is 3.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosarcina pheposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosarcina pheposa (N.L. fem. n. *pheposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosarcina sp004099695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_004099695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.46 % and the genome length is 3.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanosphaera adeposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera adeposa (N.L. fem. n. *adeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp001729965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001729965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.7 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanosphaera ecapia sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera ecapia (N.L. fem. n. *ecapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp003266145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003266145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.0 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanosphaera ecarosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera ecarosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp003268005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905236795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.89 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Methanosphaera elafaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera elafaria (N.L. fem. n. *elafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp902797085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902797085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.93 % and the genome length is 1.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera evabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera evabaria (N.L. fem. n. *evabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp017652595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017652595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.42 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera ofamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera ofamana (N.L. fem. n. *ofamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp003266165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003266165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.25 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera ogalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera ogalia (N.L. fem. n. *ogalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp016282985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016282985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.8 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera ogavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera ogavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp017431845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017431845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.59 % and the genome length is 2.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera opabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera opabana (N.L. fem. n. *opabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp900322125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.95 % and the genome

length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera osaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera osaxella (N.L. fem. n. *osaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp003266065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003266065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.83 % and the genome length is 2.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera udacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera udacaria (N.L. fem. n. *udacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp003266105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003266105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.92 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera ufatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera ufatana (N.L. fem. n. *ufatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp003266075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003266075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.52 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera usabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera usabana (N.L. fem. n. *usabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanosphaera sp017430835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017430835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.55 % and the genome length is 3.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosphaera vucaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanosphaera vucaria (N.L. fem. n. *vucaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Methanosphaera* sp11921u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.21 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanospirillum ecavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Methanospirillum ecavana* (N.L. fem. n. *ecavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanospirillum* sp012729535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012729535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.93 % and the genome length is 3.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanospirillum osavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Methanospirillum osavana* (N.L. fem. n. *osavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanospirillum* sp012729995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_018502485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.08 % and the genome length is 3.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanospirillum upagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Methanospirillum upagella* (N.L. fem. n. *upagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanospirillum* sp012520015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012520015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.21 % and the genome length is 2.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanosuratus enacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Methanosuratus enacaria* (N.L. fem. n. *enacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanosuratus* sp014361455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.66 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothermobacter odabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Methanothermobacter odabella* (N.L. fem. n. *odabella* a species epithet created

arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothermobacter sp000828575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000828575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.35 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothermobacter acagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothermobacter acagia (N.L. fem. n. *acagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothermobacter_A sp012840175. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012840175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.12 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothermobacter acavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothermobacter acavana (N.L. fem. n. *acavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothermobacter_A sp001507955. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.77 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothermobacter agevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothermobacter agevana (N.L. fem. n. *agevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothermobacter_A sp011370395. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011370395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.69 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothermobacter upacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothermobacter upacella (N.L. fem. n. *upacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanothermobacter_A* sp003584625. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012840205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.96 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothermococcus upelana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothermococcus upelana (N.L. fem. n. *upelana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanothermococcus_A* sp015523155. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.49 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherrix agavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherrix agavosa (N.L. fem. n. *agavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanotherrix* sp002067365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.33 % and the genome length is 2.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherrix cixosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherrix cixosa (N.L. fem. n. *cixosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Methanotherrix* sp903871465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903840245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.63 % and the genome length is 3.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherrix ebamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothrix ehamella (N.L. fem. n. *ehamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothrix sp011620785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.96 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothrix efexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothrix efexaria (N.L. fem. n. *efexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothrix sp011391755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011391755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.91 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothrix ibapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothrix ibapana (N.L. fem. n. *ibapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothrix sp902385025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.51 % and the genome length is 2.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothrix ifagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothrix ifagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothrix sp016706325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018434885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.5 % and the genome length is 2.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanothrix ifalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanothrix ifalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothrix sp002067755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.88 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix ilavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix ilavana (N.L. fem. n. *ilavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix sp016927055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016927055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.21 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix imadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix imadana (N.L. fem. n. *imadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix sp002505805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.21 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix itagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix itagosa (N.L. fem. n. *itagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix sp003857025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003857025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.0 % and the genome length is 3.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix ivafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix ivafella (N.L. fem. n. *ivafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix sp002256595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002256595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.81 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix ocabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix ocabana (N.L. fem. n. *ocabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix sp018052825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018052825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.13 % and the genome length is

1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix ocavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix ocavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix sp002067705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.85 % and the genome length is 3.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix omevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix omevosa (N.L. fem. n. *omevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix sp017994055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017994055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.11 % and the genome length is 2.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix oraparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix oraparia (N.L. fem. n. *oraparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix sp012798025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012798025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.79 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix phabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix phabana (N.L. fem. n. *phabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanotherix_A sp9297u. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.91 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Methanotherix vubana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Methanotherix vubana (N.L. fem. n. *vubana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Methanothrix_A sp001602645. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018432365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.71 % and the genome length is 2.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Metosarcha ovabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Metosarcha ovabella (N.L. fem. n. *ovabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCFN01 sp017609245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.0 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Metosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Metosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Metosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCFN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Metosarcha ovabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Metosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Metosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Metosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Metosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFCFN01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Metosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Metosarcha uvadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Metosarcha uvadaria (N.L. fem. n. *uvadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCFN01 sp017608625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_017608625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.19 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mexatrarcha ugacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mexatrarcha ugacella (N.L. fem. n. *ugacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MFWN01 sp001786395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001786395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.56 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 13ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Mexatrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mexatrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mexatrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MFWN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mexatrarcha ugacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mexerarcha ifalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mexerarcha ifalella (N.L. fem. n. *ifalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAPY01 sp015520525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.16 % and the genome length is 0.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mexerarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mexerarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mexerarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAPY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mexerarcha ifalella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Mexerarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mexerarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Mexerarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Mexerarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WAPY01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Mexerarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Mexiprarcha irafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mexiprarcha irafana (N.L. fem. n. *irafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSQZ01 sp011331665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011331665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 26.43 % and the genome length is 0.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mexiprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mexiprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mexiprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSQZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mexiprarcha irafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nanopusillaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mibrucarcha agavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mibrucarcha agavella (N.L. fem. n. *agavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOV01 sp018302985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.97 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mibrucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mibrucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mibrucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JACOV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mibrucarcha agavella*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Giboxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mibrucarcha onexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mibrucarcha onexosa (N.L. fem. n. *onexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOV01 sp016177265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016177265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.95 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Micubrarcha elafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Micubrarcha elafia (N.L. fem. n. *elafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTIR01 sp011362825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011362825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.91 % and the genome length is 0.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Micubrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Micubrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Micubrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTIR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Micubrarcha elafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Micubrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Micubrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Micubrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Micubrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTIR01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Micubrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pacearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Midifarcha buvosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Midifarcha buvosa (N.L. fem. n. *buvosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR1 sp002762735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009992385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.0 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Midifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Midifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Midifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Midifarcha buvosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Midifarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Midifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Midifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Midifarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pacearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Midifarcha esaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Midifarcha esaxana (N.L. fem. n. *esaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR1 sp009992215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009992215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.05 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Midifarcha icabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Midifarcha icabana (N.L. fem. n. *icabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR1 sp903831045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903831045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.79 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Midifarcha idaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Midifarcha idaparia (N.L. fem. n. *idaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR1 sp018830845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.39 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Midifarcha ogafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Midifarcha ogafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR1 sp009992175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009992175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.58 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Midifarcha upedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Midifarcha upedaria (N.L. fem. n. *upedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR1 sp018303925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.61 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Midricarcha ibalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Midricarcha ibalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ibalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALD01 sp015523055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.02 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Midricarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Midricarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Midricarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Midricarcha ibalosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lanaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Midricarcha upagaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Midricarcha upagaria (N.L. fem. n. *upagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALD01 sp018897475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018897475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.53 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Midrofrarcha phedosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Midrofrarcha phedosa (N.L. fem. n. *phedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-45-29 sp002778455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002778455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.16 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Midrofrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Midrofrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Midrofrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 1-14-0-10-45-29. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Midrofrarcha phedosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Anstonellaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Mitifrarcha ifamosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Mitifrarcha ifamosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-34-76 sp002763075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank

assembly GCA_002763075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.44 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mitifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mitifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mitifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 1-14-0-10-34-76. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mitifrarcha ifamosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mixasarcha ucatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mixasarcha ucatana (N.L. fem. n. *ucatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAANXF01 sp018263395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018263395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.75 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mixasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mixasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mixasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAANXF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mixasarcha ucatana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Mixasarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mixasarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Mixasarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Mixasarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAANXF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Mixasarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Mixasarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Mixasarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Mixasarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Mixasarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAANXF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Mixasarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Methanonatronarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus* Mobetrarcha ocagana sp. nov.

Candidatus Mobetrarcha ocagana (N.L. fem. n. *ocagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGPE01 sp016926055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.58 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Mobetrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Mobetrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mobetrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGPE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Mobetrarcha ocagana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fitomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Mocixarcha opaxella sp. nov.

Candidatus Mocixarcha opaxella (N.L. fem. n. *opaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKV01 sp014728875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014728875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.52 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Mocixarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Mocixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mocixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is WJKV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Mocixarcha opaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Mocixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Mocixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus *Mocixarchaceae* (N.L. fem. n. *Mocixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WJKV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* *Mocixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Mosagrarcha ovagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Mosagrarcha ovagella* (N.L. fem. n. *ovagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B24-G1 sp003662535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.0 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Mosagrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus *Mosagrarcha* (N.L. fem. n. *Mosagrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B24-G1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Mosagrarcha ovagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Mosagrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Mosagrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus *Mosagrarchaceae* (N.L. fem. n. *Mosagrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B24-G1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* *Mosagrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Dunularchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Mostixarcha ebexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mostixarcha ebexana (N.L. fem. n. *ebexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GLR71 sp013138765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013138765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.39 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mostixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mostixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mostixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GLR71. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mostixarcha ebexana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Mostixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mostixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Mostixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Mostixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GLR71. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Mostixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Axalarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Mostixarcha orecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mostixarcha orecosa (N.L. fem. n. *orecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GLR71 sp013138805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013138805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.32 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mostularcha ebafofa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mostularcha ebafofa (N.L. fem. n. *ebafofa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BIN-L-1 sp004376385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004376385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.35 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mostularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mostularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mostularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BIN-L-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mostularcha ebafofa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Saxararchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mostularcha idaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mostularcha idaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *idaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BIN-L-1 sp003096255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003096255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.5 % and the genome length is 2.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mostularcha itedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mostularcha itedosa (N.L. fem. n. *itedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BIN-L-1 sp016930555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016930555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.8 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mostularcha udaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mostularcha udaparia (N.L. fem. n. *udaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BIN-L-1 sp003096235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003096235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.65 % and the genome length is 2.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Moxedarcha ufasia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Moxedarcha ufasia (N.L. fem. n. *ufasia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYJ01 sp018303315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.7 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Moxedarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Moxedarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Moxedarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Moxedarcha ufasia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Moxedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Moxedarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Moxedarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Moxedarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVYJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Moxedarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Moxofarcha ivaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Moxofarcha ivaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ivaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SP79 sp002715545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002715545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.36 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Moxofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Moxofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Moxofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is SP79. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Moxofarcha ivaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Moxofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Moxofarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Moxofarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Moxofarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SP79. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Moxofarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Poseidoniales*.

Description of *Candidatus Mufroparcha ucanana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mufroparcha ucanana (N.L. fem. n. *ucanana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S014-41 sp015522955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.52 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mufroparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mufroparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mufroparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S014-41. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mufroparcha ucanana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aciduliprofundaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Muprostarcha icebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Muprostarcha icebaria (N.L. fem. n. *icebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIRT01 sp018818285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018818285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.2 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Muprostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Muprostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Muprostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIRT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Muprostarcha icebaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mustigarcha idabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mustigarcha idabella (N.L. fem. n. *idabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Tc-Br11 sp017357105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017357105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.54 % and the genome length is 4.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mustigarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Mustigarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Mustigarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Tc-Br11. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Mustigarcha idabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natrialbaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Mustigarcha ocadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mustigarcha ocadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Tc-Br11 sp003552325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003552325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.93 % and the genome length is 2.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Mustigarcha ugaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Mustigarcha ugaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ugaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Tc-Br11 sp001564275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001564275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.6 % and the genome length is 3.16 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample Tc-Br; brine of Tanatar trona crystallizer".

Description of *Candidatus Nablufarcha upacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nablufarcha upacosa (N.L. fem. n. *upacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LW60-42 sp019058515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.97 % and the genome length is 6.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nablufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nablufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nablufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is LW60-42. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nablufarcha upacosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Naclutarcha ubavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naclutarcha ubavella (N.L. fem. n. *ubavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSFO01 sp011056475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011056475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.24 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naclutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Naclutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Naclutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSFO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Naclutarcha ubavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gearchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nanohalobium orecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nanohalobium orecana (N.L. fem. n. *orecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Nanohalobium* sp001761425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001761425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.37 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Halite rock".

Description of *Candidatus Nanosalina itagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nanosalina itagella (N.L. fem. n. *itagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Nanosalina* sp000220375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000220375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.58 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Lake Tyrrell".

Description of *Candidatus Nanosalinarum ebavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nanosalinarum ebavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Nanosalinarum* sp000220355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000220355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.2 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Lake Tyrrell".

Description of *Candidatus Naplefrarcha otevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naplefrarcha otevosa (N.L. fem. n. *otevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TH5893 sp014523685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.25 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naplefrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Naplefrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Naplefrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TH5893. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Naporarcha otevosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrososphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha arexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha arexaria (N.L. fem. n. *arexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp902531985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902531985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.56 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Naporarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG-Epi1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Naporarcha arexaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Naporarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Naporarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Naporarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG-Epi1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Naporarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *MGIII*.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha ecarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha ecarana (N.L. fem. n. *ecarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp002724775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002696565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.82 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha esebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha esebaria (N.L. fem. n. *esebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp001875365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001875365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.43 % and the genome length is 0.71 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "marine water".

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha evebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha evebella (N.L. fem. n. *evebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp902533295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902533295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.28 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha ipegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha ipegella (N.L. fem. n. *ipegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp014240055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014240055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.05 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha obefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha obefosa (N.L. fem. n. *obefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp002718915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002718915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.93 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha ocafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha ocafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp014240255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_014240255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.44 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha olacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha olacosa (N.L. fem. n. *olacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp016845825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016845825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.18 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha onavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha onavosa (N.L. fem. n. *onavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp002506485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.99 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha ovagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha ovagaria (N.L. fem. n. *ovagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp001875345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001875345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.57 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "marine water".

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha ovelosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha ovelosa (N.L. fem. n. *ovelosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp902627615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902627615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.7 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha ulabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha ulabana (N.L. fem. n. *ulabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp015658585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015658585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.62 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naporarcha usagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naporarcha usagana (N.L. fem. n. *usagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG-Epi1 sp002497685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.12 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naprotrarcha upefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naprotrarcha upefana (N.L. fem. n. *upefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PCWY01 sp002762975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002762975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.27 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naprotrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Naprotrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Naprotrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PCWY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Naprotrarcha upefana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iainarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Naraxarcha asebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naraxarcha asebaria (N.L. fem. n. *asebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA183 sp014874415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014874415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.4 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naraxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Naraxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Naraxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA183. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Naraxarcha asebaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Naraxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Naraxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Naraxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Naraxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA183. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Naraxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Naraxarcha irefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naraxarcha irefia (N.L. fem. n. *irefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA183 sp002495205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.67 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naraxarcha ivapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naraxarcha ivapia (N.L. fem. n. *ivapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA183 sp016432545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016432545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.29 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naraxarcha ivepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naraxarcha ivepia (N.L. fem. n. *ivepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA183 sp016200025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016200025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.45 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Naraxarcha ubenia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Naraxarcha ubenia (N.L. fem. n. *ubenia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA183 sp016200045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016200045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.61 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natagrarcha asafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natagrarcha asafella (N.L. fem. n. *asafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA102 sp002509225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.19 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natagrarcha gen. nov.*

Candidatus Natagrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Natagrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA102. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Natagrarcha asafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Naporarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Natagrarcha idanana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natagrarcha idanana (N.L. fem. n. *idanana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA102 sp001875425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001875425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.55 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "marine water".

Description of *Candidatus Natrarchaeobaculum edexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natrarchaeobaculum edexella (N.L. fem. n. *edexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natrarchaeobaculum sp001563885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.91 % and the genome length is 2.01 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample B1-Br-g2; brine of Lake Bitter-1".

Description of *Candidatus Natrarchaeobaculum ubafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natrarchaeobaculum ubafia (N.L. fem. n. *ubafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natrarchaeobaculum sp001563805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.72 % and the genome length is 2.87 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample B1-Br-g2; brine of Lake Bitter-1".

Description of *Candidatus Natrarchaeobaculum ulavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natrarchaeobaculum ulavella (N.L. fem. n. *ulavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natrarchaeobaculum sp001861355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001861355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.47 % and the genome length is 4.58 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "brine sample".

Description of *Candidatus Natrinema epadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natrinema epadana (N.L. fem. n. *epadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natrinema sp002572525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_002572525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.27 % and the genome length is 5.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natrinema ipedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natrinema ipedana (N.L. fem. n. *ipedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natrinema sp005938085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_005938085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.49 % and the genome length is 4.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natrinema onacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natrinema onacaria (N.L. fem. n. *onacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natrinema sp013456555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_013456555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.53 % and the genome length is 3.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natrinema ucerella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natrinema ucerella (N.L. fem. n. *ucerella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natrinema sp013402815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_013402815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.62 % and the genome length is 4.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronoarchaeum otavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronoarchaeum otavella (N.L. fem. n. *otavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronoarchaeum sp017094485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017094485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.79 % and the genome length is 3.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronococcus abafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronococcus abafia (N.L. fem. n. *abafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronococcus sp003559215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003559215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.79 % and the genome length is 3.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronococcus onaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronococcus onaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *onaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronococcus sp008122205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_008122205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.19 % and the genome length is 5.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Natronolimnobius ubefia sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronolimnobius ubefia (N.L. fem. n. *ubefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronolimnobius sp011043775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_011043775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.85 % and the genome length is 4.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Natronomonas ebecia sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas ebecia (N.L. fem. n. *ebecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronomonas sp003021005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.73 % and the genome length is 2.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Natronomonas emadosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas emadosa (N.L. fem. n. *emadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronomonas sp003021745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.58 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Natronomonas enaxana sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas enaxana (N.L. fem. n. *enaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronomonas sp003021325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 70.05 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas icavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas icavaria (N.L. fem. n. *icavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp007122455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007127355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.1 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas igefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas igefia (N.L. fem. n. *igefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp007121575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007121575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.7 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas isecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas isecosa (N.L. fem. n. *isecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp018609665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018609665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 71.35 % and the genome length is 2.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas ofegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas ofegia (N.L. fem. n. *ofegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp013839515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_013839515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.53 % and the genome length is 2.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas ogexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas ogexosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp007135435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007135435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.8 % and the genome

length is 3.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas ucafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas ucafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp003020965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003020965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.11 % and the genome length is 2.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas ucalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas ucalana (N.L. fem. n. *ucalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp003022905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.18 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas udabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas udabella (N.L. fem. n. *udabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp003023535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 70.3 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas ufacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas ufacia (N.L. fem. n. *ufacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp009741925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009741925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.91 % and the genome length is 3.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas ufacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas ufacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Natronomonas* sp003022815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.27 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronomonas umafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronomonas umafella (N.L. fem. n. *umafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronomonas* sp003022945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.84 % and the genome length is 2.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronoplasma enexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronoplasma enexosa (N.L. fem. n. *enexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronoplasma* sp003555395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003555395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.54 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronoplasma icadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronoplasma icadaria (N.L. fem. n. *icadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronoplasma* sp018334755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018334755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.69 % and the genome length is 2.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronoplasma ilacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronoplasma ilacella (N.L. fem. n. *ilacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Natronoplasma* sp003554965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003554965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.73 % and the genome length is 2.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronoplasma unabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronoplasma unabana (N.L. fem. n. *unabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronoplasma sp018334835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018334835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.47 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Natronorubrum obaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Natronorubrum obaxia (N.L. fem. n. *obaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Natronorubrum sp003670115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003670115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.87 % and the genome length is 4.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Necosarcha efavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Necosarcha efavosa (N.L. fem. n. *efavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B24-2 sp002490245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002490245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.36 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Necosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Necosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Necosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B24-2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Necosarcha efavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Necosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Necosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Necosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Necosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B24-2. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Necosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omagarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha acaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha acaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *acaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002457145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002171445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.63 % and the genome length is 1.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nefestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIb-O3. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nefestarcha acaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thalassarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha agafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha agafia (N.L. fem. n. *agafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp902573115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902573115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.88 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha avaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha avaxana (N.L. fem. n. *avaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002457155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002457155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.4 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha ebarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ebarella (N.L. fem. n. *ebarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is MGIIb-O3 sp004195615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012960735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.89 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha ecagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ecagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002716085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002693905.2. The GC content of the type genome is 50.28 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha ece maria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ece maria (N.L. fem. n. *ece maria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002719615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002719615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.04 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha efatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha efatosa (N.L. fem. n. *efatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002506755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.99 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha egaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha egaparia (N.L. fem. n. *egaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp905182515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905182515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.72 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha egavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha egavaria (N.L. fem. n. *egavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002172375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002172375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.77 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha emefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha emefia (N.L. fem. n. *emefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp902573085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902573085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.2 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha enabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha enabia (N.L. fem. n. *enabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002731195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002731195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.82 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha eravia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha eravia (N.L. fem. n. *eravia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002712575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002712575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.37 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha esefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha esefaria (N.L. fem. n. *esefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002728565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002728565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.69 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha etacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha etacella (N.L. fem. n. *etacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002720055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002720055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.54 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha etamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha etamella (N.L. fem. n. *etamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002683155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002683155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.63 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha guxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha guxella (N.L. fem. n. *guxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp001629235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902530535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.7 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha ibetosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ibetosa (N.L. fem. n. *ibetosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp902573015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902573015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.95 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha idacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha idacaria (N.L. fem. n. *idacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002725315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001629165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.14 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described

as "Red Sea water column Station 108 - depth 100m".

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha idanella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha idanella (N.L. fem. n. *idanella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002718695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002718695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.73 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha igabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha igabosa (N.L. fem. n. *igabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002713185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002713185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.64 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha mivella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha mivella (N.L. fem. n. *mivella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp001628485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001628485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.98 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Red Sea water column Station 34 - depth 25m".

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha mivia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha mivia (N.L. fem. n. *mivia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002503285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.72 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha mubarica* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha mubarica (N.L. fem. n. *mubarica* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp001629255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902578795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.64 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha ofagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ofagia (N.L. fem. n. *ofagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp001629205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001629205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.9 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Red Sea water column Station 149 - depth 50m".

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha ogebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ogebaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002730445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002730445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.8 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha olabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha olabella (N.L. fem. n. *olabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp003602515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.16 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha oladaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha oladaria (N.L. fem. n. *oladaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp003602595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.88 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha opagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha opagella (N.L. fem. n. *opagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002172185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002689165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.84 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Nefestarcha osagaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha osagaria (N.L. fem. n. *osagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002697065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002697065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.28 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Nefestarcha otxaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha otxaria (N.L. fem. n. *otxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp902601345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902601345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.55 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Nefestarcha ovagosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ovagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ovagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002723045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002723045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.94 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Nefestarcha quafosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha quafosa (N.L. fem. n. *quafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002496485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.18 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha ulabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ulabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ulabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp902625325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902625325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.35 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha ulacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha ulacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ulacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp014239955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014239955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.61 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nefestarcha utagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nefestarcha utagosa (N.L. fem. n. *utagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-O3 sp002722735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.64 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Neglifrarcha ipetia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Neglifrarcha ipetia (N.L. fem. n. *ipetia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXA01 sp018304025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.55 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Neglifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Neglifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Neglifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Neglifrarcha ipetia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nerabrarcha eceposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nerabrarcha eceposa (N.L. fem. n. *eceposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA284 sp018304245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.15 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nerabrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nerabrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nerabrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA284. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nerabrarcha eceposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nerabrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nerabrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Nerabrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nerabrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA284. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Nerabrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pacearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nerabrarcha omevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nerabrarcha omevella (N.L. fem. n. *omevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA284 sp002499185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.26 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nerisarcha edafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nerisarcha edafella (N.L. fem. n. *edafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSVV01 sp011368255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011368255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.61 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Nerisarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Nerisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nerisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSVV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Nerisarcha edafella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nerisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Nerisarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Nerisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nerisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DSVV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Nerisarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Nestodarcha quavosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Nestodarcha quavosa (N.L. fem. n. *quavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEW01 sp017608955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.78 % and the genome length is 0.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Nestodarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Nestodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nestodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JAFCEW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nestodarcha quavosa*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Isoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Niblixarcha ocania* sp. nov.

Candidatus Niblixarcha ocania (N.L. fem. n. *ocania* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZL01 sp018302505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.13 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Niblixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Niblixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Niblixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Niblixarcha ocania*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lagoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Niclaparcha emafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Niclaparcha emafella (N.L. fem. n. *emafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JGI-0000106-J15 sp011363825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011363825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.61 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Niclaparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Niclaparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Niclaparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JGI-0000106-J15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Niclaparcha emafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cesedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Niclaparcha itacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Niclaparcha itacosa (N.L. fem. n. *itacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JGI-0000106-J15 sp011337925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000405685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.87 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Niclaparcha opavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Niclaparcha opavana (N.L. fem. n. *opavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JGI-0000106-J15 sp011375845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011375845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.98 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Niclaparcha upacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Niclaparcha upacaria (N.L. fem. n. *upacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JGI-0000106-J15 sp011364615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.38 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nigodarcha mupia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nigodarcha mupia (N.L. fem. n. *mupia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR11 sp12027u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.76 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nigodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nigodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nigodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR11. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nigodarcha mupia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nigodarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Nigodarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nigodarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR4. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Nigodarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nipetarcha onemana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nipetarcha onemana (N.L. fem. n. *onemana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PNOQ01 sp013824915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013824915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.96 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nipetarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nipetarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nipetarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PNOQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nipetarcha onemana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nipetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nipetarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Nipetarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nipetarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PNOQ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Nipetarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nipetarcha uvafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nipetarcha uvafana (N.L. fem. n. *uvafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PNOQ01 sp018302135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.33 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Niplaprarcha ugeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Niplaprarcha ugeparia (N.L. fem. n. *ugeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKO01 sp014729055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.38 % and the genome length is 5.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Niplaprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Niplaprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Niplaprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJKO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Niplaprarcha ugeparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haxemarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nipreocrarchaifaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nipreocrarchaifaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-71 sp002254395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.36 % and the genome length is 0.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nipreocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nipreocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nipreocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is EX4484-71. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nipreocrarcha efaxella*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nistefrarcha obefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nistefrarcha obefana (N.L. fem. n. *obefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVVV01 sp018304615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.56 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nistefrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nistefrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nistefrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVVV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nistefrarcha obefana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nistufarcha osavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nistufarcha osavaria (N.L. fem. n. *osavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIBT01 sp018652625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018657985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.16 % and the genome length is 0.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nistufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nistufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nistufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABIBT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nistufarcha osavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nipetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Niterarcha udagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Niterarcha udagella (N.L. fem. n. *udagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKGA01 sp007117735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007117735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.4 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Niterarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Niterarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Niterarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SKGA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Niterarcha udagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Niterarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Niterarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Niterarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Niterarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SKGA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Niterarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Niterarcha ugafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Niterarcha ugafia (N.L. fem. n. *ugafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKGA01 sp016926395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.16 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitigarcha egapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitigarcha egapella (N.L. fem. n. *egapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTGE01 sp011389385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011389385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.47 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitigarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nitigarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nitigarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTGE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nitigarcha egapella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitigarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nitigarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Nitigarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nitigarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTGE01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Nitigarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omubarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nitigarcha ivamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitigarcha ivamella (N.L. fem. n. *ivamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTGE01 sp018396725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.83 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum eracaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum eracaria (N.L. fem. n. *eracaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp018334095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018334095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.54 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum etamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum etamia (N.L. fem. n. *etamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp009697485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009697485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.31 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ifaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ifaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp004297665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016186075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.18 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ivetaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ivetaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivetaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp012030815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012030815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.45 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum obagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum obagia (N.L. fem. n. *obagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp003569705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003569705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.0 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ofarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ofarella (N.L. fem. n. *ofarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp002737445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016106185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.13 % and the genome

length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ogepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ogepella (N.L. fem. n. *ogepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp016844465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016844465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.3 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum quebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum quebana (N.L. fem. n. *quebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp016234975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016234975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.56 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum usavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum usavaria (N.L. fem. n. *usavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp013140415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013140415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.15 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum utagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum utagella (N.L. fem. n. *utagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum sp005798405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005798995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.25 % and the genome length is 0.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ogedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum ogedana (N.L. fem. n. *ogedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Nitrosarchaeum_A sp018128925. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_018128925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.86 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum oraxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosarchaeum oraxaria (N.L. fem. n. *oraxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosarchaeum_A sp002781805. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002781805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.07 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocaldus inegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocaldus inegana (N.L. fem. n. *inegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocaldus sp013538675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013538675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.77 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocaldus ufepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocaldus ufepana (N.L. fem. n. *ufepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocaldus sp002898655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002898655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.77 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocaldus uvadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocaldus uvadana (N.L. fem. n. *uvadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocaldus sp013538805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013538805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.96 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus apevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus apevosa (N.L. fem. n. *apevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocosmicus sp013694585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013694585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.61 % and the genome length is 2.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus emalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus emalosa (N.L. fem. n. *emalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocosmicus sp008389435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_008389435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.43 % and the genome length is 3.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus enagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus enagaria (N.L. fem. n. *enagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocosmicus sp016782315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016782265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.65 % and the genome length is 1.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus ifedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus ifedella (N.L. fem. n. *ifedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocosmicus sp013821245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013821245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.07 % and the genome length is 2.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus igapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus igapana (N.L. fem. n. *igapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocosmicus sp009379865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009379865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.53 % and the genome

length is 3.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus unagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus unagana (N.L. fem. n. *unagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocosmicus sp016782225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016782225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.62 % and the genome length is 2.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus usaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosocosmicus usaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *usaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosocosmicus sp013114705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013114705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.31 % and the genome length is 2.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus adeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus adeparia (N.L. fem. n. *adeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp001510295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001510295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.48 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Capian Sea".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus afacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus afacia (N.L. fem. n. *afacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902578515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002709285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.44 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ebacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ebacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp018263495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018263495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.72 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ebavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ebavella (N.L. fem. n. *ebavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902512865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902512865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.07 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ecabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ecabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp002698885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002698885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.65 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus efabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus efabia (N.L. fem. n. *efabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp012964965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012964965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.81 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus efanaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus efanaria (N.L. fem. n. *efanaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp000484935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013390385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.02 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus emefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus emefella (N.L. fem. n. *emefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp013390785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013390785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.21 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus epebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus epebaria (N.L. fem. n. *epebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp013390745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013390745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.54 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus gexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus gexia (N.L. fem. n. *gexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp018647405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018647405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.66 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus icabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus icabaria (N.L. fem. n. *icabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902566725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902566725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.86 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus icavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus icavana (N.L. fem. n. *icavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp000402075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014384145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.8 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus igepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus igepella (N.L. fem. n. *igepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902590655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902590655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.51 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ipegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ipegia (N.L. fem. n. *ipegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902608175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902608175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.89 % and the genome length is 0.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ivadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ivadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp001627235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001627235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.05 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Red Sea water column Station 149 - depth 100m".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ivedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus ivedaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp000746705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000746705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.68 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "single cell amplified by MDA; Atlantis II deep Red Sea brine-seawater interface".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus opaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus opaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *opaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902606945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902606945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.66 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus otevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus otevaria (N.L. fem. n. *otevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902606965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902606965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.45 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus phabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus phabosa (N.L. fem. n. *phabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902511735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902511735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.6 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus quavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus quavaria (N.L. fem. n. *quavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp902552015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902552015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.61 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus udafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus udafana (N.L. fem. n. *udafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp013390765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013390765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.6 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus vucosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopelagicus vucosa (N.L. fem. n. *vucosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopelagicus sp018691945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018661625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.03 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus afevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus afevia (N.L. fem. n. *afevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp007571225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007571225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.87 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus anacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus anacella (N.L. fem. n. *anacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp900620265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900620265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.82 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus apegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus apegana (N.L. fem. n. *apegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp002788515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002788515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.75 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus asagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus asagana (N.L. fem. n. *asagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp905616385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905620515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.87 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus asavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus asavana (N.L. fem. n. *asavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp013043295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013043295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.28 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ebasaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ebasaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebasaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp002690535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002690535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.05 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ecalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ecalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp018668425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018661305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.85 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus edagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus edagaria (N.L. fem. n. *edagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp003702495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003702495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.55 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus emafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus emafana (N.L. fem. n. *emafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp013911135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013911135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.27 % and the genome

length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus enaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus enaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *enaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp008080815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008080815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.56 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus enaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus enaxella (N.L. fem. n. *enaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp905612295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905612295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.4 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus epaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus epaxana (N.L. fem. n. *epaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp000484975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000484975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.37 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus esabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus esabosa (N.L. fem. n. *esabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp014075315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011087695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.44 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus etafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus etafana (N.L. fem. n. *etafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Nitrosopumilus sp003724285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003724235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.21 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus etavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus etavella (N.L. fem. n. *etavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp001543015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001543015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.64 % and the genome length is 1.93 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "glass sponge collected from seamount of South China Sea".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus eveparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus eveparia (N.L. fem. n. *eveparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp013203245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013203245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.74 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus gexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus gexana (N.L. fem. n. *gexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp018674605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018696375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.38 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus idalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus idalosa (N.L. fem. n. *idalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp014078525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_014078525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.35 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus imabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus imabaria (N.L. fem. n. *imabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp003702545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003702545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.87 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus imadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus imadaria (N.L. fem. n. *imadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp007571135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007571005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.9 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus iraxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus iraxosa (N.L. fem. n. *iraxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp003702525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003702525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.53 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ivacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ivacana (N.L. fem. n. *ivacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp013867245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013867245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.65 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ivadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ivadella (N.L. fem. n. *ivadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp001437625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.26 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ivaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ivaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp002317795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002317795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.44 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ivetia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ivetia (N.L. fem. n. *ivetia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp905612275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905612275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.66 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus mivaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus mivaria (N.L. fem. n. *mivaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp013390905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013390395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.18 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus muvella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus muvella (N.L. fem. n. *muvella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp000746765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000722915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.21 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "single cell amplified by MDA; Atlantis II Deep Red Sea brine-seawater interface".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ofavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ofavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Nitrosopumilus* sp014384555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016784665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.31 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ofebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ofebia (N.L. fem. n. *ofebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Nitrosopumilus* sp902514275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902514275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.0 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ofegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ofegana (N.L. fem. n. *ofegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Nitrosopumilus* sp018263505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018263505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.22 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ogaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ogaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ogaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Nitrosopumilus* sp003175215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003175215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.84 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ogavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ogavia (N.L. fem. n. *ogavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Nitrosopumilus* sp002730325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002730325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.66 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ogavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ogavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp905479565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905479565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.62 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus omacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus omacaria (N.L. fem. n. *omacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp014384445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014384445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.97 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus omavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus omavosa (N.L. fem. n. *omavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp003702465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003702465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.91 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus onadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus onadana (N.L. fem. n. *onadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp002506665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.3 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus orafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus orafana (N.L. fem. n. *orafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp003724325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003724325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.91 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus osafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus osafella (N.L. fem. n. *osafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp018657375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018653745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.92 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus otavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus otavaria (N.L. fem. n. *otavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp902514095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902514095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.4 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ovabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ovabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ovabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp001541925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001541925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.4 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ucenana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ucenana (N.L. fem. n. *ucenana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp016125975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016125975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.59 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ufexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ufexaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp001510275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001510275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.77 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type

genome is described as "Capian Sea".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ulavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus ulavia (N.L. fem. n. *ulavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp016784625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016784625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.2 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus umenella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus umenella (N.L. fem. n. *umenella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp013002265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013002265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.89 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus umexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus umexosa (N.L. fem. n. *umexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp013215285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013215285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.98 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus upexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus upexaria (N.L. fem. n. *upexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp006740685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_006740685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.76 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus utacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus utacana (N.L. fem. n. *utacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Nitrosopumilus sp905612485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905620485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.54 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosopumilus vubosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosopumilus vubosa (N.L. fem. n. *vubosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosopumilus sp002737455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001510225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.33 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Capian Sea".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrososphaera ecedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrososphaera ecedana (N.L. fem. n. *ecedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrososphaera sp002494895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.69 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrososphaera igaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrososphaera igaposa (N.L. fem. n. *igaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrososphaera sp013114715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013114715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.23 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrososphaera ubavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrososphaera ubavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ubavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrososphaera sp013388945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013388945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.54 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrososphaera vubia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrososphaera vubia (N.L. fem. n. *vubia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrososphaera sp002501845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002508435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.14 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotalea ebaiana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotalea ebaiana (N.L. fem. n. *ebaiana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotalea sp007280465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007280465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.1 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotalea epafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotalea epafosa (N.L. fem. n. *epafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotalea sp013288545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013288545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.81 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotalea erepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotalea erepana (N.L. fem. n. *erepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotalea sp011319475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_011319475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.8 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotalea etarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotalea etarana (N.L. fem. n. *etarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotalea sp011319465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_011319465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.09 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotalea ifavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotalea ifavia (N.L. fem. n. *ifavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotalea sp001920395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001920395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.08 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Soil sample from Angelo meadow plot 1; 20cm depth; 4 days after first rain event (27mm)".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotalea ofaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotalea ofaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotalea sp001917995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001917995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.21 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Soil sample from Angelo meadow plot 1; 40cm depth; 2 days after first rain event (91mm)".

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotalea uraposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotalea uraposa (N.L. fem. n. *uraposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotalea sp005877205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005877205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.69 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis amacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis amacana (N.L. fem. n. *amacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp016215465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016215465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.87 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis efaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis efaxana (N.L. fem. n. *efaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp016872055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016872055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.26 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis gexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis gexella (N.L. fem. n. *gexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp010028495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_010028425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.07 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis itecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis itecosa (N.L. fem. n. *itecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp013407275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_013407275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.25 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis mubia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis mubia (N.L. fem. n. *mubia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp002499525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.08 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis olacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis olacella (N.L. fem. n. *olacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp016872015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016872015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.26 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis omeperia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis omeperia (N.L. fem. n. *omeperia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp004322465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004322465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.65 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis ucatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis ucatella (N.L. fem. n. *ucatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp900299125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900299125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.39 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis unapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis unapia (N.L. fem. n. *unapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp005240025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005240025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.26 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nitrosotenuis uvafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nitrosotenuis uvafia (N.L. fem. n. *uvafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Nitrosotenuis sp016844685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016844685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.53 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nobrusarcha acavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nobrusarcha acavosa (N.L. fem. n. *acavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRVV01 sp011373895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011388725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.7 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nobrusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nobrusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nobrusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRVV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nobrusarcha acavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nobrusarcha afacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nobrusarcha afacella (N.L. fem. n. *afacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRVV01 sp011373445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011046575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.95 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Noclufarcha etarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Noclufarcha etarella (N.L. fem. n. *etarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKIS01 sp007117755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007117755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.69 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Noclufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Noclufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Noclufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SKIS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Noclufarcha etarella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Siluxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Noclufarcha ofamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Noclufarcha ofamia (N.L. fem. n. *ofamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKIS01 sp007116295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007116295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.26 % and the genome length is 0.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Noclufarcha ugacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Noclufarcha ugacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ugacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKIS01 sp007117145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007117145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.99 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nodrifarcha edapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nodrifarcha edapella (N.L. fem. n. *edapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JWKY01 sp016176815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.94 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nodrifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nodrifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nodrifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JWKY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Nodrifarcha edapella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nodrifarcha ogafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nodrifarcha ogafana (N.L. fem. n. *ogafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JWKY01 sp000806015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000806015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.12 % and the genome length is 0.68 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle groundwater metagenome at time 1".

Description of *Candidatus Nodristarcha odegaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nodristarcha odegaria (N.L. fem. n. *odegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIWSB01 sp903915225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903915225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.54 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nodristarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nodristarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nodristarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIWSB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nodristarcha odegaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Febimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nodroxarcha uraxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nodroxarcha uraxella (N.L. fem. n. *uraxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJFH01 sp018824925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018812445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.72 % and the genome length is 2.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nodroxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nodroxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nodroxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJFH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nodroxarcha uraxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nogelarcha ilafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nogelarcha ilafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ilafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688035 sp002688035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.28 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nogelarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nogelarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nogelarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2688035. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Nogelarcha ilafaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nogelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nogelarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Nogelarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nogelarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-2688035. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Nogelarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nopostarcha ocamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nopostarcha ocamella (N.L. fem. n. *ocamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S012-22 sp015523445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.02 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nopostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nopostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nopostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S012-22. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Nopostarcha ocamella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Acidilobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Noradarcha ategella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Noradarcha ategella (N.L. fem. n. *ategella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-217-1 sp002254745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.23 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Noradarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Noradarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Noradarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-217-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Noradarcha ategella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Noradarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Noradarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Noradarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Noradarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-217-1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Noradarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Noradarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Noradarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Noradarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Noradarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-217-1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Noradarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoproteia*.

Description of *Candidatus Norongarragalina ufataria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Norongarragalina ufataria (N.L. fem. n. *ufataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Norongarragalina sp002763345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002763345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.18 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Notrasarcha ucedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Notrasarcha ucedana (N.L. fem. n. *ucedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRPH01 sp016213985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016213985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.72 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Notrasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Notrasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Notrasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRPH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Notrasarcha ucedana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Notrasarcha umabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Notrasarcha umabia (N.L. fem. n. *umabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRPH01 sp016214025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016214025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.32 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nudoxarcha cuxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nudoxarcha cuxia (N.L. fem. n. *cuxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR17 sp10136u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.29 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nudoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nudoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nudoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nudoxarcha cuxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nudoxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Nudoxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nudoxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GW2011-AR17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Nudoxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nudoxarcha ebavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nudoxarcha ebavana (N.L. fem. n. *ebavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR17 sp009691355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009691355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.33 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nudoxarcha ovamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nudoxarcha ovamia (N.L. fem. n. *ovamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR17 sp016235495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016235495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.25 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nufagarcha esafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nufagarcha esafosa (N.L. fem. n. *esafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIVOO01 sp903907555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903892325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.23 % and the genome length is 1.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nufagarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nufagarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nufagarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIVOO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nufagarcha esafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nufagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nufagarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Nufagarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nufagarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CAIVOO01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Nufagarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nufotrarcha egacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nufotrarcha egacia (N.L. fem. n. *egacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSDF01 sp011048835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011048835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.25 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nufotrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nufotrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nufotrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSDF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nufotrarcha egacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomicrobiaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nufotrarcha omacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nufotrarcha omacia (N.L. fem. n. *omacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSDF01 sp016841665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016841665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.95 % and the genome length is 2.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nugitrarcha esalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nugitrarcha esalosa (N.L. fem. n. *esalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPBS01 sp016180195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.64 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nugitrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nugitrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nugitrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPBS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nugitrarcha esalosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha anabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha anabia (N.L. fem. n. *anabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002712645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002712645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.62 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nulutrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is MGIIb-N1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nulutrarcha anabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thalassarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha asafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha asafia (N.L. fem. n. *asafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002717835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002717835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.03 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha duvosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha duvosa (N.L. fem. n. *duvosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002505695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002685735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.87 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha ebadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha ebadella (N.L. fem. n. *ebadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002504845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.46 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha gexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha gexaria (N.L. fem. n. *gexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002499585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.64 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha guxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha guxia (N.L. fem. n. *guxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp011523055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011523055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.62 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha idacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha idacella (N.L. fem. n. *idacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002505455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002686775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.85 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha isadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha isadosa (N.L. fem. n. *isadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002170775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002170775.2. The GC content of the type genome is 49.39 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha obefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha obefia (N.L. fem. n. *obefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002507175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002507175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.76 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha ocabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha ocabella (N.L. fem. n. *ocabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002495675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.11 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nulutrarcha unaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nulutrarcha unaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *unaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N1 sp002497295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.19 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nupofarcha egamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nupofarcha egamana (N.L. fem. n. *egamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-31-34 sp018829335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018826425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.52 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nupofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nupofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nupofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 1-14-0-10-31-34. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nupofarcha egamana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nupofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nupofarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Nupofarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Nupofarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is 1-14-0-10-31-34. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Nupofarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Nupofarcha inaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nupofarcha inaxana (N.L. fem. n. *inaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-31-34 sp002763225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002763225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.85 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nupofarcha orabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nupofarcha orabana (N.L. fem. n. *orabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-31-34 sp017609625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.72 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nusadrarcha enacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nusadrarcha enacella (N.L. fem. n. *enacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTU008 sp002498285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.04 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nusadrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nusadrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nusadrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTU008. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nusadrarcha enacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomassiliicoccaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nusadrarcha epecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nusadrarcha epecana (N.L. fem. n. *epecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTU008 sp012518185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012518185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.96 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nusadrarcha gixosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nusadrarcha gixosa (N.L. fem. n. *gixosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTU008 sp002504525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.08 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nusadrarcha ibacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nusadrarcha ibacella (N.L. fem. n. *ibacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTU008 sp001512965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001512965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.82 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "pool of bioreactors CSTR01a; CSTR02a; and CSTR03a; thermophilic anaerobic digestion of cattle manure in continuous reactors for biogas production (methane)".

Description of *Candidatus Nusadrarcha ocanana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nusadrarcha ocanana (N.L. fem. n. *ocanana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTU008 sp012519255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012519255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.5 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nusadrarcha ubefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nusadrarcha ubefosa (N.L. fem. n. *ubefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTU008 sp001421185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001421185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.09 % and the genome length is 2.12 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "enrichment culture inoculated with rumen fluid from *Bos taurus*".

Description of *Candidatus Nustitrarcha erabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nustitrarcha erabia (N.L. fem. n. *erabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is LC-2 sp001940725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001940725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.64 % and the genome length is 4.84 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "LokiAmp MDA-amplified sample from Loki s castle hydrothermal vent sediment".

Description of *Candidatus Nustitrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nustitrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nustitrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is LC-2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nustitrarcha erabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Kariarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nutrorarcha irafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nutrorarcha irafia (N.L. fem. n. *irafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S143-63 sp015521115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.26 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nutrorarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Nutrorarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Nutrorarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S143-63. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Nutrorarcha irafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Acidilobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Nutrorarcha odabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nutrorarcha odabana (N.L. fem. n. *odabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S143-63 sp015521185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.25 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Nutrorarcha opaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Nutrorarcha opaxana (N.L. fem. n. *opaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S143-63 sp015521095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.35 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Oblenarcha ucagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oblenarcha ucagia (N.L. fem. n. *ucagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B69-G16 sp003649235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.87 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Oblenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Oblenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Oblenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B69-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Oblenarcha ucagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Oblenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Oblenarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Oblenarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Oblenarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B69-G16. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Oblenarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Thermofilales*.

Description of *Candidatus Oclimarcha cuxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oclimarcha cuxosa (N.L. fem. n. *cuxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA57 sp002494565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.54 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Oclimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Oclimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Oclimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA57. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Oclimarcha cuxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Oclimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Oclimarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Oclimarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Oclimarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA57. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Oclimarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Oclimarcha esafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oclimarcha esafia (N.L. fem. n. *esafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA57 sp002495905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002717165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.07 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Oclimarcha ifesaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oclimarcha ifesaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifesaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA57 sp002713205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002713205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.06 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Oclimarcha iraxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oclimarcha iraxella (N.L. fem. n. *iraxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA57 sp013378385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013378385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.02 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Oclimarcha ugapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oclimarcha ugapia (N.L. fem. n. *ugapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA57 sp002693165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013378375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.32 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ocuparcha ecasella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ocuparcha ecasella (N.L. fem. n. *ecasella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SG8-5 sp001595885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001595885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.51 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-rich zone estuary sediments 8-12 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Ocuparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ocuparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ocuparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SG8-5. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ocuparcha ecasella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ocuparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ocuparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ocuparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ocuparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SG8-5. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Ocuparcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ocuparchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Ocuparchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Ocuparchales (N.L. fem. n. *Ocuparchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SG8-5. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Ocuparcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus* Oferarcha ifetia sp. nov.

Candidatus Oferarcha ifetia (N.L. fem. n. *ifetia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B1Sed10-29 sp003551125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003551125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.37 % and the genome length is 0.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Oferarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Oferarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Oferarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B1Sed10-29. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Oferarcha ifetia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Oferarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Oferarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Oferarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Oferarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B1Sed10-29. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Oferarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Oferarchales.

Description of *Candidatus Oferarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Oferarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Oferarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B1Sed10-29. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Oferarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Oferarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Oferarchota* phyl. nov.

Candidatus Oferarchota (N.L. fem. n. *Oferarchota* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B1Sed10-29. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Oferarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this phylum belongs to the domain *Archaea*.

Description of *Candidatus Oferarcha ogefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oferarcha ogefosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B1Sed10-29 sp003553825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003553825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.44 % and the genome length is 0.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha atafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha atafana (N.L. fem. n. *atafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABLT101 sp016840945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.7 % and the genome length is 4.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ofraparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the

phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABLT101. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ofraparcha atafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ofraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ofraparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JABLT101. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ofraparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ofraparchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparchales (N.L. fem. n. *Ofraparchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JABLT101. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ofraparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Heimdallarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha epafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha epafia (N.L. fem. n. *epafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABLT101 sp019058275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.46 % and the genome length is 4.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha epegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha epegana (N.L. fem. n. *epegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JABLT101 sp016839405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.02 % and the genome length is 3.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha etamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha etamana (N.L. fem. n. *etamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABLT101 sp018238155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018238155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.79 % and the genome length is 4.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha icanosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha icanosa (N.L. fem. n. *icanosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABLT101 sp019056785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019056785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.58 % and the genome length is 2.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha iraxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha iraxaria (N.L. fem. n. *iraxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABLT101 sp019058165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.77 % and the genome length is 3.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha obamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha obamosa (N.L. fem. n. *obamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABLT101 sp016840905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.06 % and the genome length is 2.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ofraparcha usabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ofraparcha usabaria (N.L. fem. n. *usabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABLT101 sp013166835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013166835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.72 % and the genome length is 3.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Oglafarcha etecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oglafarcha etecosa (N.L. fem. n. *etecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SW-7-71-33 sp003023195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.42 % and the genome length is 3.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Oglafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Oglafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Oglafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SW-7-71-33. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Oglafarcha etecosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Oglafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Oglafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Oglafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Oglafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SW-7-71-33. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Oglafarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Halobacteriales*.

Description of *Candidatus Oglafarcha upamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Oglafarcha upamaria (N.L. fem. n. *upamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SW-7-71-33 sp003022865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 71.17 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ogusarcha acavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ogusarcha acavia (N.L. fem. n. *acavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SCGC-AAA011-G17 sp000402515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000380905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.95 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ogusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ogusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ogusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SCGC-AAA011-G17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ogusarcha acavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ogusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ogusarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ogusarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ogusarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SCGC-AAA011-G17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ogusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ogusarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Ogusarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Ogusarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SCGC-AAA011-G17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ogusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Nanoarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Omagarcha ofavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omagarcha ofavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B26-1 sp001593925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001593925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.68 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "marine sediment sample collected by push cores at a deep sea vent site during cruise AT15-25 on Alvin dive 4358; sediment was oily and the sediment surface was covered with a white microbial mat".

Description of *Candidatus Omagarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Omagarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Omagarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B26-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Omagarcha ofavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Omagarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Omagarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Omagarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B26-1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Omagarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omagarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Omagarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Omagarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Omagarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B26-1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Omagarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Bathyarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Omagarcha ovaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omagarcha ovaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ovaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B26-1 sp001593935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001593935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.92 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "marine sediment sample collected by push cores at a deep sea vent site during cruise AT15-25 on Alvin dive 4358; sediment was oily and the sediment surface was covered with a white microbial mat".

Description of *Candidatus Omexarcha quafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omexarcha quafaria (N.L. fem. n. *quafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B24 sp001593865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.93 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Omexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Omexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B24. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Omexarcha quafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Omexarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Omexarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Omexarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B24. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Omexarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omexarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Omexarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Omexarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Omexarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B24. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Omexarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Bathyarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha asafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha asafaria (N.L. fem. n. *asafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005884195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005884195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.91 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Omubarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 40CM-2-53-6. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Omubarcha asafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omubarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Omubarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Omubarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is 40CM-2-53-6. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Omubarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omubarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Omubarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Omubarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is 40CM-2-53-6. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Omubarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Bathyarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha ebasana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha ebasana (N.L. fem. n. *ebasana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005882895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005882885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.18 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha efalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha efalia (N.L. fem. n. *efalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp002495485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.1 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha efavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha efavaria (N.L. fem. n. *efavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp001919285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005884635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.02 % and the genome length is 2.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha epecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha epecia (N.L. fem. n. *epecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005884605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005884605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.84 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha etavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha etavaria (N.L. fem. n. *etavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005881695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005881695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.16 % and the genome

length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha evecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha evecana (N.L. fem. n. *evecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005888755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005888755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.98 % and the genome length is 2.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha evegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha evegosa (N.L. fem. n. *evegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005881615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005881615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.92 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha igeposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha igeposa (N.L. fem. n. *igeposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005882955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005882955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.88 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha ileparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha ileparia (N.L. fem. n. *ileparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005888745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005888745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.72 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha odagara* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha odagara (N.L. fem. n. *odagara* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005883075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005884215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.88 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha onadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha onadaria (N.L. fem. n. *onadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp001918745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001918745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.8 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Soil sample from Angelo meadow plot 1; 40cm depth; 6 days after first rain event (27mm)".

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha oragana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha oragana (N.L. fem. n. *oragana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005888635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005888635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.95 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha ovelella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha ovelella (N.L. fem. n. *ovelella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005883085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005883085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.03 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha unegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha unegosa (N.L. fem. n. *unegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005883695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005883695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.02 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha upagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha upagosa (N.L. fem. n. *upagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp001915065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001920575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.31 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Soil sample from Angelo meadow plot 1; 20cm depth; 4 days after first rain event (27mm)".

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha urapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha urapana (N.L. fem. n. *urapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp001918765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001918765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.94 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Soil sample from Angelo meadow plot 1; 40cm depth; 6 days after first rain event (27mm)".

Description of *Candidatus Omubarcha utaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Omubarcha utaxella (N.L. fem. n. *utaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 40CM-2-53-6 sp005882905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005881655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.34 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ostegarcha ulavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ostegarcha ulavana (N.L. fem. n. *ulavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXY01 sp018303545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.92 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ostegarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ostegarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ostegarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ostegarcha ulavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ostegarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ostegarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ostegarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ostegarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVXY01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ostegarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Otrunarcha itacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Otrunarcha itacia (N.L. fem. n. *itacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B9-G17 sp003649225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.23 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Otrunarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Otrunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Otrunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B9-G17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Otrunarcha itacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Otrunarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Otrunarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Otrunarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Otrunarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B9-G17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Otrunarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Thermofilales.

Description of *Candidatus Pacredarcha obafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pacredarcha obafosa (N.L. fem. n. *obafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMWT01 sp003661775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.31 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pacredarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pacredarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pacredarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMWT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pacredarcha obafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ignisphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pacredarcha ofabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pacredarcha ofabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMWT01 sp003661865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.11 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Padragarcha ifamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Padragarcha ifamaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPII01 sp016188175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.12 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Padragarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Padragarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Padragarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPII01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Padreprarcha ifamaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hocularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Padreprarcha apafana sp. nov.

Candidatus Padreprarcha apafana (N.L. fem. n. *apafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOXZ01 sp018221085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.13 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Padreprarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Padreprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Padreprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOXZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Padreprarcha apafana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Pafrosarcha ifetosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Pafrosarcha ifetosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifetosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALR01 sp015522765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.75 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Pafrosarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Pafrosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pafrosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pafrosarcha ifetosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Pafrosarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Pafrosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pafrosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pafrosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WALR01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pafrosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pafrucarcha uvadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pafrucarcha uvadella (N.L. fem. n. *uvadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-000496135 sp000496135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.27 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pafrucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pafrucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pafrucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-000496135. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pafrucarcha uvadella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermoplasmataceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pafruprarcha adepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pafruprarcha adepana (N.L. fem. n. *adepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B17-G17 sp003662645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003662645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.1 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pafruprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pafruprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pafruprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B17-G17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pafruprarcha adepana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Palaeococcus ebasosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Palaeococcus ebasosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebasosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Palaeococcus sp003663695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.59 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Paneprrarcha itafella sp. nov.

Candidatus Paneprrarcha itafella (N.L. fem. n. *itafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAOL01 sp015521295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.63 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Paneprrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Paneprrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Paneprrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAOL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Paneprrarcha itafella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Zestosphaeraceae*@.

Description of *Candidatus* Parutarcha ebatana sp. nov.

Candidatus Parutarcha ebatana (N.L. fem. n. *ebatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-43 sp002011355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_002011355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.88 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Parutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Parutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Parutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-43. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Parutarcha ebatana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Parutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Parutarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Parutarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Parutarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JdFR-43. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Parutarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Enedarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pasoprarcha uravosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pasoprarcha uravosa (N.L. fem. n. *uravosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAOK01 sp015521325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.62 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pasoprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pasoprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pasoprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAOK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pasoprarcha uravosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Zestosphaeraceae@*.

Description of *Candidatus Patresarcha efadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Patresarcha efadaria (N.L. fem. n. *efadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQSW01 sp016211095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016211095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.93 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Patresarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Patresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Patresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQSW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Patresarcha efadaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Patrirarcha ecafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Patrirarcha ecafia (N.L. fem. n. *ecafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Tc-Br11-E2g1 sp001564255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001564255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.49 % and the genome length is 2.16 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample Tc-Br; brine of Tanatar trona crystallizer".

Description of *Candidatus Patrirarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Patrirarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Patrirarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Tc-Br11-E2g1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Patrirarcha ecafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natrialbaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Patrostarcha ulacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Patrostarcha ulacia (N.L. fem. n. *ulacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDT01 sp017609525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.91 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Patrostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Patrostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Patrostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Patrostarcha ulacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Paxotarcha enacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Paxotarcha enacia (N.L. fem. n. *enacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AG1 sp011056395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011056395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.83 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Paxotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Paxotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Paxotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is AG1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Paxotarcha enacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Paxotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Paxotarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Paxotarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Paxotarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is AG1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Paxotarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Sulfolobales*.

Description of *Candidatus Paxotarcha unadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Paxotarcha unadosa (N.L. fem. n. *unadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AG1 sp003116855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009889545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.33 % and the genome length is 2.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pecrucrarcha iveparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pecrucrarcha iveparia (N.L. fem. n. *iveparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS150m-G67 sp016784085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016784085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.49 % and the genome length is 0.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pecrucrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pecrucrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pecrucrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BS150m-G67. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pecrucrarcha iveparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pefridarcha ocevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pefridarcha ocevella (N.L. fem. n. *ocevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHLMP01 sp018920315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018920315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.87 % and the genome length is 0.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pefridarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pefridarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pefridarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JAHLMP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pefridarcha ocevella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pefridarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Pefridarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Pefridarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pefridarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHLMP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Pefridarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Coxosarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Pegistarcha efanía sp. nov.

Candidatus Pegistarcha efanía (N.L. fem. n. *efanía* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WANO01 sp015521765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.64 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Pegistarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Pegistarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pegistarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WANO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pegistarcha efanía.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Paxotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Pemitrarcha ivaxia sp. nov.

Candidatus Pemitrarcha ivaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ivaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRYM01 sp011375895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011375895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.56 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pemitrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pemitrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pemitrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRYM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pemitrarcha ivaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Noradarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha erebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha erebana (N.L. fem. n. *erebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10216 sp016180065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.58 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Penularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10216. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Penularcha erebana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Penularchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Penularchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Penularchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10216. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Penularcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha evafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha evafana (N.L. fem. n. *evafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10216 sp016184345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016184345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.18 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha icafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha icafaria (N.L. fem. n. *icafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10216 sp10216u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.41 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha ogadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha ogadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10216 sp016188145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.82 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha otafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha otafella (N.L. fem. n. *otafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10216 sp016192915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016192915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.69 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha ufacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha ufacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10216 sp016180105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.43 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha umegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha umegana (N.L. fem. n. *umegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10216 sp016180085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.72 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Penularcha unarosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Penularcha unarosa (N.L. fem. n. *unarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10216 sp016188155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.86 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Peplifarcha ecasosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Peplifarcha ecasosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecasosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOJA01 sp014859805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014859805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.11 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Peplifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Peplifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Peplifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SOJA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Peplifarcha ecasosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Peplifarcha quavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Peplifarcha quavella (N.L. fem. n. *quavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOJA01 sp004376975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004376975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.87 % and the genome length is

1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pepruprarcha atedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pepruprarcha atedana (N.L. fem. n. *atedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPBJ01 sp016180375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.79 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pepruprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pepruprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pepruprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPBJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pepruprarcha atedana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Oclimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Petregrarcha imecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Petregrarcha imecosa (N.L. fem. n. *imecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S146-127 sp015520375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.51 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Petregrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Petregrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Petregrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S146-127. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Petregrarcha imecosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cesedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phabigarchaifaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phabigarchaifaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-11 sp002011035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002009985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.79 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phabigarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phabigarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phabigarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-11. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phabigarcha afaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Honifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phacrenarcha itedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phacrenarcha itedia (N.L. fem. n. *itedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQNI01 sp016203135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.96 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phacrenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phacrenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phacrenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQNI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phacrenarcha itedia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phadabarcha ipavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phadabarcha ipavella (N.L. fem. n. *ipavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGRO01 sp016935095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.64 % and the genome length is 1.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phadabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phadabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phadabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGRO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phadabarcha ipavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hudomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phadefarcha etararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phadefarcha etararia (N.L. fem. n. *etararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO10 sp014361445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.94 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phadefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phadefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phadefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WYZ-LMO10. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phadefarcha etararia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylicaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phadefarcha omabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phadefarcha omabaria (N.L. fem. n. *omabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO10 sp011362965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011362965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.39 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phadefarcha ucamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phadefarcha ucamella (N.L. fem. n. *ucamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO10 sp004347955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004347955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.26 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phadramarcha ifetella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phadramarcha ifetella (N.L. fem. n. *ifetella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QBUR01 sp013374385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013374385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.27 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phadramarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phadramarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phadramarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QBUR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phadramarcha ifetella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanocomedenaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phafatarcha ibalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phafatarcha ibalaria (N.L. fem. n. *ibalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGGZ01 sp016939415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016939415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.42 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phafatarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phafatarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phafatarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGGZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phafatarcha ibalaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Astofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phafebarcha acevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phafebarcha acevella (N.L. fem. n. *acevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKXI01 sp007128515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007128515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.45 % and the genome length is 2.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phafebarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phafebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phafebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SKXI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phafebarcha acevella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Halalkalicoccaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phafebarcha icagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phafebarcha icagosa (N.L. fem. n. *icagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKXI01 sp007129135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007131485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.08 % and the genome length is 2.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phafilarcha opamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phafilarcha opamella (N.L. fem. n. *opamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is A05DMB-2 sp018475625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018475625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.71 % and the genome length is 2.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phafilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phafilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phafilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is A05DMB-2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phagutarcha opamella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phagutarcha atedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phagutarcha atedella (N.L. fem. n. *atedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACAEJ01 sp013388925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013388925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.02 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phagutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phagutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phagutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACAEJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phagutarcha atedella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Phagutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phagutarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Phagutarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Phagutarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACAEJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Phagutarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Phagutarcha edefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phagutarcha edefella (N.L. fem. n. *edefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACAEJ01 sp011358735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011358735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.91 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phalibarcha udagara* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phalibarcha udagara (N.L. fem. n. *udagara* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is KZCA124 sp017357405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_017357405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 63.39 % and the genome length is 5.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phalibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phalibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phalibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is KZCA124. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phalibarcha udagara*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natrialbaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phaplufarcha iperia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phaplufarcha iperia (N.L. fem. n. *iperia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXZ01 sp018303515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.3 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phaplufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phaplufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phaplufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phaplufarcha iperia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Deraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pharidarcha emavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pharidarcha emavella (N.L. fem. n. *emavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXM01 sp018304055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.48 % and the genome length is 1.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pharidarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pharidarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pharidarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pharidarcha emavella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pharidarcha eregaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pharidarcha eregaria (N.L. fem. n. *eregaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXM01 sp018303785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.23 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phastobarcha umefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phastobarcha umefosa (N.L. fem. n. *umefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-37 sp002010215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002010215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.81 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phastobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phastobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phastobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-37. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Phastobarcha umefosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Archaeoglobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phebrocarcha ivetella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phebrocarcha ivetella (N.L. fem. n. *ivetella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QS-4-69-31 sp003021655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.03 % and the genome length is 2.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phebrocarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phebrocarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phebrocarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QS-4-69-31. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phebrocarcha ivetella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloarculaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phecimarcha gexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecimarcha gexosa (N.L. fem. n. *gexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA412 sp002495685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002508885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.06 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phecimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phecimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phecimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA412. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phecimarcha gexosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanobacteriaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phecorarcha acafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha acafia (N.L. fem. n. *acafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp014384685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014384685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.75 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phecorarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phecorarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIb-Q1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phecorarcha acafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thalassarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phecorarcha avaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha avaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *avaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp018650285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018650285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.61 % and the genome length is 2.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phecorarcha evebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha evebosa (N.L. fem. n. *evebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp002505495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.79 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phecorarcha itafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha itafia (N.L. fem. n. *itafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp002685895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002685895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.98 % and the genome length is 1.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phecorarcha oladosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha oladosa (N.L. fem. n. *oladosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp002725475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002725475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.11 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Phecorarcha omapana sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha omapana (N.L. fem. n. *omapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp002727675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002727675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.56 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Phecorarcha onacana sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha onacana (N.L. fem. n. *onacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp016845345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016845345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.15 % and the genome length is 2.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Phecorarcha onagosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha onagosa (N.L. fem. n. *onagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp012959435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012959435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.17 % and the genome length is 2.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Phecorarcha vuxosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Phecorarcha vuxosa (N.L. fem. n. *vuxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-Q1 sp012964335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012966225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.49 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phederarcha esalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phederarcha esalia (N.L. fem. n. *esalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-204 sp002255065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002255065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.15 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phederarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phederarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phederarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-204. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phederarcha esalia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Zestosphaeraceae*@.

Description of *Candidatus Phefredarcha edabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phefredarcha edabella (N.L. fem. n. *edabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPTG01 sp016192905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016192905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.12 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phefredarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phefredarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phefredarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPTG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phefredarcha edabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phelefarcha asaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phelefarcha asaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *asaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOJZ01 sp004376295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004376295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.23 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phelefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phelefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phelefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SOJZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phelefarcha asaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Saxararchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phemifarcha avagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phemifarcha avagella (N.L. fem. n. *avagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is HARCEL1 sp003058365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003058365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.74 % and the genome length is 2.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phemifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phemifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phemifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is HARCEL1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phemifarcha avagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloarculaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phepafarcha imafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phepafarcha imafaria (N.L. fem. n. *imafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWVY01 sp003561665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003561665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.82 % and the genome length is 2.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phepafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phepafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phepafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PWVY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phepafarcha imafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Urusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pheplesarcha ebexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pheplesarcha ebexia (N.L. fem. n. *ebexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTIM01 sp011333975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011333975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.76 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pheplesarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pheplesarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pheplesarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTIM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pheplesarcha ebexia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phepradarcha abevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phepradarcha abevaria (N.L. fem. n. *abevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTGI01 sp011362975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011362975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.77 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phepradarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phepradarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phepradarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTGI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phepradarcha abevaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiresarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pherusarcha urelella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pherusarcha urelella (N.L. fem. n. *urelella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGTL01 sp016874675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016874675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.26 % and the genome length is 3.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pherusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pherusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pherusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGTL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pherusarcha urelella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pherusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pherusarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pherusarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pherusarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is VGTL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pherusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Redixarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Phesirarcha ovafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phesirarcha ovafana (N.L. fem. n. *ovafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHHN01 sp018671515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018653265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 26.9 % and the genome length is 1.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phesirarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phesirarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phesirarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHHN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phesirarcha ovafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hudomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phicabarcha igacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phicabarcha igacosa (N.L. fem. n. *igacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 6H3-1 sp019058135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.15 % and the genome length is 3.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phicabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phicabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phicabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 6H3-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phicabarcha igacosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phicabarcha ofadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phicabarcha ofadana (N.L. fem. n. *ofadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 6H3-1 sp019058015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.34 % and the genome length is 4.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiclusarcha udepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiclusarcha udepella (N.L. fem. n. *udepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJQH01 sp018819375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018819375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.1 % and the genome length is 0.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiclusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phiclusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phiclusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJQH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phiclusarcha udepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phicrudarcha quexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phicrudarcha quexaria (N.L. fem. n. *quexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGCE01 sp016932755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.9 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phicrudarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phicrudarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phicrudarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGCE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phicrudarcha quexaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Luglotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phiglefarcha upetaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiglefarcha upetaria (N.L. fem. n. *upetaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is NZBF01 sp002687775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002687775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.3 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiglefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phiglefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phiglefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is NZBF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phiglefarcha upetaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phimigarcha unavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phimigarcha unavia (N.L. fem. n. *unavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA207 sp002503135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.55 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phimigarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phimigarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phimigarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA207. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phimigarcha unavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanoculleaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phinasarcha ifaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phinasarcha ifaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ifaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS10 sp002690445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002690445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.83 % and the genome length is 6.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phinasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phinasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phinasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS10. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phinasarcha ifaparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha agevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha agevia (N.L. fem. n. *agevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016185865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.18 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phiperarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2688775. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phiperarcha agevia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha aselia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha aselia (N.L. fem. n. *aselina* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016192985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016192985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.25 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha avapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha avapella (N.L. fem. n. *avapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp018303655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.01 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha ebacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha ebacana (N.L. fem. n. *ebacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016185915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.01 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha edebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha edebosa (N.L. fem. n. *edebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp018303505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.9 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha egacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha egacaria (N.L. fem. n. *egacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016187465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.36 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha epebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha epebia (N.L. fem. n. *epebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016185875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.12 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha esacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha esacosa (N.L. fem. n. *esacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016185945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.84 % and the genome

length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha esecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha esecia (N.L. fem. n. *esecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016177615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016177615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.8 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha ibetella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha ibetella (N.L. fem. n. *ibetella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016185815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.59 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha ifeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha ifeparia (N.L. fem. n. *ifeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016185805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.54 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha inaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha inaxia (N.L. fem. n. *inaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016185755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.75 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha ipegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha ipegana (N.L. fem. n. *ipegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is GCA-2688775 sp018303645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.84 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha isadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha isadella (N.L. fem. n. *isadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp018303685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.59 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha opafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha opafia (N.L. fem. n. *opafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016211245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016211245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.21 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha phafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha phafaria (N.L. fem. n. *phafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016185845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.62 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha phagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha phagosa (N.L. fem. n. *phagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016188245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.09 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha phedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha phedia (N.L. fem. n. *phedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016192955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016192955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.41 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha umefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha umefana (N.L. fem. n. *umefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp002688775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.71 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phiperarcha uravella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiperarcha uravella (N.L. fem. n. *uravella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688775 sp016181305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.09 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phipoxarcha omaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phipoxarcha omaparia (N.L. fem. n. *omaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA493 sp002687735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.01 % and the genome length is 0.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phipoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phipoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phipoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA493. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phipoxarcha omaparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iainarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phiricarcha igaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiricarcha igaxana (N.L. fem. n. *igaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B1-Br10-U2g21 sp001564035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001564035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.15 % and the genome length is 0.58 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample PL-Br10; brine of Picturesque Lake".

Description of *Candidatus Phiricarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phiricarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phiricarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B1-Br10-U2g21. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phiricarcha igaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nanosaliniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phiricarcha ubapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiricarcha ubapia (N.L. fem. n. *ubapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B1-Br10-U2g21 sp001563915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.37 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample B1-Br-g2; brine of Lake Bitter-1".

Description of *Candidatus Phiricarcha ubemella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phiricarcha ubemella (N.L. fem. n. *ubemella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B1-Br10-U2g21 sp001564145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001564145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.1 % and the genome length is 0.53 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample B1-Br-g2; brine of Lake Bitter-1".

Description of *Candidatus Phisaxarcha quavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisaxarcha quavia (N.L. fem. n. *quavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGTM01 sp016874685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016874685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.6 % and the genome length is 2.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phisaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phisaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGTM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phisaxarcha quavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanobacteriaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phisibarcha igafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisibarcha igafana (N.L. fem. n. *igafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 20-14-0-80-47-9 sp002779555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002779555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.44 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phisibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phisibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 20-14-0-80-47-9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phisibarcha igafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha afedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha afedana (N.L. fem. n. *afedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002702985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002702985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.83 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phisofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIb-N2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phisofarcha afedana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thalassarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha inaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha inaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *inaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002718215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002718215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.53 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha iralosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha iralosa (N.L. fem. n. *iralosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002506875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.7 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha obamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha obamana (N.L. fem. n. *obamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002708015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002708015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.77 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha ofadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha ofadia (N.L. fem. n. *ofadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is MGIIb-N2 sp002502625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002170365.2. The GC content of the type genome is 39.31 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha ubamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha ubamaria (N.L. fem. n. *ubamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002497905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.28 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha ubamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha ubamia (N.L. fem. n. *ubamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002712285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.54 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha ucamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha ucamaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002697105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002697105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.0 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha ufagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha ufagana (N.L. fem. n. *ufagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002708695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002708695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.5 % and the genome length is 1.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha upexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha upexia (N.L. fem. n. *upexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002503045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.36 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha utefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha utefella (N.L. fem. n. *utefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002503665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.39 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phisofarcha uvadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phisofarcha uvadosa (N.L. fem. n. *uvadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIb-N2 sp002713585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002700955.2. The GC content of the type genome is 48.9 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phistemarcha iregosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phistemarcha iregosa (N.L. fem. n. *iregosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGBX01 sp016932935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.68 % and the genome length is 5.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phistemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phistemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phistemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGBX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phistemarcha iregosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxistarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phitragarcha ivapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phitragarcha ivapana (N.L. fem. n. *ivapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688355 sp002688355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.63 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phitragarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phitragarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phitragarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2688355. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phitragarcha ivapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phobimarcha onagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phobimarcha onagaria (N.L. fem. n. *onagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10214 sp10214u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.44 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phobimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phobimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phobimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10214. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phobimarcha onagaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phofracarcha elafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phofracarcha elafana (N.L. fem. n. *elafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PIYF01 sp003601875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003601875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.27 % and the genome length is 0.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phofracarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phofracarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phofracarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PIYF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phofracarcha elafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phofumarcha phafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phofumarcha phafia (N.L. fem. n. *phafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGJW01 sp016928835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016928835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.81 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phofumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phofumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phofumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGJW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phofumarcha phafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hudomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phogafarcha efavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phogafarcha efavana (N.L. fem. n. *efavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAILMQ01 sp903835385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903916535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.08 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phogafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phogafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phogafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAILMQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phogafarcha efavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phoglaparcha uvecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phoglaparcha uvecana (N.L. fem. n. *uvecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9915 sp9915u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.58 % and the genome length is 0.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phoglaparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phoglaparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phoglaparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA9915. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phoglaparcha uvecana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phonobarcha inafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phonobarcha inafana (N.L. fem. n. *inafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHLMN01 sp018920345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018920345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.14 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phonobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phonobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phonobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHLMN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phonobarcha inafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Isoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phonobarcha ofagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phonobarcha ofagaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHLMN01 sp018920365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018920365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.61 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phopasarcha inegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phopasarcha inegia (N.L. fem. n. *inegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYO01 sp018303225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.8 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phopasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phopasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phopasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phopasarcha inegia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Phopasarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phopasarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Phopasarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Phopasarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVYO01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Phopasarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Phostucarcha ogebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phostucarcha ogebella (N.L. fem. n. *ogebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is M3-22 sp013343275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013343275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.95 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phostucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phostucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phostucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is M3-22. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phostucarcha ogebella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nanosalinaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Photonarcha egararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Photonarcha egararia (N.L. fem. n. *egararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQBR01 sp016194335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016212415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.65 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Photonarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Photonarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Photonarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQBR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Photonarcha egararia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Caxorarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phoxesarcha afacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phoxesarcha afacaria (N.L. fem. n. *afacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AAA261-N23 sp000375685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000375685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.04 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phoxesarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phoxesarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phoxesarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is AAA261-N23. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phoxesarcha afacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gearchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phoxesarcha icabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phoxesarcha icabia (N.L. fem. n. *icabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AAA261-N23 sp017857595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017857595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.01 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phoxinarcha idapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phoxinarcha idapana (N.L. fem. n. *idapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPGZ01 sp016188895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.31 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phoxinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phoxinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phoxinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPGZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phoxinarcha idapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phucasarcha olagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phucasarcha olagana (N.L. fem. n. *olagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHIB01 sp018671245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018696235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.33 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phucasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phucasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phucasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHIB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phucasarcha olagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nipetarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phucoxarcha icavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phucoxarcha icavella (N.L. fem. n. *icavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZG01 sp003663045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011042275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.11 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phucoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phucoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phucoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMZG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phucoxarcha icavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lanaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phudrosarcha uceparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phudrosarcha uceparia (N.L. fem. n. *uceparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZK01 sp018302685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.75 % and the genome length is 0.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phudrosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phudrosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phudrosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phudrosarcha uceparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha ebafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha ebafia (N.L. fem. n. *ebafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp001940705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001940705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.58 % and the genome length is 2.86 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Marine sediment".

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phulemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SMTZ1-45. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phulemarcha ebafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha emefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha emefosa (N.L. fem. n. *emefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp016840855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.93 % and the genome length is 3.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha isalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha isalaria (N.L. fem. n. *isalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp011364905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.97 % and the genome length is 3.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha omabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha omabia (N.L. fem. n. *omabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp004376265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004376265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.33 % and the genome length is 3.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha omecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha omecella (N.L. fem. n. *omecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp001563335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.16 % and the genome length is 3.54 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-methane transition zone estuary sediments 16-26 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha otevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha otevella (N.L. fem. n. *otevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp002825515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002825515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.59 % and the genome length is 3.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha quaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha quaxella (N.L. fem. n. *quaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp016839345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_016839345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.45 % and the genome length is 3.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha ucaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha ucaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ucaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp016840965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.19 % and the genome length is 3.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha ufadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha ufadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp019057595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.06 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phulemarcha utafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phulemarcha utafosa (N.L. fem. n. *utafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SMTZ1-45 sp016840685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.79 % and the genome length is 3.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phunadarcha uvataria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phunadarcha uvataria (N.L. fem. n. *uvataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S014-50 sp015522935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.35 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phunadarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phunadarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phunadarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S014-50. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phunadarcha uvataria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aciduliprofundaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phusotarcha imabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phusotarcha imabella (N.L. fem. n. *imabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S013-73 sp015523295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.91 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phusotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phusotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phusotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S013-73. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phusotarcha imabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Zestosphaeraceae*@.

Description of *Candidatus Phustixarcha edevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phustixarcha edevosa (N.L. fem. n. *edevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPNF01 sp016185635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.94 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phustixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phustixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phustixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPNF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phustixarcha edevosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hicrosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phutacarcha asavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phutacarcha asavia (N.L. fem. n. *asavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SD8 sp018432765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018432765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.55 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phutacarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phutacarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phutacarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SD8. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phutacarcha asavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanoregulaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phutacarcha iperosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phutacarcha iperosa (N.L. fem. n. *iperosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SD8 sp002509485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002509485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.3 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phutacarcha ufagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phutacarcha ufagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SD8 sp001412335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001412335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.23 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "methanogenic consortium capable of long-chain paraffin degradation (SDB culture) enriched from contaminated sediments of San Diego Bay; California; degrades n-alkanes from C25 to C50".

Description of *Candidatus Phuxifarcha ifesosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phuxifarcha ifesosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifesosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIDS01 sp018651605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018651605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.43 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Phuxifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Phuxifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Phuxifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABIDS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Phuxifarcha ifesosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Phuxifarcha uvapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Phuxifarcha uvapana (N.L. fem. n. *uvapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIDS01 sp018653485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018653485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.5 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Picoxarcha emadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Picoxarcha emadella (N.L. fem. n. *emadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10200 sp016180275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.77 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Picoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Picoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Picoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10200. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Picoxarcha emadella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Picoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Picoxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Picoxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Picoxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10200. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Picoxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Picoxarcha odabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Picoxarcha odabosa (N.L. fem. n. *odabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10200 sp018302185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.12 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Picoxarcha ufaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Picoxarcha ufaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ufaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10200 sp10200u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.25 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pigafarcha ugadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pigafarcha ugadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ugadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPNG01 sp016185605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.63 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pigafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pigafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pigafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JACPNG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pigafarcha ugadosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pigafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pigafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pigafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPNG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pigafarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pimisarcha efadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pimisarcha efadana (N.L. fem. n. *efadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQPN01 sp016207515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016207515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.3 % and the genome length is 2.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pimisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pimisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pimisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQPN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pimisarcha efadana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pimisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pimisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pimisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pimisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQPN01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pimisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pimisarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pimisarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Pimisarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Pimisarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQPN01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pimisarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Urusarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Piploxarcha asabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Piploxarcha asabella (N.L. fem. n. *asabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACGMN01 sp016930255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016930255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.23 % and the genome length is 2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Piploxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Piploxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Piploxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACGMN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Piploxarcha asabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Piploxarcha ogeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Piploxarcha ogeparia (N.L. fem. n. *ogeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACGMN01 sp014061035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014061035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.52 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Piploxarcha phagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Piploxarcha phagella (N.L. fem. n. *phagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACGMN01 sp016928455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016928455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.61 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Piploxarcha ufasella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Piploxarcha ufasella (N.L. fem. n. *ufasella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACGMN01 sp016649585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016649585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.76 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Piploxarcha uvafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Piploxarcha uvafella (N.L. fem. n. *uvafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACGMN01 sp011049045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011049045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.24 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pipludrarcha ipetaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pipludrarcha ipetaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipetaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIMOB01 sp903842985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903842985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.44 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pipludrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pipludrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pipludrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIMOB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pipludrarcha ipetaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nufagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pisedrarcha esebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pisedrarcha esebana (N.L. fem. n. *esebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-21 sp014523495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.22 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Pisedrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Pisedrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pisedrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TA-21. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pisedrarcha esebana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrososphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Pisedrarcha ilemana sp. nov.

Candidatus Pisedrarcha ilemana (N.L. fem. n. *ilemana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-21 sp005877345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005877345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.06 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Pisedrarcha odabaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Pisedrarcha odabaria (N.L. fem. n. *odabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-21 sp014523525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.01 % and the genome length is 1.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Pisedrarcha ofalia sp. nov.

Candidatus Pisedrarcha ofalia (N.L. fem. n. *ofalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-21 sp014381105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014381105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.04 % and the genome length is

1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pisedrarcha ufadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pisedrarcha ufadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-21 sp014523595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014523595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.37 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pisedrarcha utaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pisedrarcha utaxia (N.L. fem. n. *utaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TA-21 sp005877075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005877385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.31 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pisenarcha ivebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pisenarcha ivebia (N.L. fem. n. *ivebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-48-13 sp001775995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001775995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.14 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 16ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Pisenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pisenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pisenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is RBG-16-48-13. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pisenarcha ivebia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pisenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pisenarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pisenarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pisenarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is RBG-16-48-13. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pisenarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pisenarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pisenarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Pisenarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Pisenarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is RBG-16-48-13. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pisenarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Bathyarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Pitecrarcha amapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pitecrarcha amapella (N.L. fem. n. *amapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is COMBO-56-21 sp018814355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018824625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.24 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pitecrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pitecrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pitecrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is COMBO-56-21. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pitecrarcha amapella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiturarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pitecrarcha egafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pitecrarcha egafaria (N.L. fem. n. *egafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is COMBO-56-21 sp016930135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016930135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.18 % and the genome

length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pitocrarcha obaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pitocrarcha obaposa (N.L. fem. n. *obaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is COMBO-56-21 sp001800675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001800675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.05 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 13ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Pitocrarcha odapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pitocrarcha odapella (N.L. fem. n. *odapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is COMBO-56-21 sp001800815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001800815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.4 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 19ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Pitrafrarcha ucedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pitrafrarcha ucedella (N.L. fem. n. *ucedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAKA01 sp015523565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.58 % and the genome length is 3.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pitrafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pitrafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pitrafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAKA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pitrafrarcha ucedella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Kariarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pixastarcha avacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pixastarcha avacana (N.L. fem. n. *avacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRGC01 sp016212475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016212475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.25 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pixastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pixastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pixastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRGC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pixastarcha avacana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ticixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pixelarcha ocarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pixelarcha ocarella (N.L. fem. n. *ocarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALJ01 sp015522885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.83 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pixelarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pixelarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pixelarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pixelarcha ocarella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pixelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pixelarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pixelarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pixelarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WALJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pixelarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pixelarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pixelarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Pixelarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Pixelarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WALJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Pixelarcha.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus Pixitrarcha utafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pixitrarcha utafella (N.L. fem. n. *utafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA12276 sp8261u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.04 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pixitrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pixitrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pixitrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA12276. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pixitrarcha utafella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Micrarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plafesarcha ifapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plafesarcha ifapia (N.L. fem. n. *ifapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-21 sp004524425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.46 % and the genome length is 2.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plafesarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plafesarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plafesarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TEKIR-21. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Plafesarcha ifapia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Plafitarcha ubavaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Plafitarcha ubavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ubavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVVZ01 sp018304545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.77 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Plafitarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Plafitarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plafitarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVVZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Plafitarcha ubavaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Isoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Plamidarcha muvia sp. nov.

Candidatus Plamidarcha muvia (N.L. fem. n. *muvia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA93 sp002792915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001871655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.85 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "groundwater filtered through a 3.0 um filter and then through a 0.2 um filter".

Description of *Candidatus* Plamidarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Plamidarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plamidarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA93. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plasafarcha muvia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Norongarragalinae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plasafarcha ofebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plasafarcha ofebosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOIM01 sp004377185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004377185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.23 % and the genome length is 2.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plasafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plasafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plasafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SOIM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plasafarcha ofebosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Plasafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plasafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Plasafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Plasafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SOIM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Plasafarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Figanarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Plegimarcha uvapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plegimarcha uvapia (N.L. fem. n. *uvapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-39-14 sp001872315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009992305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.0 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plegimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plegimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plegimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG1-02-39-14. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plegimarcha uvapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha ebamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha ebamosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L3 sp002496845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.13 % and the genome length is 1.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plemecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIa-L3. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plemecarcha ebamosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha epabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha epabaria (N.L. fem. n. *epabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L3 sp12206u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.97 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha ibacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha ibacaria (N.L. fem. n. *ibacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L3 sp002731395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.48 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha igacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha igacaria (N.L. fem. n. *igacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L3 sp002694585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002694585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.58 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha igapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha igapella (N.L. fem. n. *igapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L3 sp003602635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.89 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha upagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha upagia (N.L. fem. n. *upagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L3 sp002722135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.7 % and the genome length is 1.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha uraxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha uraxana (N.L. fem. n. *uraxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L3 sp002723635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002507165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.25 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plemecarcha vuposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plemecarcha vuposa (N.L. fem. n. *vuposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-L3 sp11892u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.68 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plidroxarcha utefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plidroxarcha utefia (N.L. fem. n. *utefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-12S sp004524435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.44 % and the genome length is 2.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plidroxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plidroxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plidroxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TEKIR-12S. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plidroxarcha utefia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plixacarcha udacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plixacarcha udacosa (N.L. fem. n. *udacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PFCU01 sp002763155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002763155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.25 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plixacarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plixacarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plixacarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PFCU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plixacarcha udacosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Midifarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Plofrutarcha umapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plofrutarcha umapana (N.L. fem. n. *umapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMGC01 sp902385515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.9 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plofrutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plofrutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plofrutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CABMGC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plofrutarcha umapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Micrarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plosimarcha idavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plosimarcha idavia (N.L. fem. n. *idavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEY01 sp017608945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.16 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plosimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plosimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plosimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCEY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plosimarcha idavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plostenarcha evecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plostenarcha evecia (N.L. fem. n. *evecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOZQ01 sp016181275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.5 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plostenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plostenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plostenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOZQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plostenarcha evacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hopelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ploxefarcha evafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ploxefarcha evafaria (N.L. fem. n. *evafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG07-land sp016931175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016931175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.3 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ploxefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ploxefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ploxefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG07-land. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ploxefarcha evafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiddalikarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ploxefarcha icavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ploxefarcha icavosa (N.L. fem. n. *icavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG07-land sp002779595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_002779795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.33 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plufamarcha erabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plufamarcha erabosa (N.L. fem. n. *erabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FT1-020 sp019057355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.47 % and the genome length is 3.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plufamarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plufamarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plufamarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is FT1-020. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plufamarcha erabosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plufamarcha onaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plufamarcha onaparia (N.L. fem. n. *onaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FT1-020 sp016930515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016930515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.06 % and the genome length is 4.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plufamarcha otamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plufamarcha otamana (N.L. fem. n. *otamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FT1-020 sp016839425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.64 % and the genome length is 4.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plufamarcha quebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plufamarcha quebella (N.L. fem. n. *quebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FT1-020 sp016840695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.46 % and the genome length is 2.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plufrugarcha amevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plufrugarcha amevosa (N.L. fem. n. *amevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQSP01 sp018303325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.13 % and the genome length is 1.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plufrugarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plufrugarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plufrugarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQSP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Plufrugarcha amevosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nerisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plufrugarcha ivepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plufrugarcha ivepella (N.L. fem. n. *ivepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQSP01 sp016205905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016205905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.65 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plusudarcha ivamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Plusudarcha ivamosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRVD01 sp011371765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011371765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.45 % and the genome length is 0.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Plusudarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Plusudarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Plusudarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRVD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Plusudarcha ivamosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Plusudarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Plusudarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Plusudarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Plusudarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DRVD01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Plusudarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pacearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pluxetarcha evepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pluxetarcha evepia (N.L. fem. n. *evepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CBA1134 sp003021175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.67 % and the genome length is 2.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pluxetarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pluxetarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pluxetarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CBA1134. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pluxetarcha evepia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloarculaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pluxetarcha ifalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pluxetarcha ifalia (N.L. fem. n. *ifalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CBA1134 sp001950595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001950595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.36 % and the genome length is 2.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pluxetarcha ipaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pluxetarcha ipaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ipaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CBA1134 sp009184545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009184575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.73 % and the genome length is 2.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pluxetarcha ofavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pluxetarcha ofavella (N.L. fem. n. *ofavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CBA1134 sp003021785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003021785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.11 % and the genome length is 2.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pluxetarcha utebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pluxetarcha utebella (N.L. fem. n. *utebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CBA1134 sp003023185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.06 % and the genome length is 2.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pocrifarcha ubegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pocrifarcha ubegella (N.L. fem. n. *ubegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQG01 sp015520395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.79 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pocrifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pocrifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pocrifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pocrifarcha ubegella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pocrifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Pocrifarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Pocrifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pocrifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WAQG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Pocrifarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Gearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Pocudrarcha ocagella sp. nov.

Candidatus Pocudrarcha ocagella (N.L. fem. n. *ocagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGKP01 sp016866975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016866975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.8 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Pocudrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Pocudrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pocudrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGKP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pocudrarcha ocagella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Podaprarcha ucamosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Podaprarcha ucamosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSLF01 sp011051215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011054055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.48 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Podaprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Podaprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Podaprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSLF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Podaprarcha ucamosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Podoxarcha uvatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Podoxarcha uvatella (N.L. fem. n. *uvatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B50-G16 sp003663345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.38 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Podoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Podoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Podoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B50-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Podoxarcha uvatella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Podoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Podoxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Podoxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Podoxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B50-G16. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Podoxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Butolarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Podrixarcha edefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Podrixarcha edefosa (N.L. fem. n. *edefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZJ01 sp018302725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.6 % and the genome length is 0.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Podrixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Podrixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Podrixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Podrixarcha edefosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Podrixarcha otavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Podrixarcha otavana (N.L. fem. n. *otavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZJ01 sp018302465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.92 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pofedarcha osaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pofedarcha osaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *osaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2687815 sp002687815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002687815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.4 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pofedarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pofedarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pofedarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is GCA-2687815. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pofedarcha osaxosa*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pofedarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pofedarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pofedarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pofedarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-2687815. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pofedarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pofeprarcha edavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pofeprarcha edavella (N.L. fem. n. *edavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ANME-1-THS sp004212135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004212135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.73 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pofeprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pofeprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pofeprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ANME-1-THS. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pofeprarcha edavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pofeprarcha evepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pofeprarcha evepana (N.L. fem. n. *evepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ANME-1-THS sp014859735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014859735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.27 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poglexarcha epagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poglexarcha epagia (N.L. fem. n. *epagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PIYB01 sp018397055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018397055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.33 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poglexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Poglexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Poglexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PIYB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Poglexarcha epagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Poglexarcha itagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poglexarcha itagaria (N.L. fem. n. *itagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PIYB01 sp003601835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003601835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.82 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poglexarcha ufalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poglexarcha ufalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PIYB01 sp018397065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018397065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.4 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poglotrarcha ogaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poglotrarcha ogaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ogaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JACPNH01 sp016185565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.88 % and the genome length is 0.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poglotrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Poglotrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Poglotrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPNH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Poglotrarcha ogaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gosularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ponexarcha elacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ponexarcha elacana (N.L. fem. n. *elacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA141 sp002495315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.96 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ponexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ponexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ponexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA141. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ponexarcha elacana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ponexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ponexarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ponexarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ponexarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA141. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ponexarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Poplicarcha adafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poplicarcha adafana (N.L. fem. n. *adafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAXQB01 sp012329085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012329085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.82 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poplicarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Poplicarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Poplicarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAXQB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Poplicarcha adafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanosarcinaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Poprefrarcha utefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poprefrarcha utefosa (N.L. fem. n. *utefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CSSED10-239 sp003559395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003559395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.35 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poprefrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Poprefrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Poprefrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CSSED10-239. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Poprefrarcha utefosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Forterreaceae*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia buvia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia buvia (N.L. fem. n. *buvia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp002714305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.98 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia ebagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia ebagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp002725275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002703295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.98 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia edagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia edagosa (N.L. fem. n. *edagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp002497765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.3 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia emabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia emabosa (N.L. fem. n. *emabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp002728035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002728035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.86 % and the genome length is 1.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia epabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia epabana (N.L. fem. n. *epabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp003602475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.66 % and the genome length is 1.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia esalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia esalella (N.L. fem. n. *esalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp902625885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902625885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.18 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia ibadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia ibadella (N.L. fem. n. *ibadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp016778305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016777075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.17 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia iragella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia iragella (N.L. fem. n. *iragella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp002722695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003672845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.32 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia isabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia isabana (N.L. fem. n. *isabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp002494645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_905477435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.33 % and the genome length is 1.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia odacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia odacana (N.L. fem. n. *odacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp002726495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002690785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.22 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia onadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia onadosa (N.L. fem. n. *onadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp002495645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002716785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.69 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia orecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia orecia (N.L. fem. n. *orecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp016779705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016779705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.19 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia ovaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia ovaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ovaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp003602485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.68 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia phaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia phaxella (N.L. fem. n. *phaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp002502295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002502295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.88 % and the genome length is 1.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia uceria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia uceria (N.L. fem. n. *uceria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Poseidonia* sp002694525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002694525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.62 % and the genome length is 1.6

Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia ugavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia ugavia (N.L. fem. n. *ugavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp011524855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011524855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.63 % and the genome length is 1.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia upavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia upavana (N.L. fem. n. *upavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp002689105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.88 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia upefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia upefosa (N.L. fem. n. *upefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp002704515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002704515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.13 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia uvabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia uvabella (N.L. fem. n. *uvabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Poseidonia sp8339u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003602525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.91 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Poseidonia uvaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Poseidonia uvaparia (N.L. fem. n. *uvaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is *Poseidonia* sp018662715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018665145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.73 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha guxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha guxosa (N.L. fem. n. *guxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp019057865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.83 % and the genome length is 2.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Postorarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Loki-b32. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Postorarcha guxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha ifatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha ifatosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp019057975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.18 % and the genome length is 5.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha igabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha igabaria (N.L. fem. n. *igabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp019058245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.98 % and the genome length is 3.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha ipemana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha ipemana (N.L. fem. n. *ipemana* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp016839635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.63 % and the genome length is 4.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha isecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha isecella (N.L. fem. n. *isecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp016840085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.54 % and the genome length is 4.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha obaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha obaparia (N.L. fem. n. *obaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp019057775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.37 % and the genome length is 6.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha odacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha odacaria (N.L. fem. n. *odacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp005223125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005223125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.85 % and the genome length is 4.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha odaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha odaparia (N.L. fem. n. *odaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp013375485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013375485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.93 % and the genome length is 4.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha odexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha odexaria (N.L. fem. n. *odexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp016839585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.17 % and the genome length is 3.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha odexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha odexia (N.L. fem. n. *odexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp016839705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.38 % and the genome length is 3.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha onexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha onexella (N.L. fem. n. *onexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp016839655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.19 % and the genome length is 4.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha ucagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha ucagosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp016839845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.45 % and the genome length is 5.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha umabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha umabosa (N.L. fem. n. *umabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp019058425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.84 % and the genome length is

4.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha umavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha umavia (N.L. fem. n. *umavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp016839915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.89 % and the genome length is 3.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Postorarcha usaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Postorarcha usaxia (N.L. fem. n. *usaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Loki-b32 sp019058365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.53 % and the genome length is 4.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pracuxarcha cebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pracuxarcha cebaria (N.L. fem. n. *cebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIKK01 sp018658955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018666265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.63 % and the genome length is 0.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pracuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pracuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pracuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABIKK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pracuxarcha cebaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Giboxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pracuxarcha efatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pracuxarcha efatella (N.L. fem. n. *efatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIKK01 sp018658265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018658265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.48 % and the genome length is 0.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pracuxarcha inacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pracuxarcha inacosa (N.L. fem. n. *inacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIKK01 sp016845225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016845225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.42 % and the genome length is 0.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pracuxarcha upacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pracuxarcha upacia (N.L. fem. n. *upacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIKK01 sp018655015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018697815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.06 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pregofarcha agacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pregofarcha agacaria (N.L. fem. n. *agacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIPOI01 sp016867035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016867035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.48 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pregofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pregofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pregofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIPOI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pregofarcha agacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pregofarcha ebadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pregofarcha ebadia (N.L. fem. n. *ebadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIPOI01 sp903866625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903828205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.81 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pregrudarcha ebefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pregrudarcha ebefella (N.L. fem. n. *ebefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B9-G16 sp003660965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003660965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.63 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pregrudarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pregrudarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pregrudarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B9-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pregrudarcha ebefella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Burarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pritrocarcha ecedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pritrocarcha ecedaria (N.L. fem. n. *ecedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAML01 sp015522345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.67 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pritrocarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pritrocarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pritrocarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is WAML01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Pritrocarcha ecedaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Desulfurococcaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Procrsarcha ecatosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Procrsarcha ecatosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecatos* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALU01 sp015522685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.82 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Procrsarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Procrsarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Procrsarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Procrsarcha ecatos.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Korarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Procrsarcha inegaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Procrsarcha inegaria (N.L. fem. n. *inegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALU01 sp015521385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.92 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Prodrenarcha unexella sp. nov.

Candidatus Prodrenarcha unexella (N.L. fem. n. *unexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGEM01 sp016931555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016931555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.18 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Prodrenarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Prodrenercha (N.L. fem. n. *Prodrenercha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGEM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Prodrenercha unexella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nogelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Prometheoarchaeum irafosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Prometheoarchaeum irafosa (N.L. fem. n. *irafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Prometheoarchaeum sp018238965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018238965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.38 % and the genome length is 3.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Prudrafarcha ipetana sp. nov.

Candidatus Prudrafarcha ipetana (N.L. fem. n. *ipetana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACTUC01 sp015660995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015660995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.88 % and the genome length is 1.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Prudrafarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Prudrafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Prudrafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACTUC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Prudrafarcha ipetana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylicaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Prustitarcha omabana sp. nov.

Candidatus Prustitarcha omabana (N.L. fem. n. *omabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JAGVXW01 sp018303575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.45 % and the genome length is 1.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Prustitarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Prustitarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Prustitarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Prustitarcha omabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixiprarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pucerarcha esalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pucerarcha esalaria (N.L. fem. n. *esalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZY01 sp018302225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.81 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pucerarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pucerarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pucerarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pucerarcha esalaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pucerarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pucerarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pucerarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pucerarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVZY01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pucerarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pucrasarcha onaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pucrasarcha onaxia (N.L. fem. n. *onaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVWS01 sp018304165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.35 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pucrasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pucrasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pucrasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVWS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pucrasarcha onaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pucreprarcha ogemia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pucreprarcha ogemia (N.L. fem. n. *ogemia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHENW01 sp018610025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018610025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.08 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pucreprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pucreprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pucreprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHENW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pucreprarcha ogemia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natronoplasmataceae*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Pudistarcha ofebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pudistarcha ofebana (N.L. fem. n. *ofebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCW01 sp017609985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.75 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pudistarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pudistarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pudistarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pudistarcha ofebana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pudistarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pudistarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pudistarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pudistarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFCCW01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pudistarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pudofarcha usavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pudofarcha usavana (N.L. fem. n. *usavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFNFQ01 sp017885655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017885655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.19 % and the genome length is 2.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pudofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pudofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pudofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFNFQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pudofarcha usavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pudofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pudofarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pudofarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pudofarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFNFQ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pudofarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Figanarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pufisarcha enabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pufisarcha enabaria (N.L. fem. n. *enabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-33-12 sp017610275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.55 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pufisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Pufisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Pufisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG1-02-33-12. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Pufisarcha enabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pufisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Pufisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Pufisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Pufisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG1-02-33-12. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Pufisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Pufisarcha ipaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pufisarcha ipaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ipaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-33-12 sp017610505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.92 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pufisarcha odagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pufisarcha odagosa (N.L. fem. n. *odagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-33-12 sp018819345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018897235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.27 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pufisarcha osacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pufisarcha osacosa (N.L. fem. n. *osacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-33-12 sp002762865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002762865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.28 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pufisarcha ovacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pufisarcha ovacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ovacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-33-12 sp017609385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.64 % and the genome length is 0.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pufisarcha ulacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pufisarcha ulacella (N.L. fem. n. *ulacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-33-12 sp018901315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018901315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.47 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Puplatarcha ogalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Puplatarcha ogalaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFDFS01 sp017608525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.72 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Puplatarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Puplatarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Puplatarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFDFS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Puplatarcha ogalaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Puresarcha igecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Puresarcha igecana (N.L. fem. n. *igecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSCA01 sp011049295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011049295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.09 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Puresarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Puresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Puresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSCA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Puresarcha igecana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Puresarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Puresarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Puresarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Puresarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

taxon is DSCA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Puresarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Enedarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Purufrarcha avaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Purufrarcha avaxella (N.L. fem. n. *avaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABXJT01 sp013375405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013375405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.42 % and the genome length is 4.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Purufrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Purufrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Purufrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABXJT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Purufrarcha avaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tixirarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Purufrarcha ocepama* sp. nov.

Candidatus Purufrarcha ocepama (N.L. fem. n. *ocepama* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABXJT01 sp013375455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013375455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.63 % and the genome length is 5.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Purufrarcha ugacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Purufrarcha ugacia (N.L. fem. n. *ugacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABXJT01 sp016840125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.46 % and the genome length is 7.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pyrobaculum ivalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pyrobaculum ivalana (N.L. fem. n. *ivalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Pyrobaculum sp009903905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009903905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.8 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Pyrobaculum ivebella sp. nov.

Candidatus Pyrobaculum ivebella (N.L. fem. n. *ivebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Pyrobaculum sp001189275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001189275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.31 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sediment".

Description of *Candidatus* Pyrococcus ecaxella sp. nov.

Candidatus Pyrococcus ecaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ecaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Pyrococcus sp003660485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003660485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.0 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Pyrococcus egasia sp. nov.

Candidatus Pyrococcus egasia (N.L. fem. n. *egasia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Pyrococcus sp000211475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000211475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.74 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "hydrothermal vent area; 1650 m depth".

Description of *Candidatus* Pyrococcus ileposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Pyrococcus ileposa (N.L. fem. n. *ileposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Pyrococcus sp000263735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

RS_GCF_000263735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.29 % and the genome length is 1.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Pyrolobus etacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Pyrolobus etacia (N.L. fem. n. *etacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Pyrolobus sp015521195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.68 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quabilarcha buvella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quabilarcha buvella (N.L. fem. n. *buvella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-35-32 sp002792635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002792635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.1 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quabilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quabilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quabilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG1-02-35-32. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quabilarcha buvella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quabronarcha ipemosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quabronarcha ipemosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipemosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAKO01 sp015523325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.69 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quabronarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quabronarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quabronarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAKO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quacidarcha ipemosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiresarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quacidarcha ucaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quacidarcha ucaria (N.L. fem. n. *ucaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-22 sp002010045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002010045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.8 % and the genome length is 2.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quacidarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quacidarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quacidarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-22. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quacidarcha ucaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Archaeoglobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quaclanarcha usecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quaclanarcha usecaria (N.L. fem. n. *usecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is TEKIR-14 sp004524445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.58 % and the genome length is 2.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quaclanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quaclanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quaclanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is TEKIR-14. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quaclanarcha usecaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Thorarchaeaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Quacloparcha esecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quacloparcha esecosa (N.L. fem. n. *esecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQMS01 sp016203445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.11 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quacloparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quacloparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quacloparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQMS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quacloparcha esecosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quacofarcha ebavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quacofarcha ebavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJJS01 sp014729505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.77 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quacofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quacofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quacofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJJS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quacofarcha ebavosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quadelarcha ucagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quadelarcha ucagana (N.L. fem. n. *ucagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGMR01 sp016927425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016927425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.06 % and the genome length is 2.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quadelarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quadelarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quadelarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGMR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quadelarcha ucagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanotrichaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quadrufarcha umegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quadrufarcha umegia (N.L. fem. n. *umegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCD01 sp017609845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.44 % and the genome length is 0.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quadrufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quadrufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quadrufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quadrufarcha umegia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quafrexarcha ogavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quafrexarcha ogavella (N.L. fem. n. *ogavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQM01 sp015520245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_015520245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.44 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quafrexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quafrexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quafrexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quafrexarcha ogavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pyrodictiaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Qualeparcha ocanaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Qualeparcha ocanaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocanaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACROM01 sp016214445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016214445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.62 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Qualeparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Qualeparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Qualeparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACROM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Qualeparcha ocanaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Uclobarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Qualinarcha otamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Qualinarcha otamosa (N.L. fem. n. *otamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QENJ01 sp013374505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013374505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.28 % and the genome length is 2.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Qualinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Qualinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Qualinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QENJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Qualinarcha otamosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Qualinarcha phaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Qualinarcha phaparia (N.L. fem. n. *phaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QENJ01 sp013180585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013180585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.67 % and the genome length is 2.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quamularcha quafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quamularcha quafana (N.L. fem. n. *quafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJMO01 sp014727915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014727915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.31 % and the genome length is 1.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quamularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quamularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quamularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJMO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quamularcha quafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiragarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quanixarcha obafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quanixarcha obafia (N.L. fem. n. *obafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J091 sp003695045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_003695045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.17 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quanixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quanixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quanixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J091. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quanixarcha obafia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Quanixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quanixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Quanixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Quanixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is J091. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Quanixarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Quapifarcha iralella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quapifarcha iralella (N.L. fem. n. *iralella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHUUF01 sp018817005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018814205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.22 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quapifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quapifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quapifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHUUF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quapifarcha iralella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ifrisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quapusarcha unafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quapusarcha unafella (N.L. fem. n. *unafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAEHKU01 sp016838825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016838825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.83 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quapusarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Quapusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quapusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAEHKU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quapusarcha unafella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quarasarcha efagana sp. nov.

Candidatus Quarasarcha efagana (N.L. fem. n. *efagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIPHS01 sp903864915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903857235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.29 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quarasarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Quarasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quarasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIPHS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quarasarcha efagana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Laxucarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quasacarcha ubemaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Quasacarcha ubemaria (N.L. fem. n. *ubemaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JACQNA01 sp016203335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.17 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quasacarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quasacarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quasacarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQNA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quasacarcha ubemaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Quasacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quasacarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Quasacarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Quasacarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQNA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Quasacarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Quastalarcha quebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quastalarcha quebaria (N.L. fem. n. *quebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGDG01 sp016932245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.62 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quastalarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quastalarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quastalarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGDG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quastalarcha quebaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quastebarcha epebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quastebarcha epebana (N.L. fem. n. *epebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFMDN01 sp017857235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017857235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.88 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quastebarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quastebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quastebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFMDN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quastebarcha epebana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tuxefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quatexarcha ebapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quatexarcha ebapana (N.L. fem. n. *ebapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHZQ01 sp018656555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018649855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.27 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quatexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quatexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quatexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHZQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quatexarcha ebapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quatruxarcha inemaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quatruxarcha inemaria (N.L. fem. n. *inemaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPLS01 sp016186375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016186375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.31 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quatruxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quatruxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quatruxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPLS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quatruxarcha inemaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quatugarcha asabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quatugarcha asabosa (N.L. fem. n. *asabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSAX01 sp011046235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011046235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.46 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quatugarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quatugarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quatugarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSAX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quatugarcha asabosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cutiparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quebrexarcha apevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quebrexarcha apevana (N.L. fem. n. *apevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRGT01 sp016838795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016838795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.93 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quebrexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quebrexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quebrexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRGT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quebrexarcha apevana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quebrexarcha ifatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quebrexarcha ifatella (N.L. fem. n. *ifatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRGT01 sp016838845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016838845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.02 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quebrexarcha uvacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quebrexarcha uvacosa (N.L. fem. n. *uvacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRGT01 sp011055585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011055585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.19 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quecanarcha ugepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quecanarcha ugepana (N.L. fem. n. *ugepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SpSt-1120 sp011373045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011373045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.23 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quecanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quecanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quecanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is SpSt-1120. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quecanarcha ugepana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Quecanarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quecanarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Quecanarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Quecanarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SpSt-1120. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Quecanarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Coxosarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Quecirarcha itavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quecirarcha itavosa (N.L. fem. n. *itavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJGQ01 sp018824365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018812845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.2 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quecirarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quecirarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quecirarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJGQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quecirarcha itavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quedrogarcha ibetana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quedrogarcha ibetana (N.L. fem. n. *ibetana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAISDH01 sp903884115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903884115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.05 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quedrogarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quedrogarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quedrogarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAISDH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quedrogarcha ibetana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Micrarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quedrumarcha ecaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quedrumarcha ecaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQNW01 sp016202845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.24 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quedrumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quedrumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quedrumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQNW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quedrumarcha ecaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Queficarcha omaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Queficarcha omaposa (N.L. fem. n. *omaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B78-G9 sp003650975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.04 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Queficarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Queficarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Queficarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B78-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Queficarcha omaposa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Parutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quefresarcha acafana sp. nov.

Candidatus Quefresarcha acafana (N.L. fem. n. *acafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPKT01 sp016186855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016186855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.45 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quefresarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Quefresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quefresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPKT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quefresarcha acafana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lagufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quefrobarcha adevosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Quefrobarcha adevosa (N.L. fem. n. *adevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS23 sp002686195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002686195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.72 % and the genome length is 3.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quefrobarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Quefrobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quefrobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS23. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quefrobarcha adevosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quemidarcha odecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quemidarcha odecaria (N.L. fem. n. *odecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRKL01 sp016219835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016219835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.18 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quemidarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quemidarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quemidarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRKL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quemidarcha odecaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Quemidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quemidarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Quemidarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Quemidarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACRKL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Quemidarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Quenucarcha ogalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quenucarcha ogalana (N.L. fem. n. *ogalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQLL01 sp016234025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016234025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.14 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quenucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quenucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quenucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQLL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quenucarcha ogalana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quepligarcha umacosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Quepligarcha umacosa (N.L. fem. n. *umacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTNT01 sp011358475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011358475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.69 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quepligarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Quepligarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quepligarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTNT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quepligarcha umacosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Queplusarcha ecemosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Queplusarcha ecemosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecemosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJIL01 sp018335335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018335335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.17 % and the genome length is 2.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Queplusarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Queplusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Queplusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJIL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Queplusarcha ecemosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Queplusarcha etecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Queplusarcha etecia (N.L. fem. n. *etecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJIL01 sp014730275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014730275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.22 % and the genome length is 3.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Queprefarcha etecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Queprefarcha etecana (N.L. fem. n. *etecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPNC01 sp016185685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016185685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.33 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Queprefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Queprefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Queprefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPNC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Queprefarcha etecana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Queprudarcha udexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Queprudarcha udexana (N.L. fem. n. *udexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIVW01 sp018816245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018816245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.85 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Queprudarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Queprudarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Queprudarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JAHIVW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Queprudarcha udexana. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Queragarcha iregana sp. nov.

Candidatus Queragarcha iregana (N.L. fem. n. *iregana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACAEI01 sp013388905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013388905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.74 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Queragarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Queragarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Queragarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACAEI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Queragarcha iregana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Queragarcha ofabella sp. nov.

Candidatus Queragarcha ofabella (N.L. fem. n. *ofabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACAEI01 sp013388895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013388895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.09 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Questofarcha uvecaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Questofarcha uvecaria (N.L. fem. n. *uvecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JDFR-14 sp002011085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002011085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.96 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Questofarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Questofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Questofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JDFR-14. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Questofarcha uvecaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quetaparcha ivalosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetaparcha ivalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGCN01 sp016932615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.71 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quetaparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Quetaparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quetaparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGCN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quetaparcha ivalosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Idrufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quetisarcha duvella sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha duvella (N.L. fem. n. *duvella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp018694115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018696115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.95 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quetisarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quetisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JAGVXH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quetisarcha duvella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quetisarcha ecedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha ecedosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp018303845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.01 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetisarcha elaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha elaxella (N.L. fem. n. *elaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp018697035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018692495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.38 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetisarcha eveposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha eveposa (N.L. fem. n. *eveposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp002688415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.72 % and the genome length is 0.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetisarcha ibaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha ibaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ibaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp018830525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.5 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetisarcha ogedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha ogedella (N.L. fem. n. *ogedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp018901375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018901375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.11 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetisarcha ucepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha ucepia (N.L. fem. n. *ucepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp018693315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018693315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.66 % and the genome length is 0.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetisarcha umacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha umacella (N.L. fem. n. *umacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp003693875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003693875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.68 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetisarcha urabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetisarcha urabosa (N.L. fem. n. *urabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXH01 sp018697295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018697295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.84 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetrirarcha erabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quetrirarcha erabaria (N.L. fem. n. *erabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPLT01 sp016186365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016186365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.79 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quetrirarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quetrirarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quetrirarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPLT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quetrirarcha erabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quexocarcha cufia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quexocarcha cufia (N.L. fem. n. *cufia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHQR01 sp018696395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018674115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.07 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quexocarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quexocarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quexocarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHQR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quexocarcha cufia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quexurarcha itabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quexurarcha itabana (N.L. fem. n. *itabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIVP01 sp018816335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018816335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.79 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quexurarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quexurarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quexurarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIVP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quexurarcha itabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quibuxarcha ipabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quibuxarcha ipabella (N.L. fem. n. *ipabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJJK01 sp014729705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.51 % and the genome length is 2.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quibuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quibuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quibuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJJK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quibuxarcha ipabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiragarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quicasarcha ecafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quicasarcha ecafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ecafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-I sp002720275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.72 % and the genome length is 1.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quicasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quicasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quicasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MGIIa-I. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quicasarcha ecafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Poseidoniaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quicasarcha efaella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quicasarcha efaella (N.L. fem. n. *efaella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-I sp002692465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002692465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.75 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quicasarcha ilepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quicasarcha ilepia (N.L. fem. n. *ilepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-I sp002699515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002699515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.74 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quicasarcha ofamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quicasarcha ofamosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-I sp002498205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.32 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quicasarcha omafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quicasarcha omafana (N.L. fem. n. *omafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-I sp002696315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002504695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.49 % and the genome length is 1.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quicasarcha ovafofa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quicasarcha ovafofa (N.L. fem. n. *ovafofa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MGIIa-I sp002720095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.51 % and the genome length is

2.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quidefarcha ofepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quidefarcha ofepella (N.L. fem. n. *ofepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRNV01 sp016214785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016214785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.22 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quidefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quidefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quidefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRNV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quidefarcha ofepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Quidefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quidefarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Quidefarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Quidefarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACRNV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Quidefarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ocuparchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Quiglusarcha iveposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quiglusarcha iveposa (N.L. fem. n. *iveposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTOY01 sp011358085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011358085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.1 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quiglusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quiglusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quiglusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTOY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quimapsarcha iveposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitigarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quimapsarcha adepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quimapsarcha adepella (N.L. fem. n. *adepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJOV01 sp009618475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009618475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.24 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quimapsarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quimapsarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quimapsarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJOV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quimapsarcha adepella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quimapsarcha elacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quimapsarcha elacosa (N.L. fem. n. *elacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJOV01 sp016782355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016782355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.17 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quisalsarcha ibalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quisalsarcha ibalana (N.L. fem. n. *ibalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALW01 sp015522645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.16 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quisalarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quisalarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quisalarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quisalarcha ibalana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Acidilobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quisalarcha umenosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quisalarcha umenosa (N.L. fem. n. *umenosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALW01 sp015522635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.61 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quisebarcha ebagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quisebarcha ebagana (N.L. fem. n. *ebagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCFJ01 sp017608705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.43 % and the genome length is 0.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quisebarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quisebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quisebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCFJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quisebarcha ebagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quisodarcha omecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quisodarcha omecia (N.L. fem. n. *omecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MNVX01 sp018304325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.86 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quisodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quisodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quisodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MNVX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quisodarcha omecia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quisodarcha ubamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quisodarcha ubamosa (N.L. fem. n. *ubamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MNVX01 sp001872185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002792685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.56 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quistetarcha umenia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quistetarcha umenia (N.L. fem. n. *umenia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJKD01 sp014729315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014729315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.64 % and the genome length is 6.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quistetarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quistetarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quistetarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJKD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quistetarcha umenia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quistoxarcha evegaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quistoxarcha evegaria (N.L. fem. n. *evegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS150m-G64 sp016784195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016784195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.75 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quistoxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quistoxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quistoxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BS150m-G64. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quistoxarcha evegaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quistugarcha ibavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quistugarcha ibavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ibavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMGN01 sp018303895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.48 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quistugarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quistugarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quistugarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CABMGN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quistugarcha ibavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quistugarcha ogedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quistugarcha ogedia (N.L. fem. n. *ogedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMGN01 sp902385635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.86 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quixinarcha isataria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quixinarcha isataria (N.L. fem. n. *isataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS1309 sp002688015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.43 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quixinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quixinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quixinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS1309. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quixinarcha isataria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quofrirarcha asedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quofrirarcha asedana (N.L. fem. n. *asedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPLR01 sp018304985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.56 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quofrirarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quofrirarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quofrirarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPLR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quofrirarcha asedana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quofrirarcha otevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quofrirarcha otevia (N.L. fem. n. *otevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPLR01 sp016186425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016186425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.47 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quolodarcha ucaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quolodarcha ucaxella (N.L. fem. n. *ucaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIEH01 sp018901675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018901675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.95 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quolodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quolodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quolodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIEH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quolodarcha ucaxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quopotarcha ibafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quopotarcha ibafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ibafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADIF01 sp013151465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013151465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.42 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quopotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quopotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quopotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JAADIF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quopotarcha ibafaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Badimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quopotarcha ufebaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Quopotarcha ufebaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADIF01 sp016932735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016932735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.53 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quosexarcha ebefaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Quosexarcha ebefaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOYA01 sp018221105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.23 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Quosexarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Quosexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quosexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOYA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Quosexarcha ebefaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Quosexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Quosexarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Quosexarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Quosexarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAAOYA01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Quosexarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Quosimarcha avefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quosimarcha avefosa (N.L. fem. n. *avefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B72-G16 sp003650545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.23 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quosimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quosimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quosimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B72-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quosimarcha avefosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Quosimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quosimarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Quosimarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Quosimarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B72-G16. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Quosimarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Quostomarcha edebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quostomarcha edebella (N.L. fem. n. *edebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOXV01 sp018220955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018220955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.09 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quostomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quostomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quostomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOXV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quostomarcha edebella*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iduparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Quoxefarcha epavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Quoxefarcha epavella (N.L. fem. n. *epavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QCWD01 sp013114725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013114725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.82 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Quoxefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Quoxefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Quoxefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QCWD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Quoxefarcha epavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrososphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rafemarcha ecabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rafemarcha ecabaria (N.L. fem. n. *ecabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PEVX01 sp002780285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002780285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.25 % and the genome length is 0.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rafemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rafemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rafemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PEVX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rafemarcha ecabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rafemarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rafemarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Rafemarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Rafemarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PEVX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Rafemarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pacearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ragrugrarcha aselaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ragrugrarcha aselaria (N.L. fem. n. *aselaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYR01 sp018303185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.85 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ragrugrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ragrugrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ragrugrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ragrugrarcha aselaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ramotarcha buvaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ramotarcha buvaria (N.L. fem. n. *buvaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIAG01 sp018653365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018672335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.95 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ramotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ramotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ramotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABIAG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ramotarcha buvaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ramotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ramotarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ramotarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ramotarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JABIAG01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ramotarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Rasafrarcha ovabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rasafrarcha ovabana (N.L. fem. n. *ovabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VHBL01 sp016871995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016871995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.9 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rasafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rasafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rasafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VHBL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rasafrarcha ovabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Oclimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ratistarcha itaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ratistarcha itaparia (N.L. fem. n. *itaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SKVC01 sp007129655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003559355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.32 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ratistarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ratistarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ratistarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SKVC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ratistarcha itaparia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natronoplasmataceae*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Ratrecarcha isadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ratrecarcha isadana (N.L. fem. n. *isadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQT01 sp015520105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.91 % and the genome length is 0.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ratrecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ratrecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ratrecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ratrecarcha isadana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ratrigrarcha ifevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ratrigrarcha ifevaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXI01 sp018303855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.85 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ratrigrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ratrigrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ratrigrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ratrofrarcha ifevaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Ratrofrarcha abemosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Ratrofrarcha abemosa (N.L. fem. n. *abemosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCGF01 sp017608295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.12 % and the genome length is 3.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Ratrofrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Ratrofrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ratrofrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCGF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ratrofrarcha abemosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tafrurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Raxestarcha itacella sp. nov.

Candidatus Raxestarcha itacella (N.L. fem. n. *itacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2726865 sp014381835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014381835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.4 % and the genome length is 2.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Raxestarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Raxestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Raxestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2726865. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Raxestarcha itacella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ibidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Raxestarcha usecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Raxestarcha usecana (N.L. fem. n. *usecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2726865 sp002726865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002726865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.4 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rebasarcha atafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rebasarcha atafaria (N.L. fem. n. *atafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-002838935 sp002838935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002838935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.69 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rebasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rebasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rebasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-002838935. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rebasarcha atafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rebasarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rebasarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Rebasarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Rebasarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-002838935. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Rebasarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Dumacarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Rebretarcha igafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rebretarcha igafosa (N.L. fem. n. *igafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTIH01 sp011334515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011334515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.66 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rebretarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rebretarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rebretarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTIH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rebretarcha igafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Anstonellaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rebrosarcha edevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rebrosarcha edevana (N.L. fem. n. *edevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGTRE01 sp018396415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.81 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rebrosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rebrosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rebrosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGTRE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rebrosarcha edevana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rebrosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rebrosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Rebrosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Rebrosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGTRE01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Rebrosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pisenarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Redixarcha avaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Redixarcha avaparia (N.L. fem. n. *avaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTKX01 sp011333475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011333475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.11 % and the genome length is 3.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Redixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Redixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Redixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTKX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Redixarcha avaparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Redixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Redixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Redixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Redixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTKX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Redixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Redixarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Redixarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Redixarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Redixarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTKX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Redixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha ecarella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha ecarella (N.L. fem. n. *ecarella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp018238205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018238205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.77 % and the genome length is 3.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Refrexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MP8T-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Refrexarcha ecarella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha efatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha efatia (N.L. fem. n. *efatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp018238825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018238825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.68 % and the genome length is 2.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha esefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha esefosa (N.L. fem. n. *esefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp003345545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003345545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.11 % and the genome length is 2.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha idapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha idapia (N.L. fem. n. *idapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp016840385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.09 % and the genome length is 3.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha itapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha itapana (N.L. fem. n. *itapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp002825465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002825465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.62 % and the genome length is 3.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha otexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha otexella (N.L. fem. n. *otexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp016839245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.14 % and the genome length is 3.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha umaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha umaposa (N.L. fem. n. *umaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp016933575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016933575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.33 % and the genome length is 3.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha unafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha unafana (N.L. fem. n. *unafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp004524565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.58 % and the genome length is 3.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha unavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha unavosa (N.L. fem. n. *unavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp016839275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.17 % and the genome length is

3.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrexarcha usegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrexarcha usegia (N.L. fem. n. *usegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MP8T-1 sp004524595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.65 % and the genome length is 4.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrodarcha onabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refrodarcha onabaria (N.L. fem. n. *onabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGJA01 sp016867655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016867655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.97 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refrodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Refrodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Refrodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGJA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Refrodarcha onabaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiragarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Refuxarcha ogalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Refuxarcha ogalosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGUC01 sp016938695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016938695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.35 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Refuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Refuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Refuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGUC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Refuxarcha ogalosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Refuxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Refuxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Refuxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Refuxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGUC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Refuxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Regomarcha ovamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Regomarcha ovamaria (N.L. fem. n. *ovamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BM511 sp002867475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002867475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.0 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Regomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Regomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Regomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BM511. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Regomarcha ovamaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Regomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Regomarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Regomarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Regomarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is BM511. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Regomarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Regrisarcha egavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Regrisarcha egavia (N.L. fem. n. *egavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SICV01 sp016866955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016866955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.72 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Regrisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Regrisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Regrisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SICV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Regrisarcha egavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Regrisarcha ogapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Regrisarcha ogapia (N.L. fem. n. *ogapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SICV01 sp009694725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009694725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.29 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Regrisarcha onevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Regrisarcha onevaria (N.L. fem. n. *onevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SICV01 sp016196285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016196285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.28 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Remegrarcha imadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Remegrarcha imadia (N.L. fem. n. *imadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA285 sp011364525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011366445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.06 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Remegrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Remegrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Remegrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA285. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Remegrarcha imadia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Desulfurococcaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Remegrarcha ipetella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Remegrarcha ipetella (N.L. fem. n. *ipetella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA285 sp011380285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011380285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.65 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Remegrarcha obavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Remegrarcha obavella (N.L. fem. n. *obavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA285 sp011056815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011056815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.53 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Remegrarcha ocabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Remegrarcha ocabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA285 sp011380145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011380145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.58 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Remegrarcha udafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Remegrarcha udafia (N.L. fem. n. *udafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA285 sp011375785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011375785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.86 % and the genome length is 0.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Remegrarcha upavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Remegrarcha upavella (N.L. fem. n. *upavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA285 sp002495025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.98 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Reprifrarcha upetosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Reprifrarcha upetosa (N.L. fem. n. *upetosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10204 sp10204u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.38 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Reprifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Reprifrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Reprifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10204. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Reprifrarcha upetosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Restaprarcha ucerosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Restaprarcha ucerosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucerosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is DTMT01 sp018396565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.05 % and the genome length is 1.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Restaprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Restaprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Restaprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTMT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Restaprarcha ucerosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bosatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Restaprarcha ufecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Restaprarcha ufecosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTMT01 sp011355205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011355205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.36 % and the genome length is 1.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Restaprarcha usegaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Restaprarcha usegaria (N.L. fem. n. *usegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTMT01 sp018396915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.49 % and the genome length is 1.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rideprarcha ocanosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rideprarcha ocanosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocanosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQOC01 sp016202785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.67 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rideprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rideprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rideprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving

the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQOC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rideprarcha ocanosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Riprefarcha onexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Riprefarcha onexia (N.L. fem. n. *onexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJTO01 sp018829845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018829845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.96 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Riprefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Riprefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Riprefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJTO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Riprefarcha onexia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Riprefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Riprefarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Riprefarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Riprefarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHJTO01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Riprefarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pacearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Risibarcha ulabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Risibarcha ulabia (N.L. fem. n. *ulabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JAFGSV01 sp016934325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016934325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.06 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Risibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Risibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Risibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGSV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Risibarcha ulabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Risibarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Risibarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Risibarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Risibarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGSV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Risibarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Bimafarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Ristotrarcha eraparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ristotrarcha eraparia (N.L. fem. n. *eraparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRKK01 sp016219795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016219795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.73 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ristotrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ristotrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ristotrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRKK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ristotrarcha eraparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Quemidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Robatarcha edavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robatarcha edavaria (N.L. fem. n. *edavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA525 sp10207u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331575.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.84 % and the genome length is 1.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Robatarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Robatarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Robatarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA525. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Robatarcha edavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Robatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Robatarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Robatarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Robatarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA525. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Robatarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Robatarcha evecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robatarcha evecaria (N.L. fem. n. *evecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA525 sp018221245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.47 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Robatarcha otafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robatarcha otafana (N.L. fem. n. *otafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA525 sp002498125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002498125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.19 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Robemarcha ebevaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robemarcha ebevaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebevaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EA-27 sp005878375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005878375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.29 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Robemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Robemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Robemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EA-27. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Robemarcha ebevaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Robemarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Robemarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Robemarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Robemarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EA-27. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Robemarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Figanarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Robemarcha odafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robemarcha odafosa (N.L. fem. n. *odafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EA-27 sp016207545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016207545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.93 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Robestarcha efanella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robestarcha efanella (N.L. fem. n. *efanella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTCV01 sp011337845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011056405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.29 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Robestarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Robestarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Robestarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTCV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Robestarcha efanella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Zestosphaeraceae*@.

Description of *Candidatus Robestarcha usagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robestarcha usagosa (N.L. fem. n. *usagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTCV01 sp011366425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011369745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.55 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Robufrarcha ofagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robufrarcha ofagella (N.L. fem. n. *ofagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCZ01 sp017610175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.77 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Robufrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Robufrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Robufrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JAFCCZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Robufrarcha ofagella*. According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nogelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Robufrarcha ufadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Robufrarcha ufadana (N.L. fem. n. *ufadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCZ01 sp017609945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.8 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rocruxarcha emagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rocruxarcha emagosa (N.L. fem. n. *emagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QS-5-68-33 sp003023785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003023785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.35 % and the genome length is 2.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rocruxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rocruxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rocruxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QS-5-68-33. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rocruxarcha emagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloarculaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rogrimarcha gixella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rogrimarcha gixella (N.L. fem. n. *gixella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIKOD01 sp903819595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903914655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.45 % and the genome length is 2.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rogrimarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rogrimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rogrimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIKOD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Rogrimarcha gixella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanoregulaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Rogrimarcha irebosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Rogrimarcha irebosa (N.L. fem. n. *irebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIKOD01 sp903828975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903828975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.59 % and the genome length is 2.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Ropricarcha ecalella sp. nov.

Candidatus Ropricarcha ecalella (N.L. fem. n. *ecalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADFH01 sp015521945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.59 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Ropricarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Ropricarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ropricarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADFH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Ropricarcha ecalella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dufoparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Ropricarcha obapana sp. nov.

Candidatus Ropricarcha obapana (N.L. fem. n. *obapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JAADFH01 sp013152995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013152995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.77 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rosutarcha ebasia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rosutarcha ebasia (N.L. fem. n. *ebasia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-42 sp002010305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003935005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.22 % and the genome length is 2.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rosutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rosutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rosutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-42. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rosutarcha ebasia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rosutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rosutarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Rosutarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Rosutarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JdFR-42. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Rosutarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Archaeoglobales*.

Description of *Candidatus Rotegrarcha icabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rotegrarcha icabella (N.L. fem. n. *icabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCJ01 sp017610305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.08 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rotegrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rotegrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rotegrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Rotegrarcha icabella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rotegrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Rotegrarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Rotegrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Rotegrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFCCJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Rotegrarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Iainarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Rucodrarcha opebana sp. nov.

Candidatus Rucodrarcha opebana (N.L. fem. n. *opebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-15 sp002254595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.59 % and the genome length is 0.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Rucodrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Rucodrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rucodrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Rucodrarcha opebana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rucodrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Rucodrarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Rucodrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Rucodrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Rucodrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Thermofilales*.

Description of *Candidatus Rucrafrarcha itedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rucrafrarcha itedana (N.L. fem. n. *itedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PCXY01 sp002762785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002762785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.81 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rucrafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rucrafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rucrafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PCXY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rucrafrarcha itedana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rudrefarcha etaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rudrefarcha etaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *etaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAZWY01 sp014240455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018650895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.26 % and the genome length is 0.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rudrefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rudrefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rudrefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAZWY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rudrefarcha etaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gilonarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rudufarcha inafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rudufarcha inafaria (N.L. fem. n. *inafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAZWY01 sp018698915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018661765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.84 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rudufarcha itavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rudufarcha itavana (N.L. fem. n. *itavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZO01 sp017601145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017601145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.73 % and the genome length is 1.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rudufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rudufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rudufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOZO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rudufarcha itavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rudufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rudufarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Rudufarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Rudufarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAAOZO01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Rudufarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ifutarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Rudufarcha ufabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rudufarcha ufabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ufabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOZO01 sp011605715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011605715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.21 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rufecarcha ufapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rufecarcha ufapana (N.L. fem. n. *ufapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-57-44 sp001871415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.12 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rufecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rufecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rufecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG1-02-57-44. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rufecarcha ufapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rufecarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Rufecarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Rufecarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Rufecarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG1-02-57-44. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Rufecarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Rustenarcha otaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Rustenarcha otaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *otaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIHG01 sp018898425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018898425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.71 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Rustenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Rustenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Rustenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIHG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Rustenarcha otaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sabafarcha vubella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sabafarcha vubella (N.L. fem. n. *vubella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABGXB01 sp018675975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018675975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 23.41 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sabafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sabafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sabafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABGXB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sabafarcha vubella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sabafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sabafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sabafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sabafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JABGXB01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sabafarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sabreocrarcha oceparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sabreocrarcha oceparia (N.L. fem. n. *oceparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA8516 sp8516u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.89 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sabreocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sabreocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sabreocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA8516. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sabreocrarcha ocephala*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Saccharolobus ebamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saccharolobus ebamaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Saccharolobus sp009601705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_009601705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.74 % and the genome length is 2.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saccharolobus ruxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saccharolobus ruxia (N.L. fem. n. *ruxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Saccharolobus sp001719125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007050255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.77 % and the genome length is 2.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saclaxarcha osebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saclaxarcha osebaria (N.L. fem. n. *osebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PL-Br10-U2g16 sp001563995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001563995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.17 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample PL-Br10; brine of Picturesque Lake".

Description of *Candidatus Saclaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Saclaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Saclaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PL-Br10-U2g16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Saclaxarcha osebaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nanosalinaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Saclaxarcha udacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saclaxarcha udacana (N.L. fem. n. *udacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PL-Br10-U2g16 sp014297435. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014297435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.31 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saclocrarcha itecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saclocrarcha itecana (N.L. fem. n. *itecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J152 sp003694525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003694525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.78 % and the genome length is 0.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saclocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Saclocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Saclocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J152. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Saclocrarcha itecana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sacomarcha acagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sacomarcha acagana (N.L. fem. n. *acagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS150m-G63 sp016784165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016784165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.45 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sacomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sacomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sacomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BS150m-G63. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sacomarcha acagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sacomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sacomarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sacomarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sacomarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is BS150m-G63. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sacomarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sadogarcha idavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sadogarcha idavana (N.L. fem. n. *idavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAINOH01 sp903851445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903851445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.6 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sadogarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sadogarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sadogarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAINOH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sadogarcha idavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sadogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sadogarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sadogarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sadogarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CAINOH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Sadogarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Safaprarcha uvatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Safaprarcha uvatana (N.L. fem. n. *uvatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B91-G9 sp003650935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.43 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Safaprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Safaprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Safaprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B91-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Safaprarcha uvatana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gifisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Safebarcha phagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Safebarcha phagana (N.L. fem. n. *phagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WANQ01 sp015521735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.63 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Safebarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Safebarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Safebarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WANQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Safebarcha phagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Safebarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Safebarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Safebarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Safebarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WANQ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Safebarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Sulfolobales*.

Description of *Candidatus Safrostarcha ecataria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Safrostarcha ecataria (N.L. fem. n. *ecataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is A07HB70 sp000496195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000496195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 70.99 % and the genome length is 2.39 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "hypersaline water sample from Lake Tyrrell".

Description of *Candidatus Safrostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Safrostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Safrostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is A07HB70. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Safrostarcha ecataria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloferacaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Salarchaeum esacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Salarchaeum esacella (N.L. fem. n. *esacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Salarchaeum sp007833275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_007833275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.16 % and the genome length is

2.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Salecarcha uvaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Salecarcha uvaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *uvaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRAE01 sp011041895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011041895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.94 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Salecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Salecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Salecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRAE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Salecarcha uvaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Salecarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Salecarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Salecarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Salecarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DRAE01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Salecarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Salecarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Salecarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Salecarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Salecarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DRAE01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Salecarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Korarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Salinarchaeum ipafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Salinarchaeum ipafia (N.L. fem. n. *ipafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Salinarchaeum sp000403645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000403645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 66.59 % and the genome length is 3.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Saliphagus ifesia sp. nov.

Candidatus Saliphagus ifesia (N.L. fem. n. *ifesia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Saliphagus sp003344565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003344565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.37 % and the genome length is 4.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Samitarcha egasella sp. nov.

Candidatus Samitarcha egasella (N.L. fem. n. *egasella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO8 sp003649565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.23 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Samitarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Samitarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Samitarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WYZ-LMO8. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Samitarcha egasella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Samitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Samitarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Samitarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Samitarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WYZ-LMO8. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Samitarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nezhaarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Samitarcha etabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Samitarcha etabia (N.L. fem. n. *etabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO8 sp011362155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011362155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.29 % and the genome length is 0.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Samitarcha evabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Samitarcha evabosa (N.L. fem. n. *evabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO8 sp011605835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011605835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.5 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Samitarcha igacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Samitarcha igacia (N.L. fem. n. *igacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO8 sp003650865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.44 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Samitarcha ubegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Samitarcha ubegana (N.L. fem. n. *ubegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO8 sp011369545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011369545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.21 % and the genome length is 0.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Samitarcha upafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Samitarcha upafaria (N.L. fem. n. *upafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYZ-LMO8 sp004347965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011366535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.58 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saplustarcha usabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saplustarcha usabia (N.L. fem. n. *usabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQA01 sp015520475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.07 % and the genome length is 1.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saplustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Saplustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Saplustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Saplustarcha usabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sapruncha acamia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sapruncha acamia (N.L. fem. n. *acamia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBU01 sp011374155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011374155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.04 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sapruncha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sapruncha (N.L. fem. n. *Sapruncha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTBU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sapruncha acamia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Saprunchaifaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saprunchaifaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBU01 sp011369595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011369595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.4 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saprunchaetavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saprunchaetavana (N.L. fem. n. *etavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBU01 sp011361905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011361905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.88 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saprunchaitafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saprunchaitafaria (N.L. fem. n. *itafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBU01 sp018396755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.82 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saprunchauracaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saprunchauracaria (N.L. fem. n. *uracaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBU01 sp011366665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011366665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.36 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sarafrarchaabevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sarafrarchaabevosa (N.L. fem. n. *abevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-07 sp002010975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002010975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.74 % and the genome length is

0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sarafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sarafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sarafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-07. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sarafrarcha abevosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sarafrarcha olabosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sarafrarcha olabosa (N.L. fem. n. *olabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-07 sp003601605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003601605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.83 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sarobrarcha ucatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sarobrarcha ucatosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucatos*a a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVXK01 sp018303825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.9 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sarobrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sarobrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sarobrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVXK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sarobrarcha ucatosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Satrexarcha ebarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Satrexarcha ebarana (N.L. fem. n. *ebarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA588 sp002509085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003600755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.46 % and the genome length is 2.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Satrexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Satrexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Satrexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA588. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Satrexarcha ebarana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanobacteriaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Satrexarcha osacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Satrexarcha osacella (N.L. fem. n. *osacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA588 sp019084405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018902415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.3 % and the genome length is 2.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Satrexarcha utefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Satrexarcha utefaria (N.L. fem. n. *utefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA588 sp003558085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003558085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.42 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Satrocrarcha phedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Satrocrarcha phedaria (N.L. fem. n. *phedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJW01 sp016198625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.63 % and the genome length is 0.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Satrocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Satrocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Satrocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPJW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Satrocrarcha phedaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Satrocrarcha upefia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Satrocrarcha upefia (N.L. fem. n. *upefia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJW01 sp016187335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.04 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saxararcha onemella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saxararcha onemella (N.L. fem. n. *onemella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BA1 sp001399805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001399805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.09 % and the genome length is 1.93 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Formation waters from coalbed methane well".

Description of *Candidatus Saxararcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Saxararcha (N.L. fem. n. *Saxararcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BA1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Saxararcha onemella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Saxararchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Saxararchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Saxararchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Saxararchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is BA1. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Saxararcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omagarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Saxicarcha igaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saxicarcha igaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *igaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4484-31 sp002254805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.14 % and the genome length is 0.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saxicarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Saxicarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Saxicarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4484-31. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Saxicarcha igaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Saxicarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Saxicarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Saxicarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Saxicarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is EX4484-31. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Saxicarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Pacearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Saxodrarcha egapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Saxodrarcha egapia (N.L. fem. n. *egapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQFM01 sp016200035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016200035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.31 % and the genome length is 1.2

Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Saxodrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Saxodrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Saxodrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQFM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Saxodrarcha egapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Secafarcha idalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Secafarcha idalaria (N.L. fem. n. *idalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B15-G2 sp003649445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.6 % and the genome length is 3.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Secafarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Secafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Secafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B15-G2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Secafarcha idalaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Secafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Secafarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Secafarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Secafarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B15-G2. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Secafarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Thermofilales*.

Description of *Candidatus Secafarcha obalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Secafarcha obagaria (N.L. fem. n. *obagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B15-G2 sp003650815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.18 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Seclotarcha ucataria sp. nov.

Candidatus Seclotarcha ucataria (N.L. fem. n. *ucataria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGRH01 sp016935265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.95 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Seclotarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Seclotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Seclotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGRH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Seclotarcha ucataria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Secoparcha ivabia sp. nov.

Candidatus Secoparcha ivabia (N.L. fem. n. *ivabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10107 sp10107u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.8 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Secoparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Secoparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Secoparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10107. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Secoparcha ivabia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Secoparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Secoparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Secoparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Secoparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA10107. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Secoparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Secoparcha ivedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Secoparcha ivedana (N.L. fem. n. *ivedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10107 sp016935155. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935155.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.75 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Secribrarcha itepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Secribrarcha itepia (N.L. fem. n. *itepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQJF01 sp016198165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.52 % and the genome length is 0.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Secribrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Secribrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Secribrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQJF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Secribrarcha itepia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lagufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Secrofrarcha icebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Secrofrarcha icebana (N.L. fem. n. *icebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACCLJ01 sp011358535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011358535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.13 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Secrofrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Secrofrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Secrofrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACCLJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Secrofrarcha icebana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Secrofrarcha ocavella sp. nov.

Candidatus Secrofrarcha ocavella (N.L. fem. n. *ocavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACCLJ01 sp013425425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013425425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.42 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Secubrarcha epadaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Secubrarcha epadaria (N.L. fem. n. *epadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA467 sp002503825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.91 % and the genome length is 2.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Secubrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Secubrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Secubrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA467. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Secubrarcha epadaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanoregulaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sedrerarcha ogabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sedrerarcha ogabia (N.L. fem. n. *ogabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAQV01 sp015520065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.55 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sedrerarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sedrerarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sedrerarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAQV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sedrerarcha ogabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sefacrarcha igefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sefacrarcha igefana (N.L. fem. n. *igefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADEL01 sp015520875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.55 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sefacrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sefacrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sefacrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADEL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sefacrarcha igefana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiresarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sefacrarcha opaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sefacrarcha opaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *opaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADEL01 sp013153395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013153395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.96 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sefacrarcha osagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sefacrarcha osagosa (N.L. fem. n. *osagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADEL01 sp011380495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011380495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.4 % and the genome length is 0.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sefrubrarcha etamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sefrubrarcha etamosa (N.L. fem. n. *etamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is S143-98 sp015520975. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.56 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sefrubrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sefrubrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sefrubrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is S143-98. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sefrubrarcha etamosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aciduliprofundaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Segludrarcha ocavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Segludrarcha ocavaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAMV01 sp015522145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.18 % and the genome length is

0.32 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Segludrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Segludrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Segludrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAMV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Segludrarcha ocavaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Disocarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Semastarcha opabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Semastarcha opabaria (N.L. fem. n. *opabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GW2011-AR13 sp9966u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.61 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Semastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Semastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Semastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GW2011-AR13. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Semastarcha opabaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Semiprarcha obavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Semiprarcha obavaria (N.L. fem. n. *obavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJSX01 sp018830205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018830205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.25 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Semiprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Semiprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Semiprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJSX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Semiprarcha obavaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hydrothermarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Senicrarcha eceparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Senicrarcha eceparia (N.L. fem. n. *eceparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QS-1-68-20 sp007122875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007122875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 64.69 % and the genome length is 1.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Senicrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Senicrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Senicrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QS-1-68-20. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Senicrarcha eceparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Senicrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Senicrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Senicrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Senicrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QS-1-68-20. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Senicrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Halobacteriales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sepodrarcha udefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sepodrarcha udefosa (N.L. fem. n. *udefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRMZ01 sp016219455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016219455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.15 % and the genome length is

0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sepodrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sepodrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sepodrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRMZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sepodrarcha udefosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sepodrachaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sepodrachaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sepodrachaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sepodrachaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACRMZ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sepodrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Butolarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sepotarcha uvabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sepotarcha uvabana (N.L. fem. n. *uvabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCC01 sp017610385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.36 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sepotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sepotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sepotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sepotarcha uvabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sepotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sepotarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sepotarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sepotarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFCCC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Sepotarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nanosalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Seprecarcha iregella sp. nov.

Candidatus Seprecarcha iregella (N.L. fem. n. *iregella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGKX01 sp016866895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016866895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.04 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Seprecarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Seprecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Seprecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGKX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Seprecarcha iregella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Seprecarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Seprecarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Seprecarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Seprecarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is VGKX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Seprecarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Anstonellales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Serofarcha uvagella sp. nov.

Candidatus Serofarcha uvagella (N.L. fem. n. *uvagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG1-02-47-40 sp001871475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.03 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Serofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Serofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Serofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG1-02-47-40. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Serofarcha uvagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Serofarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Serofarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Serofarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Serofarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG1-02-47-40. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Serofarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Anstonellales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sestadrarcha idaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sestadrarcha idaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *idaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAYZC01 sp012515075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012515075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.92 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sestadrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sestadrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sestadrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAYZC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sestadrarcha idaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sestecrarcha epegia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sestecrarcha epegia (N.L. fem. n. *epegia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIVR01 sp018816625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018816625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.88 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sestecrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sestecrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sestecrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIVR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sestecrarcha epegia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sestilarcha asaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sestilarcha asaxia (N.L. fem. n. *asaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBJ01 sp011364225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011369685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.66 % and the genome length is 0.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sestilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sestilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sestilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTBJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sestilarcha asaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Desulfurococcaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Setreprarcha ofalaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Setreprarcha ofalaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofalaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOYF01 sp018221205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.3 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Setreprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Setreprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Setreprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOYF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Setreprarcha ofalaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixiprarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Setrustarcha opebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Setrustarcha opebia (N.L. fem. n. *opebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYM01 sp018303245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.45 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Setrustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Setrustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Setrustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Setrustarcha opebia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sicatrarcha acegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sicatrarcha acegosa (N.L. fem. n. *acegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACOVT01 sp016177165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016177165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.34 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sicatrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sicatrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sicatrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACOVT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sicatrarcha acegosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sicatrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sicatrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sicatrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sicatrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACOVT01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sicatrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Oferarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Siclunarcha uraxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Siclunarcha uraxosa (N.L. fem. n. *uraxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MVQI01 sp002067795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.33 % and the genome length is 1.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Siclunarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Siclunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Siclunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MVQI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Siclunarcha uraxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanotrichaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sidrufrarcha itecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sidrufrarcha itecia (N.L. fem. n. *itecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYZ01 sp018303025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.98 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sidrufrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sidrufrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sidrufrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sidrufrarcha itecia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sifixarcha igaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sifixarcha igaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *igaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTDX01 sp011338225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011338225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.71 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sifixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sifixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sifixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTDX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sifixarcha igaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sifixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sifixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sifixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sifixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTDX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sifixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Omubarchales.

Description of *Candidatus Sifixarcha ofapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sifixarcha ofapella (N.L. fem. n. *ofapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTDX01 sp011369655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011369655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.81 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sifixarcha ufadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sifixarcha ufadia (N.L. fem. n. *ufadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTDX01 sp018396815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.94 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sifixarcha umavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sifixarcha umavana (N.L. fem. n. *umavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTDX01 sp018396775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.45 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sifomarcha eravella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sifomarcha eravella (N.L. fem. n. *eravella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is YT1-057 sp016839955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.72 % and the genome length is 5.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sifomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sifomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sifomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is YT1-057. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sifomarcha eravella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sifomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sifomarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sifomarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sifomarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is YT1-057. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sifomarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Hodarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Siglefarcha ategia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Siglefarcha ategia (N.L. fem. n. *ategia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9653 sp011391345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011391345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.59 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Siglefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Siglefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Siglefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA9653. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Siglefarcha ategia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hiturarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Siglefarcha ecanaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Siglefarcha ecanaria (N.L. fem. n. *ecanaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9653 sp018818785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014859835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.79 % and the genome length is 1.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Siglefarcha ucanosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Siglefarcha ucanosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucanosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9653 sp9653u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 60.23 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sigolarcha epavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sigolarcha epavia (N.L. fem. n. *epavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGPW01 sp016935985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016935985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.79 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sigolarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sigolarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sigolarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGPW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sigolarcha epavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sigolarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sigolarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sigolarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sigolarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGPW01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sigolarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sigrabarcha ifararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sigrabarcha ifararia (N.L. fem. n. *ifararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCU01 sp017610005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.96 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sigrabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sigrabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sigrabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sigrabarcha ifararia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Febimarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Silucrarcha udapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Silucrarcha udapia (N.L. fem. n. *udapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1452 sp015662385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015662385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.12 % and the genome length is 0.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Silucrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Silucrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Silucrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZUA-1452. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Silucrarcha udapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dupisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Siluxarcha ifapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Siluxarcha ifapana (N.L. fem. n. *ifapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 21-14-0-10-32-9 sp903891505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903891505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.83 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Siluxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Siluxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Siluxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 21-14-0-10-32-9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Siluxarcha ifapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Siluxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Siluxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Siluxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Siluxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is 21-14-0-10-32-9. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Siluxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Siluxarcha ocabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Siluxarcha ocabia (N.L. fem. n. *ocabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 21-14-0-10-32-9 sp002762915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002762915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.71 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sinedrarcha icaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sinedrarcha icaxia (N.L. fem. n. *icaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS150m-G60 sp016784245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016784245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.62 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sinedrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sinedrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sinedrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BS150m-G60. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sinedrarcha icaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sinedrarcha vuxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sinedrarcha vuxaria (N.L. fem. n. *vuxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS150m-G60 sp018692925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018661605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.12 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Siribarcha upamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Siribarcha upamella (N.L. fem. n. *upamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B87-G9 sp003649695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.15 % and the genome length is 1.35 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Siribarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Siribarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Siribarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B87-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Siribarcha upamella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Siribarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Siribarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Siribarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Siribarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B87-G9. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Siribarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Siribarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Siribarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Siribarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Siribarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B87-G9. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Siribarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus Sistabrarcha ipefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sistabrarcha ipefella (N.L. fem. n. *ipefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PFCY01 sp002763085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002763085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.27 % and the genome length is 1.15 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sistabrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sistabrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sistabrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PFCY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sistabrarcha ipefella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sistogarcha anacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sistogarcha anacaria (N.L. fem. n. *anacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA164 sp009903795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009903795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.84 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sistogarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sistogarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sistogarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA164. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sistogarcha anacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sistogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sistogarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sistogarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sistogarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA164. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sistogarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Conexivisphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sistogarcha esefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sistogarcha esefana (N.L. fem. n. *esefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA164 sp002506605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.72 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sistogarcha umegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sistogarcha umegella (N.L. fem. n. *umegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA164 sp002499005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.0 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sitrifarcha icagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sitrifarcha icagia (N.L. fem. n. *icagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAH1EM01 sp018901625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018899435.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.34 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sitrifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sitrifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sitrifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIEM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sitrifarcha icagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sixutarcha elaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sixutarcha elaxana (N.L. fem. n. *elaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZ-28-30 sp018992565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018992565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.74 % and the genome length is 2.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sixutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sixutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sixutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZ-28-30. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sixutarcha elaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sixutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sixutarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sixutarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sixutarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SZ-28-30. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sixutarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanofastidiosales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sixutarcha icadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sixutarcha icadella (N.L. fem. n. *icadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZ-28-30 sp018992685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018992685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.69 % and the genome length is 3.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha duvaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha duvaria (N.L. fem. n. *duvaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA460 sp018238545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018238545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.01 % and the genome length is 3.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sobomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA460. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sobomarcha duvaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sobomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sobomarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA460. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sobomarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Kariarchaeales*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha idaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha idaxella (N.L. fem. n. *idaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA460 sp016839985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.85 % and the genome length is 2.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha ivedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha ivedella (N.L. fem. n. *ivedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA460 sp013166775. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013166775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.91 % and the genome length is 3.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha ocesosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha ocesosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocesosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA460 sp001940755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001940755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.36 % and the genome length is 2.28 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Marine sediment".

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha opamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha opamaria (N.L. fem. n. *opamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA460 sp016840095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016840095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.24 % and the genome length is 3.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha ubemana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha ubemana (N.L. fem. n. *ubemana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA460 sp016839945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.16 % and the genome length is 3.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha ufatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha ufatia (N.L. fem. n. *ufatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA460 sp016839875. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_016839875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.64 % and the genome length is 3.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobomarcha urafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobomarcha urafia (N.L. fem. n. *urafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA460 sp002505645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.09 % and the genome length is 3.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobridarcha ecatella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobridarcha ecatella (N.L. fem. n. *ecatella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRZP01 sp011373125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011373125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.13 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobridarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sobridarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sobridarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRZP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sobridarcha ecatella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Zestosphaeraceae*@.

Description of *Candidatus Sobridarcha onabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobridarcha onabella (N.L. fem. n. *onabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRZP01 sp011375535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011375535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.63 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobucarcha ebatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobucarcha ebatosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA184 sp002495185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.84 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sobucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sobucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA184. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sobucarcha ebatosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sobucarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sobucarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sobucarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sobucarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA184. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sobucarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Sobucarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sobucarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Sobucarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Sobucarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA184. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sobucarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus Sobucarcha egafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobucarcha egafosa (N.L. fem. n. *egafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA184 sp013290045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013290045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.38 % and the genome length is

2.23 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobucarcha olacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobucarcha olacia (N.L. fem. n. *olacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA184 sp013044425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013044425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.3 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sobucarcha usecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sobucarcha usecella (N.L. fem. n. *usecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA184 sp002503985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.14 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Soclostarcha unapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Soclostarcha unapella (N.L. fem. n. *unapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTQF01 sp011332735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011332735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.11 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Soclostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Soclostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Soclostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTQF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Soclostarcha unapella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Filatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sodacrarcha ecaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sodacrarcha ecaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ecaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SZUA-1508 sp015661855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015661855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.51 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sodacrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sodacrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sodacrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SZUA-1508. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sodacrarcha ecaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sodacrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sodacrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sodacrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sodacrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SZUA-1508. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sodacrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Noradarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sodirarcha amecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sodirarcha amecella (N.L. fem. n. *amecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA213 sp011331095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011331095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.59 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sodirarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sodirarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sodirarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA213. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sodirarcha amecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family

Sodirarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus Sodirarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sodirarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sodirarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA213. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sodirarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nitrososphaerales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sodirarcha ebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sodirarcha ebaria (N.L. fem. n. *ebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA213 sp002713325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.76 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sodofrarcha egarosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sodofrarcha egarosa (N.L. fem. n. *egarosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIKBN01 sp903825675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903825675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.89 % and the genome length is 0.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sodofrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sodofrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sodofrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIKBN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sodofrarcha egarosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sodricarcha edafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sodricarcha edafosa (N.L. fem. n. *edafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGAZ01 sp016933455. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016933455.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.42 % and the genome length is 0.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sodricarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sodricarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sodricarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGAZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sodricarcha edafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aenigmataarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sodunarcha ecatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sodunarcha ecatia (N.L. fem. n. *ecatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B31-G17 sp003649915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.96 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sodunarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sodunarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sodunarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B31-G17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sodunarcha ecatia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sodunarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sodunarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sodunarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sodunarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B31-G17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sodunarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Sodunarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sodunarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Sodunarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Sodunarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B31-G17. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sodunarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus Sofetrarcha onacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sofetrarcha onacella (N.L. fem. n. *onacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALN01 sp015522865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.19 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sofetrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sofetrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sofetrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sofetrarcha onacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofetrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sofetrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sofetrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sofetrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WALN01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sofetrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sofogarcha itefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sofogarcha itefaria (N.L. fem. n. *itefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA233 sp002010925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002010925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.91 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sofogarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sofogarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sofogarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA233. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sofogarcha itefaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sofogarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sofogarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sofogarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA233. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sofogarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omagarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sofogarcha ogebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sofogarcha ogebana (N.L. fem. n. *ogebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA233 sp002507245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002507245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.91 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sofogarcha upamosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sofogarcha upamosa (N.L. fem. n. *upamosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA233 sp003661945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.67 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sofrotrarcha amacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sofrotrarcha amacaria (N.L. fem. n. *amacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMZZ01 sp003663445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.9 % and the genome length is 0.57 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sofrotrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sofrotrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sofrotrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMZZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sofrotrarcha amacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sogexarcha emagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sogexarcha emagaria (N.L. fem. n. *emagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA472 sp016926075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016926075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.09 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sogexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sogexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sogexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA472. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sogexarcha emagaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sogexarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sogexarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sogexarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sogexarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA472. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sogexarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanomassiliicoccales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sogexarcha ilepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sogexarcha ilepana (N.L. fem. n. *ilepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA472 sp002067045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002067045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.09 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sogexarcha ivamana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sogexarcha ivamana (N.L. fem. n. *ivamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA472 sp004525545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004525545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.37 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sogexarcha udexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sogexarcha udexella (N.L. fem. n. *udexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA472 sp002497075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.94 % and the genome length is 1.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sogexarcha ufavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sogexarcha ufavella (N.L. fem. n. *ufavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is UBA472 sp8940u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013329565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.4 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sogexarcha utavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sogexarcha utavaria (N.L. fem. n. *utavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA472 sp012729095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012729095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.71 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Somaxarcha movana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Somaxarcha movana (N.L. fem. n. *movana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABGUJ01 sp018646625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018658585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.89 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Somaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Somaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Somaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABGUJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Somaxarcha movana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Somaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Somaxarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Somaxarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Somaxarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JABGUJ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Somaxarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Somigarcha inafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Somigarcha inafosa (N.L. fem. n. *inafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CG08-08-20-14 sp002762705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002794135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.58 % and the genome length is 1.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Somigarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Somigarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Somigarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CG08-08-20-14. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Somigarcha inafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Somigarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Somigarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Somigarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Somigarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CG08-08-20-14. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Somigarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sonubarcha agepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sonubarcha agepana (N.L. fem. n. *agepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPZZ01 sp016202815. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202815.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.52 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sonubarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sonubarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sonubarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JACPZZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sonubarcha agepana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sonubarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sonubarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sonubarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sonubarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPZZ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sonubarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Sonubarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sonubarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Sonubarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Sonubarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPZZ01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sonubarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Aenigmataarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Sonubarcha erapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sonubarcha erapella (N.L. fem. n. *erapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPZZ01 sp016177205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016177205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.56 % and the genome length is 0.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sonubarcha idanaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sonubarcha idanaria (N.L. fem. n. *idanaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPZZ01 sp016180965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.19 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sonubarcha inegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sonubarcha inegella (N.L. fem. n. *inegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPZZ01 sp016195275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016195275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.29 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sonubarcha ugacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sonubarcha ugacana (N.L. fem. n. *ugacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPZZ01 sp016202795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.17 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sopalarcha uvagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sopalarcha uvagosa (N.L. fem. n. *uvagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOXT01 sp018221045. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221045.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.09 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sopalarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sopalarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sopalarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOXT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sopalarcha uvagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sopalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sopalarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sopalarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sopalarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

taxon is JAAOXT01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Soplarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Getofarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Soplarcha onacia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Soplarcha onacia (N.L. fem. n. *onacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B8-G13 sp003649745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.09 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Soplarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Soplarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Soplarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B8-G13. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Soplarcha onacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Soplarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Soplarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Soplarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Soplarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is B8-G13. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Soplarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Esacarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Soprufarcha apevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Soprufarcha apevella (N.L. fem. n. *apevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGLI01 sp016928115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016928115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.06 % and the genome length is 0.77 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Soprufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Soprufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Soprufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGLI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Soprufarcha apevella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Soprufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Soprufarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Soprufarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Soprufarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGLI01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Soprufarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sorodrarcha utapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sorodrarcha utapia (N.L. fem. n. *utapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEU01 sp017608995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.2 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sorodrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sorodrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sorodrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCEU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sorodrarcha utapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gudamarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sostafrarcha afedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sostafrarcha afedella (N.L. fem. n. *afedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B75-G9 sp012962055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012962055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.47 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sostafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sostafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sostafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B75-G9. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sostafrarcha afedella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hadarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sostafrarcha enaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sostafrarcha enaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *enaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B75-G9 sp003661465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.1 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sotabrarcha emalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sotabrarcha emalana (N.L. fem. n. *emalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BA2 sp001399795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001399795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.2 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Formation waters from coalbed methane well".

Description of *Candidatus Sotabrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sotabrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sotabrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BA2. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sotabrarcha emalana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Saxararchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Soxebrarcha ilasosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Soxebrarcha ilasosa (N.L. fem. n. *ilasosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Tc-Br11-E2g8 sp001564115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001564115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.58 % and the genome length is 2.29 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sample Tc-Br; brine of Tanatar trona crystallizer".

Description of *Candidatus Soxebrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Soxebrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Soxebrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Tc-Br11-E2g8. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Soxebrarcha ilasosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Natrialbaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Soxebrarcha onapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Soxebrarcha onapella (N.L. fem. n. *onapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Tc-Br11-E2g8 sp003552885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003552885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 68.78 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stacremarcha adevia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stacremarcha adevia (N.L. fem. n. *adevia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPRW01 sp016193585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016193585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.53 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stacremarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stacremarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stacremarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPRW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Stacremarcha adevia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Stafegarcha itapia sp. nov.

Candidatus Stafegarcha itapia (N.L. fem. n. *itapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIVED01 sp903904885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903904885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.49 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Stafegarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Stafegarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stafegarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAIVED01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Stafegarcha itapia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nufagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Stafriparcha ucepana sp. nov.

Candidatus Stafriparcha ucepana (N.L. fem. n. *ucepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEJ01 sp017609175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.57 % and the genome length is 0.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Stafriparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Stafriparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stafriparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCEJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Stafriparcha ucepana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stagrofarcha asedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stagrofarcha asedaria (N.L. fem. n. *asedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA153 sp014874255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014874255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.67 % and the genome length is 1.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stagrofarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stagrofarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stagrofarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA153. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stagrofarcha asedaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Robatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stagrofarcha efaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stagrofarcha efaxia (N.L. fem. n. *efaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA153 sp018221165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.85 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stagrofarcha esecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stagrofarcha esecana (N.L. fem. n. *esecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA153 sp002503705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002503705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.63 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stagrofarcha ufexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stagrofarcha ufexia (N.L. fem. n. *ufexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is UBA153 sp003694385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003694385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.03 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stagruxarcha ugafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stagruxarcha ugafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ugafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SG8-52-3 sp001595915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001595915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.37 % and the genome length is 1.91 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-rich zone estuary sediments 8-12 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Stagruxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stagruxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stagruxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SG8-52-3. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stagruxarcha ugafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stapaxarcha ruxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stapaxarcha ruxana (N.L. fem. n. *ruxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA447 sp002503205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002499685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.98 % and the genome length is 1.67 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stapaxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stapaxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stapaxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA447. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stapaxarcha ruxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thermoplasmataceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Statrilarcha ocebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Statrilarcha ocebella (N.L. fem. n. *ocebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is M9B1D sp002900535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002900535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.44 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Statrilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Statrilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Statrilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is M9B1D. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Statrilarcha ocebella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stecuxarcha igafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stecuxarcha igafella (N.L. fem. n. *igafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is FT1-004 sp016839445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016839445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.57 % and the genome length is 2.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stecuxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stecuxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stecuxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is FT1-004. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stecuxarcha igafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stedomarcha ibavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stedomarcha ibavella (N.L. fem. n. *ibavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CSP1-1 sp016276965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016276965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.0 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stedomarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stedomarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stedomarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CSP1-1. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stedomarcha ibavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stedomarcha idalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stedomarcha idalella (N.L. fem. n. *idalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CSP1-1 sp001443365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001443365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.42 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sediment at 5m depth".

Description of *Candidatus Stedomarcha odegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stedomarcha odegana (N.L. fem. n. *odegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CSP1-1 sp008974855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008974855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.21 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stegibarcha elagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stegibarcha elagaria (N.L. fem. n. *elagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJBD01 sp018813725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018813725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.33 % and the genome length is 1.48 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stegibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stegibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stegibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJBD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stegibarcha elagaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Stegibarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stegibarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Stegibarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Stegibarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHJBD01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Stegibarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Stegrobarcha umapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stegrobarcha umapia (N.L. fem. n. *umapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYE01 sp018303445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.61 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stegrobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stegrobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stegrobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYE01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stegrobarcha umapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Steneparcha ipefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Steneparcha ipefana (N.L. fem. n. *ipefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHKAF01 sp018825865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018825865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.5 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Steneparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Steneparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Steneparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHKAF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Steneparcha ipefana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Steneparcha upaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Steneparcha upaxia (N.L. fem. n. *upaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHKAF01 sp018221285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.57 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stetrixarcha acafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stetrixarcha acafella (N.L. fem. n. *acafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is OWC5 sp003345595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003345595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.2 % and the genome length is 2.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stetrixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stetrixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stetrixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is OWC5. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stetrixarcha acafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stetrixarcha ifedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stetrixarcha ifedaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is OWC5 sp003345555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003345555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.12 % and the genome length is 2.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stetromarcha ilevosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stetromarcha ilevosa (N.L. fem. n. *ilevosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPAG01 sp016180945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.72 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stetromarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stetromarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stetromarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPAG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stetromarcha ilevosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stexifarcha ufeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stexifarcha ufeparia (N.L. fem. n. *ufeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PZKD01 sp003034855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003034855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.52 % and the genome length is 1.42 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stexifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stexifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stexifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is PZKD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stexifarcha ufeitaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Stexifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stexifarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Stexifarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Stexifarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is PZKD01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Stexifarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanonatronarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Stibegarcha umabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stibegarcha umabella (N.L. fem. n. *umabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CADDZR01 sp902812495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902812495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.13 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stibegarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stibegarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stibegarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CADDZR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stibegarcha umabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Naraxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stibrutarcha odexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stibrutarcha odexella (N.L. fem. n. *odexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIEG01 sp018901655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018901655.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.51 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stibrutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stibrutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stibrutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIEG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stibrutarcha odexella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Aenigmatarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sticefarcha utavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sticefarcha utavosa (N.L. fem. n. *utavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACAEL01 sp013388835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013388835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.18 % and the genome length is 3.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sticefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sticefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sticefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACAEL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sticefarcha utavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sticilarcha idatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sticilarcha idatia (N.L. fem. n. *idatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WANL01 sp015521825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.99 % and the genome length is 0.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sticilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sticilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sticilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WANL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sticilarcha idatia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ferumarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sticretarcha ucafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sticretarcha ucafella (N.L. fem. n. *ucafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABWCK01 sp013360305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013360305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.04 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sticretarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sticretarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sticretarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABWCK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sticretarcha ucafella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cestotarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stidrifarcha apafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stidrifarcha apafia (N.L. fem. n. *apafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QS-5-70-15 sp003022005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003022005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 70.42 % and the genome length is 3.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stidrifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stidrifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stidrifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QS-5-70-15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stidrifarcha apafia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Haloarculaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stidrucarcha enafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stidrucarcha enafana (N.L. fem. n. *enafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CSSED10-269 sp003558235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003558235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.18 % and the genome length is 0.83 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stidrucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stidrucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stidrucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CSSED10-269. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stidrucarcha enafana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Oferarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stifrugarcha ifabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stifrugarcha ifabana (N.L. fem. n. *ifabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADEY01 sp013153145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013153145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.4 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stifrugarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stifrugarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stifrugarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADEY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stifrugarcha ifabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pyrodictiaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stigodarcha ofapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stigodarcha ofapana (N.L. fem. n. *ofapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BMS3ABIN17 sp002897655. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011050875.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.67 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stigodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stigodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stigodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BMS3ABIN17. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stigodarcha ofapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stinifarcha emavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stinifarcha emavia (N.L. fem. n. *emavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGDV01 sp016931955. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016931955.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.83 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stinifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stinifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stinifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGDV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stinifarcha emavia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Lanaxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stiprinarcha inemella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stiprinarcha inemella (N.L. fem. n. *inemella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOXX01 sp018220935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018220935.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.69 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stiprinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stiprinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stiprinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAAOXX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stiprinarcha inemella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iduparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stiprinarcha obafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stiprinarcha obafella (N.L. fem. n. *obafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAAOXX01 sp018221025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018221025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.8 % and the genome length is 0.63 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stipruxarcha usegella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stipruxarcha usegella (N.L. fem. n. *usegella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRDJ01 sp016218635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016218635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.41 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stipruxarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stipruxarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stipruxarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRDJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stipruxarcha usegella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Goxograrchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stipularcha asabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stipularcha asabana (N.L. fem. n. *asabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BA-13 sp005888695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005888695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.79 % and the genome length is 2.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stipularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stipularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stipularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BA-13. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stipularcha asabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omubarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stipularcha evebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stipularcha evebaria (N.L. fem. n. *evebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BA-13 sp005888675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005888675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.69 % and the genome length is 1.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stitabarcha muparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stitabarcha muparia (N.L. fem. n. *muparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SCGC-AAA471-B05 sp000380705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011380355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.71 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stitabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stitabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stitabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SCGC-AAA471-B05. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stitabarcha muparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gearchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stiximarcha agecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stiximarcha agecella (N.L. fem. n. *agecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10205 sp016202305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.93 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stiximarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stiximarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stiximarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA10205. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stiximarcha agecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iainarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stiximarcha ivetana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stiximarcha ivetana (N.L. fem. n. *ivetana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10205 sp10205u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.78 % and the genome length is 1.43 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stiximarcha phabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stiximarcha phabaria (N.L. fem. n. *phabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA10205 sp005239615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005239615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.26 % and the genome length is 1.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stiximarcha usavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stiximarcha usavosa (N.L. fem. n. *usavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is UBA10205 sp902386385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902386385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.88 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stixucarcha osafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stixucarcha osafosa (N.L. fem. n. *osafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JADFAT01 sp015122075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015122075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.49 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stixucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stixucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stixucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JADFAT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stixucarcha osafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Parvarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stodagarcha elacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stodagarcha elacaria (N.L. fem. n. *elacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDK01 sp017609745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.59 % and the genome length is 0.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stodagarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stodagarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stodagarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stodagarcha elacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stodrabarcha ivedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stodrabarcha ivedia (N.L. fem. n. *ivedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QNYQ01 sp003978665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003978665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.4 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stodrabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stodrabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stodrabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QNYQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stodrabarcha ivedia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pyrodictiaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stodrabarcha ogedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stodrabarcha ogedosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QNYQ01 sp013153105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013153105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 65.54 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stodrabarcha ubegaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stodrabarcha ubegaria (N.L. fem. n. *ubegaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QNYQ01 sp013540595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013540595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.32 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stodufarcha avapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stodufarcha avapana (N.L. fem. n. *avapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEO01 sp017609085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.72 % and the genome length is

0.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stodufarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stodufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stodufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCEO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stodufarcha avapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stofudarcha ivagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stofudarcha ivagia (N.L. fem. n. *ivagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPCA01 sp016177345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016177345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.12 % and the genome length is 1.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stofudarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stofudarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stofudarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPCA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stofudarcha ivagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hamosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stofudarcha ivetosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stofudarcha ivetosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivetosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPCA01 sp016180035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.34 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stolanarcha ipafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stolanarcha ipafaria (N.L. fem. n. *ipafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZM01 sp018302545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.85 % and the genome length is 1.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stolanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stolanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stolanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stolanarcha ipafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Deraparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stoxotarcha igabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stoxotarcha igabana (N.L. fem. n. *igabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHXF01 sp018657385. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018657385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 28.93 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stoxotarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stoxotarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stoxotarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABHXF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stoxotarcha igabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nerisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stoxotarcha urabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stoxotarcha urabia (N.L. fem. n. *urabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABHXF01 sp018661705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018673555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.53 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stublucarcha ofeparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stublucarcha ofeparia (N.L. fem. n. *ofeparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYI01 sp018303365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.93 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stublucarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stublucarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stublucarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYI01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stublucarcha ofeparia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pigafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stubodarcha anabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stubodarcha anabana (N.L. fem. n. *anabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B83-G16 sp003661745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.07 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stubodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stubodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stubodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B83-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stubodarcha anabana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Zestosphaeraceae*@.

Description of *Candidatus Stubrifarcha uvacaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stubrifarcha uvacaria (N.L. fem. n. *uvacaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CABMGU01 sp902385765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_902385765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.36 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stubrifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stubrifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stubrifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CABMGU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stubrifarcha uvacaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Studularcha esecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Studularcha esecella (N.L. fem. n. *esecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHLMR01 sp018920255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018920255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 25.68 % and the genome length is 0.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Studularcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Studularcha (N.L. fem. n. *Studularcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHLMR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Studularcha esecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Studularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Studularchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Studularchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Studularchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHLMR01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Studularcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Aenigmatarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Stufrolarcha enxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stufrolarcha enxaria (N.L. fem. n. *enxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQLK01 sp016204145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016204145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.3 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stufrolarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stufrolarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stufrolarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQLK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stufrolarcha enxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stufrolarcha ilemosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stufrolarcha ilemosa (N.L. fem. n. *ilemosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQLK01 sp016181895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.87 % and the genome length is 0.74 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stumacarcha ogexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stumacarcha ogexana (N.L. fem. n. *ogexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PCYB01 sp002762845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002762845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.94 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stumacarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stumacarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stumacarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is PCYB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stumacarcha ogexana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stumacarcha urabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stumacarcha urabana (N.L. fem. n. *urabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PCYB01 sp018676855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018659235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.35 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stumerarcha idabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stumerarcha idabia (N.L. fem. n. *idabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGHY01 sp016929855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016929855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.78 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stumerarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stumerarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stumerarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGHY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stumerarcha idabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tisoparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stunetarcha imafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stunetarcha imafia (N.L. fem. n. *imafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARS50 sp002687255. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002687255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.45 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stunetarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stunetarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stunetarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARS50. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Stunetarcha imafia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Stupufarcha uvecia sp. nov.

Candidatus Stupufarcha uvecia (N.L. fem. n. *uvecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYF01 sp018303425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.94 % and the genome length is 0.94 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Stupufarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Stupufarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stupufarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYF01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Stupufarcha uvecia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Stupufarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Stupufarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Stupufarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Stupufarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVYF01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Stupufarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Stuxibarcha ivabella sp. nov.

Candidatus Stuxibarcha ivabella (N.L. fem. n. *ivabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WYEQ01 sp009904015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011048525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.5 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Stuxibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Stuxibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Stuxibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WYEQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Stuxibarcha ivabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fervidicoccaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Stygiolobus ocesia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Stygiolobus ocesia (N.L. fem. n. *ocesia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Stygiolobus sp003086555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003086555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.98 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Subixarcha ugadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Subixarcha ugadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ugadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGBV01 sp017610545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017610545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.83 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Subixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Subixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Subixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGBV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Subixarcha ugadaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Subixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Subixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Subixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Subixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAFGBV01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Subixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Axalarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sucastarcha onatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sucastarcha onatana (N.L. fem. n. *onatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJBR01 sp018813445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018813445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.73 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sucastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sucastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sucastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJBR01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sucastarcha onatana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bilamarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sucefrarcha igepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sucefrarcha igepia (N.L. fem. n. *igepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAPT01 sp015520605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.32 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sucefrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sucefrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sucefrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAPT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Sucefrarcha igepia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sucefrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Sucefrarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Sucefrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sucefrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is WAPT01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Sucefrarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Axalarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Sucudarcha afavella sp. nov.

Candidatus Sucudarcha afavella (N.L. fem. n. *afavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVYU01 sp018303105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018303105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.62 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Sucudarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Sucudarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sucudarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVYU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Sucudarcha afavella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sucudarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Sucudarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Sucudarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sucudarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVYU01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Sucudarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order

Woesearchaeales.

Description of *Candidatus Sufilarcha emavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sufilarcha emavana (N.L. fem. n. *emavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMVU01 sp003661265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.86 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sufilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sufilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sufilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMVU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sufilarcha emavana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sufilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sufilarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sufilarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sufilarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMVU01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sufilarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Korarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sufilarcha ocavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sufilarcha ocavia (N.L. fem. n. *ocavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMVU01 sp003661365. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.56 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sufilarcha elaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sufilarcha elaposa (N.L. fem. n. *elaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGTQV01 sp018397035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018397035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.9 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sufrabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sufrabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sufrabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGTQV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sufrabarcha elaposa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bosatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sufrodarcha edalosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sufrodarcha edalosa (N.L. fem. n. *edalosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA73 sp018304105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.89 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sufrodarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sufrodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sufrodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA73. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sufrodarcha edalosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sufrodarcha ogebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sufrodarcha ogebosa (N.L. fem. n. *ogebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA73 sp018817405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_018817405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.3 % and the genome length is 1.07 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sufrodarcha ucadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sufrodarcha ucadella (N.L. fem. n. *ucadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA73 sp018816205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018816205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.52 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sufrodarcha ugepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sufrodarcha ugepella (N.L. fem. n. *ugepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA73 sp018817905. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018817905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.86 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sufrodarcha uvacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sufrodarcha uvacella (N.L. fem. n. *uvacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA73 sp002496015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.78 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sulfodiicoccus uraparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sulfodiicoccus uraparia (N.L. fem. n. *uraparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Sulfodiicoccus sp017857195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017857195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.71 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sulfuracidifex odafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sulfuracidifex odafana (N.L. fem. n. *odafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Sulfuracidifex sp002495845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.06 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sulfurisphaera omepella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sulfurisphaera omepella (N.L. fem. n. *omepella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Sulfurisphaera sp012222305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012222305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.64 % and the genome length is 2.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sumafrarcha uvatosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sumafrarcha uvatosa (N.L. fem. n. *uvatosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is VGLU01 sp016882195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016882195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.34 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sumafrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sumafrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sumafrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is VGLU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sumafrarcha uvatosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylicaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Supocrarcha udacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Supocrarcha udacella (N.L. fem. n. *udacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJTU01 sp018829485. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018829485.1. The GC content of the type genome is 29.86 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Supocrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Supocrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Supocrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJTU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Supocrarcha udacella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Casibarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Supoprarcha edebaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Supoprarcha edebaria (N.L. fem. n. *edebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WALP01 sp015522785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.3 % and the genome length is 0.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Supoprarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Supoprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Supoprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WALP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Supoprarcha edebaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixabarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Sustodarcha ebacella sp. nov.

Candidatus Sustodarcha ebacella (N.L. fem. n. *ebacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIYL01 sp018815145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018815145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.73 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Sustodarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Sustodarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sustodarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JAHYIL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sustodarcha ebacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hudomarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sutibarcha ilaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sutibarcha ilaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ilaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPBO01 sp016180285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.82 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sutibarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sutibarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sutibarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPBO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sutibarcha ilaxosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sutibarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Sutibarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Sutibarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Sutibarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPBO01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Sutibarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Sutostarcha ruxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Sutostarcha ruxella (N.L. fem. n. *ruxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAISET01 sp903884505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903830965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.98 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Sutostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Sutostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Sutostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAISET01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Sutostarcha ruxella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Uglutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Suxenarcha onaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Suxenarcha onaxana (N.L. fem. n. *onaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAITNU01 sp903893865. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903893865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.24 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Suxenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Suxenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Suxenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is CAITNU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Suxenarcha onaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Suxenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Suxenarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Suxenarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Suxenarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is CAITNU01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Suxenarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Suxustarcha alebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Suxustarcha alebella (N.L. fem. n. *alebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWWA01 sp003562145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003562145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.88 % and the genome length is 0.66 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Suxustarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Suxustarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Suxustarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PWWA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Suxustarcha alebella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Siluxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Suxustarcha ebasella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Suxustarcha ebasella (N.L. fem. n. *ebasella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWWA01 sp007131205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007131205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.99 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Suxustarcha quexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Suxustarcha quexana (N.L. fem. n. *quexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWWA01 sp003560545. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003560545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.26 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tabrecarcha ebaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tabrecarcha ebaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Fen-7 sp003162615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003170635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.17 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tabrecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tabrecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tabrecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Fen-7. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tabrecarcha ebaxosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanotrachaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Taceprarcha ilevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Taceprarcha ilevella (N.L. fem. n. *ilevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQX01 sp016208715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016208715.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.91 % and the genome length is 2.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Taceprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Taceprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Taceprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Taceprarcha ilevella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hicuparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Taceprarcha ocafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Taceprarcha ocafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ocafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQX01 sp016219765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016219765.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.55 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tafresarcha agecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tafresarcha agecosa (N.L. fem. n. *agecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPIN01 sp018302705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.52 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tafresarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tafresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tafresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPIN01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tafresarcha agecosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Hopelarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tafresarcha ofaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tafresarcha ofaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ofaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPIN01 sp016188065. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.85 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tafrurarcha erabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tafrurarcha erabella (N.L. fem. n. *erabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZT01 sp018302335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 62.52 % and the genome length is 1.56 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tafrurarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tafrurarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tafrurarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tafrurarcha erabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tafrurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tafrurarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Tafrurarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tafrurarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVZT01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Tafrurarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tagristarcha ufacana sp. nov.

Candidatus Tagristarcha ufacana (N.L. fem. n. *ufacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRZC01 sp011380215. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011380215.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.43 % and the genome length is 1.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tagristarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Tagristarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tagristarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRZC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tagristarcha ufacana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fervidicoccaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tamastarcha elacia sp. nov.

Candidatus Tamastarcha elacia (N.L. fem. n. *elacia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WJLC01 sp014728745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014728745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.97 % and the genome length is 0.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tamastarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Tamastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tamastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WJLC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tamastarcha elacia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha acagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha acagella (N.L. fem. n. *acagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp017885605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017885605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.9 % and the genome length is 2.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tarutrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SM1-50. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tarutrarcha acagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha avacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha avacella (N.L. fem. n. *avacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp002506745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.99 % and the genome length is 1.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha duvana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha duvana (N.L. fem. n. *duvana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp002496355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013331255.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.11 % and the genome length is 1.54 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha iledosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha iledosa (N.L. fem. n. *iledosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp016930995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016930995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.33 % and the genome length is 2.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha imavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha imavana (N.L. fem. n. *imavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp002900555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002900545.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.58 % and the genome length is 1.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha ivepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha ivepana (N.L. fem. n. *ivepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp001595945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001595945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.01 % and the genome length is 2.09 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-methane transition zone estuary sediments 16-26 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha obavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha obavia (N.L. fem. n. *obavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp016927555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016927555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.31 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha obefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha obefaria (N.L. fem. n. *obefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp902384685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_902384685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.51 % and the genome length is 2.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha oladia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha oladia (N.L. fem. n. *oladia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp003942085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003942085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.15 % and the genome length is 2.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tarutrarcha ufaparia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tarutrarcha ufaparia (N.L. fem. n. *ufaparia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SM1-50 sp014894395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014894395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.28 % and the genome length is 2.73 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Taxugrarcha avagosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Taxugrarcha avagosa (N.L. fem. n. *avagosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAOB01 sp015521505. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521505.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.32 % and the genome length is 0.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Taxugrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Taxugrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Taxugrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAOB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Taxugrarcha avagosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Beximarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Teclusarcha idacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Teclusarcha idacosa (N.L. fem. n. *idacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACEMX01 sp013867335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013867335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.88 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Teclusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Teclusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Teclusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACEMX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Teclusarcha idacosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrosopumulaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Teclusarcha uvadia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Teclusarcha uvadia (N.L. fem. n. *uvadia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACEMX01 sp011773785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011771385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.77 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tefagarcha egafia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tefagarcha egafia (N.L. fem. n. *egafia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRAC01 sp016219465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016219465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.48 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tefagarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tefagarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tefagarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRAC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tefagarcha egafia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tefagarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tefagarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tefagarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tefagarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACRAC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tefagarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Coxosarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tefagarcha ofaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tefagarcha ofaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *ofaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACRAC01 sp016213555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016213555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.58 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tefrenarcha egarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tefrenarcha egarana (N.L. fem. n. *egarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDU01 sp017609535. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.98 % and the genome length is 0.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tefrenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tefrenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tefrenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tefrenarcha egarana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tegruprarcha odecana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tegruprarcha odecana (N.L. fem. n. *odecana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPJS01 sp016187405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016187405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.44 % and the genome length is 0.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tegruprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tegruprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tegruprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPJS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tegruprarcha odecana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Maposarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tepleprarcha ebefosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tepleprarcha ebefosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebefosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JdFR-41 sp002010285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002010285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.32 % and the genome length is 1.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tepleprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tepleprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tepleprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JdFR-41. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tepleprarcha ebefosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Archaeoglobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Testotrarcha udefaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Testotrarcha udefaria (N.L. fem. n. *udefaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPBT01 sp016180145. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016180145.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.65 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Testotrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Testotrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Testotrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPBT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Testotrarcha udefaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Penularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tesumarcha ipatana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tesumarcha ipatana (N.L. fem. n. *ipatana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHLSM01 sp018920245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018920245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.9 % and the genome length is 0.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tesumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tesumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tesumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHLSM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tesumarcha ipatana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tesumarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tesumarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tesumarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tesumarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHLSM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tesumarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Aenigmatarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Thalassarchaeum afadella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum afadella (N.L. fem. n. *afadella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp002505325. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002505325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.1 % and the genome length is 1.22 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thalassarchaeum cixana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum cixana (N.L. fem. n. *cixana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp002501885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.58 % and the genome length is 1.24 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thalassarchaeum ebaposa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum ebaposa (N.L. fem. n. *ebaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp004195715. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_012960685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.57 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thalassarchaeum ebegana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum ebegana (N.L. fem. n. *ebegana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp002495735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002495735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.94 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thalassarchaeum efacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum efacella (N.L. fem. n. *efacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp002457605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002457605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.64 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thalassarchaeum emagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum emagana (N.L. fem. n. *emagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp014240285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014240285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.8 % and the genome length is 1.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Thalassarchaeum guxana sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum guxana (N.L. fem. n. *guxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp002714745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002501685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.22 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Thalassarchaeum ivadana sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum ivadana (N.L. fem. n. *ivadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp002503055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002506495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.28 % and the genome length is 1.08 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Thalassarchaeum odexana sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum odexana (N.L. fem. n. *odexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp002727275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002727275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.2 % and the genome length is 1.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Thalassarchaeum ofavia sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum ofavia (N.L. fem. n. *ofavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thalassarchaeum sp002507125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013214115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.14 % and the genome

length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thalassarchaeum upabaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thalassarchaeum upabaria (N.L. fem. n. *upabaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thalassarchaeum* sp002698225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002698225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.42 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermocladium obefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermocladium obefella (N.L. fem. n. *obefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermocladium* sp001516585. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001516585.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.83 % and the genome length is 1.88 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "coculture of 3 archaeal species originally obtained from terrestrial hot spring (Echinus Geyser; YNP)".

Description of *Candidatus Thermocladium unexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermocladium unexana (N.L. fem. n. *unexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermocladium* sp002508315. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002508315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.69 % and the genome length is 1.31 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus agavaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus agavaria (N.L. fem. n. *agavaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus* sp900198835. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_900198835.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.58 % and the genome length is 2.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus avagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus avagaria (N.L. fem. n. *avagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp015522395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.94 % and the genome length is 1.49 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ecavia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ecavia (N.L. fem. n. *ecavia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp012027395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.87 % and the genome length is 2.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus egasana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus egasana (N.L. fem. n. *egasana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp015523195. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.7 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus esepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus esepia (N.L. fem. n. *esepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp012027615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.39 % and the genome length is 2.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus icadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus icadosa (N.L. fem. n. *icadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp000221185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000221185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.08 % and the genome length is 2.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus icaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus icaxella (N.L. fem. n. *icaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus* sp013153595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013153595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.6 % and the genome length is 1.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus igexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus igexosa (N.L. fem. n. *igexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus* sp002214525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_002214525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.88 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus isatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus isatia (N.L. fem. n. *isatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus* sp000151205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_000151205.2. The GC content of the type genome is 54.78 % and the genome length is 2.09 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "2600 m depth".

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus isecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus isecaria (N.L. fem. n. *isecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus* sp012027635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.59 % and the genome length is 1.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ocarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ocarana (N.L. fem. n. *ocarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus* sp012027355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank

assembly RS_GCF_012027355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.6 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ofamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ofamella (N.L. fem. n. *ofamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp015521605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.48 % and the genome length is 2.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ofavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ofavana (N.L. fem. n. *ofavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp015523185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.18 % and the genome length is 1.71 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ofaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ofaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp012027645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.37 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus opagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus opagana (N.L. fem. n. *opagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp015520705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.38 % and the genome length is 1.26 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ovaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ovaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ovaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp012027595. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.21 % and the genome length is 2.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus phagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus phagia (N.L. fem. n. *phagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp012027555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.58 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus phedella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus phedella (N.L. fem. n. *phedella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp011050175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011050175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.42 % and the genome length is 1.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ucadosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ucadosa (N.L. fem. n. *ucadosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp012027495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.69 % and the genome length is 2.14 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus unarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus unarana (N.L. fem. n. *unarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus sp012027305. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.52 % and the genome length is 2.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus avaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus avaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *avaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus_A sp012027425. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.7 % and the genome length is 1.98 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus egaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus egaxella (N.L. fem. n. *egaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus_A sp001484685. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_902813195.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.39 % and the genome length is 1.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus elaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus elaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *elaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus_A sp003663525. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003650075.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.03 % and the genome length is 1.46 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ofebella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ofebella (N.L. fem. n. *ofebella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus_A sp003663535. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003663535.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.34 % and the genome length is 1.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus onavella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus onavella (N.L. fem. n. *onavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily,

while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus_A* sp000430485. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013330365.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.2 % and the genome length is 1.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus quefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus quefella (N.L. fem. n. *quefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus_A* sp001317345. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_001317345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.28 % and the genome length is 1.82 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sediment".

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus emabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus emabia (N.L. fem. n. *emabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus_B* sp012027325. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_012027325.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.2 % and the genome length is 2.28 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ucalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ucalella (N.L. fem. n. *ucalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Thermococcus_B* sp017656495. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017656495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.27 % and the genome length is 2.05 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermococcus ogedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermococcus ogedaria (N.L. fem. n. *ogedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermococcus_C sp002009975. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002009975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.13 % and the genome length is 2.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermofilum ilafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermofilum ilafosa (N.L. fem. n. *ilafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermofilum_C sp011047595. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011047595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.68 % and the genome length is 0.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermofilum inabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermofilum inabana (N.L. fem. n. *inabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermofilum_C sp011364825. Although GTDB has assigned a genus name with an alphabetic suffix, this genus designation cannot be incorporated into a well-formed binomial, so in naming this species, we have used the basonym for the genus. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.03 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermoplasma anacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermoplasma anacana (N.L. fem. n. *anacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermoplasma sp003205235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly RS_GCF_003205235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.96 % and the genome length is 1.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermoplasma edebia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermoplasma edebia (N.L. fem. n. *edebia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermoplasma sp008709555. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008709555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.83 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermoproteus emefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermoproteus emefana (N.L. fem. n. *emefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermoproteus sp000960885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000960885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.95 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "muddy water from acid hot spring".

Description of *Candidatus Thermoproteus ofarana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermoproteus ofarana (N.L. fem. n. *ofarana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermoproteus sp002077075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011056725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 61.71 % and the genome length is 2.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Thermoproteus utebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Thermoproteus utebosa (N.L. fem. n. *utebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Thermoproteus sp002497345. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002497345.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.91 % and the genome length is 1.36 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tibenarcha ocafana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tibenarcha ocafana (N.L. fem. n. *ocafana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACIVX01 sp014361295. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014361295.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.98 % and the genome length is 2.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tibenarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tibenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tibenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACIVX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tibenarcha ocafana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tibenarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tibenarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Tibenarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tibenarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACIVX01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Tibenarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Methanomassiliicoccales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tibenarcha udavana sp. nov.

Candidatus Tibenarcha udavana (N.L. fem. n. *udavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACIVX01 sp011334735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011334735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.28 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tibrixarcha vuxana sp. nov.

Candidatus Tibrixarcha vuxana (N.L. fem. n. *vuxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is CAIYHQ01 sp903926075. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_903828555.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.57 % and the genome length is 3.17 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tibrixarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Tibrixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tibrixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is CAIYHQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tibrixarcha vuxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanospirillaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ticixarcha apabia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ticixarcha apabia (N.L. fem. n. *apabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SBBD01 sp005239845. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005239845.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.69 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ticixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ticixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ticixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SBBD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ticixarcha apabia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ticixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ticixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ticixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ticixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SBBD01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ticixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tifostarcha ebararia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tifostarcha ebararia (N.L. fem. n. *ebararia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADCY01 sp015520735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015520735.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.91 % and the genome length is 1.53 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tifostarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tifostarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tifostarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADCY01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tifostarcha ebararia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Desulfurococcaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tifostarcha ivalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tifostarcha ivalella (N.L. fem. n. *ivalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADCY01 sp013154205. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013154205.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.47 % and the genome length is 1.85 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tifraprarcha edexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tifraprarcha edexia (N.L. fem. n. *edexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPDL01 sp016184005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016184005.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.73 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tifraprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tifraprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tifraprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPDL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tifraprarcha edexia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Coxosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tifraprarcha ufacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tifraprarcha ufacella (N.L. fem. n. *ufacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPD01 sp018304565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018304565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.17 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tilastarcha odegosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tilastarcha odegosa (N.L. fem. n. *odegosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QEXZ01 sp003601795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003601795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.97 % and the genome length is 1.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tilastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tilastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tilastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QEXZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tilastarcha odegosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Rixusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tilastarcha phaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tilastarcha phaxana (N.L. fem. n. *phaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QEXZ01 sp013180605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013180605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.66 % and the genome length is 2.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tilastarcha ufasana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tilastarcha ufasana (N.L. fem. n. *ufasana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QEXZ01 sp003160755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003160755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.3 % and the genome length is 1.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tilastarcha umabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tilastarcha umabana (N.L. fem. n. *umabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QEXZ01 sp003661125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.99 % and the genome length is 2.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tinitrarcha ocamana sp. nov.

Candidatus Tinitrarcha ocamana (N.L. fem. n. *ocamana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIDZ01 sp018691995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018664565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.36 % and the genome length is 0.97 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tinitrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Tinitrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tinitrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JABIDZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tinitrarcha ocamana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Cofanarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tinitrarcha orafosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Tinitrarcha orafosa (N.L. fem. n. *orafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JABIDZ01 sp018651445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018656625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.16 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tinosarcha phavella sp. nov.

Candidatus Tinosarcha phavella (N.L. fem. n. *phavella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTBS01 sp011366705. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011366705.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.71 % and the genome length is

0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tinosarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tinosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tinosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTBS01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tinosarcha phavella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tinosarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tinosarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tinosarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tinosarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTBS01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tinosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Tinosarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tinosarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Tinosarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Tinosarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTBS01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tinosarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Nanoarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Tiresarcha phedana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tiresarcha phedana (N.L. fem. n. *phedana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J096 sp015522475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015522475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.81 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tiresarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tiresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tiresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J096. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tiresarcha phedana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiresarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tiresarchaceae fam. nov.

Candidatus Tiresarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tiresarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is J096. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Tiresarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Anstonellales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tiresarcha udepana sp. nov.

Candidatus Tiresarcha udepana (N.L. fem. n. *udepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J096 sp003694965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003694965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.7 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tirofrarcha ivecosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Tirofrarcha ivecosa (N.L. fem. n. *ivecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J072 sp003695265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003695265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.33 % and the genome length is 1.06 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tirofrarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Tirofrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tirofrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is J072. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tirofrarcha ivecosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tirofrarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tirofrarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tirofrarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tirofrarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is J072. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tirofrarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tiserarcha ubamella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tiserarcha ubamella (N.L. fem. n. *ubamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is AWOC01 sp000494185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_000402965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.8 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tiserarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tiserarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tiserarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is AWOC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tiserarcha ubamella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tiserarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tiserarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tiserarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tiserarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is HR02. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tiserarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Caldarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tisoparcha odecosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tisoparcha odecosa (N.L. fem. n. *odecosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHJEM01 sp018825425. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018825425.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.87 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tisoparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tisoparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tisoparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHJEM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tisoparcha odecosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tisoparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tisoparchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tisoparchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tisoparchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHJEM01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tisoparcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tistelarcha ocagia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tistelarcha ocagia (N.L. fem. n. *ocagia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGBP01 sp016930415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016930415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 49.74 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tistelarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tistelarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tistelarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGBP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tistelarcha ocagia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dobararchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tistelarcha usaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tistelarcha usaxana (N.L. fem. n. *usaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGBP01 sp016933095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016933095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.73 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tixirarcha igexaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tixirarcha igexaria (N.L. fem. n. *igexaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is HEL-GB-A sp005191415. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005191415.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.53 % and the genome length is 3.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tixirarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tixirarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tixirarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is HEL-GB-A. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tixirarcha igexaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tixirarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tixirarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tixirarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tixirarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is HEL-GB-A. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tixirarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Helarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tocemarcha epebosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tocemarcha epebosa (N.L. fem. n. *epebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA168 sp002507085. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002507085.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.38 % and the genome length is 0.89 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tocemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tocemarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tocemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA168. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tocemarcha epebosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tocemarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tocemarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tocemarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tocemarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA168. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Tocemarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Marsarchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tocemarcha ugavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tocemarcha ugavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ugavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA168 sp011055275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011055275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.03 % and the genome length is 0.81 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tocitrarcha ucatia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tocitrarcha ucatia (N.L. fem. n. *ucatia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2688925 sp002688925. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002688925.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.55 % and the genome length is 0.86 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tocitrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tocitrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tocitrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2688925. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tocitrarcha ucatia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Togastarcha urelaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Togastarcha urelaria (N.L. fem. n. *urelaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J110 sp003694805. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003694805.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.75 % and the genome length is 1.21 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Togastarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Togastarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Togastarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J110. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Togastarcha urelaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Togastarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Togastarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Togastarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Togastarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is J110. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Togastarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woeseearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Topagrarcha amevana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Topagrarcha amevana (N.L. fem. n. *amevana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4572-165 sp002254885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002254885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.07 % and the genome length is 1.2 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Topagrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Topagrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Topagrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is EX4572-165. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Topagrarcha amevana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Esacarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Topagrarcha emabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Topagrarcha emabana (N.L. fem. n. *emabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is EX4572-165 sp018334795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018335115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.56 % and the genome length is 1.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Toplitrarcha ifevella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Toplitrarcha ifevella (N.L. fem. n. *ifevella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is RBG-16-49-10 sp001784635. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001784635.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.62 % and the genome length is 0.92 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Rifle background sediment; well D04 at 16ft depth".

Description of *Candidatus Toplitrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Toplitrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Toplitrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is RBG-16-49-10. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Toplitrarcha* ifevella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Isoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Totrifrarcha* *ebecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Totrifrarcha* *ebecaria* (N.L. fem. n. *ebecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGLL01 sp016929175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016929175.1. The GC content of the type genome is 53.21 % and the genome length is 2.38 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Totrifrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus *Totrifrarcha* (N.L. fem. n. *Totrifrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFGLL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Totrifrarcha* *ebecaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Atilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* *Totrifrarcha* *unapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Totrifrarcha* *unapana* (N.L. fem. n. *unapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFGLL01 sp016928095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016928095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.33 % and the genome length is 2.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* *Totromarcha* *onalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Totromarcha* *onalana* (N.L. fem. n. *onalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is PWVO01 sp003561825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003561825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.99 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Totromarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Totromarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Totromarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is PWVO01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Totromarcha onalana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Pufisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Toxoprarcha ubapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Toxoprarcha ubapana (N.L. fem. n. *ubapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGVZH01 sp018302745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018302745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.33 % and the genome length is 0.7 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Toxoprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Toxoprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Toxoprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGVZH01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Toxoprarcha ubapana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Toxoprarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Toxoprarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Toxoprarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Toxoprarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAGVZH01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Toxoprarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tracisarcha ifagana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tracisarcha ifagana (N.L. fem. n. *ifagana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MX-02 sp006954405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_900769185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.81 % and the genome length is 1.09 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tracisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tracisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tracisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is MX-02. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tracisarcha ifagana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Methanomethylophilaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tracisarcha ivamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tracisarcha ivamaria (N.L. fem. n. *ivamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is MX-02 sp017455785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017455785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.79 % and the genome length is 1.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trafabarcha ifagaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trafabarcha ifagaria (N.L. fem. n. *ifagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCCFP01 sp017608575. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608865.1. The GC content of the type genome is 38.16 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trafabarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trafabarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trafabarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCCFP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Trafabarcha ifagaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Gudamarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trasobarcha uracosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Trasobarcha uracosa* (N.L. fem. n. *uracosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is B3-G16 sp003649665. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003649665.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.21 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trasobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus *Trasobarcha* (N.L. fem. n. *Trasobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is B3-G16. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Trasobarcha uracosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Mefularchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trastemarcha esecaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Trastemarcha esecaria* (N.L. fem. n. *esecaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SHMX01 sp008080745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_008080745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.23 % and the genome length is 3.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trastemarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus *Trastemarcha* (N.L. fem. n. *Trastemarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SHMX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* *Trastemarcha esecaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trastemarcha ivebaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus *Trastemarcha ivebaria* (N.L. fem. n. *ivebaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SHMX01 sp014728035. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014728035.1. The GC content of the type genome is 39.54 % and the genome length is 4.33 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Traxasarcha egacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Traxasarcha egacana (N.L. fem. n. *egacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J144 sp003694055. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003694055.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.27 % and the genome length is 0.99 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Traxasarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Traxasarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Traxasarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J144. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Traxasarcha egacana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Treplecarcha onexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Treplecarcha onexana (N.L. fem. n. *onexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPHA01 sp016188825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.13 % and the genome length is 1.01 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Treplecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Treplecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Treplecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPHA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Treplecarcha onexana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Treplifarcha uceraria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Treplifarcha uceraria (N.L. fem. n. *uceraria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFQB01 sp019246625. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019246625.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.77 % and the genome length is 3.96 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Treplifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Treplifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Treplifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFQB01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Treplifarcha uceraria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nitrososphaeraceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trepromarcha ufecella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trepromarcha ufecella (N.L. fem. n. *ufecella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is J104 sp003694495. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003694495.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.22 % and the genome length is 0.84 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trepromarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trepromarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trepromarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is J104. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Trepromarcha ufecella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nudoxarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tresanarcha egacella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tresanarcha egacella (N.L. fem. n. *egacella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy

Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WTCK01 sp019057475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019057475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.27 % and the genome length is 3.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tresanarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tresanarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tresanarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WTCK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tresanarcha egacella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Thorarchaeaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tresanarcha ifaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tresanarcha ifaxia (N.L. fem. n. *ifaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WTCK01 sp018238375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018238375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.0 % and the genome length is 2.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tresanarcha ufexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tresanarcha ufexana (N.L. fem. n. *ufexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WTCK01 sp013138615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013138615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.13 % and the genome length is 1.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trexifarcha apavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trexifarcha apavosa (N.L. fem. n. *apavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WANZ01 sp015521515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.0 % and the genome length is 0.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trexifarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trexifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trexifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WANZ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Trexifarcha apavosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family Dupisarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus* Tricimarcha ocadaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Tricimarcha ocadaria (N.L. fem. n. *ocadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPTA01 sp016193005. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016186065.1. The GC content of the type genome is 54.12 % and the genome length is 1.41 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tricimarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Tricimarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tricimarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPTA01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tricimarcha ocadaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family Naraxarchaceae.

Description of *Candidatus* Trifenarcha udabia sp. nov.

Candidatus Trifenarcha udabia (N.L. fem. n. *udabia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCD01 sp017609885. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609885.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.49 % and the genome length is 0.75 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trifenarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Trifenarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trifenarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

genus is JAFCD01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Trifenarcha udabia.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Trigresarcha arexella sp. nov.

Candidatus Trigresarcha arexella (N.L. fem. n. *arexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCDQ01 sp017609645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.18 % and the genome length is 1.13 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trigresarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Trigresarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trigresarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCDQ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Trigresarcha arexella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Trimafarcha phagaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Trimafarcha phagaria (N.L. fem. n. *phagaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LW40-45 sp004524515. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_004524515.1. The GC content of the type genome is 30.41 % and the genome length is 3.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trimafarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Trimafarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trimafarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is LW40-45. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Trimafarcha phagaria.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Iblitarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trimafarcha ugavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trimafarcha ugavana (N.L. fem. n. *ugavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is LW40-45 sp019058445. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_019058445.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.0 % and the genome length is 4.61 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trinexarcha etaxella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trinexarcha etaxella (N.L. fem. n. *etaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEV01 sp017609755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017608905.1. The GC content of the type genome is 27.3 % and the genome length is 0.51 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trinexarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trinexarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trinexarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAFCEV01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Trinexarcha etaxella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Midifarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trinexarcha ocadana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trinexarcha ocadana (N.L. fem. n. *ocadana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAFCEV01 sp017608985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_017609315.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.09 % and the genome length is 0.47 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trinoparcha ipavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trinoparcha ipavosa (N.L. fem. n. *ipavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is JACRDW01 sp016212785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016212785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.38 % and the genome length is 1.11 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trinoparcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trinoparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trinoparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACRDW01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Trinoparcha ipavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fosilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trirocarcha enacana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trirocarcha enacana (N.L. fem. n. *enacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSQK01 sp016203225. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203225.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.2 % and the genome length is 1.0 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trirocarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trirocarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trirocarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DSQK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Trirocarcha enacana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Madeparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trirocarcha odecia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trirocarcha odecia (N.L. fem. n. *odecia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSQK01 sp016203265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 55.01 % and the genome length is 0.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trirocarcha ogavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trirocarcha ogavana (N.L. fem. n. *ogavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DSQK01 sp011331795. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011331795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 57.36 % and the genome length is 1.03 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trixaparcha obaxella sp. nov.

Candidatus Trixaparcha obaxella (N.L. fem. n. *obaxella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BA-19 sp005888735. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_005888795.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.9 % and the genome length is 2.65 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trixaparcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Trixaparcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trixaparcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BA-19. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Trixaparcha obaxella.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Omubarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Trogrifarcha ecepana sp. nov.

Candidatus Trogrifarcha ecepana (N.L. fem. n. *ecepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is WAKM01 sp015523335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015523335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.13 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trogrifarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Trogrifarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trogrifarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is WAKM01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Trogrifarcha ecepana.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Archaeoglobaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trosecarcha itafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trosecarcha itafosa (N.L. fem. n. *itafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHIRU01 sp018818465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018829405.1. The GC content of the type genome is 36.04 % and the genome length is 0.87 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trosecarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trosecarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trosecarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHIRU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Trosecarcha itafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trubrisarcha ecaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trubrisarcha ecaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ecaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQNJ01 sp016181245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016181245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.12 % and the genome length is 0.91 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trubrisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trubrisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trubrisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQNJ01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Trubrisarcha ecaxana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fixurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trubrisarcha quexosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trufelarcha quexosa (N.L. fem. n. *quexosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQNJ01 sp016203115. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016203115.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.24 % and the genome length is 0.76 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trufelarcha afebosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Trufelarcha afebosa (N.L. fem. n. *afebosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SG8-32-3 sp007050895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_007050895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.31 % and the genome length is 1.59 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trufelarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Trufelarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trufelarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SG8-32-3. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Trufelarcha afebosa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Trufelarcha esacana sp. nov.

Candidatus Trufelarcha esacana (N.L. fem. n. *esacana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SG8-32-3 sp016927895. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016927895.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.16 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Trufelarcha ifabosa sp. nov.

Candidatus Trufelarcha ifabosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifabosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SG8-32-3 sp016927015. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016927015.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.87 % and the genome length is

1.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trufelarcha umexana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trufelarcha umexana (N.L. fem. n. *umexana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SG8-32-3 sp001273335. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001273335.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.01 % and the genome length is 0.67 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "Sulfate-rich zone estuary sediments 8-12 cm".

Description of *Candidatus Truficarcha avafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Truficarcha avafaria (N.L. fem. n. *avafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SpSt-28 sp011047985. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011047985.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.34 % and the genome length is 0.79 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Truficarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Truficarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Truficarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SpSt-28. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Truficarcha avafaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Disocarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trufrolarcha otafosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trufrolarcha otafosa (N.L. fem. n. *otafosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is BS150m-G66 sp016784105. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016784105.1. The GC content of the type genome is 34.3 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trufrolarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trufrolarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trufrolarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is BS150m-G66. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Trunurarcha otafosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Nigodarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trunurarcha upefella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Trunurarcha upefella (N.L. fem. n. *upefella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-2687185 sp002687185. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002687185.1. The GC content of the type genome is 37.33 % and the genome length is 1.58 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Trunurarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Trunurarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Trunurarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-2687185. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Trunurarcha upefella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Trunurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Trunurarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Trunurarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Trunurarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-2687185. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Trunurarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Ogusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Truranarcha erepia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Truranarcha erepia (N.L. fem. n. *erepia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADFX01 sp013152685. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013152685.1. The GC content of the type genome is 59.96 % and the genome length is 1.8

Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Truranarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Truranarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Truranarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAADFX01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Truranarcha erepia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Dufoparchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Truranarcha idalana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Truranarcha idalana (N.L. fem. n. *idalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADFX01 sp015521565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.0 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Truranarcha urapella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Truranarcha urapella (N.L. fem. n. *urapella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAADFX01 sp015521615. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015521615.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.1 % and the genome length is 1.8 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tufolarcha quexella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tufolarcha quexella (N.L. fem. n. *quexella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQPP01 sp016207465. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016207465.1. The GC content of the type genome is 67.72 % and the genome length is 1.5 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tufolarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tufolarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tufolarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQPP01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tufolarcha quexella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tufolarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tufolarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tufolarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tufolarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQPP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tufolarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Tufolarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tufolarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Tufolarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Tufolarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACQPP01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tufolarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Syntropharchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Tufoprarcha egaxaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tufoprarcha egaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *egaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAGTQU01 sp018396695. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018396695.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.33 % and the genome length is 1.9 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tufoprarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tufoprarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tufoprarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAGTQU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tufoprarcha egaxaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ibidarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tuglonarcha etavosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tuglonarcha etavosa (N.L. fem. n. *etavosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DRUK01 sp011370995. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011370995.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.7 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tuglonarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tuglonarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tuglonarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DRUK01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tuglonarcha etavosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Sofogarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tunebrarcha edalella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tunebrarcha edalella (N.L. fem. n. *edalella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQIG01 sp016198605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016198605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.88 % and the genome length is 0.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tunebrarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tunebrarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tunebrarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACQIG01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tunebrarcha edalella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Bimafarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tunebrarcha isadaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tunebrarcha isadaria (N.L. fem. n. *isadaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACQIG01 sp016202745. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016202745.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.95 % and the genome length is 1.02 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tuplosarcha idaposa sp. nov.

Candidatus Tuplosarcha idaposa (N.L. fem. n. *idaposa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-32-24 sp013204355. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013204355.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.5 % and the genome length is 1.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tuplosarcha gen. nov.

Candidatus Tuplosarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tuplosarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is 1-14-0-10-32-24. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus* Tuplosarcha idaposa.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Fipalarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus* Tuplosarcha olagella sp. nov.

Candidatus Tuplosarcha olagella (N.L. fem. n. *olagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-32-24 sp018655525. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018650605.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.78 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Tuplosarcha ovamella sp. nov.

Candidatus Tuplosarcha ovamella (N.L. fem. n. *ovamella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is 1-14-0-10-32-24 sp002763025. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002763025.1. The GC content of the type genome is 32.14 % and the genome

length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tusixarcha ufasaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tusixarcha ufasaria (N.L. fem. n. *ufasaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9642 sp011329125. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011329125.1. The GC content of the type genome is 31.07 % and the genome length is 0.88 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tusixarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tusixarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tusixarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is UBA9642. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tusixarcha ufasaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tusixarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tusixarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tusixarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tusixarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is UBA9642. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tusixarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Woesearchaeales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tusixarcha vucana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tusixarcha vucana (N.L. fem. n. *vucana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is UBA9642 sp12459u. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_013328975.1. The GC content of the type genome is 33.53 % and the genome length is 1.52 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tuxefarcha atedaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tuxefarcha atedaria (N.L. fem. n. *atedaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-001856825 sp014874235. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014874235.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.73 % and the genome length is 1.3 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Tuxefarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Tuxefarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Tuxefarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is GCA-001856825. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Tuxefarcha atedaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Tuxefarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Tuxefarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Tuxefarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Tuxefarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is GCA-001856825. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Tuxefarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Thermoplasmatales*.

Description of *Candidatus Tuxefarcha phavana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tuxefarcha phavana (N.L. fem. n. *phavana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-001856825 sp001856825. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001856825.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.3 % and the genome length is 1.69 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "isolated from slime streamers and attached to pyrite surfaces at a sulfide ore body".

Description of *Candidatus Tuxefarcha udefana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Tuxefarcha udefana (N.L. fem. n. *udefana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is GCA-001856825 sp011358095. The type genome for the species is the GenBank

assembly GCA_011358095.1. The GC content of the type genome is 42.85 % and the genome length is 1.55 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Uclobarcha avapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Uclobarcha avapia (N.L. fem. n. *avapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPGT01 sp016212375. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016212375.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.9 % and the genome length is 1.34 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Uclobarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Uclobarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Uclobarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JACPGT01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Uclobarcha avapia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Uclobarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Uclobarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Uclobarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Uclobarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JACPGT01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Uclobarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Norongarragalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Uclobarcha ebacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Uclobarcha ebacosa (N.L. fem. n. *ebacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPGT01 sp016207165. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016207165.1. The GC content of the type genome is 56.4 % and the genome length is 1.27 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Uclobarcha esepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Uclobarcha esepana (N.L. fem. n. *esepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while

preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JACPGT01 sp016188965. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_016188965.1. The GC content of the type genome is 58.0 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Udisarcha igepana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Udisarcha igepana (N.L. fem. n. *igepana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is QMWL01 sp003661605. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003661605.2. The GC content of the type genome is 50.78 % and the genome length is 0.78 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Udisarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Udisarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Udisarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is QMWL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Udisarcha igepana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Udisarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Udisarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Udisarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Udisarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMWL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Udisarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Udisarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Udisarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Udisarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Udisarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is QMWL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Udisarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Udisarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Ufrilarcha orabella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ufrilarcha orabella (N.L. fem. n. *orabella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is JAHENU01 sp018609855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_018609855.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.93 % and the genome length is 0.68 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ufrilarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ufrilarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ufrilarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is JAHENU01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ufrilarcha orabella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ufrilarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ufrilarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ufrilarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ufrilarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is JAHENU01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ufrilarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Nanosalinales*.

Description of *Candidatus Uglutarcha ovelia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Uglutarcha ovelia (N.L. fem. n. *ovelia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is DTNL01 sp011358645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011358645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.5 % and the genome length is 0.95 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Uglutarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Uglutarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Uglutarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is DTNL01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Uglutarcha ovelia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Uglutarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Uglutarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Uglutarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Uglutarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is DTNL01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Uglutarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Fermentimicrarchaeales*[@].

Description of *Candidatus Undinarchaeum esafaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Undinarchaeum esafaria (N.L. fem. n. *esafaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Undinarchaeum sp002687935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002494525.1. The GC content of the type genome is 40.91 % and the genome length is 0.64 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Undinarchaeum onabana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Undinarchaeum onabana (N.L. fem. n. *onabana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Undinarchaeum sp014189675. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_014189675.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.76 % and the genome length is 0.62 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Urusarcha efacosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Urusarcha efacosa (N.L. fem. n. *efacosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is SW-10-69-26 sp003009755. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003009755.1. The GC content of the type genome is 69.28 % and the genome length is 2.82 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Urusarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Urusarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Urusarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SW-10-69-26. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Urusarcha efacosa*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Urusarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Urusarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Urusarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Urusarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SW-10-69-26. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Urusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Urusarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Urusarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Urusarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Urusarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SW-10-69-26. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Urusarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Urusarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus Usatarcha edagella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Usatarcha edagella (N.L. fem. n. *edagella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARK-15 sp009758405. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009758305.1. The GC content of the type genome is 35.95 % and the genome length is 1.4 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Usatarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Usatarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Usatarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is ARK-15. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Usatarcha edagella*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Usatarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Usatarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Usatarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Usatarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is ARK-15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Usatarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Usatarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Usatarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Usatarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Usatarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is ARK-15. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Usatarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Thermoplasmata*.

Description of *Candidatus Usatarcha egaxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Usatarcha egaxosa (N.L. fem. n. *egaxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is ARK-15 sp002878135. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002878135.1. The GC content of the type genome is 41.01 % and the genome length is 1.37 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Usinarcha utebana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Usinarcha utebana (N.L. fem. n. *utebana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is IMC4 sp001742785. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001742785.1. The GC content of the type genome is 48.48 % and the genome length is 1.39 Mbp. The isolation source for the NCBI BioSample associated with the type genome is described as "sulfidic groundwater".

Description of *Candidatus Usinarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Usinarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Usinarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is IMC4. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Usinarcha utebana*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Usinarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Usinarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Usinarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Usinarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is IMC4. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Usinarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Usinarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Usinarchales* ord. nov.

Candidatus Usinarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Usinarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is IMC4. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Usinarcha*.

.According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Altiarchaeia*.

Description of *Candidatus Ustumarcha ofamaria* sp. nov.

Candidatus Ustumarcha ofamaria (N.L. fem. n. *ofamaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is SOJC01 sp004376645. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly

GCA_004376645.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.59 % and the genome length is 1.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Ustumarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Ustumarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Ustumarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is SOJC01. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Ustumarcha ofamaria*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Ustumarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Ustumarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Ustumarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Ustumarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is SOJC01. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus Ustumarcha*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Omagarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus Usurarcha gaxia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Usurarcha gaxia (N.L. fem. n. *gaxia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bog-38 sp003162175. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003171385.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.28 % and the genome length is 1.72 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Usurarcha* gen. nov.

Candidatus Usurarcha (N.L. fem. n. *Usurarcha* a name created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this genus is Bog-38. The type species for the genus is *Candidatus Usurarcha gaxia*.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this genus belongs to the family *Usurarchaceae*.

Description of *Candidatus Usurarchaceae* fam. nov.

Candidatus Usurarchaceae (N.L. fem. n. *Usurarchaceae* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of an appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is Bog-38. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Usurarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this family belongs to the order *Usurarchales*.

Description of *Candidatus* Usurarchales ord. nov.

Candidatus Usurarchales (N.L. fem. n. *Usurarchales* a name created from the name of the type genus by addition of the appropriate suffix).

A taxon identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this taxon is Bog-38. The type genus for the taxon is *Candidatus* Usurarcha.

According to the renamed version of GTDB Release R207, this order belongs to the class *Usurarchia*.

Description of *Candidatus* Usurarcha icafella sp. nov.

Candidatus Usurarcha icafella (N.L. fem. n. *icafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bog-38 sp015660915. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015660915.1. The GC content of the type genome is 50.98 % and the genome length is 2.04 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Usurarcha icaxaria sp. nov.

Candidatus Usurarcha icaxaria (N.L. fem. n. *icaxaria* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bog-38 sp015661395. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_015661395.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.04 % and the genome length is 2.16 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus* Usurarcha ifalana sp. nov.

Candidatus Usurarcha ifalana (N.L. fem. n. *ifalana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this

species is Bog-38 sp003158275. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003158275.1. The GC content of the type genome is 51.51 % and the genome length is 2.1 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Usurarcha naxosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Usurarcha naxosa (N.L. fem. n. *naxosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bog-38 sp003139855. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003163595.1. The GC content of the type genome is 52.04 % and the genome length is 1.45 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Usurarcha utapana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Usurarcha utapana (N.L. fem. n. *utapana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Bog-38 sp003170935. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_003141775.1. The GC content of the type genome is 47.82 % and the genome length is 1.19 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Vulcanisaeta ifedosa* sp. nov.

Candidatus Vulcanisaeta ifedosa (N.L. fem. n. *ifedosa* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Vulcanisaeta sp001316285. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001316285.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.93 % and the genome length is 2.29 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Vulcanisaeta ivaxana* sp. nov.

Candidatus Vulcanisaeta ivaxana (N.L. fem. n. *ivaxana* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Vulcanisaeta sp001316265. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001316265.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.28 % and the genome length is 2.25 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Vulcanisaeta ocafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Vulcanisaeta ocafella (N.L. fem. n. *ocafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Vulcanisaeta sp001316245. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_001316245.1. The GC content of the type genome is 46.73 % and the genome length is 2.44 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Vulcanisaeta quexia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Vulcanisaeta quexia (N.L. fem. n. *quexia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Vulcanisaeta sp002496475. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_002496475.1. The GC content of the type genome is 44.57 % and the genome length is 1.6 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Vulcanisaeta urafella* sp. nov.

Candidatus Vulcanisaeta urafella (N.L. fem. n. *urafella* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Vulcanisaeta sp001516765. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_009903725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.64 % and the genome length is 2.18 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Zestosphaera emalia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Zestosphaera emalia (N.L. fem. n. *emalia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Zestosphaera sp011364565. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011364565.1. The GC content of the type genome is 43.18 % and the genome length is 1.12 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Zestosphaera ifedia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Zestosphaera ifedia (N.L. fem. n. *ifedia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is Zestosphaera sp011361945. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011361945.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.89 % and the genome length is 0.93 Mbp.

Description of *Candidatus Zestosphaera omapia* sp. nov.

Candidatus Zestosphaera omapia (N.L. fem. n. *omapia* a species epithet created arbitrarily, while preserving the phonotactics and morphology of Latin; used as a noun in apposition).

A species identified and delineated according to the algorithms of the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) Release R207. The GTDB alphanumeric placeholder designation for this species is *Zestosphaera* sp011375725. The type genome for the species is the GenBank assembly GCA_011375725.1. The GC content of the type genome is 45.98 % and the genome length is 1.51 Mbp.